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WATER RECORDS OF U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS
1962-69

UNITED STATES DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR
U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY
IN COOPERATION WITH THE
NATIONAL PARK SERVICE
AND THE
GOVERNMENT OF THE VIRGIN ISLANDS OF THE UNITED STATES

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WATER RECORDS OF THE
U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1962 - 69

by

Tully M. Robison and others
U.S. Geological Survey

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Prepared in cooperation with
The Government of the
Virgin Islands of the United States
and the National Park Service

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INTRODUCTION

The surface-water, quality of water, and ground-water records of the Virgin Islands from 1962 through 1969 are presented in this report. The location of all stations in this report are shown on the individual island maps. Each island map is followed by the tabulation of water records for that island. The records were collected by the Caribbean District of the Water Resources Division, U.S. Geological Survey in financial cooperation with the Government of the Virgin Islands of the United States and the National Park Service.

Stage-discharge relation is the relation between gage height and the amount of water flowing in a channel, the flow being expressed as volume per unit of time (locally, in gallons per minute).

Control designates a feature downstream from the gage that determines the stage-discharge relation at the gage. This feature may be a natural constriction of the channel, a long reach of the channel, or an artificial structure.

Drainage area of a stream at a specified location is that area, measured in a horizontal plane, which is so enclosed by a topographic divide that direct surface runoff from precipitation normally would drain by gravity into the river above the specified point. Figures of drainage area given herein include non-contributing areas within the area unless otherwise noted.

Hardness as CaCO₃ is the calcium and magnesium expressed as an equivalent amount of calcium carbonate.

Carbonate hardness is the hardness caused by calcium and magnesium equivalent to the carbonate and bicarbonate.

Noncarbonate hardness is the hardness caused by calcium and magnesium in excess of the carbonate hardness.

Specific conductance is a measure of the ability of a water sample to conduct electricity. It gives a rough measure of the degree of mineralization of the water.

DEFINITION OF TERMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

The terms of hydrologic data used in this report are defined as follows:

Streamflow station, or gaging station, is a site on a stream or canal where observations of gage height and discharge are obtained. In general, there are three types of streamflow stations.

a. Continuous-record station is a site where continuous record of stage and discharge is obtained. Information collected is used for various management, planning, hydrologic analysis, and project purposes.

b. Partial-record station is a site where limited streamflow data are collected systematically over a period of years for use in hydrologic analyses.

c. Miscellaneous-record station is a site where special-purpose streamflow data are collected on a non-systematic basis.

pH is the negative logarithm of the hydrogen-ion concentration expressed in gram-moles per liter. However, when determined with a pH meter, which is the procedure normally used in Geological Survey laboratories, pH is an expression of the hydrogen-ion activity or the effective hydrogen-ion concentration. A neutral solution has a pH of 7; pH less than 7 indicates acidity, and pH greater than 7 indicates alkalinity.

Land-surface datum (lsd) is a datum plane that is approximately at the natural land surface at a well.

Mean sea level (msl) is the datum plane on which the Island-wide network of precise levels is based.

DOWNSTREAM ORDER AND STATION NUMBERS

Streamflow stations are listed in a downstream direction along the main stem of a stream, with all stations on a tributary entering above a main-stem station listed before that station. If a tributary enters between two main-stem stations, it is listed between them. A similar order is followed listing stations on first rank, second rank, and other ranks of tributaries. To indicate the rank of any tributary on which a streamflow station is situated, and the stream to which it is immediately tributary, each indentation in the listing of streamflow stations in the table of contents of this report represents one rank. This downstream order and system of indentation shows which stations are on tributaries between any two stations on a main-stream and the rank of the tributary on which each station is situated.

Each recording and partial-record streamflow station has been assigned a station number in downstream order. No distinction is made between continuous-record and partial-record stations in assigning station numbers. In addition to assignment by downstream order, station numbers are determined by the station's location on each island. The numbering of stations begins at the northwest corner of each Island, basin by basin in clockwise direction around the island. Gaps are left between numbers to allow for streamflow stations that later may be established; hence the numbers are not consecutive.

EXPLANATION OF DATA

Surface Water

Continuous Streamflow Stations

The base data collected at streamflow stations consist of records of stage and measurements of discharge. In addition, observations of factors affecting the stage-discharge relation, weather records, and other information are used to supplement base data. The records of stage obtained either from direct readings of a non-recording gage or from a water-stage recorder that makes a continuous record of river stage. Measurements of discharge are made with a current meter by the general methods adopted by the Geological Survey on the basis of experience in stream gaging since 1888. These methods are described in Water-Supply Paper 888 and also are outlined in textbooks on the measurement of stream discharge.

Rating tables giving the discharge for any stage are prepared from stage-discharge relation curves defined by discharge measurements. If extensions to the rating curves are necessary to define the extremes of discharge, they are made on the basis of indirect measurements of peak discharge (such as slope-area or contraction measurements, computation of flow over dams or weirs, and by other methods), velocity-area studies, and logarithmic plotting. The application of the daily mean gage height to the rating tables gives the daily mean discharge, from which the monthly and the yearly mean discharge are computed. If the stage-discharge relation is subject to change because of frequent or continual change in the physical features that form the control, the daily mean discharge is determined by the shifting-control method, in which correction factors based on individual discharge measurements and notes by engineers and observers are used in applying the gage heights to the rating tables. If the stage-discharge relation for a station is temporarily changed by the presence of aquatic growth or debris on the control, the daily mean discharge is computed by what is essentially the shifting-control method.

For some streamflow stations, there are periods when no gage-height record is obtained or the recorded gage height is so faulty that it cannot be used to compute the daily discharge.

This happens when the recorder stops or otherwise fails to operate properly, when intakes are plugged, or for various other reasons. For such periods the daily discharge is estimated on the basis of recorded range in stage, adjoining good record, discharge measurements, weather records, and comparison with other station records from the same or nearby basins.

The streamflow data presented in this report for continuous-record station is comprised of a description of the station, and a table showing daily, monthly, and yearly discharge of the stream. Records are published on a calendar-year basis.

The description of the station gives the location, drainage area, records available, type and history of gages, extremes of stage and discharge, and general remarks. The location of the station is determined from the most accurate maps available and from field observations and notes. Drainage area is obtained from U.S. Geological Survey topographic maps. Under "Records available" are given the periods and types of records which have been collected at the site. Under "Gage" are given the type of gage currently in use, the datum of gage above mean sea level.

Under "Extremes" are given the maximum and minimum values for selected data at the station. If a particular maximum or minimum value is affected by factors such as diversion, regulation, etc., it is so indicated either in "Extremes" or under "Remarks." In the first paragraph, the data given are for each calendar year of record included in this report unless otherwise specified. In the second paragraph, the data given are for the period of record within the calendar years indicated in the heading of the paragraph. Reliable information concerning major floods that have occurred outside the period of record is given in the third or last paragraph. Information pertaining to the accuracy of the records and to conditions which affect the natural flow or the water quality at the streamflow station is given under "Remarks."

For stations equipped with water-stage recorders, the table of daily discharge gives the discharge corresponding to the daily mean gage height, unless there are large or rapid changes in discharge during a day. For days having these large or rapid changes, discharge for the day is computed by averaging the mean discharge for

several parts of a day. For stations equipped with nonrecording gages, the table of daily discharge gives the discharge corresponding to once-daily readings of the gage, or to the mean of twice-daily readings, or to the mean gage height determined from a synthetic gage-height graph based on gage readings. For periods of rapidly changing stage, the daily mean discharge is determined from a gage-height graph based on gage readings, the frequency of which is stated in the station description.

In the table of daily discharge, the figures for the maximum day and minimum day for each month are underlined. If two or more days have the same figure, it is underlined only on the first day of its occurrence.

In the monthly summary below the daily table, the line headed "Total" gives the sum of the daily figures; it is the total cfs-days for the month. The line headed "Mean" gives the average flow in cubic feet per second during the month. Discharge for the month is expressed in thousands of gallons.

In the yearly summary below the monthly summary, the figure for maximum is the maximum daily discharge, not the momentary discharge when the water was at crest stage. Likewise, the minimum in this summary is the minimum daily discharge.

Peak discharge and the time of its occurrence and corresponding gage height for most stations are listed below the table of daily and montly discharge. All independent peaks above the selected base are given. The base discharge, which is given in parentheses, is selected so that an average of about three peaks a year can be presented. Peak discharges usually are not published for any stream for which the peaks are subject to substantial control by man.

Footnotes to the table of daily discharge indicate periods for which the discharge was computed or estimated by unusual or special methods because of no gage-height record or other conditions that reduce the accuracy of the records. The footnotes are either reference footnotes, with corresponding symbols used in the table of daily discharge to indicate the days included; or they are general footnotes, introduced by the word "Note," in which the days

included are stated. The methods used in computing data for such footnoted periods have been explained in preceding paragraphs.

Partial-Record Stations

As the number of streams on which information is desired far exceeds the number of stations feasible to operate at one time, the Geological Survey collects limited data at sites other than continuous streamflow stations. When limited data are collected on a systematic basis over a period of years, the site at which the data are collected is called a "partial-record station." Records for partial-record stations are used in low-flow or flood-flow analyses, water-quality variation studies, etc., depending on the type of data collected.

In addition, measurements are made at sites not included in the partial-record network, generally in times of drought or of flood to give better areal coverage. These measurements, and other collected for some special reasons, are called measurements at miscellaneous sites.

Generally, streamflow data are collected at partial-record stations in conjunction with quality-of-water data. Most partial-record station data are given in this report in combined surface-water and quality-of-water tables because of this close interrelation.

A separate section for miscellaneous data in a river basin follows the information presented for other types of streamflow stations. This miscellaneous-records section also is presented in a downstream order. Each station location is described briefly, and drainage area, type of data, period of record, etc., are included if available. The data collected for a miscellaneous station are listed in a table following the station description.

Measurements of discharge by indirect methods are made at streamflow stations of all types. These measurements are made following noteworthy floods, sometimes at locations where conditions prohibit measurements by current meter.

Additional information on streamflow stations in the Virgin Islands can be obtained by request to the Caribbean District, Water Resources Division, U.S. Geological Survey, San Juan, Puerto Rico.

Quality of Water

The quality-of-water investigations of the U.S. Geological Survey are concerned with chemical and physical characteristics of surface-water and ground-water supplies. Most of the investigations deal with the amount of matter in solution and in suspension, in streams and underground. Samples for chemical analyses usually are collected at, or near, points on streams where streamflow stations are maintained for measurement of water discharge, and at ground-water observation wells.

Chemical analyses and water temperature of streamflow often serve as a basis for determining the suitability of water for industrial, agricultural, and domestic uses. Stream discharge, and chemical quality to a lesser extent, are related to variations in rainfall. In general, lower concentrations of dissolved minerals may be expected during periods of high flow than during periods of low flow. The concentration in some streams may change materially with relatively small variations in flow, whereas for other streams the quality may remain relatively uniform throughout a wide range in discharge.

Records of chemical analyses and water temperature for selected ground-water observation wells and locations are a basis for determining suitability of water for most of the uses listed above for surface waters. These records also are used as an aid in determining ground-water origin and movement, and the composition of the material through which the water has passed.

A descriptive statement is given for each quality-of-water data station, usually combined with the description for a streamflow station or observation-well station. This statement includes the location of the sampling station, drainage area, period of record, records available, and selected extremes. Records of streamflow at the time of sampling are included in most tables of chemical analyses.

Expression of Results

The dissolved mineral constituents are reported in milligrams per liter (equivalent to parts per million in dilute solutions). A calculated quantity of sodium and potassium is given in many analyses, which is the quantity

of sodium needed in addition to the calcium and magnesium to balance the acid constituents. In most waters of moderate to high concentration, the proportion of potassium is much smaller than that of sodium.

The hardness, as calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), is calculated from the equivalents of calcium and magnesium. The hardness caused by calcium and magnesium (and other ions if significant) equivalent to the carbonate and bicarbonate is called carbonate hardness; the hardness in excess of this quantity is called non-carbonate hardness.

This discharge of the stream is reported in gallons per minute and the temperature in degrees Celsius (centigrade, $^{\circ}\text{C}$). Color is expressed in units of the platinum-cobalt scale proposed by Hazen. Hydrogen-ion concentration (pH) is given as the negative logarithm of the number of moles of ionized hydrogen per liter of water.

Composition of Surface Water

Dissolved minerals.--All natural waters contain dissolved mineral matter. Water in contact with soils or rock, even for only a few hours, will dissolve some rock materials. The quantity of dissolved mineral matter in a natural water depends primarily on the type of rocks or soils through which the water has passed and the length of time it has been in contact with the rocks or soils. Streams are fed both by surface runoff and by underground water from springs or seeps. They reflect the chemical character of their concentrated underground sources during dry periods and are more dilute during periods of heavy rainfall. Underground water usually is more highly concentrated than surface runoff because it remains in contact with the rocks and soils for much longer periods. The concentration of dissolved solids in a river water frequently is increased by drainage from mines or oil fields, by the addition of industrial or municipal wastes, or by water excess to irrigation of crops.

The mineral constituents and physical properties of natural waters reported in the tables of analyses in this report include those that have a practical bearing on the value of the waters for most purposes. The analyses generally include concentration of silica, iron,

calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, bicarbonate, sulfate, chloride, fluoride, nitrate, and dissolved solids. Color, pH, and other dissolved constituents and physical properties are reported for certain streams.

Ground Water

Water-level data presented in this report were obtained from a network of observation wells located at significant places in important aquifers. Ground-water data tables follow those for streamflow stations in a stream basin. Data from observation wells outside defined drainage basins are included in this report with the records for a nearby basin.

Water-level measurements are given in feet with reference to land-surface datum (lsd). Land-surface datum is approximately at land surface at each well. If known, the altitude of the land-surface datum above mean sea level is given in the well description. The height of the measuring point (MP) above or below land-surface datum is given in each well description. The water level in wells equipped with recording gages is given for every fifth day and for the end of each month.

In the collection of water-level data to serve the objectives of the observation-well program, the need generally is to measure changes in water level, rather than to determine the absolute position of the water surface. Because measurements are made in many types of wells and under varying conditions, neither the method of measurement nor the equipment can be standardized. At each observation well, however, the best possible combination of measuring technique and equipment is selected, and if no changes are made, the measurement at each well will be consistent.

Water levels are reported to as many significant figures as can be justified by measuring conditions and the use of the information. In general, measurements are reported to a hundredth of a foot, but some may be to tenths or whole feet.

A well description precedes each data table. Included in this description are the type, geology, and location of the well, the extremes of water level, and the period of record.

SUPPLEMENTAL DATA

Information of a more detailed nature than that published for many streamflow and ground-water stations is on file in the USGS office. This information includes discharge measurements, stage readings, chemical and physical parameters, and diverse well information. It may be obtained by request or inspected at Caribbean District, Water Resources Division, U.S. Geological Survey, Building 652, Fort Buchanan, Puerto Rico 00934.

SELECTED REFERENCES

- Corbett, D. M. and others, 1943, Stream-gaging procedure, a manual describing methods and practices of the Geological Survey: U.S. Geol. Survey Water-Supply Paper 888, 245 p.
- Lane, E. W. and others, 1947, Report of subcommittee on sediment terminology: Am. Geophys. Union Trans., v. 28, no. 6, p. 936-938.

Figure 1.--Geographic setting of the Virgin Islands of the United States.

Figure 2.--Locations of stations in St. Thomas.

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1963

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	33	23	14	39	61	23	14	70	41	22	22	16
2	34	43	14	39	39	34	14	440	36	19	22	16
3	47	39	14	39	39	43	14	70	47	19	19	16
4	49	14	14	34	39	43	14	39	31	19	60	16
5	23	14	14	34	39	34	14	38	31	19	19	16
6	14	14	14	34	43	23	131	34	36	16	19	16
7	14	14	14	67	43	23	330	34	31	16	50	16
8	14	14	14	1,460	43	23	39	45	31	19	55	16
9	14	14	14	520	43	23	23	43	26	16	40	16
10	14	14	14	100	39	23	23	39	22	16	22	16
11	14	14	14	61	375	23	23	34	26	16	22	16
12	14	14	14	43	165	23	14	34	22	16	19	16
13	14	14	23	39	330	23	14	34	26	360	19	16
14	14	14	23	34	180	23	14	34	22	150	19	13
15	14	14	14	34	87	23	14	34	22	41	19	13
16	14	14	14	260	120	23	14	34	26	31	19	13
17	14	14	14	107	1,300	23	14	23	22	26	19	13
18	14	14	14	61	1,400	14	14	23	22	22	22	13
19	14	14	14	43	122	14	14	23	22	19	19	13
20	14	14	14	43	93	14	14	34	22	26	22	13
21	14	14	14	34	48	14	23	54	19	19	22	13
22	14	14	14	34	39	14	34	39	19	22	19	13
23	14	14	14	34	34	14	23	34	19	100	19	13
24	14	14	23	23	39	14	45	23	19	31	19	13
25	14	14	66	23	34	14	23	23	16	26	19	13
26	14	14	350	23	34	14	23	23	54	90	19	13
27	14	14	70	23	34	14	14	290	31	63	70	13
28	23	14	48	23	34	23	14	6,000	22	41	26	13
29	14	--	39	34	34	14	14	2,600	19	31	19	13
30	14	-- -- --	34	131	34	14	14	110	22	26	16	13
31	14	-- -- --	39	-- -- --	34	-- -- --	85	63	-- -- --	22	-- -- --	13
Total	569	455	1,009	3,473	4,999	644	802	10,385	823	1,359	775	442
Mean	18.4	16.2	32.6	116	161	21.5	25.9	335	27.4	43.8	25.8	14.3
Max	49	39	350	1,460	1,400	43	330	6,000	54	360	70	16
Min	14	14	14	23	34	14	14	23	16	16	16	13
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1963 : Total	25,735		Mean	70.5	Max	6,000	Min	13	Cfsm	--	In.	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1964

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	31	28	10	16	8	6	44	10	8	31	6	6
2	26	19	10	16	8	8	16	10	8	13	6	6
3	22	19	10	13	8	11	6	10	8	8	6	6
4	16	16	10	13	8	6	5	10	8	6	6	6
5	13	13	10	13	8	5	5	8	6	6	6	6
6	19	13	10	13	8	6	5	8	6	6	6	6
7	16	16	10	13	8	6	5	8	6	6	6	6
8	20	13	8	13	8	6	5	8	6	6	6	44
9	16	16	8	13	8	6	5	8	6	6	25	13
10	16	13	8	10	8	8	5	8	6	6	8	8
11	16	35	13	8	8	6	8	8	6	6	10	8
12	26	19	10	67	8	6	50	8	6	6	10	8
13	26	102	19	13	8	6	93	8	6	6	8	8
14	26	27	22	13	8	6	13	8	6	6	6	8
15	22	22	19	8	8	6	13	8	6	6	6	8
16	22	19	16	8	8	6	10	8	6	6	6	8
17	19	19	13	8	8	6	10	8	6	6	6	8
18	19	16	10	8	8	6	10	8	6	6	6	8
19	13	16	10	8	8	6	10	8	6	6	6	8
20	25	19	10	8	8	6	10	8	7	6	6	8
21	16	16	10	8	8	6	10	8	23	6	6	8
22	16	13	10	10	8	6	10	6	47	6	6	8
23	16	13	10	8	6	6	10	18	24	6	6	8
24	13	13	8	8	6	6	10	24	13	6	6	8
25	13	13	8	8	40	6	10	22	38	10	44	8
26	13	13	10	8	10	6	10	16	8	13	6	8
27	13	13	54	8	27	5	66	16	8	6	6	8
28	13	13	22	8	13	5	13	54	8	6	8	8
29	13	10	19	8	10	5	13	22	8	6	8	8
30	13	---	16	8	8	5	10	13	8	6	8	8
31	13	---	16	---	6	---	10	13	---	6	---	8
Total	561	577	419	364	302	184	500	382	319	231	255	275
Mean	18.1	19.9	13.5	12.1	9.74	6.13	16.1	12.3	10.6	7.45	8.50	8.87
Max	31	102	54	67	40	11	93	54	47	31	44	44
Min	13	10	8	8	6	5	5	6	5	6	6	6
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1964 : Total	4,369		Mean	11.9	Max	102	Min	5	Cfsm	--	In.	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1965

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	13	5	3.5	3.5	10	19	13	13	14	10	16	72
2	8	5	3.5	3.5	10	16	13	10	10	28	16	63
3	6	5	3.5	4	10	16	10	13	8	18	16	41
4	8	5	3.5	147	171	16	10	8	10	10	2,270	36
5	11	5	3.5	36	682	13	13	28	10	13	3,860	36
6	8	5	3.5	55	212	13	13	10	10	39	240	31
7	8	5	3.5	31	83	13	13	10	10	48	105	26
8	6	5	3.5	19	2,036	16	13	10	13	22	63	26
9	8	5	3.5	8	530	16	13	10	13	19	48	26
10	8	5	3.5	6	123	16	13	10	13	19	36	3,064
11	8	5	3.5	5	41	16	13	10	34	16	31	5,241
12	8	5	3.5	5	39	16	13	10	19	19	26	1,360
13	8	5	3.5	5	31	16	13	10	10	19	26	1,889
14	6	5	3.5	5	16	16	13	8	20	16	26	650
15	6	5	3.5	5	13	13	13	8	34	13	26	420
16	6	5	3.5	5	10	13	13	13	8	13	31	240
17	5	5	3.5	5	342	28	13	13	8	56	41	140
18	5	5	3.5	5	120	16	13	18	14	36	2,038	105
19	5	5	3.5	5	55	16	10	10	13	22	640	94
20	5	5	3.5	5	41	13	10	10	13	2,062	1,040	83
21	5	5	3.5	5	31	13	10	6	40	245	2,325	72
22	5	5	3.5	5	26	13	10	10	31	120	530	63
23	5	5	3.5	5	22	16	10	8	48	63	145	55
24	5	5	3.5	5	27	16	10	32	36	55	4,716	5,338
25	5	3.5	3.5	14	22	16	10	60	16	48	3,180	780
26	5	3.5	3.5	6	90	16	30	16	13	41	1,204	1,792
27	5	3.5	3	150	41	16	14	13	13	36	530	650
28	5	3.5	2.5	22	41	19	8	8	19	31	240	530
29	5	--	2.5	16	31	13	8	18	13	26	140	420
30	5	--	2.5	16	26	13	75	10	13	19	83	170
31	5	--	2.5	--	22	--	16	8	--	16	--	140
Total	201	134	104	607	4,954	468	449	411	526	3,198	23,688	23,653
Mean	6.48	4.79	3.34	20.2	160	15.6	14.5	13.3	17.5	103	790	769
Max	13	5	3.5	150	2,036	23	75	60	48	2,062	4,716	5,338
Min	5	3.5	2.5	3.5	10	13	8	6	8	10	16	26
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-Fb	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1965 : Total	58,393											
Mean	160											
Max	5,338											
Min	2.5											
Cfsm	--											
In.	--											

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1966

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	140	94	48	48	22	22	22	19	19	72	31	31
2	170	83	48	48	22	22	22	16	19	140	31	31
3	794	72	48	48	22	22	37	22	19	94	31	103
4	320	72	72	48	22	22	36	22	19	72	31	41
5	170	72	63	48	22	22	26	22	19	55	31	31
6	120	72	72	48	22	22	26	22	19	41	31	31
7	105	63	48	48	26	22	26	22	35	41	31	31
8	94	63	48	41	26	22	26	32	31	36	47	31
9	94	63	48	41	31	26	26	26	36	48	48	31
10	83	63	55	41	31	31	26	26	2,710	36	36	26
11	72	63	48	41	31	31	22	26	420	31	31	26
12	200	55	55	41	31	31	22	22	94	1,481	31	26
13	1,350	48	48	36	26	31	19	19	41	780	31	26
14	420	36	48	41	26	31	31	16	31	240	31	64
15	170	36	48	41	26	147	31	16	26	120	31	117
16	140	36	229	41	26	63	19	16	22	33	31	36
17	94	72	94	36	26	41	48	13	22	63	31	31
18	83	63	101	36	26	36	31	13	19	41	31	177
19	83	63	1,400	31	31	36	22	8	16	41	31	36
20	83	63	240	26	31	36	39	10	1,308	48	31	31
21	72	55	94	26	31	31	36	10	170	41	31	31
22	112	55	959	22	36	31	194	23	83	48	78	31
23	72	55	105	22	31	26	55	6	170	41	36	41
24	72	55	63	19	26	26	41	6	83	36	163	41
25	72	55	55	19	26	36	26	8	48	36	36	36
26	72	55	48	19	26	31	26	8	41	31	31	31
27	72	55	48	26	31	31	22	39	36	31	31	41
28	72	48	48	26	31	31	19	22	2,241	36	31	36
29	730	--	48	26	26	31	19	19	780	31	31	31
30	420	--	63	22	26	26	19	19	140	31	31	31
31	120	--	48	--	26	--	19	19	--	31	--	36
Total	6,671	1,685	4,440	1,056	842	1,016	1,033	567	8,717	3,956	1,157	1,343
Mean	215	60.2	143	35.2	27.2	33.9	33.3	18.3	291	128	38.6	43.3
Max	1,350	94	1,400	48	36	147	194	39	2,710	1,481	163	177
Min	72	36	48	19	22	22	19	6	16	31	31	26
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1966 : Total	32,483		Mean	89.0	Max	2,710	Min	6	Cfsm	--	In.	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1967

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	19	36	78	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
2	31	26	36	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
3	31	26	31	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
4	31	26	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
5	31	26	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
6	31	26	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
7	31	26	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
8	36	26	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
9	31	26	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
10	31	26	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
11	31	26	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
12	31	26	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
13	26	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
14	26	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
15	26	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
16	26	77	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
17	210	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
18	63	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
19	48	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
20	41	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
21	36	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
22	31	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
23	31	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
24	53	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
25	36	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
26	31	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
27	31	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
28	31	109	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
29	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
30	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
31	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Total	1,189	844	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Mean	38.4	30.1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Max	210	109	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Min	19	22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1967 : Total	--	--	Mean	--	Max	--	Min	--	Cfsm	--	In.	--

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Dec. 30, 1962	10.8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	245	--	--	--	--	--	174	--	--	--	22	--
Feb. 23, 1963	8.4	25	0.02	--	39	24	375	712	16	55	240	0.06	6.5	--	* 1,150	196	0	1,870	8.3	22	--
Apr. 20	11.7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	195	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--	23	--
May 25	25.1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--	--	114	--	--	--	25	--
June 22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--	--	148	--	--	--	28	--
Aug. 24	13.7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	125	--	--	--	--	224	--	--	--	26	--
Sept. 10	19.2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	262	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--	27	--
Sept. 28	17.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	102	--	--	--	26	--
Oct. 12	10.4	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--	--	126	--	--	--	27	--
Oct. 26	16.5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	178	--	--	--	24	--
Nov. 16	15.0	26	.00	--	34	36	363	772	0	51	235	.5	3.8	--	* 1,110	233	0	1,820	8.1	24	--
Nov. 30	12.2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	280	--	--	--	--	186	--	--	--	24	--
Dec. 7	11.5	25	.06	--	42	34	377	808	0	60	238	.5	2.3	--	* 1,100	245	0	1,880	7.7	24	--
Jan. 25, 1964	8.9	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	232	--	--	--	22	--
Feb. 29	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--	--	214	--	--	--	23	--
Mar. 15	10.8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--	23	--
Mar. 28	--	21	.00	--	32	35	270	572	0	48	205	.6	2.3	--	* 960	224	0	1,570	8.1	25	--
Apr. 25	5.7	21	.15	--	24	36	360	652	12	66	258	.5	4.0	--	* 1,080	208	0	1,860	8.3	27	--
May 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--	--	156	--	--	--	28	--
May 23	6.5	26	.00	--	36	36	346	696	0	50	258	.6	2.0	--	* 1,120	238	0	1,890	8.1	--	--
June 20	6.2	25	.00	--	36	33	315	636	0	46	240	.7	1.7	--	* 1,020	225	0	1,770	8.2	26	--
June 20	--	25	.02	--	36	34	313	638	0	45	240	.5	.7	--	* 1,010	230	0	1,770	7.9	26	--
July 18	8.35	24	.00	--	44	41	373	736	0	68	292	.7	2.3	--	* 1,230	278	0	2,050	8.0	26	--
July 25	7.9	24	.00	--	58	28	341	688	0	55	265	.7	2.3	--	* 1,120	260	0	1,890	8.0	27	--
Aug. 22	4.6	25	.00	--	40	39	353	704	0	56	275	.8	2.3	--	* 1,150	260	0	1,910	7.9	27	--
Sept. 19	4	26	.00	--	36	39	369	730	0	57	280	.4	.0	--	* 1,250	250	0	1,990	8.0	27	6
Oct. 23	7.0	24	.00	--	36	32	336	654	10	46	248	.3	1.8	--	* 1,110	222	0	1,790	8.3	25	30
Nov. 21	3.5	30	.00	--	44	40	446	956	0	56	283	.7	1.0	--	* 1,197	275	0	2,010	8.0	24	10
Dec. 21	5.5	23	.02	--	44	41	331	686	0	60	262	.6	2.9	--	* 1,140	278	0	1,880	7.8	22	12
Jan. 18, 1965	2.9	24	.02	--	48	39	368	734	0	64	290	.5	1.0	--	* 1,180	280	0	2,020	8.1	22	22
Feb. 15	4.0	24	.00	--	34	38	366	696	12	24	298	.6	1.3	--	* 1,160	242	0	2,060	8.3	22	10
Mar. 15	--	24	.00	--	32	44	367	716	8	18	310	.6	1.1	--	* 1,180	261	0	2,070	8.3	23	--
Apr. 26	5.3	22	.02	--	48	40	295	678	20	12	225	.7	.6	--	* 1,160	284	0	2,050	8.3	24	5
May 5	750	14	.09	--	22	23	169	270	0	61	160	.5	6.2	--	* 649	150	0	1,000	7.8	24	10
May 24	15.4	24	.00	--	50	36	312	614	10	70	245	.6	14	--	* 1,040	273	0	1,750	8.3	24	20
June 22	8.0	25	.00	--	56	40	372	734	10	74	290	.6	8.8	--	* 1,190	304	0	2,070	8.3	24	5
July 12	--	24	.00	--	48	41	371	724	12	58	295	.6	5.1	--	* 1,210	288	0	2,070	8.3	26	5
Aug. 8	--	18	.00	--	28	24	243	470	0	42	188	.6	2.4	--	* 785	168	0	1,340	7.9	27	15
Sept. 17	--	23	.00	--	40	29	312	626	8	36	235	.7	1.3	--	* 968	219	0	1,730	8.3	29	15
Sept. 24	23.0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--	--	188	--	--	--	27	--
Oct. 15	9.7	24	.00	--	44	28	320	674	14	32	218	.6	3.3	--	* 1,040	225	0	1,770	8.3	26	10
Oct. 27	23.1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	196	--	--	--	26	--
Nov. 5	355	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--	--	68	--	--	--	24	--
Nov. 11	20	27	.00	--	48	33	300	580	0	104	220	.6	14	--	* 970	256	0	1,630	8.0	26	--
Nov. 19	150	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--	--	119	--	--	--	24	--
Nov. 26	--	22	.04	0.00	16	12	90	196	0	20	72	.0	2.7	--	* 358	90	0	588	7.8	26	30
Nov. 26	--	27	.00	--	50	35	281	540	0	100	225	.6	18	--	* 947	269	0	1,600	8.1	26	--
Dec. 3	37.5	24	.00	--	44	28	320	702	--	32	218	.6	3.3	--	* 1,040	225	0	1,770	8.3	26	10
Dec. 19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	50	--	--	--	--	132	--	--	--	23	--
Dec. 20	58	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	23	--
Dec. 27	--	23	.03	.00	24	14	148	294	4	26	115	.1	5.2	--	* 520	118	0	870	8.3	--	20
Jan. 10, 1966	53.6	25	.01	.00	40	29	257	504	10	40	215	.1	4.8	--	* 900	219	0	1,510	8.4	--	15

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color			
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃		
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non- carbonate	
Dec. 27, 1965	--	23	0.03	0.00	24	14	148	294	4	26	115	0.1	5.2	--	* 520	118	0	870	8.3	--	20	
Jan. 10, 1966	53.6	26	.01	.00	40	29	257	504	10	40	215	.1	4.8	--	* 900	219	0	1,510	8.4	--	15	
Jan. 17	60	24	.02	.00	32	29	240	474	8	44	186	.5	12	--	* 905	199	0	1,380	8.3	23	5	
Jan. 24	53.5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	22	--	--
Jan. 31	68.2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--	--	176	--	--	--	22	--	--
Feb. 7	50	25	.02	.00	36	34	290	566	8	52	226	1.0	11	--	* 927	230	0	1,640	8.3	21	10	
Feb. 14	35.8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	192	--	--	--	22	--	--
Feb. 21	28	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--	--	216	--	--	--	23	--	--
Feb. 28	8.1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--	--	208	--	--	--	23	--	--
Mar. 7	37	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	245	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	37	--	--
Mar. 14	33.3	25	.01	.00	39	25	312	560	12	54	242	.1	3.2	--	* 1,000	200	0	1,680	8.4	23	10	
Mar. 21	68.2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--	23	--	--
Mar. 28	15	25	.01	.00	36	28	276	548	12	36	209	.1	4.0	--	* 928	205	0	1,550	8.3	23	20	
Apr. 4	10.9	25	.00	.00	34	26	310	560	10	54	235	.0	3.7	--	* 961	192	0	1,640	8.4	24	10	
Apr. 11	30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	24	--	--
Apr. 18	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	236	--	--	--	--	--	--
Apr. 25	.95	25	.01	.00	44	33	326	640	16	52	252	.1	4.8	--	* 1,070	246	0	1,820	8.3	23	15	
May 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--	--	328	--	--	--	--	--	--
May 9	37.5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	216	--	--	--	24	--	--
May 16	.3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--	--	212	--	--	--	24	--	--
May 23	23.1	26	.01	.00	38	32	452	1,332	0	42	48	.8	5	--	* 1,060	227	0	1,760	8.2	24	20	
May 30	18.3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--	--	192	--	--	--	25	--	--
June 6	0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	270	--	--	--	--	236	--	--	--	26	--	--
June 13	0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	280	--	--	--	--	232	--	--	--	27	--	--
June 24	--	28	.00	.00	28	36	358	664	8	54	268	.4	4.3	--	* 1,168	218	0	1,900	8.5	27	20	
July 2	--	28	.00	.00	45	35	353	708	0	43	276	.6	8.5	--	* 1,170	256	0	1,950	8.2	28	10	
July 8	--	27	.03	.00	31	32	359	650	8	45	275	1.0	7.4	--	* 1,140	209	0	1,880	8.3	30	10	
Aug. 29	7.15	26	.01	.00	44	36	345	680	6	45	275	.7	4.4	--	* 1,170	258	0	1,920	8.3	28	20	
Sept. 28	682	19	.00	.00	10	10	72	166	0	17	48	.2	1.5	--	* 347	66	0	442	7.4	24	70+	
Oct. 31	--	25	.00	.00	46	35	309	664	0	54	231	.5	4.1	--	* 1,040	259	0	1,790	8.1	--	30	
Nov. 30	--	22	.34	.00	32	41	210	502	0	36	176	.3	8.4	--	* 820	248	0	1,390	8.0	29	70+	
Jan. 3, 1967	--	26	.00	.00	24	47	310	616	6	56	245	.3	8.9	--	* 1,130	253	0	1,780	8.3	--	4.0	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

2580. Lovenlund Gut at Lovenlund, St. Thomas, V.I.

Location.--Lat 18° 21' 39", long 64° 54' 28", 400 ft north of Lovenlund Road, 0.2 mile east of Estate Lovenlund, and 0.7 mile upstream from Atlantic Ocean.

Drainage area.--0.55 sq mi.

Records available.--Indirect discharge measurement of 1963 flood which occurred on Aug. 28, discharge 89,800 gpm.

2740. Turpentine Run at Mt. Zion, St. Thomas, V.I.

Location.--Lat 18° 19' 56", long 64° 53' 20", on left bank 1.8 miles upstream from mouth and 2.7 miles east of Fort Christian, Charlotte Amalie.

Drainage area.--2.32 sq mi.

Records available.--Discharge: January 1963 to December 1969.

Chemical analyses: 1962-68.

Gage.--Water-stage recorder with 90-degree V-notch weir in concrete control. Altitude of gage is 90 ft (from topographic map).

Extremes.--Maximums and minimums (discharge in gallons per minute, gage height in feet).

Annual maximum discharge for years 1963-69				Annual minimum discharge for years 1963-69			
Date	Time	Discharge	Gage height	Year	Date	Discharge	Gage height
Aug. 28, 1963	2200	150,000	3.33	1963	Dec. 17	4	0.10
Nov. 9, 1964	0430	120	.40	1964	Nov. 6	0.5	.05
Dec. 10, 1965	0015	65,000	2.95	1965	Many days	No flow	--
Oct. 11, 1966	1745	20,000	2.41	1966	Aug. 24	3	.09
May 11, 1967	0015	1,000	.99	1967	Sept. 4 to 10	.14	.02
Aug. 8, 1968	1145	12,000	2.18	1968	Many days	No flow	--
May 23, 1969	1600	2,250,000	5.00	1969	Jan. 13 to 14	4	.10

1963-1969: Maximum discharge 2,250,000 gpm May 23, 1969 (gage height 5.00 ft); minimum discharge many days of no flow in 1965 and 1968.

Remarks.--Discharge records fair below 3740 tgd and poor above.

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1963

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	58	58	17	30	190	26	15	26	89	20	11	15
2	58	342	17	30	69	23	13	237	52	20	11	15
3	76	69	17	30	48	23	15	39	43	17	11	15
4	121	43	17	30	35	23	13	23	43	17	9	13
5	58	43	17	35	23	20	13	17	43	17	9	13
6	43	35	17	39	26	17	436	17	429	17	13	13
7	39	30	17	124	30	17	315	15	252	17	11	13
8	35	30	17	154	26	17	63	23	157	17	11	13
9	35	30	17	189	682	17	30	291	104	15	15	13
10	35	30	17	112	213	15	23	39	63	15	13	13
11	39	30	17	58	260	15	17	26	63	15	11	13
12	39	30	15	43	477	15	15	20	43	15	11	13
13	43	26	15	30	1,070	15	15	17	39	15	9	13
14	48	26	15	23	825	15	15	15	35	15	9	13
15	52	35	15	20	308	15	15	15	53	15	7	13
16	39	30	15	37	167	15	13	15	58	15	7	13
17	39	30	15	121	276	15	15	15	39	15	5.5	13
18	30	26	15	30	532	15	15	15	48	15	11	13
19	30	26	15	26	406	13	13	15	52	15	15	13
20	30	26	15	20	178	13	13	15	39	15	15	13
21	26	23	13	17	97	13	11	15	30	15	15	13
22	26	23	13	17	63	11	11	15	26	17	9	13
23	23	17	13	17	52	11	11	15	23	20	62	13
24	23	17	13	17	48	11	11	15	20	17	17	13
25	30	17	41	17	43	11	11	15	17	17	17	13
26	35	17	468	17	39	11	11	15	26	15	13	13
27	30	17	58	17	39	11	11	80	43	20	66	13
28	35	17	48	17	39	17	11	4,880	30	15	23	11
29	39	--	35	17	35	13	11	3,830	23	15	15	11
30	43	--	30	446	35	26	11	626	20	11	15	11
31	48	--	30	--	30	--	26	190	--	11	--	11
Total	1,305	1,143	1,084	1,780	6,361	479	1,218	10,611	2,002	495	466	401
Mean	42.1	40.8	35.0	59.3	205	16.0	39.3	342	66.7	16.0	15.5	12.9
Max	121	342	468	446	1,070	26	436	4,880	429	20	66	15
Min	23	17	13	17	23	11	11	15	17	11	5.5	11
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1963 : Total	27,345		Mean	74.9	Max	4,880	Min	5.5	Cfsm	--	In.	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1964

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	11	7.2	5.5	4	4	2.8	5.5	1.9	1.9	5.5	1.2	1.2
2	13	17	5.5	4	4	2.8	2.8	1.9	1.2	2.8	1.2	1.2
3	13	13	5.5	5.5	4	2.8	2.8	1.9	1.2	2.8	1.2	1.2
4	13	13	5.5	5.5	4	2.8	1.9	1.9	1.2	1.9	1.2	1.2
5	13	11	5.5	5.5	4	2.8	1.9	1.9	1.2	1.9	1.2	1.2
6	11	11	4	5.5	4	4	1.2	1.9	1.2	1.2	.7	1.2
7	11	13	4	5.5	4	4	1.2	1.9	1.2	1.2	.7	1.2
8	11	11	4	5.5	4	4	1.2	1.9	1.2	1.2	.7	1.2
9	13	9	4	7.2	4	4	1.2	1.9	1.2	1.2	19	1.2
10	13	7.2	4	5.5	4	4	.7	1.9	1.2	1.2	1.9	1.2
11	13	11	4	5.5	2.8	4	.7	1.9	5.5	1.2	1.9	1.2
12	13	9	5.5	4	2.8	4	7.2	1.9	5.5	1.2	1.9	1.2
13	13	7.2	5.5	5.5	2.8	4	5.5	1.9	5.5	1.2	4	1.2
14	17	7.2	5.5	9	2.8	4	2.8	1.9	5.5	1.2	1.9	1.2
15	13	7.2	5.5	5.5	2.8	2.8	1.9	1.9	4	1.2	1.2	1.2
16	11	7.2	5.5	5.5	2.8	2.8	1.9	1.9	2.8	1.2	1.2	1.2
17	11	5.5	5.5	5.5	2.8	2.8	1.9	1.9	2.8	1.2	1.2	1.2
18	11	5.5	5.5	5.5	2.8	2.8	1.9	1.2	2.8	1.2	1.2	1.2
19	11	5.5	5.5	5.5	2.8	2.8	1.9	1.2	1.9	1.2	1.2	1.2
20	13	7.2	5.5	5.5	2.8	2.8	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
21	13	5.5	5.5	9	1.9	2.8	1.2	1.2	5.5	1.2	1.2	1.2
22	9	5.5	5.5	5.5	1.9	5.5	1.2	2.8	11	11	1.2	1.2
23	9	5.5	5.5	5.5	1.9	1.9	1.2	4	7.2	1.9	1.2	1.2
24	9	5.5	5.5	5.5	2.8	1.9	1.2	4	4	1.9	1.2	1.2
25	7.2	5.5	5.5	7.2	2.8	1.9	1.2	1.9	1.9	1.9	2.8	1.2
26	7.2	5.5	5.5	5.5	2.8	1.9	1.2	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.2	1.2
27	7.2	5.5	5.5	5.5	11	1.9	2.8	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.2	1.2
28	7.2	5.5	5.5	5.5	4	1.2	1.2	7.2	1.2	1.9	1.2	1.2
29	7.2	5.5	4	4	2.8	.7	7.2	1.9	4	1.9	1.2	1.2
30	7.2	---	4	4	2.8	.7	4	1.9	9	1.2	1.2	1.2
31	7.2	---	4	---	2.8	---	2.8	1.9	---	1.2	---	1.2
Total	338.4	234.4	157.0	167.9	105.5	87.2	72.5	66.5	97.8	60.8	59.5	37.2
Mean	10.9	8.05	5.06	5.60	3.40	2.91	2.34	2.15	3.26	1.96	1.98	1.20
Max	17	17	5.5	9	11	5.5	7.2	7.2	11	5.5	19	1.2
Min	7.2	5.5	4	4	1.9	.7	.7	1.2	1.2	1.2	.7	1.2
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1964 : Total	1,484.7		Mean	4.06	Max	19	Min	0.7	Cfsm	--	In.	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1965

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	1.2	0.7	0	0	0.4	0.7	0.4	0	0	0.3	0.7	11
2	1.2	.7	0	0	.3	.7	.4	0	0	.3	.7	11
3	1.2	.7	0	0	.2	.7	.4	0	0	.3	.7	11
4	1.2	.7	0	0	.2	.4	.3	0	0	.3	1,127	13
5	1.2	.7	0	0	.2	.7	.3	0	0	.3	4,155	11
6	1.2	.7	0	0	3.0	.7	.3	0	0	.3	843	9
7	1.2	.7	0	0	5.5	.7	.3	0	0	.3	130	9
8	1.2	.7	0	0	4	.7	.3	0	0	.3	69	11
9	1.2	.7	0	0	266	.7	.3	0	0	.2	30	9
10	1.2	.7	0	0	30	.7	.3	0	0	.2	15	8,303
11	1.2	.7	0	0	5.5	.7	.2	0	0	.2	2.8	5,071
12	1.2	.4	0	0	2.8	.7	.2	0	0	.1	1.9	3,461
13	1.2	.4	0	0	1.9	.7	.2	0	.1	0	1.2	2,330
14	1.9	.4	0	0	1.2	.7	.2	0	.1	.3	.7	916
15	4	.3	0	0	.7	.7	.1	0	0	.3	.7	419
16	2.8	.3	0	0	.7	.7	.1	0	0	.4	.7	226
17	1.9	.3	0	0	2.8	.7	.1	0	.2	1.9	.7	138
18	1.2	.3	0	0	2.8	.7	.1	0	.2	.4	.7	104
19	1.2	.3	0	0	1.2	.7	0	0	.2	3.2	.7	76
20	.7	.2	0	0	.7	.4	0	0	.1	623	.7	63
21	.7	.2	0	0	.7	.3	0	0	.7	272	.4	58
22	.7	.2	0	0	.7	.3	0	0	.7	150	.4	52
23	.7	.2	0	0	.7	.3	0	0	9.0	30	.4	48
24	.7	.1	0	0	.7	.3	0	0	.7	13	.4	1,050
25	.7	.1	0	0	4	.3	0	0	.3	9	10.3	309
26	.7	.1	0	0	4	.3	0	0	.4	5.5	902	397
27	.7	.1	0	0	1.9	4.8	0	0	.4	2.8	301	130
28	.7	.1	0	.7	1.9	1.2	0	0	.4	1.9	97	121
29	.7	--	0	.7	1.9	.7	0	0	.4	1.2	23	104
30	.7	--	0	.4	1.9	.4	0	0	.4	1.2	15	82
31	.7	--	0	--	1.2	--	0	0	--	1.2	--	76
Total	37.0	11.7	0	1.8	349.7	22.3	4.5	0	14.3	1,120.4	7,731.8	23,629
Mean	1.19	.42	0	.06	11.3	.74	.15	0	.48	36.1	257	762
Max	4	.07	0	.7	266	4.8	.4	0	9.0	623	4,155	8,303
Min	.7	.1	0	0	.2	.3	0	0	0	0	.4	9
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1965 : Total	32,922		Mean	90.2	Max	8,303	Min	0	Cfsm	--	In.	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1966

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	63	52	23	26	23	13	11	15	5.5	15	17	17
2	76	52	23	26	23	15	11	13	5.5	20	15	15
3	76	48	20	23	23	15	11	13	5.5	15	15	15
4	66	48	23	23	23	15	13	15	5.5	15	15	43
5	63	48	26	23	23	15	11	9	5.5	13	15	92
6	58	43	26	23	23	15	9	9	5.5	13	15	96
7	58	39	23	23	20	15	9	7.2	7.2	13	15	43
8	52	39	23	20	23	15	9	11	7.2	13	15	23
9	52	35	23	23	30	15	9	11	7.2	97	20	17
10	58	35	71	23	23	15	9	9	187	30	57	17
11	63	30	52	23	23	13	9	9	50	1,055	46	17
12	63	30	52	20	23	13	11	9	13	3,242	20	17
13	1,102	35	43	20	20	13	35	7.2	11	1,038	17	17
14	413	35	43	23	20	13	23	7.2	11	1,136	15	17
15	105	35	30	159	20	15	15	7.2	11	504	15	39
16	82	35	30	48	20	17	13	7.2	9	222	17	20
17	76	48	35	35	20	15	15	7.2	9	398	17	17
18	69	48	35	35	17	15	11	5.5	9	157	17	17
19	63	43	165	84	23	15	11	5.5	7.2	97	17	17
20	63	35	96	97	20	15	15	5.5	9	69	17	17
21	63	43	69	43	20	13	13	5.5	7.2	58	26	17
22	58	30	133	30	17	13	17	9	5.5	43	35	17
23	58	30	52	26	17	13	13	5.5	7.2	35	87	113
24	58	30	43	23	17	13	13	4	7.2	39	42	152
25	58	30	43	23	17	13	11	4	7.2	30	35	82
26	58	26	35	23	17	13	11	9	5.5	35	23	30
27	58	26	30	23	17	11	13	5.5	11	35	20	17
28	58	23	35	23	17	11	13	7.2	438	26	17	17
29	58	--	30	20	15	11	11	5.5	60	30	17	17
30	58	--	30	20	15	11	11	5.5	13	23	17	15
31	58	--	30	--	13	--	13	5.5	--	20	--	15
Total	3,364	1,051	1,392	1,031	622	414	399	248.9	942.6	8,536	716	1,065
Mean	109	37.5	44.9	33.4	20.1	13.8	12.9	8.0	31.4	275	23.9	34.4
Max	1,102	52	133	159	30	15	35	15	438	3,242	87	152
Min	52	23	20	20	13	11	9	4	5.5	13	15	15
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1966 : Total	19,781.5											
Mean	54.2											
Max	3,242											
Min	4											
Cfsm	--											
In.	--											

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1967

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	15	15	17	11	9	2.8	1.9	1.2	0.3	0.4	2.8	2.8
2	15	15	15	9	84	2.8	1.9	1.2	.3	.4	2.8	2.8
3	15	13	15	9	243	2.8	1.9	.7	.3	.3	2.8	1.9
4	15	13	15	7.2	36	2.8	1.9	.7	.3	.3	4	1.9
5	15	13	13	7.2	17	2.8	1.9	.7	.2	.3	4	1.9
6	15	13	13	7.2	15	2.8	1.9	.7	.2	.3	4	5.5
7	15	13	13	7.2	15	2.8	1.9	.7	.2	.3	4	2.8
8	15	11	13	7.2	15	2.8	1.9	.7	.2	.3	4	1.9
9	15	11	11	7.2	15	2.8	1.9	.4	.2	.3	4	7.2
10	15	11	11	7.2	13	2.8	1.9	.4	.2	10	4	9
11	13	11	11	7.2	13	2.8	1.9	.4	5.5	373	4	2.8
12	13	11	11	7.2	9	2.8	1.9	.4	2.8	11	4	1.9
13	13	11	9	5.5	7.2	4	1.9	.4	2.8	5.5	2.8	1.9
14	13	11	9	7.2	7.2	4	1.9	.4	1.9	2.8	2.8	1.9
15	13	13	13	7.2	7.2	2.8	1.9	.4	1.9	1.9	11	1.9
16	13	25	11	7.2	9	2.8	1.9	.4	1.9	5.5	4	1.9
17	33	20	11	7.2	7.2	5.5	1.9	.4	1.2	5.5	4	1.9
18	66	20	11	7.2	7.2	4	1.9	.4	1.2	1.9	4	1.9
19	15	20	11	7.2	7.2	4	1.9	.4	1.2	1.9	4	1.9
20	15	20	11	7.2	7.2	4	1.9	.4	.7	1.9	4	1.9
21	15	20	9	7.2	7.2	4	1.9	.4	.7	1.9	2.8	1.2
22	15	20	9	7.2	5.5	2.8	1.9	.4	.7	1.9	2.8	1.2
23	17	20	9	7.2	5.5	2.8	1.9	.4	.7	2.8	2.8	.7
24	15	17	9	12	5.5	5.5	1.9	.4	.4	2.8	2.8	.7
25	15	17	9	11	5.5	5.5	1.2	.4	.4	1.9	2.8	.7
26	15	19	7.2	9	5.5	5.5	1.2	.4	.4	1.9	2.8	.7
27	15	23	7.2	7.2	5.5	4	1.2	.4	.4	1.9	5.5	1.2
28	15	20	7.2	5.5	4	2.8	1.2	.3	.4	1.9	2.8	1.2
29	15	--	7.2	10	4	2.8	1.2	.3	.4	1.9	2.8	1.2
30	15	--	7.2	11	4	1.9	1.2	.3	.4	1.9	2.8	1.2
31	15	--	13	--	4	--	1.2	.3	--	2.8	--	1.2
Total	524	446	338.0	237.0	599.6	102.3	54.0	15.4	28.4	447.4	111.7	68.8
Mean	16.9	15.9	10.9	7.90	19.3	3.41	1.74	0.50	0.95	14.4	3.72	2.22
Max	66	25	17	12	243	5.5	1.9	1.2	5.5	373	11	9
Min	13	11	7.2	5.5	4	1.9	1.2	0.3	0.2	0.3	2.8	0.7
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1967 : Total	2,972.6		Mean	8.14	Max	373	Min	0.2	Cfsm	--	In.	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1968

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	1.2	0.3	1.9	1.2	1.2	0.1	0	1.2	2.8	1.9	0	1,158
2	1.2	.3	1.2	2.8	.7	.1	0	11	2.8	.4	0	368
3	.7	.3	1.2	1.9	.7	.1	0	7.2	2.8	.3	0	104
4	.7	.3	1.2	1.9	.7	.1	.2	7.2	2.8	2.8	.1	39
5	.7	.3	1.2	1.2	.7	0	.3	7.2	2.8	.7	.1	56
6	.7	.3	1.2	1.2	.7	0	.3	7.2	2.8	.7	.1	17
7	.7	.3	1.2	1.2	.4	0	.2	1,983	2.8	.7	.1	7.2
8	.7	.3	1.2	1.2	.4	0	.2	1,905	25	.4	.1	4.0
9	.7	.4	1.2	1.2	.4	0	.2	98	13	.4	.1	13
10	.7	.4	.7	1.2	.4	0	.2	17	7.2	.4	.1	7.2
11	.7	.4	.7	.7	.3	0	.3	2.8	4.0	.4	.1	4.0
12	.7	.4	.7	.7	.3	0	2.8	1.9	5.5	.4	.1	4.0
13	.7	.3	.7	.7	.3	.1	1.9	4.0	4.0	.4	.1	7.2
14	.7	.3	.7	1.2	.2	.1	5.5	5.5	7.2	.4	.1	9.0
15	.7	.3	.7	1.2	.2	.1	1.2	5.5	4.0	.4	1.9	11
16	.7	.3	.4	.7	.2	0	.4	7.2	4.0	.4	1.9	5.5
17	.7	.7	.4	.7	.2	0	.4	7.2	2.8	.4	5.5	4.0
18	.7	.7	38	1.9	.2	0	.7	7.2	2.8	.4	2.8	2.8
19	.7	.4	11	2.8	.3	0	1.2	7.2	2.8	.4	1.9	2.8
20	.7	.4	7.2	1.9	.4	0	.7	7.2	2.8	.4	1.9	2.8
21	.7	.4	4.0	1.2	.4	0	687	7.2	5.5	.4	1.9	2.8
22	.7	.4	2.8	.7	.4	0	17	7.2	5.5	.4	1.2	2.8
23	.4	.4	1.9	.7	.4	0	485	7.2	2.8	.4	1.2	2.8
24	.4	.4	1.2	.7	.3	0	45	7.2	1.2	.4	1.9	2.8
25	.4	.4	1.2	.7	.3	0	11	7.2	1.2	.3	.7	2.8
26	.4	.4	1.2	.7	.3	0	5.5	7.2	1.2	.3	1.9	2.8
27	.4	17	1.2	.7	.3	0	1.2	7.2	2.8	.2	521	2.8
28	.4	7.2	1.2	.7	.2	0	2.8	7.2	2.8	.1	136	20
29	.4	2.8	1.2	.7	.2	0	4.0	7.2	2.8	0	583	11
30	.3	---	1.9	4.0	.2	0	2.8	4.0	1.9	0	573	9
31	.3	---	1.2	---	.2	---	1.9	4.0	---	0	---	7.2
Total	19.8	36.8	91.7	38.3	12.1	0.7	1,279.9	4,172.5	132.4	15.2	1,838.8	1,893.3
Mean	6.39	1.27	2.96	3.19	0.39	0.02	41.3	135	4.41	0.49	61.3	61.1
Max	1.2	17	38	4	1.2	0.1	687	1,983	25	2.8	583	1,158
Min	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.7	0.2	0	0	1.2	1.2	0	0	2.8
Cfsm	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
In.	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Ac-ft	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Year 1968 : Total	9,531.5		Mean	26.0	Max	1,983	Min	0	Cfsm	---	In.	---

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1969

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	7.2	51	11,691	35	20	121	89	70	65	52	58	213
2	7.2	20	764	30	20	112	76	74	63	48	52	20
3	7.2	15	349	30	20	104	95	43	63	43	48	2,801
4	9	13	202	30	20	97	104	43	77	43	48	308
5	79	13	176	30	106	97	89	39	157	43	43	265
6	15	11	112	26	111	82	82	39	89	43	43	375
7	13	11	76	26	69	76	69	39	82	89	52	226
8	11	11	69	26	58	76	63	39	82	52	63	167
9	9	11	63	26	30	69	58	39	63	43	1,871	130
10	9	13	52	26	35	82	52	69	76	39	366	112
11	7.2	13	43	23	30	97	52	48	63	39	157	97
12	7.2	13	39	23	26	426	52	400	177	35	147	97
13	5.5	13	39	20	23	176	52	82	112	35	121	97
14	5.5	11	39	20	34	121	48	63	89	30	112	97
15	11	11	39	36	76	202	48	76	82	30	104	97
16	13	9	35	43	76	112	48	69	76	30	112	97
17	13	9	30	30	97	82	48	63	149	30	104	97
18	11	9	35	26	347	82	43	63	850	43	126	255
19	11	16	35	26	540	82	104	104	423	48	126	193
20	9	26	35	26	360	76	52	200	226	43	97	121
21	9	15	35	23	11,912	82	121	121	311	48	241	121
22	9	13	30	23	1,581	381	82	112	252	43	41,807	239
23	9	13	30	23	108,467	112	63	112	202	43	3,900	178
24	82	11	30	23	8,836	82	63	104	147	43	1,168	138
25	50	9	30	23	3,357	82	63	104	97	43	665	112
26	971	9	26	23	1,026	82	52	104	76	43	399	104
27	334	9	23	23	541	82	52	97	69	39	340	104
28	82	538	23	20	324	82	77	82	58	39	713	170
29	35	--	26	20	226	104	48	89	52	39	496	97
30	26	--	48	20	167	69	43	52	52	264	226	97
31	20	--	35	--	138	--	43	52	--	90	--	97
Total	1,887.0	916	14,259	779	138,673	3,530	2,031	2,691	4,380	1,592	53,805	7,504
Mean	60.9	32.7	460	26.0	4,470	118	65.5	86.8	146	51.4	1,793	242
Max	971	538	11,691	43	108,476	426	121	400	850	264	41,807	2,801
Min	5.5	9	23	20	20	69	43	39	52	30	43	97
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1969 : Total	232,047		Mean	635	Max	108,476	Min	5.5	Cfsm	--	In.	--

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Dec. 18, 1962	25	30	.00	--	52	38	469	890	18	58	340	1.0	5.1	--	--	286	0	2,460	8.4	23	--
Jan. 18, 1963	24.3	26	.02	--	46	40	489	896	0	59	385	1.0	.5	--	*1,530	280	0	2,550	8.0	23	--
Feb. 21	13.4	28	.02	--	48	38	--	906	0	--	342	1.1	.7	--	--	276	0	2,380	8.2	24	--
Mar. 23	10.9	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	310	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	24	--
Apr. 8	61.0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	225	--	--	--	--	216	--	--	--	26	--
Apr. 25	14.9	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	345	--	--	--	--	342	--	--	--	25	--
May 16	194	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	165	--	--	--	--	164	--	--	--	27	--
May 20	115.8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--	--	154	--	--	--	27	--
June 18	13.5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	400	--	--	--	--	268	--	--	--	26	--
Aug. 29	1,740	20	.13	--	20	11	81	188	0	17	70	.3	.6	--	--	95	0	541	7.4	27	--
Sept. 19	25.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	124	--	--	--	--	58	--	--	--	27	--
Oct. 22	25.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,290	--	--	--	--	592	--	--	--	26	--
Oct. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	410	--	--	--	--	242	--	--	--	26	--
Dec. 24	28.3	27	.04	--	46	61	477	1,010	0	60	360	1.0	3.9	--	*1,480	366	0	2,500	7.7	26	--
Jan. 24, 1964	3.2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	336	--	--	--	23	--
Feb. 28	--	26	.02	--	44	61	439	916	0	52	360	1.1	.2	--	*1,480	361	0	2,440	8.1	24	--
Mar. 26	--	28	.00	--	44	60	458	954	0	50	365	1.0	.5	--	*1,580	356	0	2,500	8.2	24	--
Apr. 22	e 3	29	.02	--	46	57	438	878	0	63	365	1.0	.4	--	*1,430	350	0	2,440	8.1	26	--
May 26	3.3	33	.00	--	48	62	493	1,012	0	42	408	.9	.3	--	*1,600	375	0	2,570	8.1	28	--
June 23	5	32	.02	--	46	62	461	936	0	43	395	1.1	.6	--	*1,520	370	0	2,640	7.9	27	--
July 22	2.7	30	.00	--	30	77	519	1,028	0	50	440	1.3	1.8	--	*1,700	392	0	2,780	8.1	28	--
Aug. 25	--	32	.00	--	44	66	506	1,020	0	36	420	1.4	1.8	--	*1,620	382	0	2,700	8.1	30	--
Sept. 25	6.6	27	.00	--	40	55	458	808	35	42	393	1.1	.5	--	*1,540	326	0	2,450	8.5	27	70
Oct. 28	2	32	.00	--	48	63	506	992	0	48	435	.9	.5	--	*1,620	379	0	2,740	8.2	26	55
Nov. 20	2.2	39	.00	--	56	67	651	1,348	0	53	473	1.2	.2	--	*1,786	415	0	2,920	8.1	25	45
Dec. 23	4.28	34	.02	--	20	71	528	862	51	45	460	1.0	.0	--	*1,630	342	0	2,750	8.6	21	35
Jan. 11, 1965	1.67	30	.02	--	38	67	536	940	35	58	455	1.3	.5	--	*1,670	370	0	2,840	8.5	22	40
Feb. 8	1	32	.02	--	40	61	533	736	87	6.0	470	1.0	.3	--	*1,610	261	0	2,700	8.9	26	10
May 4	--	28	.08	--	58	83	799	1,174	26	88	795	1.5	1.3	--	*2,550	485	0	3,970	8.3	28	40
June 7	1.5	37	.00	--	78	91	727	1,196	0	188	688	1.2	1.2	--	*3,880	568	0	3,880	8.1	27	15
July 9	.31	42	.02	--	68	88	738	1,354	14	10	700	1.2	2.1	--	*2,370	532	0	3,910	8.3	27	20
Sept. 9	e.5	34	.00	--	42	100	835	1,350	0	20	850	1.3	1.8	--	*2,581	516	0	4,380	8.1	29	70*
Nov. 10	15	26	.00	--	40	43	281	396	14	112	298	.8	1.4	--	*1,010	277	0	1,720	8.4	25	--
Dec. 2	12	28	.02	--	50	51	410	696	0	136	362	1.0	1.3	--	*1,380	334	0	2,310	8.1	22	--
Jan. 4, 1966	--	28	.02	0.00	84	32	347	696	30	78	278	.6	.3	--	*1,230	341	0	2,010	8.5	24	40
Jan. 14	180	23	.05	.00	24	28	159	358	0	32	136	.6	.5	--	*603	175	0	1,030	7.6	24	70*
Jan. 31	48	27	.03	.00	48	51	350	752	12	60	274	.9	3.0	--	*1,220	330	0	2,020	8.3	24	3
Mar. 3	14	29	.00	.00	32	54	437	820	12	60	350	.6	2.9	--	*1,400	302	0	2,330	8.3	26	10
Apr. 6	10	29	.00	.00	80	39	442	906	0	64	362	.6	1.1	--	*1,480	360	0	2,400	8.2	26	20
May 2	10	29	.02	.00	56	49	432	858	14	56	350	.6	1.3	--	*1,430	341	0	2,350	8.3	28	15
June 3	12.5	32	.00	.00	48	55	385	894	22	54	250	.9	3.1	--	*1,524	346	0	2,490	8.5	27	15
July 7	7.24	31	.01	.00	56	56	434	936	0	62	340	.9	.2	--	*1,500	370	0	2,540	8.0	28	30
July 29	10	32	.02	.00	60	52	492	944	0	90	400	.6	.3	--	*1,600	364	0	2,580	8.2	28	30
Aug. 30	6.9	32	.01	.00	48	58	482	936	0	100	378	.9	.3	--	*1,570	358	0	2,520	8.0	29	5
Sept. 30	11.5	27	.01	.00	40	41	349	678	0	60	288	1.2	1.4	--	*1,160	268	0	1,930	8.0	28	50
Nov. 2	--	30	.00	.00	56	58	424	886	0	62	358	.9	2.3	--	*1,440	378	0	2,410	7.9	--	30
Nov. 30	15	30	.02	.00	54	48	444	906	0	52	351	.8	6.1	--	*1,420	332	0	2,440	7.9	24	20
Dec. 28	e 19	29	.02	.00	56	63	384	854	0	68	325	.9	3.0	--	*1,410	398	0	2,300	7.8	23	--
Feb. 1, 1967	--	30	.00	.00	48	57	452	922	0	64	362	.7	4.3	--	*1,500	354	0	2,460	8.0	24	--
Mar. 7	10.2	30	.00	.00	52	38	484	932	0	62	358	.9	2.0	--	*1,480	764	0	2,470	8.2	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

e Estimated

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Apr. 13, 1967	5.7	36	0.04	0.00	82	69	244	560	0	48	360	0.4	1.0	--	*1,060	488	29	1,910	8.0	27	--	
May 15	7.2	31	.07	.00	48	66	484	936	16	81	400	.9	.8	--	*1,620	392	0	2,700	8.3	28	--	
June 26	5	32	.01	.00	40	68	460	1,000	0	26	375	.9	.6	--	*1,580	380	0	2,580	8.1	27	--	
Aug. 1	3.1	33	.01	.00	48	60	491	998	0	60	390	.9	.6	--	*1,590	366	0	2,630	8.2	26	--	
Apr. 3, 1968	--	12	--	.00	2.2	44	528	3.4	352	193	102	.9	.5	0.0	1,510	186	0	2,550	9.7	--	--	
May 30	.33	34	.00	.00	26	101	750	4.5	1,156	33	84	1.2	.4	.7	2,260	480	0	3,780	8.5	--	--	
July 27	--	27	--	.00	55	52	472	1.4	604	88	177	1.1	1.0	6.8	1,590	351	0	2,580	9.0	--	--	
Aug. 28	--	37	--	.00	61	66	580	6.9	992	28	120	1.1	.2	4.5	1,890	424	0	3,140	8.4	--	--	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

e Estimated.

2760. Turpentine Run at Mariendal, St. Thomas, V.I.

Location.--Lat 18° 19' 48", long 64° 52' 58", on left bank, at Mariendal, 1.0 mile upstream from mouth, and 3.3 miles southeast of Fort Christian, Charlotte Amalie.

Drainage area.--2.97 sq mi.

Records available.--Discharge: January 1963 to April 1969 (Discontinued).

Chemical analyses: 1962-66.

Gage.--Water-stage recorder and V-notch weir in concrete control. Altitude of gage is 40 ft (from topographic map).

Extremes.--Maximums and minimums (discharge in gallons per minute, gage height in feet).

Annual maximum discharge for years 1963-68				Annual minimum discharge for years 1963-68			
Date	Time	Discharge	Gage height	Year	Date	Discharge	Gage height
Aug. 28, 1963	2230	111,000	3.00	1963	--	No	--
1964	No flow all year.	--	--	1964	--	flow	--
Dec. 10, 1965	1230	93,800	2.82	1965	--	many	--
Oct. 12, 1966	1530	33,500	1.97	1966	--	days	--
1967	No flow all year.	--	--	1967	--	each	--
July 23, 1968	1530	63,800	3.33	1968	--	year.	--
Jan. 26, 1969	2045	199,700	4.61	1969	--		--

1963-1969: Maximum discharge 199,700 gpm Jan. 26, 1969 (gage height 4.61 ft); minimum discharge no flow many days each year.

Remarks.--No flow during calendar years 1964 and 1967.

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1963

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1	0	0	0	0	465	0	0	0	73	0	0	0
2	0	200	0	0	48	0	0	121	14	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	284	0	410	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	30	0	0	632	0	290	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	103	0	0	26	0	124	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	205	800	0	0	150	76	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	66	218	0	0	0	24	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	6	219	0	0	0	7	0	0	0
12	0	0	0	0	564	0	0	0	11	0	0	0
13	0	0	0	0	1,350	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	0	0	0	885	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	20	0	0	0	342	0	0	0	25	0	0	0
16	0	0	0	7	207	0	0	0	34	0	0	0
17	0	0	0	24	182	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	0	0	0	0	1,570	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	0	0	0	0	518	0	0	0	5	0	0	0
20	0	0	0	0	199	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21	0	0	0	0	90	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	0	0	0	0	39	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	112	0
24	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
25	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
26	0	0	550	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	37	0
28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7,120	0	0	0	0
29	0	--	0	0	0	0	0	7,490	0	0	0	0
30	0	--	0	2,070	0	0	0	985	0	0	0	0
31	0	--	0	--	0	--	0	272	--	0	--	0
Total	80	200	550	2,511	7,733	0	942	16,138	1,093	0	150	0
Mean	2.58	7.14	17.7	83.7	249	0	30.4	521	36.4	0	5.00	0
Max	60	200	550	2,070	1,570	0	632	7,490	410	0	112	0
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Year 1963: Total 29,397 Mean 80.5 Max 7,490 Min 0												

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1965

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1										0	0	0
2										0	0	0
3										0	0	0
4										0	2,700	0
5										0	8,510	0
6										0	1,730	0
7										0	478	0
8										0	113	0
9										0	9	0
10										0	0	13,790
11										0	0	10,890
12										0	0	4,820
13										0	0	3,110
14										0	0	1,140
15										0	0	502
16										0	0	182
17										0	0	106
18										0	0	24
19										0	0	1
20										2,340	0	0
21										357	0	0
22										175	0	0
23										8	0	0
24										0	0	1,270
25										0	0	53
26										0	766	262
27										0	86	140
28										0	22	90
29										0	0	48
30		--								0	0	6
31		--		--		--			--	0	--	0
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2,880	14,414	36,434
Mean										92.9	480	1,175
Max										2,340	8,510	13,790
Min										0	0	0
Year 1965:	Total 53,728		Mean 147		Max 13,790		Min 0					

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1966

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1	0		0						0	0		
2	0		0						0	0		
3	0		0						0	0		
4	0		0						0	0		
5	0		0						0	0		
6	0		0						0	0		
7	0		0						0	0		
8	0		0						0	0		
9	0		0						0	0		
10	0		0						0	0		
11	0		0						0	1,650		
12	0		0						0	5,170		
13	1,410		0						0	1,550		
14	538		0						0	1,490		
15	216		0						0	548		
16	30		0						0	236		
17	0		0						0	332		
18	0		0						0	194		
19	0		0						0	63		
20	0		0						0	18		
21	0		0						0	6		
22	0		69						0	0		
23	0		3						0	0		
24	0		0						0	0		
25	0		0						0	0		
26	0		0						0	0		
27	0		0						0	0		
28	0		0						222	0		
29	0	--	0						8	0		
30	0	--	0						0	0		
31	0	--	0	--		--			--	0	--	
Total	2,194	0	72	0	0	0	0	0	230	11,457	0	0
Mean	70.8		2.32						7.67	370		
Max	1,410		69						222	5,170		
Min	0		0						0	0		
Year 1966:	Total 13,953		Mean 38.2		Max 5,170		Min 0					

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1968

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1							0	0	0		0	1,360
2							0	0	0		0	703
3							0	0	0		0	189
4							0	8	0		0	128
5							0	0	0		0	29
6							0	0	0		0	157
7							0	1,280	0		0	7
8							0	3,380	89		0	0
9							0	245	0		0	0
10							0	43	0		0	0
11							0	1	0		0	0
12							0	33	0		0	0
13							0	0	0		0	0
14							0	0	0		0	0
15							0	0	0		0	0
16							0	0	0		0	0
17							0	0	0		0	0
18							0	0	0		0	0
19							0	0	0		0	0
20							0	0	0		0	0
21							2,290	0	0		0	0
22							46	0	0		0	0
23							9,100	0	0		0	0
24							1,460	0	0		0	0
25							5	0	0		0	0
26							0	0	0		0	0
27							0	2	0		363	0
28							39	0	0		129	0
29							1	0	0		450	0
30		--				--	0	0	0		873	0
31		--		--		--	0	0	--		--	0
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0	12,941	4,992	89	0	1,815	2,573
Mean							417	161	2.97		60.5	83.0
Max							9,100	3,380	89		873	1,360
Min							0	0	0		0	0
Year 1968:	Total 22,410		Mean 61.2		Max 9,100		Min 0					

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1969

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1	0	0	11,490	0								
2	0	0	788	0								
3	0	0	358	0								
4	12	0	208	0								
5	17	0	159	0								
6	0	0	139	0								
7	0	0	56	0								
8	0	0	32	0								
9	0	0	11	0								
10	0	0	0	0								
11	0	0	0	0								
12	0	0	0	0								
13	0	0	0	0								
14	0	0	0	0								
15	0	0	0	0								
16	0	0	0	0								
17	0	0	0	0								
18	0	0	0	0								
19	0	0	0	0								
20	0	0	0	0								
21	0	0	0	0								
22	0	0	0	0								
23	0	0	0	0								
24	181	0	0	0								
25	0	0	0	0								
26	18,940	0	0	0								
27	14,260	0	0	0								
28	2,430	3,790	0	0								
29	849	--	0	Disc.								
30	306	--	0									
31	0	--	0	--		--			--		--	
Total	36,995	3,790	13,241									
Mean												
Max												
Min												

Year 1969

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Dec. 18, 1962	2	27	0.00	--	37	41	478	888	0	57	360	1.0	2.9	--	--	261	0	2,460	8.2	26	--
Jan. 13, 1963	3	31	.02	--	46	39	459	888	0	56	342	1.1	2.8	--	* 1,430	276	0	2,420	8.0	24	--
Feb. 21	--	18	.10	--	48	38	519	900	16	59	408	1.2	.2	--	* 1,590	276	0	2,570	8.3	24	--
Apr. 8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	--	296	--	--	--	27	--
May 16	199	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--	27	--
May 20	155	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	175	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--	26	--
Aug. 28	2,564	20	.10	--	28	33	272	522	0	46	225	.7	1.0	--	--	206	0	1,530	7.4	25	--
Oct. 20, 1965	6,257	13	.05	--	18	13	85	144	0	45	82	.5	1.5	--	* 430	98	0	594	7.2	24	70 ⁺
Oct. 20	3,209	10	.05	--	24	17	158	190	0	128	128	.6	2.7	--	* 569	130	0	848	7.3	24	70 ⁺
Nov. 5	3,330	21	.18	--	20	18	117	182	0	48	122	.5	7.2	--	* 450	124	0	791	7.8	25	--
Dec. 10	--	18	.04	0.00	18	25	50	172	0	26	59	.3	5.2	--	* 319	148	7	530	7.7	--	40 ⁺
Oct. 13, 1966	956	21	.03	.00	28	27	199	370	0	44	185	.7	1.8	--	* 703	181	0	1,220	7.7	29	70 ⁺

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

POND STAGE AND DISCHARGE STATION

2720. Hoffman Pond at Hoffman, St. Thomas, V.I.

Location.--Lat 18° 20' 18", long 64° 53' 54", in pond at right end of earthen dam, 300' upstream on tributary to Turpentine Run, 0.5 mile upstream of Tutu-Red Hook road junction, 2.2 miles east of Fort Christian, Charlotte Amalie.

Drainage area.--0.13 sq mi.

Records available.--Stage: Daily stage at 2400 hours, November 1962 to April 1969.

Discharge: Maximum discharge 59,000 gpm, March 1, 1969 (gage height 7.10 ft) computed flow over dam.

Occasional low-stage measurements, May 1963 to November 1965.

Chemical analyses: 1962-68.

Gage.--Water-stage recorder with Parshall flume set in concrete control. Altitude of gage is 200 ft (from topographic map).

Remarks.--Compacted earthen dam. Spillway on bedrock has concrete broad-crested weir. No means of discharging contents. Pond is used for stock watering.

Gage height, in feet, calendar year 1962

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.06
2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.04
3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.01
4	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.98
5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.95
6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.93
7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.91
8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.88
9	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.88
10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.85
11	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.84
12	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.81
13	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.53	3.79
14	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.50	3.77
15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.47	3.75
16	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.44	3.73
17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.40	3.67
18	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.38	3.65
19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.35	3.65
20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.32	3.62
21	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.29	3.60
22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.28	3.68
23	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.25	3.65
24	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.24	3.63
25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.21	3.61
26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.18	3.60
27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.16	3.58
28	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.13	3.56
29	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.11	3.54
30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.09	3.52
31	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.52
+	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.09	3.52
±	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	- .57
Max	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.53	4.06
Min	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.09	3.52

+Gage height, in feet, at end of month.

±Change in gage height.

Gage height, in feet, calendar year 1963

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	3.51	3.06	--	2.53	3.90	5.38	4.53	4.32	5.75	5.41	4.71	--
2	3.49	3.24	--	2.52	3.92	5.35	4.51	4.44	5.73	5.38	4.69	--
3	3.52	3.24	--	2.48	3.91	5.32	4.48	4.44	5.72	5.36	4.67	--
4	3.55	3.22	--	2.46	3.88	5.29	4.46	4.42	5.69	5.32	4.64	--
5	3.53	3.20	--	2.46	3.84	5.25	4.42	4.39	5.70	5.29	4.61	--
6	3.51	3.18	--	2.47	3.85	5.23	4.62	4.38	5.83	5.27	4.62	--
7	3.48	3.15	--	2.63	3.83	5.20	4.78	4.35	5.80	5.24	4.59	--
8	3.45	3.13	--	2.91	3.81	5.17	4.82	4.39	5.80	5.23	4.57	--
9	3.42	3.11	--	3.22	4.39	5.13	4.80	4.77	5.79	5.20	4.60	--
10	3.39	3.09	--	3.36	4.57	5.10	4.77	4.82	5.77	--	4.58	--
11	3.41	3.07	--	3.39	4.87	5.07	4.74	4.82	5.77	--	4.55	--
12	3.40	3.05	2.50	3.39	5.37	5.04	4.71	4.79	5.74	--	4.54	--
13	3.37	3.03	2.48	3.37	--	4.99	4.69	4.77	5.73	--	4.51	--
14	3.37	3.01	2.45	3.35	--	4.95	4.66	4.74	5.70	--	4.49	--
15	3.36	--	2.42	3.32	--	4.90	4.63	4.70	5.73	--	4.47	--
16	3.35	--	2.40	3.29	5.76	4.86	4.62	4.68	5.71	--	4.42	--
17	3.37	--	2.38	3.31	5.78	4.82	4.62	4.65	5.69	--	4.40	--
18	3.35	--	2.36	3.28	5.80	4.81	4.58	4.62	5.70	--	4.37	--
19	3.34	--	2.34	3.23	5.78	4.77	4.56	4.59	5.69	--	4.39	--
20	3.31	--	2.32	3.20	5.75	4.74	4.53	4.59	5.66	--	4.38	--
21	3.28	--	2.30	3.17	5.74	4.71	4.49	4.57	5.63	--	4.39	--
22	3.25	--	2.27	3.14	5.72	4.69	4.47	4.54	5.60	--	4.35	--
23	3.24	--	2.24	3.11	5.69	4.66	4.44	4.53	5.56	--	4.47	--
24	3.22	--	2.21	3.09	5.67	4.63	4.41	4.51	5.53	4.87	4.47	3.88
25	3.20	--	2.44	3.06	5.64	4.59	4.37	4.46	5.50	4.84	4.44	3.89
26	3.16	--	2.56	3.04	5.60	4.57	4.34	4.43	5.52	4.82	4.42	3.89
27	3.15	--	2.60	3.02	5.55	4.53	4.32	4.59	5.52	4.84	4.46	3.88
28	3.12	--	2.59	2.99	5.52	4.55	4.29	6.08	5.49	4.82	--	3.87
29	3.10	--	2.56	2.96	5.49	4.52	4.25	5.83	5.45	4.79	--	3.86
30	3.08	--	2.53	3.77	5.45	4.56	4.22	5.79	5.43	4.76	--	3.84
31	3.06	--	2.53	--	5.42	--	4.30	5.77	--	4.74	--	3.81
+	3.06	--	2.53	3.77	5.42	4.56	4.30	5.77	5.43	4.74	--	3.81
‡	-.46	--	--	1.24	1.65	-.86	-.26	1.47	-.34	-.69	--	--
Max	3.55	--	2.60	3.77	5.80	5.38	4.82	6.08	5.83	5.41	4.71	--
Min	3.06	--	2.21	2.46	3.81	4.52	4.22	4.32	5.43	4.87	4.35	--

+ Gage height, in feet, at end of month.

‡ Change in gage height.

Gage height, in feet, calendar year 1964

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	3.82	--	--	--	1.54	0.87	0.31	--	-0.78	-1.26	-1.72	--
2	3.81	--	2.71	--	1.51	.85	.30	--	-.81	-1.29	-1.73	--
3	3.79	--	2.70	2.03	1.48	.82	.30	--	-.85	-1.31	-1.74	--
4	3.78	--	2.67	2.00	1.45	.80	.29	--	-.87	-1.34	-1.76	--
5	3.75	--	--	1.97	1.42	.78	.26	--	-.90	-1.36	-1.78	--
6	3.73	--	--	1.97	1.40	.75	.24	-0.36	-.93	-1.39	-1.80	--
7	3.70	--	--	1.97	--	.72	.22	-.39	-.95	-1.42	-1.82	--
8	3.70	--	--	1.96	--	.68	.19	-.43	-.98	-1.44	-1.84	--
9	3.69	--	--	1.93	--	.65	.16	-.45	-1.00	-1.46	-1.61	--
10	3.67	--	--	1.90	--	.62	--	-.47	-1.03	-1.48	-1.60	--
11	3.66	--	--	1.87	--	.58	--	-.49	-1.06	-1.50	-1.62	--
12	3.67	--	--	1.89	1.21	.55	--	-.51	-1.08	-1.52	-1.63	--
13	3.67	--	--	1.89	1.18	.52	--	-.54	-1.10	-1.54	-1.65	--
14	3.66	--	--	1.87	1.17	.49	--	-.56	-1.13	-1.56	-1.66	--
15	3.65	--	--	1.85	1.14	.46	--	-.59	-1.15	-1.58	-1.68	--
16	3.62	--	--	1.82	1.12	.44	--	-.61	-1.18	-1.61	-1.70	--
17	3.59	--	--	1.82	1.10	.41	--	-.64	-1.20	-1.61	-1.72	--
18	3.56	--	--	1.80	1.08	.38	--	-.67	-1.20	-1.63	-1.75	--
19	3.53	--	--	1.77	1.05	.36	--	-.68	-1.23	-1.65	-1.77	--
20	3.54	--	h _{2.38}	1.81	1.02	.34	--	-.70	-1.24	-1.66	-1.79	--
21	3.51	--	--	1.82	.99	.32	--	-.71	-1.22	-1.68	-1.81	--
22	3.48	--	--	1.81	.96	--	--	-.73	-1.17	-1.55	-1.82	--
23	3.46	--	h _{2.31}	1.78	.94	--	--	-.71	-1.19	-1.57	-1.85	h _{-2.27}
24	3.42	--	--	1.74	.93	--	--	-.74	-1.20	-1.59	-1.85	--
25	3.40	--	--	1.71	.90	--	--	-.76	-1.18	-1.60	-1.82	--
26	3.37	--	h _{2.21}	1.68	.87	--	--	-.78	-1.20	-1.62	-1.83	--
27	3.34	--	--	1.65	.98	--	--	-.80	-1.22	-1.64	--	--
28	3.31	2.76	--	1.63	.96	--	--	-.70	-1.23	-1.65	--	--
29	3.28	--	--	1.60	.93	.29	--	-.72	-1.22	-1.67	--	--
30	--	--	--	1.57	.90	.25	--	-.73	-1.24	-1.68	--	--
31	--	--	--	--	.88	--	--	-.75	--	-1.70	--	--
+	--	--	--	1.57	.88	.25	--	-.75	-1.24	-1.70	--	--
‡	--	--	--	--	-.69	-.63	--	--	-.49	-.46	--	--
Max	3.82	--	--	2.03	1.54	.87	--	-.36	-.78	-1.26	-1.60	--
Min	3.28	--	--	1.57	.88	.25	--	-.80	-1.24	-1.70	-1.85	--

+ Gage height, in feet, at end of month.

‡ Change in gage height.

h^h Staff gage reading.

Gage height, in feet, calendar year 1965

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	0.65	5.67
2	--	--	h-3.36	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	.66	5.63
3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	.64	5.58
4	h-2.45	--	--	--	h-4.50	--	--	--	--	h-4.51	2.83	5.59
5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.83	5.55
6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.78	5.52
7	--	--	--	h-4.12	--	h-3.09	h-3.71	h-4.80	--	--	5.76	5.48
8	--	h-2.94	h-3.51	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.75	5.46
9	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	h-4.62	--	5.73	5.43
10	--	--	--	--	h-3.22	--	--	--	--	--	5.70	5.88
11	h-2.56	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.67	5.93
12	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.65	5.82
13	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.62	5.82
14	--	--	--	--	--	h-3.27	--	--	--	--	5.58	5.79
15	--	h-3.05	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	h-4.69	5.59	5.76
16	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.56	5.74
17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.52	5.73
18	--	--	--	--	h-3.10	--	--	--	--	--	5.52	5.72
19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.48	5.71
20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	-0.16	5.43	5.67
21	--	--	--	--	--	h-3.42	--	--	--	.44	5.40	5.64
22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	.68	5.37	5.61
23	--	h-3.19	--	--	h-3.15	--	--	--	--	.79	5.33	5.57
24	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	.81	5.28	5.78
25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	.81	5.56	5.77
26	--	--	--	h-4.60	--	--	--	--	--	.79	5.79	5.75
27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	.78	5.77	5.74
28	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	.75	5.75	5.73
29	--	--	--	--	--	h-3.87	--	--	--	.72	5.73	5.72
30	--	--	h-4.04	--	--	--	--	--	--	.70	5.70	5.70
31	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	.68	--	5.67
+	--	--	h-4.04	--	--	--	--	--	--	.68	5.70	5.67
‡	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.02	-0.03
Max	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.83	5.93
Min	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	.64	5.43

+ Gage height, in feet, at end of month.

‡ Change in gage height.

h Staff gage reading.

Gage height, in feet, calendar year 1966

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	5.63	5.40	4.39	4.35	3.60	2.70	1.78	1.13	0.41	0.48	5.28	4.46
2	5.62	5.36	4.35	4.32	3.60	2.65	1.75	1.09	.38	.50	5.24	4.45
3	5.61	5.33	4.31	4.27	3.56	2.62	1.73	1.09	.34	.49	5.20	4.44
4	5.57	5.29	4.31	4.23	3.52	2.58	1.69	1.06	.31	.47	5.18	4.49
5	5.54	5.24	4.28	4.18	3.48	2.57	1.65	1.03	.29	.44	5.14	4.50
6	5.52	5.21	4.25	4.15	3.45	2.54	1.62	.99	.26	.41	5.11	4.54
7	5.47	5.16	4.21	4.12	3.42	2.52	1.58	.95	.29	.38	5.07	4.53
8	5.43	5.11	4.17	4.07	3.39	2.48	1.55	1.00	.27	.44	5.03	4.51
9	5.39	5.04	4.15	4.03	3.41	2.44	1.51	.97	.26	.51	5.02	4.48
10	5.35	4.99	4.21	3.99	3.38	2.42	1.47	.95	.41	.50	5.05	4.45
11	5.32	4.96	4.18	3.94	3.37	2.38	1.44	.92	.45	1.78	5.00	4.43
12	5.31	4.92	4.17	3.89	3.34	2.35	1.45	.88	.41	5.40	4.98	4.40
13	5.80	4.90	4.15	3.86	3.30	2.30	1.43	.85	.38	5.79	4.94	4.37
14	5.75	4.86	4.12	3.85	3.26	2.27	1.42	.86	.38	5.78	4.91	4.34
15	5.73	4.84	4.09	3.95	3.22	2.29	1.40	.83	.35	5.75	4.87	4.33
16	5.72	4.82	4.07	3.92	3.18	2.28	1.42	.80	.32	5.75	4.83	4.30
17	5.71	4.81	4.04	3.89	3.15	2.25	1.40	.77	.30	5.74	4.80	4.27
18	5.69	4.79	4.05	3.92	3.13	2.23	1.37	.73	.27	5.73	4.77	4.24
19	5.66	4.77	4.15	3.97	3.12	2.19	1.34	.70	.25	5.70	4.74	4.21
20	5.63	4.72	4.28	3.99	3.10	2.15	1.37	.67	.23	5.68	4.71	4.19
21	5.59	4.69	4.37	3.96	3.07	2.12	1.33	.65	.20	5.66	4.69	4.16
22	5.55	4.65	4.58	3.92	3.04	2.08	1.41	.65	.20	5.63	4.68	4.13
23	5.51	4.61	4.64	3.87	3.01	2.05	1.40	.62	.18	5.60	4.69	4.20
24	5.47	4.51	4.63	3.83	2.97	2.02	1.37	.58	.17	5.56	4.70	4.24
25	5.43	4.53	4.60	3.78	2.93	2.00	1.33	.55	.15	5.52	4.66	4.24
26	5.38	4.49	4.57	3.75	2.89	1.96	1.31	.58	.11	5.48	4.63	4.21
27	5.34	4.46	4.53	3.71	2.88	1.92	1.28	.55	.11	5.46	4.59	4.19
28	5.34	4.42	4.50	3.69	2.85	1.88	1.25	.57	.43	5.45	4.55	4.17
29	5.39	--	4.47	3.66	2.82	1.86	1.19	.53	.58	5.41	4.52	4.14
30	5.42	--	4.43	3.62	2.78	1.82	1.15	.48	.50	5.37	4.49	4.11
31	5.42	--	4.39	--	2.74	--	1.15	.45	--	5.32	--	4.09
+	5.42	4.42	4.39	3.62	2.74	1.82	1.15	.45	.50	5.32	4.49	4.09
‡	-.25	-1.00	-.03	-.77	-.88	-.92	-.67	-.70	.05	4.82	-.83	-.40
Max	5.80	5.40	4.58	4.35	3.01	2.70	1.78	1.13	.58	5.79	5.28	4.53
Min	5.31	4.42	4.04	3.62	2.74	1.82	1.15	.45	.11	.38	4.49	4.09

+Gage height, in feet, at end of month.

‡Change in gage height.

Gage height, in feet, calendar year 1967

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	4.06	3.33	2.70	1.77	0.95	0.56	-0.29	-1.07	-1.89	-2.61	-1.99	-2.51
2	4.03	3.30	2.66	1.76	1.12	.50	-.33	-1.10	-1.91	-2.63	-2.00	-2.53
3	4.01	3.28	2.63	1.72	1.32	.46	-.36	-1.13	-1.94	-2.66	-2.03	-2.57
4	3.98	3.25	2.60	1.68	1.37	.43	-.40	-1.16	-1.97	-2.68	-2.06	-2.62
5	3.94	3.22	2.57	1.65	1.36	.41	-.43	-1.19	--	-2.71	-2.08	-2.63
6	3.91	3.19	2.52	1.62	1.34	.38	-.48	-1.21	--	-2.74	-2.08	-2.66
7	3.88	3.15	2.50	1.59	1.31	.34	-.48	-1.24	--	-2.76	-2.11	-2.68
8	3.85	3.12	2.46	1.56	1.29	.30	-.50	-1.26	--	-2.78	-2.13	-2.64
9	3.82	3.11	2.42	1.53	1.25	.27	-.53	-1.30	--	-2.82	-2.14	-2.65
10	3.79	3.08	2.39	1.49	1.22	.24	-.56	-1.34	--	-2.47	-2.16	-2.67
11	3.76	3.05	2.36	1.46	1.18	.21	-.59	-1.35	-2.11	-2.15	-2.16	-2.69
12	3.73	3.03	2.34	1.43	1.17	.19	-.61	-1.33	-2.13	--	-2.18	--
13	3.70	3.00	2.31	1.38	1.15	.16	-.61	-1.37	-2.15	--	--	-2.71
14	3.68	2.97	2.27	1.35	1.11	.14	-.62	-1.40	-2.17	--	--	-2.73
15	3.65	2.99	2.25	1.30	1.07	.09	-.66	-1.44	-2.20	--	-2.22	-2.75
16	3.63	3.03	2.22	1.26	1.08	.07	-.68	-1.46	-2.23	-1.88	-2.24	-2.77
17	3.71	3.00	2.18	1.22	1.05	.08	-.71	-1.49	-2.26	-1.87	-2.26	-2.79
18	3.69	2.97	2.15	1.19	1.02	.08	-.74	-1.53	-2.29	-1.88	-2.28	-2.81
19	3.66	2.94	2.12	1.17	.99	.05	-.77	-1.55	-2.30	-1.90	-2.30	-2.84
20	3.64	2.91	2.08	1.14	.96	.04	-.81	-1.59	-2.33	-1.92	-2.33	-2.86
21	3.61	2.88	2.03	1.11	.93	.00	-.85	-1.62	-2.36	-1.95	-2.35	-2.89
22	3.61	2.85	2.01	1.06	.90	-.02	-.86	-1.61	-2.39	-1.97	-2.37	-2.89
23	3.58	2.83	1.98	1.02	.86	-.04	-.89	-1.64	-2.41	-1.86	-2.40	-2.91
24	3.56	2.80	1.98	1.02	.85	-.08	-.93	-1.67	-2.44	-1.86	-2.42	-2.93
25	3.53	2.77	1.94	.98	.81	-.11	-.95	-1.70	-2.46	-1.87	-2.45	-2.95
26	3.50	2.75	1.90	.93	.78	-.13	-.96	-1.72	-2.48	-1.87	-2.44	-2.95
27	3.47	2.72	1.87	.90	.75	-.15	-.95	-1.75	-2.50	-1.89	-2.45	-2.95
28	3.45	2.72	1.83	.87	.71	-.19	-.98	-1.78	-2.54	-1.91	-2.46	-2.97
29	3.43	--	1.81	1.01	.68	-.23	-1.00	-1.81	-2.57	-1.93	-2.48	-2.99
30	3.38	--	1.78	.98	.64	-.25	-1.02	-1.84	-2.59	-1.96	-2.50	-3.00
31	3.35	--	1.80	--	.59	--	-1.03	-1.86	--	-1.97	--	-3.01
+	3.35	2.72	1.80	.98	.59	-.25	-1.03	-1.86	-2.59	-1.97	-2.50	-3.01
‡	-.74	-.63	-.92	-.82	-.39	-.84	-.78	-.83	-.73	.62	-.53	-.51
Max	4.06	3.33	2.70	1.77	1.37	.56	-.29	-1.07	-1.89	-1.86	-1.99	-2.51
Min	3.35	2.72	1.78	.87	.59	-.25	-1.03	-1.86	-2.59	-2.82	-2.50	-3.01

+ Gage height, in feet, at end of month.

‡ Change in gage height.

Gage height, in feet, calendar year 1968

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	-3.02	-3.44	-3.69	-4.09	-4.59	--	--	-3.87	3.08	2.21	1.30	3.08
2	-3.01	-3.47	-3.72	-4.03	-4.61	--	--	-3.84	3.05	2.16	1.27	3.48
3	-3.03	-3.49	-3.75	-4.05	-4.63	--	--	-3.86	3.04	2.12	1.29	3.59
4	-3.06	-3.52	-3.76	-4.08	-4.66	--	--	-3.81	3.02	2.14	1.25	3.65
5	-3.05	-3.54	-3.78	-4.11	-4.68	--	--	--	2.99	2.12	1.22	3.63
6	--	-3.56	--	-4.14	-4.72	--	--	--	2.96	2.08	1.17	3.63
7	--	-3.58	--	-4.17	-4.75	--	--	--	2.93	2.07	--	3.63
8	-3.09	-3.59	--	-4.18	-4.75	--	--	3.59	2.96	2.05	--	3.61
9	-3.11	--	--	-4.22	-4.77	--	--	3.80	2.93	2.02	--	3.59
10	-3.12	--	--	-4.25	-4.80	--	--	3.84	2.89	1.99	--	3.56
11	-3.13	--	-3.94	-4.27	-4.83	--	--	3.83	2.84	1.96	--	3.53
12	-3.14	-3.66	-3.95	-4.28	-4.86	--	--	3.80	2.81	1.92	--	3.50
13	-3.16	-3.68	-3.98	-4.30	-4.86	--	--	3.77	2.77	1.88	--	3.47
14	-3.19	-3.70	-4.00	-4.29	--	--	--	3.73	2.76	1.84	1.02	3.46
15	-3.19	-3.72	-4.03	-4.31	--	--	--	3.70	2.73	1.81	1.09	3.43
16	-3.20	-3.74	-4.04	-4.33	--	--	--	3.67	2.69	1.77	1.12	3.41
17	-3.22	-3.72	-4.06	-4.36	--	--	--	3.62	2.64	1.74	1.09	3.39
18	-3.24	-3.73	-3.92	-4.34	--	--	--	3.57	2.60	1.71	1.05	3.36
19	-3.25	-3.76	-3.88	-4.36	--	--	--	3.55	2.56	1.70	1.02	3.31
20	-3.24	-3.78	-3.88	-4.38	-5.00	--	--	3.52	2.54	1.68	1.02	3.27
21	-3.26	-3.80	-3.90	-4.41	-5.04	--	--	3.48	2.51	1.66	.99	3.23
22	-3.28	-3.80	-3.92	-4.43	-5.07	--	--	3.43	2.47	1.63	.99	3.19
23	-3.29	-3.82	-3.95	-4.46	-5.08	--	--	3.40	2.43	1.60	.95	3.15
24	-3.31	-3.84	-3.96	-4.49	-5.10	--	--	3.37	2.40	--	.94	3.12
25	-3.33	-3.86	-3.98	-4.52	-5.12	--	--	3.32	2.37	--	.91	3.09
26	-3.35	-3.86	-4.00	-4.55	-5.13	--	--	3.28	2.33	--	1.02	3.05
27	-3.37	-3.64	-4.02	-4.59	--	--	--	3.28	2.30	--	1.35	3.03
28	-3.39	-3.66	-4.05	-4.62	--	--	--	3.25	2.27	1.44	1.57	3.06
29	-3.41	-3.67	-4.07	-4.64	--	--	-3.88	3.21	2.27	1.40	1.89	3.04
30	-3.43	--	-4.04	-4.58	--	--	-3.90	3.18	2.25	1.38	2.48	3.01
31	-3.42	--	-4.07	--	--	--	-3.91	3.13	--	1.35	--	2.99
+	-3.42	-3.67	-4.07	-4.58	--	--	-3.91	3.13	2.25	1.35	2.48	2.99
‡	.41	.25	.40	.51	--	--	--	7.04	-.88	-.90	1.13	.51
Max	-3.01	-3.44	-3.69	-4.03	-4.59	--	--	3.84	3.08	2.21	2.48	3.65
Min	-3.43	-3.86	-4.07	-4.64	-5.13	--	--	3.87	2.25	1.35	.91	2.99

+ Gage height, in feet, at end of month.

‡ Change in gage height.

Gage height, in feet, calendar year 1969

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	2.96	3.59	6.52	4.82	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
2	2.93	3.56	6.43	4.79	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
3	2.92	3.55	6.28	4.76	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
4	2.94	3.51	6.17	4.71	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
5	2.93	3.46	6.14	4.67	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
6	2.91	3.42	6.06	4.62	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
7	2.88	3.38	6.02	4.58	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
8	2.84	3.34	5.97	4.54	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
9	2.81	3.32	5.92	4.51	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
10	2.77	3.30	5.88	4.46	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
11	2.73	3.26	5.82	4.41	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
12	2.70	3.22	5.77	4.37	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
13	2.68	3.20	5.72	4.33	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
14	2.64	3.17	5.67	4.29	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
15	2.66	3.14	5.61	4.27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
16	2.66	3.11	5.55	4.25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
17	2.63	3.07	5.50	4.21	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
18	2.61	3.08	5.45	4.17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
19	2.59	3.12	5.40	4.14	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
20	2.56	3.10	5.35	4.11	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
21	2.54	3.07	5.31	4.07	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
22	2.51	3.04	5.27	4.04	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
23	2.48	3.00	5.22	4.00	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
24	2.52	2.97	5.16	3.96	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
25	2.50	2.93	5.11	3.92	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
26	3.15	2.90	5.06	3.87	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
27	3.52	2.86	5.01	3.82	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
28	3.57	5.34	4.96	3.78	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
29	3.59	--	4.92	3.73	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
30	3.59	--	4.89	3.68	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
31	3.57	--	4.86	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
+	3.57	5.34	4.86	3.68	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
‡	.58	1.77	-.48	-1.18	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Max	3.59	5.34	6.52	4.82	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Min	2.48	2.86	4.86	3.68	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

+ Gage height, in feet, at end of month.

‡ Change in gage height.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter													Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)		Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Nov. 20, 1962	--	18	0.68	--	2.6	2.1	29	24	0	13	30	0.4	1.5	--	--	15	0	151	6.8	27	--	
Dec. 17	--	18	.82	--	3.0	2.1	28	26	0	8	32	.4	1.3	--	--	16	0	171	6.7	26	--	
Jan. 18, 1963	0	--	--	--	3.2	1.5	--	26	0	--	13	--	--	--	--	14	0	154	6.9	26	--	
Feb. 21	0	--	--	--	3.0	1.6	--	25	0	--	32	--	--	--	--	14	0	157	6.7	27	--	
May 16	30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	--	--	54	--	--	--	32	--	
May 20	16	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	45	--	--	--	--	24	--	--	--	26	--	
June 18	0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	50	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	27	--	
Aug. 24	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	35	--	--	--	--	38	--	--	--	31	--	
Aug. 29	584	16	.48	--	12	4.1	24	62	0	2.0	32	.1	.6	--	--	47	0	214	7.3	27	--	
Mar. 9, 1964	--	20	.44	--	3.6	4.9	26	37	0	2.8	36	.1	.6	--	* 175	29	0	193	7.3	26	--	
Mar. 16	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	--	--	28	--	--	--	31	--	
Mar. 30	--	20	.30	--	4.0	4.9	25	36	0	4.0	36	.1	.2	--	* 160	30	0	193	6.8	29	--	
Apr. 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	50	--	--	--	--	28	--	--	--	28	--	
Apr. 13	0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	--	--	28	--	--	--	27	--	
Apr. 22	--	19	.00	--	3.6	4.6	30	38	0	7.2	38	.1	.6	--	* 141	28	0	191	6.8	27	--	
May 11	0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	50	--	--	--	--	28	--	--	--	30	--	
May 18	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	45	--	--	--	--	54	--	--	--	30	--	
May 26	0	20	.13	--	4.0	4.6	30	37	0	1.6	43	.1	.7	--	* 149	29	0	228	6.8	32	--	
June 1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	46	--	--	--	--	84	--	--	--	28	--	
June 8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	49	--	--	--	--	28	--	--	--	31	--	
June 15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	47	--	--	--	--	30	--	--	--	28	--	
June 22	0	23	.16	--	5.6	5.4	28	44	0	.8	42	.2	.4	--	158	36	0	234	7.1	30	--	
June 29	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52	--	--	--	--	42	--	--	--	28	--	
July 6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	50	--	--	--	--	32	--	--	--	30	--	
July 13	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	48	--	--	--	--	28	--	--	--	29	--	
Aug. 25	0	22	.00	--	4.4	5.6	33	45	0	1.6	46	.4	1.4	--	155	34	0	231	6.7	32	--	
Aug. 31	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	57	--	--	--	--	34	--	--	--	32	--	
Sept. 9	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	56	--	--	--	--	36	--	--	--	34	--	
Sept. 14	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	57	--	--	--	--	48	--	--	--	27	--	
Sept. 24	0	21	.12	--	4.0	4.9	35	44	0	1.6	47	.4	.5	--	--	30	0	241	7.1	32	15	
Sept. 29	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	54	--	--	--	--	44	--	--	--	29	--	
Oct. 13	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	57	--	--	--	--	34	--	--	--	34	--	
Oct. 19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	56	--	--	--	--	154	--	--	--	32	--	
Oct. 27	0	21	.03	--	4.0	6.3	32	44	0	.0	50	.0	.2	--	149	36	0	244	7.2	31	--	
Nov. 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	56	--	--	--	--	104	--	--	--	30	--	
Nov. 9	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	54	--	--	--	--	36	--	--	--	--	--	
Nov. 20	--	--	--	--	1.6	2.7	--	60	0	2.4	50	--	.2	--	--	16	0	259	7.0	29	40	
Dec. 23	0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	57	--	--	--	--	52	--	--	--	23	--	
Jan. 4, 1965	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52	0	--	55	--	1.2	--	--	--	--	289	7.2	23	--	
Jan. 11	--	20	.04	--	6.4	6.8	36	52	0	3.6	54	.2	.4	--	--	44	1	279	7.4	26	--	
Feb. 8	--	23	.02	--	5.6	4.9	38	46	0	2.4	54	.2	.9	--	* 158	34	0	270	7.4	27	5	
Feb. 15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	64	--	--	--	--	34	--	--	--	25	--	
Feb. 23	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	64	--	--	--	--	108	--	--	--	28	--	
Mar. 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	66	--	--	--	--	36	--	--	--	27	--	
Mar. 8	--	22	.00	--	4.8	6.3	40	46	0	2.0	60	.2	.9	--	* 160	38	0	295	7.3	31	3	
Mar. 15	--	22	.00	--	4.8	5.8	41	42	0	2.4	60	.2	2.9	--	* 166	36	2	286	7.4	27	3	
Mar. 24	--	24	.15	--	8.0	6.8	--	44	0	--	64	.3	3.5	--	--	48	12	306	7.4	26	0	
Mar. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	69	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	--	27	--	
Apr. 5	--	22	.02	--	4.0	7.8	43	52	0	2.4	64	.4	.4	--	--	42	0	301	7.9	31	0	
Apr. 19	--	22	.02	--	6.4	6.3	--	48	0	--	66	.4	2.6	--	--	42	3	311	7.2	28	0	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Calcium, magnesium		Non-carbonate						
		--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		--	--					--
Apr. 26, 1965	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--	--	--	34	--	--	--	27	--		
May 4	0	22	0.05	--	5.6	6.3	42	42	0	2.4	66	0.3	1.3	--	* 225	40	6	310	7.2	30	5		
May 10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	73	--	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	--	29	--		
May 18	--	22	.02	--	6.4	6.3	47	42	0	8.8	70	.2	1.8	--	* 216	42	8	320	6.8	27	15		
May 24	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	75	--	--	--	--	--	42	--	--	--	29	--		
June 7	--	22	.00	--	7.2	8.3	43	44	0	6.0	72	.2	1.5	--	* 176	52	16	336	7.0	28	10		
June 14	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	76	--	--	--	--	--	98	--	--	--	29	--		
June 21	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	79	--	--	--	--	--	50	--	--	--	31	--		
June 29	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	50	--	--	--	32	--		
July 7	0	23	.00	--	8.0	8.3	44	48	0	2.0	76	.2	.6	--	* 191	54	15	342	7.0	31	10		
July 12	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	62	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--	31	--		
July 19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--	--	--	42	--	--	--	32	--		
Aug. 7	0	23	.00	--	7.2	7.8	49	50	0	.4	80	.2	.4	--	* 213	50	9	372	7.2	31	5		
Aug. 31	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	--	--	48	--	--	--	36	--		
Sept. 9	0	23	.00	--	9.6	7.3	52	58	0	1.6	82	.3	1.0	--	* 225	54	6	393	7.2	29	7		
Oct. 1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	--	--	44	--	--	--	--	--		
Oct. 15	0	22	.00	--	7.2	7.8	50	50	0	.8	81	.3	1.0	--	* 211	50	9	372	7.0	29	10		
Oct. 27	0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	--	--	--		
Nov. 5	355	18	.05	--	5.6	6.8	31	28	0	2.0	58	.1	1.2	--	* 150	42	19	256	6.9	28	--		
Dec. 2	0	21	.02	--	3.2	8.8	35	32	0	2.8	64	.1	.9	--	* 161	44	18	270	6.9	27	--		
Jan. 10, 1966	--	20	.11	0.00	4.8	3.9	34	23	0	.8	58	.0	.8	--	* 171	28	9	240	7.2	--	60		
Jan. 14	--	18	.09	.00	7.2	5.8	29	34	0	2.8	53	.1	.6	--	* 159	42	14	253	7.0	29	70+		
Jan. 17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--	--	--	28	--	--	--	31	--		
Jan. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--	--	--	32	--	--	--	26	--		
Jan. 31	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--	--	--	28	--	--	--	23	--		
Feb. 14	--	19	.13	.00	4.0	6.3	33	28	0	4.0	56	.1	1.6	--	* 165	36	13	252	6.9	25	70+		
Mar. 1	0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--	--	--	32	--	--	--	29	--		
Apr. 5	0	20	.04	.00	6.4	3.9	37	28	0	.8	62	.0	1.6	--	* 190	32	9	269	7.2	29	40		
Apr. 27	--	21	.00	.00	19	6.0	39	80	0	3.6	62	.0	1.3	--	* 204	72	6	356	7.6	27	20		
May 10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--	--	--	92	--	--	--	--	--		
May 26	0	22	.02	.00	11	5.5	42	49	0	8.0	65	.0	1.0	--	* 213	50	10	300	7.3	29	30		
June 27	--	22	.02	.00	5	6.2	43	37	0	8.0	66	.0	.3	--	* 181	38	8	286	7.2	31	40		
July 7	0	21	.03	.00	6.4	6.8	40	38	0	1.2	71	.1	.2	--	* 198	44	13	306	6.9	29	30		
July 27	--	22	.03	.00	4.8	5.8	45	40	0	2.4	70	.0	.5	--	* 196	36	0	308	7.1	--	20		
Aug. 5	--	23	.00	.00	8.0	4.9	47	38	0	13	69	.1	1.2	--	* 206	40	9	314	7.0	--	5		
Aug. 30	--	22	.02	.00	12	6.3	35	40	0	2.4	69	.1	.0	--	* 198	56	23	301	7.0	32	10		
Jan. 30, 1967	--	22	.06	.00	14	13	25	68	0	2.0	61	.1	.3	--	* 203	88	32	321	7.2	27	--		
Feb. 13	--	23	.03	.00	8.0	6.3	35	38	0	2.4	63	.1	.2	--	* 165	46	15	282	6.8	24	--		
Feb. 27	--	21	.00	.00	22	2.7	46	92	0	1.6	63	.1	.4	--	* 205	66	0	360	7.7	27	--		
Mar. 14	--	21	.00	.00	5.6	4.4	42	42	0	1.2	63	.1	.1	--	* 159	32	0	287	7.2	26	--		
Mar. 20	--	21	.03	.00	4.8	10	34	40	0	2.0	64	.0	1.0	--	* 182	53	20	290	6.9	26	--		
Apr. 3	--	22	.05	.00	4.8	16	21	40	0	1.6	64	.1	.2	--	* 176	78	45	294	7.0	25	--		
Apr. 18	--	22	.04	.00	6.4	7.3	36	44	0	2.0	62	.0	.3	--	* 201	46	10	307	7.1	27	--		
May 8	--	21	.09	.00	4.8	6.8	43	40	0	2.4	69	.0	1.2	--	* 187	40	7	308	6.8	27	--		
May 15	--	20	.03	.00	6.4	5.8	43	44	0	2.4	68	.0	.2	--	* 199	40	4	305	6.9	28	--		
May 29	--	22	.02	.00	3.2	8.8	41	40	0	2.8	69	.1	1.0	--	* 211	44	11	307	6.8	--	--		
June 13	--	22	.05	.00	6.4	8.8	42	48	0	.4	73	.1	.1	--	* 230	52	13	321	7.6	--	--		
June 13	--	22	.15	.00	6.4	7.8	43	52	0	.8	70	.1	.1	--	* 208	48	5	321	6.8	--	--		
June 13	--	22	.05	.00	4.8	7.8	44	44	0	1.6	73	.1	.1	--	* 251	44	8	321	7.0	--	--		
June 19	--	22	.05	.00	4.8	8.8	42	44	0	1.2	73	.0	.0	--	* 216	48	12	320	7.2	31	--		
June 26	--	22	.00	.00	4.8	9.7	42	46	0	2.8	72	.1	.6	--	* 221	52	14	352	6.9	30	--		
July 3	--	22	.05	.00	8.0	11	37	58	0	1.2	69	.1	.7	--	* 228	68	17	352	7.1	29	--		
July 10	--	22	.06	.00	6.4	9.7	45	48	0	2.8	77	.1	4.0	--	* 227	56	17	340	7.5	--	--		
July 17	--	29	.06	.00	7.2	10	43	44	0	4.4	80	.1	.3	--	* 217	59	23	332	6.9	28	--		
July 31	--	24	.01	.01	8.0	7.3	46	44	0	2.8	78	.1	.4	--	* 191	50	14	340	6.9	33	--		

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter																Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃						
																Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate					
Aug. 7, 1967	--	25	0.01	0.00	8.0	7.3	46	44	0	1.6	79	0.1	0.3	--	* 214	50	14	353	7.0	29	--	
Aug. 14	--	23	.03	.00	5.6	8.3	49	44	0	4.8	80	.1	.3	--	* 232	48	12	347	7.0	32	--	
Aug. 21	--	23	.00	.00	11	17	41	38	22	4.0	80	.2	.0	--	* 230	96	28	379	9.7	31	--	
Aug. 28	--	24	.04	.00	7.2	7.3	43	50	0	2.4	70	.1	.3	--	* 236	48	7	368	7.0	--	--	
Sept. 4	--	24	.02	.00	8.0	8.3	49	48	0	1.6	84	.0	1.7	--	* 230	54	15	377	6.6	30	--	
Sept. 11	--	8	.00	--	6.4	8.8	50	44	0	2.8	86	.1	1.6	--	* 210	52	16	368	7.1	--	--	
Sept. 18	--	9	.02	--	6.4	11	49	46	0	3.6	88	.2	2.4	--	* 207	61	23	380	7.1	--	--	
Sept. 25	--	26	.01	.00	6.4	16	45	62	0	3.6	90	.2	.6	--	* 240	84	33	383	7.3	32	--	
Jan. 19, 1968	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Mar. 6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Apr. 3	0	27	--	.00	9.0	7.6	58	3.9	58	0	1.6	98	.2	.4	0.0	* 234	54	6	430	7.4	--	--

*Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

GROUND-WATER STATIONS

Well 1 (21-64.58-1-43)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.

Name.--USGS-28 (Estate Santa Maria).

Location.--Lat 18° 21' 29", long 64° 58' 48".

Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
diam 6-in.

Depth.--300 ft.

Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 0.4 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--920 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--75.85 ft below lsd, Jan. 3, 1966.

Lowest water level.--98.05 ft below lsd, May 23, 1969.

Records available.--Water levels: 1965-69.

Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, August 1969.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Nov. 15, 1965	86.16	May 10, 1966	90.32	July 6, 1967	90.22	Aug. 1, 1968	94.76
Nov. 26	82.81	May 26	91.04	Aug. 1	87.71	Sept. 3	95.22
Dec. 8	83.25	June 8	91.40	Sept. 1	92.38	Oct. 1	96.72
Dec. 14	84.53	June 27	91.64	Oct. 3	91.91	Nov. 4	97.59
Dec. 22	76.67	July 12	91.74	Nov. 1	93.05	Dec. 4	92.10
Jan. 3, 1966	75.85	July 25	91.67	Dec. 7	93.42	Jan. 3, 1969	95.69
Jan. 17	84.15	Aug. 5	91.92	Dec. 8	93.43	Feb. 5	89.28
Jan. 27	83.53	Aug. 29	92.12	Jan. 4, 1968	93.37	Mar. 6	86.82
Feb. 14	83.38	Sept. 27	88.28	Feb. 2	94.33	Apr. 23	95.28
Feb. 28	87.78	Oct. 31	85.10	Mar. 4	94.93	May 23	98.05
Mar. 15	90.38	Jan. 3, 1967	90.90	Apr. 3	94.29	June 23	75.96
Mar. 30	86.21	Mar. 13	90.68	May 3	93.68	July 23	77.30
Apr. 12	86.47	Apr. 17	91.20	June 3	94.09	Aug. 19	84.23
Apr. 23	89.83	June 1	90.14	July 3	94.46		

Well 2 (21-64.57-2-33)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-4 (Estate Dorothea).
Location.--Lat 18° 21' 41", long 64° 57' 45".
Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-88.
Depth.--142 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.8 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--720 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--31.09 ft below lsd, Jan. 3, 1966.
Lowest water level.--^a78.15 ft below lsd, Nov. 30, 1964.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: September 1963
to February 1968.
Water levels: 1963-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, February 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (microhmhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated				Hardness as CaCO ₃		
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate	
Sept. 17, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--	--	--	62	--	--	--	--	
Sept. 29, 1964	--	33	0.0	--	14	15	245	524	0	37	112	0.4	3.0	--	* 724	96	0	1,210	8.1	26	--
Feb. 2, 1968	--	35	.00	0.00	17	11	277	0.7	510	10	48	.4	4.1	0.0	790	88	0	1,310	8.4	26	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 28, 1963	35.34	Apr. 25, 1964	41.08	Dec. 7, 1964	^a 75.90	May 26, 1966	42.12
Oct. 5	35.91	May 2	41.15	Dec. 14	61.05	June 13	^a 44.40
Oct. 12	36.41	May 9	41.25	Dec. 21	65.83	July 25	43.68
Oct. 19	36.84	May 16	41.32	Jan. 5, 1965	66.81	Aug. 29	44.76
Oct. 26	37.22	May 23	41.42	Jan. 11	55.14	Sept. 27	44.23
Nov. 2	37.53	May 30	41.50	Jan. 18	54.63	Oct. 31	40.74
Nov. 9	37.78	June 6	41.60	Jan. 25	54.10	Nov. 29	^a 43.40
Nov. 16	38.14	June 13	41.69	Feb. 1	54.47	Jan. 3, 1967	^a 47.60
Nov. 23	38.33	June 20	41.80	Feb. 8	55.08	Jan. 31	44.85
Nov. 30	38.57	June 26	41.88	Feb. 15	59.66	Mar. 13	^a 48.73
Dec. 7	38.77	July 3	42.00	Mar. 1	55.84	Apr. 17	48.38
Dec. 14	38.96	July 10	42.11	Mar. 15	57.36	June 1	^a 45.92
Dec. 21	39.11	July 18	42.07	Mar. 22	72.64	July 7	58.12
Dec. 28	39.29	July 25	42.35	Apr. 5	61.57	Aug. 1	50.79
Jan. 4, 1964	39.45	Aug. 3	42.49	Sept. 24	48.63	Sept. 1	51.50
Jan. 11	39.56	Aug. 15	46.51	Oct. 15	49.50	Oct. 3	52.94
Jan. 18	39.70	Aug. 22	48.32	Nov. 12	43.72	Nov. 1	54.59
Jan. 25	39.81	Aug. 30	46.26	Nov. 26	39.88	Dec. 8	50.29
Feb. 1	39.93	Sept. 5	44.97	Dec. 3	38.99	Jan. 4, 1968	50.14
Feb. 8	40.06	Sept. 19	56.36	Dec. 8	38.09	Apr. 3	51.87
Feb. 15	40.20	Sept. 26	58.30	Dec. 14	37.60	May 3	57.04
Feb. 22	40.33	Sept. 29	67.70	Dec. 22	36.14	July 3	62.00
Feb. 29	40.45	Oct. 3	63.14	Jan. 3, 1966	31.09	Aug. 1	59.88
Mar. 7	40.55	Oct. 11	63.37	Jan. 17	36.95	Sept. 3	59.63
Mar. 15	40.68	Oct. 17	70.50	Jan. 27	39.49	Oct. 1	55.78
Mar. 21	40.74	Oct. 23	52.50	Feb. 14	37.75	Nov. 4	^a 59.12
Mar. 28	40.81	Oct. 30	56.83	Mar. 15	38.75	Dec. 4	50.74
Apr. 4	40.88	Nov. 6	59.92	Mar. 30	41.38	Jan. 3, 1969	49.13
Apr. 11	40.95	Nov. 13	64.06	Apr. 23	39.90	Feb. 5	44.46
Apr. 18	41.01	Nov. 30	^a 78.15	May 10	42.60		

^a Pumping

Well 3 (22-64.57-2-74)

Owner.--K. Tyson.
Name.--Dorothea Bay Well-5.
Location.--Lat 18° 22' 13", long 64° 57' 40".
Description.--Bored water-table observation well,
 diam 4-in, cased 0-10 with perforated
 sheet-metal pipe.
Depth.--10 ft.
Aquifer.--Beach sand and alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of 4-in casing, at land surface.
Land elevation.--10 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--5.33 below lsd, Sept. 5, 1963.
Lowest water level.--Dry.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: August and
 October 1963.
Water levels: 1963-65.
Remarks.--Recorder discontinued, July 1965.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Hardness as CaCO ₃	Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated						Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Aug. 14, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--	29	--		
Oct. 12	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	138	--	--	--	27	--		

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1963												
5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5.33	6.66	6.46	7.15
10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	7.06	6.37	7.36
15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	6.09	5.75	6.79	7.58
20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	6.39	6.28	7.01	7.81
25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	6.64	5.95	7.00	7.91
eom	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	6.28	5.86	6.78	8.05
1964												
5	7.65	7.52	--	8.76	--	f	f	f	f	f	f	f
10	7.25	7.78	8.39	8.89	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f
15	6.91	6.93	8.49	8.66	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f
20	--	7.34	8.19	8.60	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f
25	--	7.72	8.46	8.85	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f
eom	7.86	8.05	8.65	8.92	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f
1965												
5	f	f	f	f	--	--	8.94	--	--	--	--	--
10	f	f	f	f	5.40	--	9.11	--	--	--	--	--
15	f	f	f	f	5.88	7.71	9.39	--	--	--	--	--
20	f	f	f	f	5.79	8.15	9.63	--	--	--	--	--
25	f	f	f	f	6.00	8.47	9.95	--	--	--	--	--
eom	f	f	f	f	6.10	8.70	10.02	--	--	--	--	--

f - dry

Well 4 (22-64.57-1-74)

Owner.--K. Tyson.
Name.--Dorothea Bay Dug Well
Location.--Lat 18° 22' 15", long 64° 57' 40".
Description.--Dug water-table production well,
 diam 10 ft.
Depth.--9 ft.
Aquifer.--Beach sand of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--SW corner of manhole, 2.7 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--8 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--1.40 ft below lsd, Dec. 11, 1965.
Lowest water level.--9.01 ft below lsd, Feb. 1, 1964.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1962-65.
Water levels: 1963-65.
Remarks.--Recorder used from January 1963 to August 1963 and
 February 1964 to December 1965. Measurement dis-
 continued, December 1965.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter													Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)		Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate					
Dec. 15, 1962	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	136	--	--	--	--	27	--	
Dec. 22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	225	--	--	--	--	128	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Dec. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	118	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Jan. 5, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--	--	124	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Jan. 12	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	144	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Jan. 19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Jan. 26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	245	--	--	--	--	146	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Feb. 9	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	166	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Feb. 17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	122	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Feb. 23	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	225	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Mar. 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	164	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Mar. 10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Mar. 16	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	235	--	--	--	--	224	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Apr. 5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	225	--	--	--	--	228	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Apr. 12	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	285	--	--	--	--	166	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Apr. 20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	245	--	--	--	--	168	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
May 25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	176	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
June 22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	255	--	--	--	--	178	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
June 20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--	--	194	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Aug. 24	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	115	--	--	--	--	200	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Sept. 28	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	148	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Oct. 12	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--	--	146	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Oct. 26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--	--	152	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Nov. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--	--	266	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Dec. 7	--	20	0.00	--	48	39	355	798	0	37	255	0.4	0.0	--	*1,080	280	0	1,870	7.8	27	--	
Jan. 25, 1964	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	224	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Feb. 29	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	218	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Mar. 15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	148	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Apr. 25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	200	--	--	--	--	204	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
May 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	200	--	--	--	--	188	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
June 20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
July 3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--	--	132	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Aug. 22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--	--	--	28	--
Sept. 19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	232	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Sept. 26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	222	--	--	--	--	--	28	--
Oct. 3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	216	--	--	--	--	--	28	--
Oct. 17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Oct. 23	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	244	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Dec. 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Dec. 21	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	108	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Jan. 11, 1965	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	224	--	--	--	--	--	25	--
Feb. 1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--	--	88	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Feb. 22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--	--	236	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Apr. 5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--	--	44	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
May 3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	412	--	--	--	--	288	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
June 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	332	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--	--	--	28	--
June 22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	360	--	--	--	--	304	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
July 6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	410	--	--	--	--	236	--	--	--	--	--	27	--
Dec. 19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	244	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180° C.

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1963												
5	5.35	6.26	7.04	--	4.26	5.18	6.88	4.08	--	--	--	--
10	5.42	6.29	7.08	3.25	4.92	5.69	4.70	4.68	--	--	--	--
15	5.77	6.57	6.84	3.93	3.43	6.31	5.52	5.27	--	--	--	--
20	5.95	6.99	6.98	--	3.19	6.46	6.24	5.67	--	--	--	--
25	6.21	6.93	6.89	4.88	4.06	6.63	6.33	5.33	--	--	--	--
eom	6.24	6.82	4.77	4.31	4.74	6.62	6.43	3.21	--	--	--	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 14, 1963	4.67	Oct. 26, 1963	4.58	Dec. 7, 1963	6.33	Jan. 18, 1964	6.01
Sept. 21	5.07	Nov. 2	4.73	Dec. 14	6.57	Jan. 25	7.23
Sept. 28	4.70	Nov. 9	4.47	Dec. 21	6.84	Feb. 1	9.01
Oct. 5	5.22	Nov. 16	5.63	Dec. 28	7.09	Feb. 8	6.80
Oct. 12	5.81	Nov. 23	5.31	Jan. 4, 1964	7.17		
Oct. 19	4.74	Nov. 30	6.01	Jan. 11	6.45		

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1964												
5	--	--	7.65	6.70	--	7.15	7.10	6.95	6.60	6.60	6.60	--
10	--	--	7.05	6.85	7.10	7.45	7.10	6.85	6.65	6.60	6.70	7.30
15	--	--	6.95	6.85	8.00	7.00	6.90	7.00	6.85	6.70	6.75	--
20	--	6.15	6.75	7.00	6.80	6.95	6.75	7.15	6.60	6.65	7.20	--
25	--	6.70	7.00	7.25	7.05	7.10	6.75	7.40	6.50	6.80	7.30	6.75
eom	--	7.95	7.60	7.35	7.25	7.50	6.70	6.70	6.55	6.70	8.00	7.20
1965												
5	6.80	7.60	8.40	5.75	3.80	--	--	--	6.70	5.90	--	2.40
10	6.85	7.80	8.00	6.55	2.75	3.90	7.10	--	6.55	5.85	--	1.90
15	7.00	7.70	7.15	6.60	3.00	--	7.00	--	6.75	5.75	2.20	1.95
20	7.45	7.55	7.85	7.30	2.95	5.25	7.10	--	6.90	4.30	2.00	2.25
25	7.75	--	7.90	8.30	3.10	5.65	8.15	--	6.20	--	1.55	1.90
eom	7.55	7.75	7.10	6.00	--	--	7.05	6.90	6.05	--	2.15	--

Well 5 (21-64.54-4-72)

Owner.--D. Raimer.Name.--Rosendal Dug WellLocation.--Lat 18° 21' 16", long 64° 54' 48".Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 7 ft.Depth.--9 ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age and volcanic
rocks of Cretaceous age.Measuring point.--Top of curb, 2.0 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--400 ft above msl.Highest water level.--3.17 ft below lsd, Dec. 17, 1962.Lowest water level.--5.53 ft below lsd, Jan. 22, 1964.Records available.--Chemical analyses: August and
December 1963.Water levels: 1962-64.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1964.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter																Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
	Discharge (gpm)	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non- carbonate
Aug. 21, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	255	--	--	--	--	310	--	--	--	28	--
Dec. 1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	470	--	--	--	--	--	308	--	--	--	26	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
Dec. 17, 1962	3.17	Apr. 26, 1963	4.69	Aug. 21, 1963	4.76	Dec. 16, 1963	4.84
Jan. 18, 1963	4.37	May 20	4.34	Sept. 19	4.04	Jan. 22, 1964	5.53
Feb. 21	4.77	June 18	4.50	Oct. 22	4.54		
Mar. 23	5.00	July 24	4.88	Nov. 20	4.79		

Well 6 (20-64.54-6-08)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-5 (Estate Wintberg).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 59", long 64° 54' 12".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-20.
Depth.--250 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 0.8 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--680 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--58.75 ft below lsd, June 23, 1969.
Lowest water level.--121.76 ft below lsd, Dec. 4, 1968.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: October 1963.
Water levels: 1963-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, July 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Calcium, magnesium		Non-carbonate					
Oct. 14, 1963	--	28	0.04	--	59	57	372	730	0	131	305	0.9	28	--	1,300	382	0	2,200	7.9	29	--	

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 28, 1963	96.27	July 6, 1964	102.90	May 3, 1965	111.58	Oct. 31, 1966	99.69
Nov. 4	109.64	July 13	102.88	May 10	111.81	Nov. 30	100.40
Nov. 12	109.80	July 20	102.67	May 24	112.32	Jan. 3, 1967	101.40
Nov. 19	109.40	Aug. 10	103.25	June 2	113.25	Jan. 31	102.25
Nov. 27	104.30	Aug. 24	103.68	June 14	118.72	Mar. 13	103.92
Dec. 2	105.02	Aug. 31	103.90	June 21	113.20	Apr. 18	105.30
Dec. 10	105.84	Sept. 9	104.22	June 29	113.41	June 1	106.54
Dec. 16	102.20	Sept. 14	104.39	July 7	113.64	July 6	107.56
Dec. 23	101.95	Sept. 23	104.67	July 19	113.95	Aug. 1	107.36
Dec. 30	101.52	Sept. 29	104.85	Aug. 5	113.81	Sept. 1	109.23
Jan. 6, 1964	101.25	Oct. 13	105.25	Aug. 21	113.81	Oct. 3	110.16
Jan. 15	101.03	Oct. 19	105.41	Nov. 2	119.30	Nov. 2	109.88
Jan. 22	100.80	Oct. 27	105.64	Nov. 26	101.60	Dec. 7	110.97
Feb. 3	100.67	Nov. 2	105.82	Dec. 8	89.48	Jan. 4, 1968	111.79
Feb. 11	100.60	Nov. 9	106.04	Dec. 14	79.68	Feb. 6	112.86
Feb. 17	100.65	Nov. 23	106.45	Dec. 22	80.55	Mar. 5	113.77
Mar. 5	101.15	Dec. 1	106.63	Jan. 3, 1966	79.18	Apr. 3	111.98
Mar. 9	100.76	Dec. 7	106.81	Jan. 17	80.95	May 3	112.72
Mar. 16	100.84	Dec. 14	106.95	Jan. 27	84.43	June 3	114.00
Mar. 24	100.97	Dec. 28	107.49	Feb. 14	88.52	July 3	115.29
Mar. 30	100.99	Jan. 4, 1965	107.71	Mar. 15	92.48	Aug. 1	117.12
Apr. 7	101.17	Jan. 12	107.95	Mar. 30	93.13	Sept. 3	118.17
Apr. 13	101.28	Jan. 26	108.41	Apr. 12	94.05	Oct. 1	118.26
Apr. 20	101.45	Feb. 8	108.84	Apr. 26	95.27	Nov. 1	121.10
May 5	101.75	Feb. 15	109.09	May 10	96.37	Dec. 4	121.76
May 11	101.85	Feb. 23	109.34	May 26	97.50	Jan. 3, 1969	121.04
May 18	102.07	Mar. 2	109.56	June 8	98.43	Feb. 5	112.67
May 26	102.23	Mar. 8	109.77	June 29	99.40	Mar. 24	97.41
June 1	102.39	Mar. 15	110.02	July 12	99.82	Apr. 23	99.64
June 8	102.57	Mar. 24	110.29	July 27	100.19	May 23	101.91
June 15	102.49	Mar. 30	110.54	Aug. 5	100.58	June 23	58.75
June 22	102.65	Apr. 5	110.65	Aug. 29	101.40	July 23	92.36
June 29	102.84	Apr. 26	111.85	Sept. 26	102.44		

Well 7 (21-64.54-5-35)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-3 (estate Lovenlund).
Location.--Lat 18° 21' 38", long 64° 54' 31".
Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-31.
Depth.--80 ft.
Aquifer.--Limestone of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.8 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--90 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--5.20 ft below lsd, Jan.17, 1966.
Lowest water level.--66.64 ft below lsd, Jan. 3, 1969.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: September 1963
 and date unknown 1966.
Water levels: 1963-69.
Remarks.--Recorder used from October 1963 to March 1965.
 Measurement discontinued, February 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Sept. 5, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	344	--	--	--	--	--	386	--	--	--	27	--
-- -- 1966	--	35	0.01	--	88	68	297	748	0	58	330	0.9	4.5	--	* 1,280	499	0	2,180	7.8	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1963												
5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	12.40	13.65	14.90
10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	12.55	13.90	15.10
15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	12.75	14.05	15.30
20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	12.95	14.35	15.55
25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	13.20	14.45	--
eom	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	13.45	14.65	16.05
1964												
5	16.20	17.08	17.92	18.63	--	20.33	21.07	21.77	22.47	22.98	23.64	24.25
10	16.35	17.23	18.05	18.78	--	20.45	21.18	21.89	22.58	23.07	23.74	24.35
15	16.50	17.36	18.17	18.91	--	20.57	21.29	22.02	22.69	23.16	23.83	24.50
20	15.65	17.49	18.27	19.04	--	20.70	21.40	22.19	22.81	23.26	23.95	24.62
25	16.77	17.63	18.39	19.17	--	20.83	21.51	22.28	22.93	23.35	24.03	24.72
eom	16.92	--	18.47	19.30	20.19	20.96	21.63	22.37	22.90	23.51	24.12	24.83
1965												
5	24.96	25.31	26.14	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
10	25.07	25.68	26.24	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
15	25.08	25.79	26.32	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
20	25.19	25.88	26.41	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
25	25.29	25.98	26.52	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
eom	25.39	26.04	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
May 3, 1965	27.33	Dec. 14, 1965	15.87	Aug. 31, 1966	14.00	Feb. 6, 1968	26.20
May 10	26.78	Dec. 22	11.79	Sept. 26	14.51	Mar. 5	26.89
May 11	26.45	Jan. 3, 1966	6.38	Oct. 31	12.50	Apr. 3	28.03
May 18	25.80	Jan. 17	5.20	Nov. 30	13.55	May 3	28.22
June 2	26.50	Jan. 27	5.30	Dec. 28	14.15	June 3	28.85
June 21	27.06	Feb. 14	6.04	Jan. 31, 1967	15.20	July 3	29.86
June 29	27.32	Mar. 15	7.24	Mar. 13	16.75	Aug. 1	30.50
July 8	27.52	Mar. 30	7.71	Apr. 18	17.90	Sept. 3	30.00
July 21	28.76	Apr. 12	8.42	June 1	18.63	Oct. 1	30.41
Aug. 5	26.94	Apr. 26	8.65	July 6	19.83	Nov. 1	49.58
Aug. 21	28.33	May 9	9.13	Aug. 1	20.82	Dec. 4	50.50
Sept. 30	29.42	May 26	9.66	Sept. 1	22.58	Jan. 3, 1969	66.64
Nov. 2	28.77	June 8	10.23	Oct. 3	22.85	Feb. 3, 1969	47.40
Nov. 16	25.09	June 29	11.08	Nov. 1	23.42		
Nov. 26	22.44	July 25	12.17	Dec. 8	24.47		
Dec. 8	20.42	Aug. 5	12.68	Jan. 4, 1968	25.22		

Well 8 (21-64.54-2-35)

Owner.--C. Petersen.

Name.--Lovenlund Dug Well.

Location.--Lat 18° 21' 40", long 64° 54' 32".

Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 7.5 ft.

Depth.--21 ft.

Aquifer.--Limestone of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of curb, 1.5 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--80 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--2.65 ft below lsd, Jan. 27, 1966.

Lowest water level.--Dry.

Records available.--Chemical analyses: August and
November 1963.

Water levels: 1962-68.

Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non- carbonate
Aug. 21, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	35	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--	28	--
Nov. 11	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--	--	--	248	--	--	--	26	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
Oct. 29, 1962	5.24	Mar. 3, 1964	13.17	July 8, 1965	f	Nov. 30, 1966	8.80
Dec. 17	6.96	Mar. 26	13.68	Sept. 30	f	Dec. 28	9.33
Jan. 18, 1963	8.03	Apr. 22	14.46	Nov. 2	f	Jan. 31, 1967	11.54
Feb. 21	9.13	May 27	15.41	Dec. 2	15.58	Mar. 13	11.93
Mar. 23	10.09	June 22	16.04	Dec. 14	7.22	June 1	13.83
Apr. 26	10.07	July 20	16.65	Dec. 29	3.98	July 6	14.37
May 20	8.60	Aug. 25	15.14	Jan. 27, 1966	2.65	Aug. 1	16.10
June 18	9.72	Sept. 23	18.18	Mar. 30	4.17	Sept. 1	17.02
July 24	10.63	Oct. 27	18.73	Apr. 26	4.82	Oct. 3	18.13
Aug. 21	10.68	Nov. 20	19.32	May 26	4.50	Nov. 1	18.42
Sept. 19	7.68	Dec. 14	19.89	June 29	6.57	Dec. 7	19.98
Oct. 22	8.32	Jan. 11, 1965	f	July 25	7.50	Jan. 4, 1968	22.43
Nov. 20	9.51	Feb. 8	f	Aug. 31	9.40		
Dec. 16	10.18	Mar. 8	f	Sept. 26	9.84		
Jan. 22, 1964	11.93	May 10	17.38	Oct. 31	7.84		

f - dry

Well 9 (20-64.52-4-24)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.

Name.--USGS-2 (Estate Fresh Meadow).

Location.--Lat 18° 20' 48", long 64° 52' 40".

Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-21.

Depth.--120 ft.

Aquifer.--Limestone of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 2.5 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--120 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--15.35 ft below lsd, Dec. 14, 1965.

Lowest water level.--32.68 ft below lsd, May 3, 1968.

Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1963-66.

Water levels: 1963-69.

Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, February 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter												Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)		Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Aug. 23, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	165	--	--	--	--	316	--	--	--	28	--	
Oct. 14	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	300	--	--	--	--	196	--	--	--	28	--	
Nov. 14	--	35	0.00	--	40	46	334	670	0	56	278	0.7	18	--	1,090	289	0	1,910	8.0	28	--
July 27, 1966	--	5.6	.00	0.00	13	7.7	31	102	0	8.8	26	.1	2.4	--	*149	64	0	276	7.6	28	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 16, 1963	23.28	June 1, 1964	28.09	Mar. 8, 1965	28.74	June 27, 1966	27.58
Sept. 24	24.64	June 8	28.14	Mar. 15	28.76	July 11	27.93
Oct. 14	25.93	June 15	28.16	Mar. 23	28.78	July 25	27.79
Oct. 24	26.21	June 22	28.18	Mar. 30	28.81	Aug. 5	27.80
Oct. 28	26.37	June 29	28.20	Apr. 5	28.82	Aug. 30	29.10
Nov. 4	26.90	July 6	28.17	Apr. 19	28.81	Sept. 26	28.05
Nov. 12	26.68	July 13	28.19	Apr. 26	28.83	Oct. 31	26.89
Nov. 19	26.79	July 20	28.13	May 3	28.84	Nov. 29	28.07
Nov. 24	26.54	Aug. 10	28.24	May 10	28.21	Dec. 28	27.54
Dec. 2	26.68	Aug. 24	28.22	May 18	27.79	Jan. 31, 1967	28.24
Dec. 10	26.74	Aug. 31	28.19	May 24	28.01	Mar. 14	28.69
Dec. 16	26.85	Sept. 9	28.28	June 2	28.07	Apr. 18	28.27
Dec. 24	27.05	Sept. 14	28.32	June 7	28.16	June 1	28.23
Dec. 30	27.06	Sept. 23	28.30	June 21	28.37	July 6	29.79
Jan. 6, 1964	27.16	Sept. 29	28.26	June 24	28.45	Aug. 2	26.68
Jan. 15	27.24	Oct. 13	28.25	July 7	28.52	Sept. 1	28.92
Jan. 23	27.31	Oct. 19	28.23	July 21	27.63	Oct. 3	30.13
Feb. 3	27.41	Oct. 28	28.29	Aug. 5	27.64	Nov. 1	29.71
Feb. 10	27.47	Nov. 2	28.32	Nov. 16	23.37	Dec. 7	29.29
Feb. 17	27.52	Nov. 9	28.35	Nov. 26	23.16	Jan. 4, 1968	29.50
Feb. 24	27.58	Nov. 23	28.39	Dec. 8	24.02	Feb. 2	29.49
Mar. 2	27.62	Nov. 30	28.41	Dec. 14	15.35	Mar. 5	30.85
Mar. 9	28.15	Dec. 7	28.43	Jan. 3, 1966	18.00	Apr. 3	31.52
Mar. 16	27.72	Dec. 14	28.46	Jan. 17	20.30	May 3	32.68
Mar. 24	27.76	Dec. 21	28.52	Jan. 27	21.77	June 3	30.19
Mar. 30	27.82	Dec. 28	28.55	Feb. 14	23.57	July 3	30.30
Apr. 7	27.87	Jan. 4, 1965	28.55	Mar. 1	24.30	Aug. 1	29.67
Apr. 13	27.84	Jan. 11	28.59	Mar. 15	24.95	Sept. 3	30.07
Apr. 20	27.82	Jan. 26	28.60	Mar. 30	24.84	Oct. 1	30.34
May 5	27.87	Feb. 8	28.69	Apr. 12	25.87	Nov. 1	30.09
May 11	27.92	Feb. 15	28.70	Apr. 26	26.39	Dec. 4	28.80
May 18	28.00	Feb. 23	28.73	May 10	26.40	Jan. 3, 1969	29.86
May 26	28.05	Mar. 2	28.73	June 8	27.06	Feb. 5	27.57

Well 10 (20-64.52-1-07)

Owner.--V.I. Government.
Name.--Frydendal Dug Well.
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 56", long 64° 52' 19".
Description.--Dug water-table production well,
 diam 10 ft.
Depth.--14 ft.
Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of curb, 3.5 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--15 ft above lsd.
Highest water level.--2.81 ft below lsd, Oct. 3, 1962.
Lowest water level.--9.84 ft below lsd, Mar. 8, 1965.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: August 1963.
Water levels: 1962-68.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter													Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote			
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)					Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Aug. 21, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	555	--	--	--	--	696	--	--	27	--		

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 3, 1962	2.81	Jan. 23, 1964	7.02	May 5, 1965	8.55	Sept. 26, 1966	5.85
Oct. 9	3.10	Mar. 3	7.53	June 18	7.21	Oct. 31	5.03
Oct. 29	3.61	Mar. 26	8.45	July 8	7.35	Nov. 29	5.50
Dec. 17	4.95	Apr. 22	7.62	Aug. 31	7.15	Dec. 28	5.20
Jan. 18, 1963	4.93	May 26	8.40	Nov. 2	5.97	Jan. 31, 1967	6.17
Feb. 21	5.30	June 22	8.60	Dec. 2	4.53	Mar. 14	6.87
Mar. 23	6.06	July 20	8.32	Dec. 14	2.97	Apr. 18	7.66
Apr. 26	5.68	Aug. 24	8.72	Dec. 29	3.17	June 1	7.72
May 20	4.56	Sept. 23	7.64	Jan. 27, 1966	3.54	July 6	8.36
June 18	5.93	Oct. 28	7.83	Mar. 1	3.85	Aug. 2	8.57
July 14	6.06	Nov. 23	8.24	Mar. 30	4.45	Sept. 1	8.79
Aug. 21	5.96	Dec. 14	8.77	Apr. 26	4.53	Oct. 3	8.82
Sept. 19	5.03	Jan. 11, 1965	9.04	May 26	4.82	Nov. 1	7.63
Oct. 22	5.80	Feb. 8	9.26	June 27	5.58	Dec. 7	7.62
Nov. 20	6.51	Mar. 8	9.84	July 25	6.08	Jan. 4, 1968	7.78
Dec. 16	7.48	Apr. 7	9.48	Aug. 30	6.15		

Well 11 (20-64.51-1-66)

Owner.--L. Lindquist.Name.--Smith Bay Dug Well.Location.--Lat 18° 20' 18", long 64° 51' 28".Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 8 ft.Depth.--12+ ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of curbing, 1.8 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--8 ft above msl.Highest water level.--3.64 ft below lsd, Oct. 29, 1962.Lowest water level.--12.75 ft below lsd, Aug. 21, 1963.Records available.--Chemical analyses: August and
November 1963.Water levels: 1962-64.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1964.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm.)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non- carbonate
Aug. 21, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	895	--	--	--	--	--	864	--	--	29	--	
Nov. 5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,660	--	--	--	--	--	262	--	--	29	--	

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 9, 1962	5.22	Mar. 23, 1963	^a 12.39	July 24, 1963	10.07	Nov. 20, 1963	^a 12.04
Oct. 29	3.64	Apr. 26	^a 11.25	Aug. 21	12.75	Dec. 16	^a 12.09
Dec. 17	5.32	May 20	^a 3.71	Sept. 19	^a 8.09	Jan. 23, 1964	5.55
Jan. 18, 1963	4.67	June 18	12.69	Oct. 22	^a 12.64		

a - pumping

Well 12 (20-64.51-13-99)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS--23 (Red Hook).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 01", long 64° 51' 09".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-23.
Depth.--56 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 2.0 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--40 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--23.82 ft below lsd, June 23, 1969.
Lowest water level.--29.35 ft below lsd, July 3, 1968.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: August 1965.
Water levels: 1965-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, July 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote			
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)					Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Aug. 12, 1965	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4,270	--	--	--	--	--	1,476	--	--	--	--	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Aug. 31, 1965	29.02	Apr. 26, 1966	27.96	Apr. 18, 1967	28.58	Aug. 1, 1968	29.17
Nov. 2	28.42	May 10	28.07	June 1	28.74	Sept. 3	28.81
Nov. 16	28.18	May 26	28.18	July 6	28.89	Oct. 1	28.58
Nov. 26	26.46	June 10	28.36	Aug. 2	28.87	Nov. 4	28.65
Dec. 8	26.42	June 27	28.44	Sept. 1	28.83	Dec. 4	28.47
Dec. 14	27.79	July 11	28.47	Oct. 3	28.60	Jan. 3, 1969	28.45
Dec. 27	27.36	July 25	28.23	Nov. 1	28.44	Feb. 5	28.53
Jan. 3, 1966	27.23	Aug. 5	28.42	Dec. 7	28.71	Mar. 24	27.62
Jan. 17	27.17	Aug. 30	28.42	Jan. 4, 1968	28.85	Apr. 23	28.14
Jan. 27	27.19	Sept. 26	28.40	Feb. 6	28.92	May 26	26.70
Feb. 14	27.38	Oct. 31	27.90	Mar. 5	29.01	June 23	23.82
Mar. 1	27.55	Nov. 29	27.90	Apr. 3	28.99	July 23	26.70
Mar. 15	27.60	Dec. 28	27.98	May 3	29.10		
Mar. 30	27.75	Jan. 31, 1967	28.10	June 3	29.16		
Apr. 12	27.84	Mar. 14	28.37	July 3	29.35		

Well 13 (19-64.51-1-41)

Owner.--V.I. Government.Name.--Benner Dug Well.Location.--Lat 18° 19' 31", long 64° 51' 55".Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 8 ft.Depth.--46 ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of curb, 2.6 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--40 ft above msl.Highest water level.--5.36 ft below lsd, Dec. 14, 1965.Lowest water level.--Dry, Dec. 16, 1963.Records available.--Chemical analysis: November 1963.Water levels: 1962-68.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter													Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote			
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)					Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Nov. 5, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--	28	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
Oct. 29, 1962	8.36	Mar. 26, 1964	44.70	July 8, 1965	40.86	Nov. 29, 1966	22.37
Dec. 17	22.23	Apr. 22	44.87	Aug. 31	40.25	Dec. 28	22.45
Jan. 18, 1963	23.92	May 26	44.54	Nov. 1	38.03	Jan. 31, 1967	22.35
Feb. 21	27.52	June 22	44.11	Dec. 2	8.80	Mar. 14	29.32
Mar. 23	32.62	July 20	43.99	Dec. 14	5.36	Apr. 18	31.48
Apr. 26	36.55	Aug. 24	42.15	Dec. 29	6.79	June 1	30.98
May 20	36.96	Sept. 23	42.17	Jan. 27, 1966	22.53	July 6	34.99
June 18	42.35	Oct. 28	41.89	Mar. 1	35.64	Aug. 2	37.71
July 24	44.29	Nov. 23	44.68	Mar. 30	36.83	Sept. 1	44.05
Aug. 21	43.92	Dec. 14	43.71	Apr. 26	38.87	Oct. 3	42.46
Sept. 19	15.65	Jan. 12, 1965	43.96	May 26	38.74	Nov. 1	41.22
Oct. 22	31.93	Feb. 8	44.54	June 27	38.89	Dec. 7	41.36
Nov. 20	42.69	Mar. 8	44.09	July 25	37.95	Jan. 4, 1968	43.75
Dec. 16	f	Apr. 7	43.36	Aug. 30	36.96		
Jan. 23, 1964	44.61	May 4	43.62	Sept. 26	36.00		
Mar. 2	44.57	June 18	41.48	Oct. 31	21.14		

f - dry

Well 14 (20-64.53-22-33)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-27 (Estate Tutu).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 40", long 64° 53' 43".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-200, perforated 60-200.
Depth.--200 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 3.6 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--175 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--20.42 ft below lsd, Jan. 27, 1966.
Lowest water level.--32.93 ft below lsd, Apr. 3, 1968.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: September 1965
and August 1966.
Water levels: 1965-68.
Remarks.--Plugged. Measurement discontinued, April 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter													Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)		Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Sept. 15, 1965	--	39	0.00	--	12	51	325	580	20	28	282	0.9	11	--	* 1,060	240	0	1,880	8.5	--	--	
Aug. 29, 1966	--	38	.00	0.00	30	40	357	692	0	86	245	1.0	14	--	* 1,090	240	0	1,830	8.1	--	--	

* Residue on evaporation at 180° C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
Nov. 15, 1965	32.80	Apr. 26, 1966	22.15	Dec. 28, 1966	23.76	Dec. 14, 1967	31.45
Nov. 26	31.50	May 10	22.68	Jan. 30, 1967	24.52	Dec. 21	31.57
Dec. 8	29.95	May 26	23.32	Mar. 14	26.23	Jan. 4, 1968	31.88
Dec. 14	27.25	June 10	24.06	Apr. 18	27.58	Jan. 9	31.92
Jan. 3, 1966	21.85	June 27	24.77	June 1	26.52	Jan. 23	32.14
Jan. 17	20.72	July 11	25.42	July 6	28.66	Feb. 6	32.39
Jan. 27	20.42	July 25	25.75	Aug. 1	29.45	Feb. 21	32.59
Feb. 14	20.55	Aug. 5	26.00	Sept. 1	30.13	Mar. 5	32.60
Mar. 15	21.32	Sept. 27	26.49	Oct. 3	31.01	Mar. 20	32.76
Mar. 30	21.28	Oct. 31	23.00	Nov. 2	30.89	Apr. 3	32.93
Apr. 12	21.88	Nov. 29	23.83	Dec. 7	31.38		

Well 15 (20-64.53-6-33)

Owner.--St. Thomas Real Estate.Location.--Lat 18° 20' 38", long 64° 53' 41".Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 7 ft.Depth.--34 ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of curb, 2.0 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--175 ft above msl.Highest water level.--10.20 ft below lsd, Oct. 20, 1963.Lowest water level.--^a27.29 ft below lsd, May 20, 1963.Records available.--Chemical analyses: February 1963,
July 1967, and May 1968.Water levels: 1962-64.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1964.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)		Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate				
Feb. 21, 1963	--	38	0.00	--	52	27	380	768	0	49	248	0.9	43	--	* 1,290	240	0	2,010	8.0	27	--	
July 19, 1967	--	28	.05	0.00	48	29	107	374	0	57	35	.3	68	--	* 641	239	0	858	8.0	--	--	
May 16, 1968	--	26	--	.00	56	24	120	340	8	--	30	.8	145	4.8	--	240	0	1,020	8.4	--	--	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 17, 1962	14.74	Jan. 28, 1963	15.77	May 20, 1963	^a 27.29	Oct. 20, 1963	10.20
Jan. 2, 1963	15.16	Feb. 4	15.82	June 18	25.54	Dec. 16	10.74
Jan. 7	15.22	Feb. 21	21.06	Aug. 3	17.00	Jan. 22, 1964	19.98
Jan. 14	15.41	Mar. 23	17.17	Aug. 22	16.80		
Jan. 21	15.66	Apr. 22	17.03	Sept. 19	15.22		
a - pumping							

Well 16 (20-64.54-1-76)

Owner.--H.E. Lockhart, Jr.
Name.--Raphane Dug Well.
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 17", long 64° 54' 24".
Description.--Dug unused water-table well,
diam 20 ft.
Depth.--32 ft.
Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of curb at lsd.
Land elevation.--270 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--5.65 ft below lsd, Oct. 29, 1962.
Lowest water level.--17.03 ft below lsd, Apr. 22, 1963.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: August and
November 1963.
Water levels: 1962-64.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1964.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Aug. 22, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	--	--	--	194	--	--	--	26	--
Nov. 1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	--	--	--	78	--	--	--	26	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 2, 1962	14.65	Jan. 7, 1963	12.95	Mar. 23, 1963	16.38	Oct. 22, 1963	13.68
Oct. 9	14.94	Jan. 14	13.42	Apr. 22	17.03	Nov. 20	11.65
Oct. 29	5.65	Jan. 21	13.76	May 21	12.06	Dec. 16	11.90
Dec. 10	10.39	Jan. 28	14.15	June 18	13.70	Jan. 23, 1964	16.09
Dec. 17	11.27	Feb. 4	14.42	Aug. 22	14.40		
Jan. 2, 1963	12.59	Feb. 21	15.14	Sept. 19	6.78		

Well 17 (20-64.53-3-71)

Owner.--H. E. Lockhart, Jr.
Name.--Donoe Dug Well.
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 17", long 64° 53' 58".
Description.--Dug water-table production well,
9 by 7 ft.
Depth.--9 ft.
Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of curb, 2.8 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--180 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--0.20 ft below lsd, May 20, 1963.
Lowest water level.--2.60 ft below lsd, Jan. 22, 1964.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1962-63.
Water levels: 1962-64.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1964.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Nov. 20, 1962	--	30	0.00	--	35	33	319	748	0	32	188	1.2	3.8	--	*1,010	223	0	1,700	8.1	26	--
Dec. 17	--	28	.00	--	41	29	327	752	0	48	185	1.2	1.5	--	--	222	0	1,690	8.1	25	--
Feb. 21, 1963	--	28	.02	--	41	25	324	750	0	35	178	1.3	6.1	--	*1,050	206	0	1,670	8.1	24	--
Aug. 22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	95	--	--	--	--	234	--	--	--	21	--
Nov. 6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--	--	200	--	--	--	26	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 2, 1962	^a 0.40	Dec. 31, 1962	0.36	Apr. 22, 1963	1.15	Sept. 19, 1963	0.24
Oct. 9	.42	Jan. 7, 1963	.32	May 20	.20	Oct. 22	1.30
Oct. 29	.35	Jan. 14	.35	June 18	1.15	Nov. 20	2.09
Dec. 10	.83	Feb. 21	.69	July 24	1.52	Dec. 16	^a 2.35
Dec. 17	.41	Mar. 23	1.45	Aug. 22	^a 1.64	Jan. 22, 1964	2.60

a - pumping

Well 18 (20-64.53-5-64)

Owner.--S. Harthman.Name.--Harthman-5 Dug Well.Location.--Lat 18° 20' 22", long 64° 53' 36".Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 6 ft.Depth.--12 ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of concrete cover, 2.0 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--150 ft above msl.Highest water level.--0.46 ft below lsd, July 26, 1968.Lowest water level.--4.24 ft below lsd, June 27, 1968.Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1966-69.Water levels: 1967-69.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, February 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter																Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium	Non- carbonate				
Aug. 10, 1966	--	34	0.00	0.00	40	24	400	724	0	106	252	1.1	6.2	--	* 1,120	198	0	1,800	8.0	--	--
May 15, 1968	--	35	--	.00	56	41	344	2.2 706	24	80	238	1.7	2.2	0.5	1,170	310	0	1,910	8.5	--	--
June 27	--	36	--	.00	21	36	327	3.1 558	35	67	240	1.0	.0	.1	1,040	200	0	1,760	8.7	--	--
Aug. 26	--	33	--	.00	76	50	350	7.3 574	30	213	282	.9	.23	1.3	1,350	395	0	2,170	8.5	--	--
Dec. 9,	--	32	--	.01	68	42	358	5.1 804	10	79	262	1.2	2.7	1.3	1,260	342	0	2,130	8.3	--	--
Jan. 9, 1969	--	33	--	.00	64	38	335	4.7 788	0	74	242	1.1	2.7	1.2	1,180	316	0	2,000	8.2	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 14, 1967	0.97	Mar. 20, 1968	0.77	July 26, 1968	0.46	Jan. 9, 1969	0.64
Jan. 9, 1968	1.75	Apr. 23	2.19	Oct. 2	.62	Feb. 11	.67
Jan. 23	1.55	May 24	2.85	Nov. 6	.65		
Feb. 21	1.80	June 27	4.24	Dec. 9	.57		

Well 19 (20-64.53-20-56)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-25 (Estate Charlotte Amalie).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 24", long 64° 53' 27".
Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-210, slotted 100-200 ft.
Depth.--210 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 2.5 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--196 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--39.07 ft below lsd, Jan. 27, 1966.
Lowest water level.--78.25 ft below lsd, May 3, 1968.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1965-68.
Water levels: 1965-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, February 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃						
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate	
Aug. 30, 1965	--	26	0.00	--	14	32	426	750	0	70	285	0.9	0.0	--	* 1,240	166	0	2,070	8.2	--	--	
Dec. 30	--	43	.00	0.02	44	55	258	712	18	26	180	.8	1.2	--	* 1,020	336	0	1,680	8.4	28	--	
Apr. 22, 1966	--	40	.00	.00	45	40	318	780	0	42	198	.8	5.7	--	* 1,080	276	0	1,780	8.3	28	--	
May 16, 1968	--	33	.00	.00	44	34	400	1.1	826	0	61	250	1.3	4.3	0	1,240	255	0	2,060	8.0	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180° C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 1, 1965	57.23	Apr. 12, 1966	40.93	Dec. 29, 1966	43.77	Feb. 6, 1968	70.57
Nov. 2	52.14	Apr. 26	43.06	Jan. 31, 1967	44.28	Apr. 3	75.68
Nov. 16	51.05	May 10	42.05	Mar. 14	45.32	May 3	78.25
Nov. 26	50.07	May 26	42.32	Apr. 18	46.21	June 3	70.85
Dec. 8	48.88	June 10	42.78	June 1	49.85	Aug. 1	68.08
Dec. 14	44.83	June 27	43.27	July 6	51.24	Sept. 3	54.55
Dec. 22	42.96	July 11	43.83	Aug. 1	54.84	Nov. 5	54.22
Jan. 3, 1966	41.79	July 25	44.28	Sept. 1	51.43	Dec. 4	52.49
Jan. 17	39.59	Aug. 5	44.48	Oct. 3	61.56	Jan. 3, 1969	49.73
Jan. 27	39.07	Aug. 29	44.99	Nov. 1	54.69	Feb. 5	^a 50.64
Feb. 14	39.17	Sept. 27	45.24	Dec. 4	70.38		
Mar. 15	40.17	Oct. 31	43.28	Dec. 7	54.07		
Mar. 30	40.49	Nov. 29	43.32	Jan. 4, 1968	63.70		

a - pumping

Well 20 (20-64.53-14-48)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.Name.--USGS-1 (Estate Tutu).Location.--Lat 18° 20' 33", long 64° 53' 15".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-13.Depth.--73 ft.Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 2.55 ft above

lsd. Casing added and land filled, June 1969; new MP.

9.0 ft above old land surface.

Land elevation.--180 ft above msl.Highest water level.--^e9.55 ft below lsd, Dec. 31,
1969.Lowest water level.--57.98 ft below lsd, May 5, 1968.Records available.--Chemical analyses: August 1964,
January 1964, and May 1968.Remarks.--Recorder. Affected by nearby pumpage.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃ Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Aug. 13, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--	--	234	--	--	28	--		
Jan. 2, 1964	--	36	0.00	--	48	46	293	758	0	32	200	1.0	9.4	--	* 963	309	0	1,670	7.9	28	--
May 16, 1968	--	27	.09	0.00	56	40	217	19	670	0	32	130	1.0	1.9	837	305	0	1,410	8.0	--	--
Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)																					
Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec									
1964																					
5	--	--	25.42	26.26	--	29.45	30.53	31.35	32.40	33.30	34.69	35.61									
10	--	24.80	25.53	26.30	27.00	29.69	30.71	31.54	32.65	33.48	34.67	--									
15	--	24.88	25.66	26.43	--	29.96	30.57	31.78	32.99	33.87	34.88	--									
20	--	24.97	26.78	26.63	--	30.16	30.65	32.04	33.14	33.95	34.98	36.98									
25	--	25.07	25.91	--	--	30.43	30.83	32.30	33.13	33.98	35.17	37.70									
eom	--	25.20	26.98	--	29.37	30.51	30.96	31.99	33.08	34.19	35.42	38.09									
1965																					
5	38.47	40.61	54.35	50.80	55.00	50.20	50.85	51.95	52.00	50.20	45.10	39.55									
10	38.67	50.09	44.80	51.10	53.00	50.45	51.35	--	51.85	50.10	--	39.65									
15	39.25	50.66	45.55	51.75	52.60	50.60	51.35	52.00	--	50.06	--	--									
20	--	51.22	46.55	52.75	51.75	50.45	51.45	52.35	51.35	49.50	--	--									
25	39.82	52.91	47.65	--	51.10	51.00	51.95	52.45	50.55	48.40	--	--									
eom	40.12	53.40	49.75	57.60	50.35	51.20	52.25	51.95	50.30	48.10	39.85	--									
1966																					
5	27.40	--	25.70	26.25	27.55	29.80	32.43	34.24	--	35.10	33.99	35.63									
10	27.00	--	25.85	26.50	27.95	29.90	33.23	34.32	36.43	35.06	34.15	35.75									
15	26.20	--	25.70	26.95	28.20	30.30	33.57	34.55	--	33.82	34.69	36.16									
20	25.80	--	25.75	26.85	28.55	30.55	33.68	34.75	35.95	--	35.10	36.80									
25	25.75	--	25.70	27.00	28.85	30.90	33.75	34.73	36.06	--	35.18	37.10									
eom	25.45	--	25.70	27.35	29.35	31.40	34.20	36.25	35.19	33.33	35.63	37.10									
1967																					
5	37.59	39.94	--	--	46.75	47.65	49.50	51.15	h53.47	55.35	55.50	55.80									
10	38.08	40.35	42.00	45.05	--	47.90	49.60	51.75	--	55.60	55.55	55.95									
15	--	40.73	42.60	45.80	46.65	48.30	50.10	51.80	--	55.05	55.55	56.05									
20	38.82	40.66	43.50	46.30	46.75	--	50.25	51.80	--	54.80	55.45	56.15									
25	39.00	--	43.85	46.50	46.90	--	50.35	52.95	--	55.05	55.55	56.50									
eom	39.50	--	44.35	46.75	47.05	49.15	--	--	--	55.30	55.70	56.55									
1968																					
5	56.37	56.97	57.43	56.94	57.98	57.51	57.55	55.58	51.07	--	52.13	48.65									
10	56.43	57.07	57.43	56.67	57.11	57.52	57.51	51.09	51.05	--	53.33	47.85									
15	56.46	57.24	57.48	56.74	57.17	57.58	57.38	51.39	50.95	--	53.95	46.85									
20	56.35	57.35	57.38	56.80	57.19	57.61	57.25	51.38	--	--	53.73	47.45									
25	56.12	57.47	57.33	56.84	57.29	57.62	55.63	51.38	--	--	53.89	47.55									
eom	56.70	57.43	57.06	56.94	57.40	57.60	55.83	51.33	50.54	--	--	47.50									
1969																					
5	47.17	44.83	--	^e 40.22	^e 40.77	--	--	--	--	--	--	--									
10	47.18	--	--	40.32	40.80	--	--	--	--	--	--	--									
15	47.26	--	--	40.47	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--									
20	46.90	44.93	39.95	40.59	--	--	--	--	--	h13.09	13.22	9.65									
25	46.85	44.89	40.02	40.67	--	--	--	--	h13.26	--	--	--									
eom	45.56	44.95	^e 40.12	^e 40.68	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	^e 9.55									

^eEstimated.^hTape measurement.

Well 21 (20-64.53-15-58)

Owner.--J. Tillet.Location.--Lat 18° 20' 29", long 64° 53' 16".Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-15.Depth.--100 ft.Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.5 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--200 ft above msl.Highest water level.--38.40 ft below lsd, Jan. 2, 1964.Lowest water level.--94.18 ft below lsd, July 5, 1968.Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1963-68.Water levels: 1964-68.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, April 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter													Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote			
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)					Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non- carbonate
Oct. 8, 1963	--	39	0.00	--	30	52	266	680	0	32	185	1.1	16	--	*888	289	0	1,535	7.9	28	--
May 13, 1964	--	39	.00	--	62	48	246	698	0	38	178	1.0	26	--	*1,060	352	0	1,680	7.7	28	--
May 26	--	44	.00	--	60	44	247	694	0	26	185	1.0	9	--	*967	330	0	1,650	8.0	--	--
June 25	--	43	.00	--	58	46	244	698	0	26	180	1.0	10	--	*965	334	0	1,650	7.9	28	--
Aug. 25	--	38	.00	--	60	48	247	702	0	28	190	.7	13	--	*953	347	0	1,650	8.2	28	--
July 25, 1966	--	41	.00	0.00	62	49	250	712	0	30	192	.8	16	--	*1,070	356	0	1,730	8.0	--	--
May 19, 1967	--	38	.06	.00	56	51	269	712	0	39	205	.8	23	--	*1,050	349	0	1,750	7.7	--	--
Sept. 1	--	39	.00	.00	56	46	268	716	0	38	195	.6	11	--	*1,060	328	0	1,720	8.0	31	--
Jan. 4, 1968	--	43	.02	.00	68	64	259	822	0	27	195	1.0	23	--	*1,060	435	0	1,760	7.7	27	--
Apr. 3	--	43	.00	.00	50	39	302	1.5 720	0	48	210	.8	22	0.0	1,070	286	0	1,750	8.1	26	--
May 15	--	45	.00	.00	60	60	267	1.5 756	0	45	192	1.3	26	.3	1,070	395	0	1,780	7.9	--	--
Dec. 4	--	41	--	.00	39	52	298	2.0 696	0	40	217	.7	44	.0	1,080	312	0	1,820	8.1	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180° C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Jan. 2, 1964	38.40	Sept. 29, 1964	47.80	June 14, 1965	^a 71.67	Oct. 31, 1966	51.23
Jan. 23	39.08	Oct. 13	48.49	June 21	^a 71.61	Nov. 29	51.10
Feb. 3	39.40	Oct. 19	49.00	June 29	^a 70.31	Dec. 28	^a 54.50
Feb. 10	39.52	Oct. 24	^a 51.22	July 7	^a 72.50	Jan. 31, 1967	55.35
Feb. 17	39.58	Nov. 2	49.39	July 21	68.60	Mar. 14	58.62
Mar. 5	40.02	Nov. 9	49.81	Aug. 5	68.69	Apr. 18	^a 65.82
Mar. 9	40.23	Nov. 23	49.80	Aug. 21	69.55	June 1	^a 66.94
Mar. 16	40.37	Nov. 30	50.40	Aug. 31	68.50	July 6	67.75
Mar. 24	40.65	Dec. 7	^a 53.16	Sept. 30	66.25	Aug. 1	^a 72.07
Mar. 30	41.00	Dec. 14	^a 54.40	Oct. 29	^a 65.48	Sept. 1	^a 75.87
Apr. 7	41.01	Dec. 21	52.29	Nov. 12	^a 58.09	Oct. 3	81.61
Apr. 13	41.10	Dec. 28	^a 53.29	Nov. 26	55.75	Nov. 1	^a 86.10
Apr. 20	41.32	Jan. 4, 1965	^a 56.30	Dec. 8	54.05	Dec. 5	^a 85.78
May 5	41.67	Jan. 11	^a 56.93	Dec. 14	47.28	Dec. 7	^a 85.67
May 11	41.96	Jan. 26	55.18	Dec. 27	42.45	Jan. 4, 1968	^a 85.72
May 13	42.05	Feb. 8	56.56	Jan. 3, 1966	42.27	Jan. 22	82.69
May 18	^a 45.60	Feb. 15	57.59	Jan. 17	40.61	Mar. 5	92.26
May 26	44.35	Feb. 23	^a 58.63	Jan. 27	40.42	Apr. 3	89.65
June 1	44.16	Mar. 2	60.81	Feb. 14	40.28	May 3	88.17
June 8	46.99	Mar. 8	61.85	Mar. 15	41.10	June 3	92.75
June 15	44.98	Mar. 15	66.10	Mar. 30	^a 42.28	July 5	94.18
June 22	47.02	Mar. 23	70.08	Apr. 12	42.51	Aug. 1	83.35
June 29	46.55	Mar. 30	^a 75.17	Apr. 26	42.79	Oct. 1	68.07
July 6	45.37	Apr. 6	75.61	May 10	43.14	Nov. 5	^a 75.10
July 13	45.28	Apr. 19	74.32	May 26	44.09	Dec. 4	66.13
July 20	45.52	Apr. 26	^a 81.62	June 8	45.40	Jan. 3, 1969	57.49
Aug. 10	46.40	May 3	75.59	June 27	46.50	Feb. 5	61.96
Aug. 24	46.94	May 15	71.68	July 11	49.83	Mar. 24	^a 58.94
Aug. 31	46.93	May 18	69.28	July 25	48.79	Apr. 23	57.55
Sept. 9	47.71	May 24	69.00	Aug. 5	49.75		
Sept. 14	48.19	June 2	67.31	Aug. 30	^a 52.34	a - pumping.	
Sept. 23	47.99	June 7	67.86	Sept. 27	50.93		

Well 22 (20-64.53-19-60)

Owner.--U.S. Government—V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS—24 (Frenchman's Hill).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 25", long 64° 53'04".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 5-in.
Depth.--222 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 5-in casing, 2.0 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--240 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--121.65 ft below lsd, Mar. 1, 1966.
Lowest water level.--137.42 ft below lsd, Oct. 20, 1967.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: August and December
 1965.
Water levels: 1965-67.
Remarks.--Recorder discontinued, October 1967.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote				
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃			
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate		
Aug. 22, 1965	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Dec. 9	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	360	--	--	--	--	188	--	--	--	--	--	28	--
Dec. 18	--	32	0.00	0.01	59	54	348	632	16	62	360	0.8	8.4	--	* 1,290	369	0	2,220	8.4	28	--	--	

* Residue on evaporation at 180° C.

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1965												
5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	129.67
10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	131.11	--
20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	131.84	--	130.72	--
25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	131.89	132.16	130.33	--
eom	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	131.93	132.10	129.96	125.58
1966												
5	124.44	121.98	121.68	122.00	122.52	123.20	123.89	124.95	--	126.24	125.92	126.14
10	123.66	121.89	121.72	122.20	122.53	123.32	124.03	125.06	--	126.32	125.92	--
15	123.11	121.85	121.78	122.30	122.65	123.43	124.19	125.17	--	126.03	125.93	--
20	122.63	121.82	121.79	122.38	122.74	123.52	124.45	125.29	--	126.07	125.95	--
25	122.29	121.81	121.79	122.44	122.85	123.64	124.64	125.42	--	126.01	125.99	--
eom	122.04	--	121.79	122.51	122.99	123.75	124.82	125.63	126.22	125.95	126.07	126.15
1967												
5	126.22	126.74	--	129.62	--	131.97	132.00	132.12	134.33	136.90	--	--
10	126.26	126.84	128.49	129.82	--	132.06	132.15	132.25	134.43	137.03	--	--
15	126.35	126.99	128.68	129.97	131.40	132.35	132.38	132.40	134.64	137.26	--	--
20	126.41	127.10	128.90	130.16	131.48	--	132.56	132.60	134.94	137.42	--	--
25	126.54	127.29	129.11	130.43	131.53	--	132.77	132.83	135.12	--	--	--
eom	126.63	127.37	129.28	130.49	131.75	131.87	--	133.17	135.37	--	--	--

Well 23 (20-64.53-7-67)

Owner.--St. Thomas Real Estate.

Location.--Lat 18° 20' 23", long 64° 53' 19".

Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 9 ft.

Depth.--31 ft.

Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of cover, 1.2 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--150 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--9.59 ft below lsd, Feb. 4, 1963.

Lowest water level.--14.35 ft below lsd, Dec. 10, 1962.

Records available.--Water levels: 1962-63.

Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, February 1963.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 10, 1962	^a 14.35	Dec. 31, 1962	^a 11.95	Jan. 14, 1963	10.11	Jan. 28, 1963	10.45
Dec. 17	^a 12.96	Jan. 7, 1963	13.30	Jan. 21	10.05	Feb. 4	9.59

Well 24 (20-64.53-9b-67)

Owner.--W. Christensen.

Location.--Lat 18° 20' 20", long 64° 53' 19".

Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-85.

Depth.--107 ft.

Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 0.4 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--137 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--25.43 ft below lsd, Mar. 24, 1969.

Lowest water level.--74.81 ft below lsd, Nov. 5, 1968.

Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1967-68.

Water levels: 1967-69.

Remarks.--Well redrilled mid-1968. Measurement discontinued, March 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter													Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote				
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)					Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Hardness as CaCO ₃		
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate	
May 19, 1967	--	37	0.01	0.01	36	41	238	594	8	38	160	0.9	11	--	*	896	258	0	1,400	8.3	--	--
July 20	--	40	.01	.02	48	39	251	612	0	44	188	.8	15	--	*	949	280	0	1,560	7.8	37	--
Jan. 4, 1968	--	40	.00	.00	52	41	323	746	0	50	225	1.2	23	--	*	1,060	300	0	1,800	7.9	26	--
Apr. 3	--	41	.00	.00	15	36	314	1.5	484	33	59	250	.8	22	0	1,010	186	0	1,710	8.7	26	--
May 16	--	41	.00	.00	50	49	316	1.3	688	0	54	255	1.5	17	0	1,120	325	0	1,910	7.9	--	--
Dec. 4	--	40	--	.00	52	42	304	1.6	644	20	56	240	.9	15	0	1,090	302	0	1,840	8.5	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180° C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Aug. 16, 1967	49.46	Feb. 6, 1968	^e 65.79	Aug. 1, 1968	58.77	Feb. 5, 1969	26.45
Nov. 1	66.41	Mar. 5	57.57	Oct. 1	44.28	Mar. 24	25.43
Dec. 4	57.62	Apr. 3	64.34	Nov. 5	^a 74.81		
Dec. 7	67.50	May 3	57.29	Dec. 4	^a 36.04		
Jan. 4, 1968	69.12	June 3	51.36	Jan. 3, 1969	^a 44.20		

a - pumping
e - estimated

Well 25 (20-64.53-21-65)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS - 26
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 20", long 64° 53' 32".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-155, perforated 75-155.
Depth.--250 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 2.1 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--135 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--15.14 ft below lsd, May 26, 1969.
Lowest water level.--29.30 ft below lsd, June 27, 1968.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1965-69.
Water levels: 1965-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, July 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter																Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)		Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
							Potassium (K)	Calcium, magnesium									Non-carbonate					
Sept. 9, 1965	--	34	0.02	--	18	40	293	600	6	36	215	0.9	3.0	--	*955	210	0	1,680	8.3	29	--	
Aug. 2, 1966	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	290	--	--	--	--	318	--	--	--	27	--	
Aug. 10	--	38	.00	0.00	56	46	354	710	0	150	250	1.4	4.5	--	*1,230	328	0	1,930	8.0	--	--	
Aug. 17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	290	--	--	--	--	336	--	--	--	27	--	
Aug. 22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	310	--	--	--	--	508	--	--	--	--	--	
May 16, 1968	--	34	.02	.00	14	44	280	1.2	580	18	6.4	215	1.0	.2	0.0	899	220	0	1,560	8.5	--	--
June 27	--	5.4	--	.00	4.8	37	288	1.5	528	31	2.0	220	.6	.2	.2	851	164	0	1,540	8.8	--	--
July 26	--	3.1	--	.02	9.6	37	289	1.5	542	26	5.6	215	.6	1.5	.0	856	176	0	1,550	8.6	--	--
Aug. 26	--	6.5	--	.00	4.6	32	255	1.6	444	35	11	188	.6	.8	.0	754	143	0	1,350	8.8	--	--
Dec. 9	--	8.2	--	.00	27	21	154	3.1	424	0	5.8	97	.4	1.3	.0	527	154	0	933	8.2	--	--
Jan. 9, 1969	--	4.5	--	.02	42	23	130	3.4	418	0	7.0	95	.4	1.2	.0	512	200	0	927	8.1	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180° C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Nov. 2, 1965	26.76	Apr. 26, 1966	16.95	July 6, 1967	20.95	Apr. 23, 1968	25.60
Nov. 16	20.95	May 10	18.19	Aug. 1	21.54	May 3	26.03
Nov. 26	20.20	May 26	18.27	Sept. 1	22.67	May 24	27.38
Dec. 8	20.00	June 10	18.40	Oct. 3	23.66	June 3	28.03
Dec. 14	18.17	June 27	18.60	Nov. 1	21.47	June 27	29.30
Dec. 22	18.43	July 11	18.84	Dec. 4	22.68	July 26	24.39
Dec. 28	18.05	July 25	18.60	Dec. 7	22.88	Aug. 26	21.46
Dec. 29	18.08	Aug. 5	18.99	Dec. 14	22.93	Oct. 2	21.07
Dec. 30	18.18	Sept. 27	18.64	Jan. 4, 1968	24.03	Nov. 6	21.04
Jan. 3, 1966	18.20	Oct. 31	17.84	Jan. 9	24.14	Dec. 9	19.97
Jan. 17	17.92	Nov. 29	18.14	Jan. 23, 1968	24.56	Jan. 9, 1969	19.93
Jan. 27	18.09	Dec. 28	18.21	Feb. 6	24.79	Feb. 11	19.32
Feb. 14	18.20	Jan. 31, 1967	18.26	Feb. 21	25.05	Mar. 26	18.42
Mar. 15	18.04	Mar. 14	18.70	Mar. 5	24.59	Apr. 24	18.29
Mar. 30	17.94	Apr. 18	19.35	Mar. 20	24.28	May 26	15.14
Apr. 12	18.15	June 1	19.75	Apr. 3	24.82	July 23	17.35

Well 26 (20-64.53-1-86)

Owner.--S. Mylner.
Name.--Mt. Zion Dug Well.
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 11", long 64° 53' 28".
Description.--Dug water-table production well,
 diam 11 ft.
Depth.--18 ft.
Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of curb, 1.5 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--120 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--0.49 ft below lsd, Apr. 30, 1963.
Lowest water level.--Dry.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1962-67.
Water levels: 1958-69.
Remarks.--Recorder used from April to May 1963.
 Measurement discontinued, April 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Dec. 17, 1962	--	33	0.02	--	35	40	402	818	0	40	285	1.0	11	--	*1,310	252	0	2,100	8.2	27	--
Feb. 21, 1963	--	33	.02	--	36	28	412	812	0	40	270	1.1	12	--	*1,300	205	0	2,050	8.2	26	--
Nov. 6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	--	--	156	--	--	--	27	--
July 21, 1967	--	26	.05	0.02	40	41	324	698	8	16	262	.6	.6	--	1,130	268	0	1,830	8.3	26	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180° C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Mar. 19, 1958	5.06	Feb. 29, 1960	14.26	Mar. 1, 1961	3.10	Oct. 9, 1962	3.57
Mar. 26	5.22	Mar. 31	15.70	Apr. 1	3.07	Oct. 29	3.37
Apr. 2	4.91	Apr. 30	13.53	May 1	3.04	Dec. 10	4.31
Apr. 9	5.55	May 10	4.11	June 1	3.11	Dec. 17	5.16
Apr. 16	5.51	May 19	3.56	June 16	3.90	Dec. 31	6.26
Apr. 23	5.18	June 3	4.18	July 1	3.18	Jan. 7, 1963	4.18
May 2	5.44	July 31	3.95	Aug. 1	3.29	Jan. 14	4.51
May 6	3.78	Aug. 31	4.15	Sept. 1	3.27	Jan. 21	5.17
May 17	3.66	Sept. 6	3.71	Oct. 1	3.49	Jan. 28	4.48
May 28	3.80	Sept. 12	3.94	Nov. 2	2.73	Feb. 4	4.34
June 5	3.70	Oct. 1	3.45	Mar. 1, 1962	2.17	Feb. 21	4.96
June 11	3.76	Nov. 1	3.38	Apr. 1	1.95	Mar. 12	5.60
June 19	3.87	Dec. 1	3.43	May 1	2.41	Mar. 23	6.63
June 24	3.84	Jan. 2, 1961	3.27	June 1	3.15		
Feb. 23, 1960	14.31	Feb. 2	2.97	Oct. 3	^a 3.60		

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1963												
5	--	--	--	--	3.57	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
10	--	--	--	--	2.80	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
15	--	--	--	--	3.51	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
20	--	--	--	--	3.80	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
25	--	--	--	4.93	3.85	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
eom	--	--	--	.49	4.03	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
June 18, 1963	4.82	Jan. 12, 1965	f	May 26, 1966	^a 4.88	Oct. 3, 1967	f
Sept. 19	4.79	Feb. 8	f	June 27	7.06	Nov. 1	16.65
Oct. 22	5.98	Mar. 8	f	July 25	7.79	Dec. 4	f
Nov. 20	5.66	Apr. 7	f	Aug. 29	9.22	Jan. 4, 1968	f
Dec. 16	5.75	May 4	f	Sept. 26	8.68	Apr. 3	f
Jan. 22, 1964	9.10	June 18	f	Oct. 31	5.15	May 3	f
Mar. 3	11.05	July 8	f	Nov. 29	5.02	June 3	f
Mar. 26	11.17	Aug. 31	f	Dec. 28	4.83	Aug. 1	f
Apr. 22	11.23	Nov. 2	f	Jan. 31, 1967	5.23	Dec. 4	f
May 26	13.53	Dec. 2	12.59	Mar. 14	7.37	Jan. 3, 1969	15.65
June 22	13.23	Dec. 14	4.48	Apr. 3	8.61	Feb. 5	12.53
July 20	12.92	Dec. 29	5.91	Apr. 18	9.55	Mar. 24	7.26
Aug. 24	14.45	Jan. 27, 1966	4.90	June 1	10.47	Apr. 23	4.74
Sept. 23	14.90	Mar. 1	4.62	July 6	12.46		
Oct. 26	^a 16.02	Mar. 30	^a 4.39	Aug. 1	13.74		
Nov. 23	15.66	Apr. 26	5.70	Sept. 1	15.09		

a - pumping
f - dry

Well 27 (19-64.52-11-43)

Owner.--V.I. Government.
Name.--Brookman Dug Well.
Location.--Lat 18° 19' 35", long 64° 52' 44".
Description.--Dug water-table well.
Depth.--19 ft.
Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of manhole, 3.0 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--30 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--2.23 ft below lsd, May 6, 1958.
Lowest water level.--10.9 ft below lsd, April 2, 1960.
Records available.--Water levels: 1958 and 1960.
Remarks.--Well destroyed, May 1960.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
May 6, 1958	2.23	June 5, 1958	2.45	June 24, 1958	4.11	Apr. 2, 1960	10.9
May 16	3.00	June 11	3.29	Feb. 23, 1960	10.81	May 2	3.5
May 28	3.44	June 19	3.91	Feb. 29	10.6		

Well 28 (19-64.52-13-43)

Owner.--V.I. Government.
Name.--Red Tank Dug Well (Brookman).
Location.--Lat 18° 19' 35", long 64° 52' 44".
Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 4 ft.
Depth.--19 ft.
Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of curb, 4.5 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--30 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--3.63 ft below lsd, May 20, 1963.
Lowest water level.--9.79 ft below lsd, Mar. 23, 1963.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: December 1962
and August 1963.
Water levels: 1962-64.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, April 1964.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Dec. 17, 1962	--	29	0.00	--	52	43	488	898	18	27	405	0.8	0.0	--	--	* 1,520	306	0	2,500	8.3	27	--
Aug. 20, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	205	--	--	--	--	--	270	--	--	--	31	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 10, 1962	7.19	Jan. 28, 1963	7.06	June 18, 1963	8.15	Dec. 16, 1963	5.59
Dec. 17	7.42	Feb. 4	5.81	July 24	^a 7.08	Jan. 23, 1964	6.77
Dec. 31	6.50	Feb. 21	6.84	Aug. 20	5.13	Mar. 2	7.60
Jan. 7, 1963	5.89	Mar. 23	9.79	Sept. 19	3.87	Mar. 26	6.64
Jan. 14	6.49	Apr. 22	5.63	Oct. 22	6.02	Apr. 22	7.17
Jan. 21	6.69	May 20	3.63	Nov. 19	6.46		

a - pumping

Well 29 (19-64.52-18-43)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS - 11 (Brookman).
Location.--Lat 18° 19' 35", long 64° 52' 44".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-38, slotted 18-38 ft.
Depth.--60 ft.
Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 2.10
 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--30 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--5.91 ft below lsd, Oct. 17, 1966.
Lowest water level.--16.58 ft below lsd, July 3, 1968.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: January 1964
 and January and June 1969.
Water levels: 1964-68.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, July 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter																Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium	Non- carbonate				
Jan. 24, 1964	--	26	0.00	--	74	108	718	848	0	120	962	0.5	15	--	* 2,380	628	0	4,240	7.8	28	--
Jan. 21, 1969	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	990	--	--	0.06	--	--	--	4,590	--	28	--
June 4	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1010	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1964												
5	--	--	9.51	10.21	10.24	10.78	11.29	11.04	11.37	--	11.04	11.20
10	--	--	9.64	10.29	10.31	10.89	11.32	11.08	11.50	--	11.10	11.32
15	--	--	9.77	10.33	10.41	10.98	11.31	11.19	11.58	--	10.95	11.45
20	--	9.23	9.84	10.38	10.49	11.09	11.28	11.31	11.66	--	10.97	11.60
25	--	9.33	10.03	10.30	10.66	11.20	11.27	11.36	11.06	--	11.04	11.72
eom	--	9.41	10.07	10.22	10.76	11.26	11.19	11.31	10.70	10.79	11.09	11.82
1965												
5	11.92	12.37	12.69	--	12.94	10.79	11.18	12.34	12.89	11.43	7.19	7.08
10	11.98	12.40	12.73	12.99	12.73	10.57	11.40	12.35	12.84	11.41	6.36	7.29
15	12.06	12.48	--	13.00	12.45	10.61	11.57	12.54	12.80	11.49	6.92	7.29
20	12.16	12.54	--	13.04	12.12	10.68	11.79	12.70	12.54	10.58	7.21	7.28
25	12.23	12.56	--	13.13	11.74	10.98	12.00	12.76	11.92	8.13	7.65	7.28
eom	12.32	12.63	--	12.97	11.07	11.09	12.17	12.84	11.61	7.97	6.84	7.28
1966												
5	6.74	7.00	8.17	7.77	8.08	9.13	10.18	10.03	9.88	7.99	7.50	7.67
10	6.98	7.32	8.36	8.11	8.31	--	10.42	9.85	9.88	7.99	7.88	7.58
15	6.33	7.57	8.34	8.39	8.47	--	10.56	9.74	9.35	5.99	8.05	7.68
20	6.48	7.73	8.00	8.14	8.56	--	10.61	9.80	9.20	6.14	8.18	7.90
25	6.87	7.88	7.69	7.76	8.67	--	10.38	9.89	9.17	6.65	7.77	7.73
eom	6.86	8.05	7.68	7.76	8.85	--	10.20	9.74	8.33	7.11	7.75	7.48
1967												
5	7.69	8.74	--	10.01	11.04	10.91	11.40	11.97	12.58	13.03	11.20	11.87
10	8.05	8.89	9.40	10.29	--	11.07	11.50	12.06	12.66	13.00	11.29	12.00
15	8.38	9.08	9.53	10.44	10.98	11.19	11.57	12.14	12.72	11.80	11.32	12.11
20	8.46	9.15	9.61	10.58	10.76	--	11.61	12.24	12.81	11.49	11.37	12.26
25	8.54	9.29	9.74	10.81	10.69	--	11.70	12.34	12.88	11.37	11.54	12.41
eom	--	9.36	9.90	10.92	10.82	11.28	--	12.45	13.01	11.18	11.70	12.59
1968												
5	12.72	13.46	13.70	14.35	15.32	16.02	16.49	--	--	--	--	--
10	12.82	13.55	13.75	14.55	15.42	16.13	16.41	--	--	--	--	--
15	12.96	13.59	13.80	14.72	15.54	16.22	15.40	--	--	--	--	--
20	13.10	13.61	13.85	14.87	15.65	16.31	--	--	--	--	--	--
25	13.22	13.65	13.90	15.03	15.77	16.39	--	--	--	--	--	--
eom	13.34	13.63	14.09	15.19	15.91	16.48	--	--	--	--	--	--

Well 30 (19-64.52-14-64)

Owner.--V.I. Government.Name.--Nadir Dug Well.Location.--Lat 18° 19' 21", long 64° 52' 38".Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 10 ft.Depth.--15 ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of cover, 4.0 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--20 ft above msl.Highest water level.--2.64 ft below lsd, Dec. 14, 1965.Lowest water level.--14.92 ft below lsd, Apr. 20, 1960.Records available.--Chemical analyses: August and
November 1963.Water levels: 1958, 1960-69.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, February 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Aug. 21, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	265	--	--	--	--	--	322	--	--	--	29	--
Nov. 5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	500	--	--	--	--	--	202	--	--	--	28	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
May 2, 1958	11.78	Oct. 3, 1962	2.89	July 20, 1964	10.75	Nov. 29, 1966	5.48
May 6	7.60	Oct. 9	3.60	Aug. 24	11.08	Dec. 28	5.86
May 16	6.57	Oct. 29	3.17	Sept. 23	11.02	Jan. 31, 1967	7.04
May 22	8.00	Dec. 3	6.01	Oct. 28	10.89	Mar. 14	9.53
May 28	6.72	Dec. 10	6.38	Nov. 23	11.13	Apr. 18	9.84
June 5	7.00	Dec. 17	6.70	Dec. 14	11.33	June 1	10.58
June 11	6.32	Dec. 31	6.89	Jan. 12, 1965	11.61	July 6	10.85
June 19	7.50	Jan. 7, 1963	6.63	Feb. 8	11.86	Aug. 2	11.15
June 24	8.14	Jan. 14	6.56	Mar. 8	12.01	Sept. 1	11.41
Feb. 23, 1960	14.53	Jan. 21	6.71	Apr. 8	12.53	Oct. 3	11.60
Feb. 29	14.17	Jan. 28	6.92	May 4	11.92	Nov. 1	11.05
Apr. 20	14.92	Feb. 4	6.94	June 18	11.46	Dec. 14	11.31
May 2	13.17	Feb. 21	6.92	July 8	11.77	Jan. 4, 1968	11.56
May 10	6.20	Apr. 22	5.25	Aug. 31	11.53	Feb. 2	11.74
May 18	6.40	May 20	2.67	Nov. 2	8.18	Mar. 5	11.88
June 2	6.17	June 18	5.85	Dec. 2	3.30	Apr. 3	11.80
July 10	7.00	July 24	6.20	Dec. 14	2.64	May 3	11.53
Aug. 5	7.00	Aug. 21	6.18	Dec. 29	2.88	June 3	11.44
Sept. 16	5.82	Sept. 19	3.66	Jan. 27, 1966	3.68	July 3	11.42
June 16, 1961	9.59	Oct. 22	6.37	Mar. 1	4.01	Aug. 1	9.43
Nov. 2	5.80	Nov. 19	7.62	Mar. 30	6.61	Sept. 3	7.35
Nov. 29	5.25	Dec. 16	7.14	Apr. 26	6.35	Oct. 1	6.38
Dec. 29	5.92	Jan. 23, 1964	8.36	May 26	8.07	Nov. 4	7.92
Jan. 29, 1962	5.96	Mar. 2	9.19	June 27	9.35	Dec. 4	3.49
Feb. 28	6.46	Mar. 26	9.60	July 25	9.85	Jan. 3, 1969	4.27
Mar. 29	8.08	Apr. 22	9.89	Aug. 30	10.23	Feb. 5	4.04
Apr. 27	9.23	May 26	10.45	Sept. 26	10.30		
June 1	8.73	June 22	10.82	Oct. 31	3.72		

Well 31 (19-64.52-15-63)

Owner.--V.I. Government.

Name.--Nadir Abattoir Dug Well.

Location.--Lat 18° 19' 19", long 64° 52' 43".

Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 3.5 ft.

Depth.--14 ft.

Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of cover, 0.0 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--15 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--2.34 ft below lsd, Sept. 16, 1960.

Lowest water level.--8.00 ft below lsd, May 2, 1958.

Records available.--Chemical analyses: December 1962
and February and November 1963.

Water levels: 1958, 1960-63.

Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, December 1963.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)		Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate				
Dec. 17, 1962	--	26	0.00	--	43	46	405	756	0	40	365	0.6	0.0	--	* 1,300	296	0	2,210	8.2	27	--	
Feb. 21, 1963	--	26	.02	--	64	48	473	826	0	63	455	.6	.2	--	* 1,570	357	0	2,610	8.1	27	--	
Nov. 5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	390	--	--	--	--	304	--	--	--	29	--	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Feb. 19, 1958	4.04	May 22, 1958	2.84	Feb. 28, 1962	6.0	Feb. 21, 1963	^a 6.39
Feb. 27	4.65	May 28	3.10	Mar. 29	4.5	Mar. 23	7.48
Mar. 5	5.15	June 5	3.32	Apr. 27	5.4	Apr. 22	^a 4.80
Mar. 11	5.46	June 11	3.05	June 1	5.0	May 20	^a 2.84
Mar. 19	6.10	June 19	3.68	Oct. 3	^a 2.77	June 18	5.07
Mar. 27	6.64	June 24	4.13	Oct. 9	^a 3.60	July 24	^a 5.66
Apr. 2	6.83	May 18, 1960	2.59	Oct. 29	^a 3.26	Aug. 20	5.58
Apr. 11	7.40	Sept. 16	2.34	Dec. 10	^a 5.92	Sept. 18	^a 3.59
Apr. 17	7.70	June 16, 1961	5.63	Dec. 17	^a 6.14	Oct. 22	5.71
Apr. 23	7.51	Nov. 2	2.50	Dec. 31	6.31	Nov. 19	^a 7.15
May 2	8.00	Nov. 29	3.2	Jan. 14, 1963	^a 5.96	Dec. 16	^a 6.58
May 6	5.27	Dec. 29	2.5	Jan. 21	6.13		
May 16	3.20	Jan. 29, 1962	2.7	Jan. 28	^a 6.40		

a - pumping

Well 32 (18-64.53-4-02)

Owner.--Unknown.Name.--Bolong Bay Dug Well.Location.--Lat 18° 18' 59", long 64° 53' 51".Description.--Dug unused water-table well,
diam 8 ft.Depth.--18 ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of curb, 2.3 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--15 ft above msl.Highest water level.--1.74 ft below lsd, May 20, 1963.Lowest water level.--3.97 ft below lsd, Jan. 23, 1964.Records available.--Chemical analyses: August and
November 1963.Water levels: 1963-64.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1964.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non- carbonate
Aug. 20, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,755	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	31	--	
Nov. 5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4,350	--	--	--	--	1,530	--	--	28	--	

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
May 20, 1963	1.74	Aug. 20, 1963	3.08	Oct. 22, 1963	2.88	Dec. 16, 1963	3.46
June 18	3.29	Sept. 19	2.43	Nov. 19	3.44	Jan. 23, 1964	3.97
July 24	3.32						

Well 33 (19-64.54-1-48)

Owner.--V.I. Government.Name.--French Bay Gut Dug Well.Location.--Lat 18° 19' 31", long 64° 54' 16".Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 7 ft.Depth.--13.6 ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of curb, 2.5 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--280 ft above msl.Highest water level.--4.87 ft below lsd, Sept. 18, 1963.Lowest water level.--7.16 ft below lsd, Dec. 16, 1963.Records available.--Chemical analyses: August and
November 1963.Water levels: 1962-63.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, December 1963.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non- carbonate
Aug. 20, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	330	--	--	--	--	652	--	--	--	--	
Nov. 6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	730	--	--	--	--	404	--	--	26	--	

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
Oct. 2, 1962	4.92	Mar. 23, 1963	6.95	July 24, 1963	6.86	Nov. 29, 1963	5.94
Dec. 17	6.03	Apr. 26	5.94	Aug. 20	6.70	Dec. 16	7.16
Jan. 18, 1963	6.09	May 20	4.94	Sept. 18	4.87		
Feb. 21	6.41	June 18	6.44	Oct. 22	5.19		

Well 35 (20-64.54-5-72)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS - 9 (Sugar Estate).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 17", long 64° 54' 53".
Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-76.
Depth.--90 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 0.7 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--48 ft above msl.
Highest water levels.--10.83 ft below lsd, Jan. 17, 1966.
Lowest water levels.--45.86 ft below lsd, Aug. 5, 1965.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: December 1963.
Water levels: 1963-67.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, March 1967.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Calcium, magnesium		Non-carbonate					
Dec. 20, 1963	--	26	0.00	--	16	16	204	454	0	11	108	1.4	13	--	* 614	106	0	1,020	7.8	32		

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 30, 1963	38.67	Aug. 31, 1964	42.24	Mar. 9, 1965	43.48	Jan. 3, 1966	11.98
Jan. 6, 1964	38.95	Sept. 9	42.40	Mar. 15	44.08	Jan. 17	10.83
Jan. 15	39.23	Sept. 14	42.49	Mar. 23	43.48	Jan. 27	11.73
Jan. 22	39.46	Sept. 23	42.60	Mar. 30	44.12	Feb. 14	16.54
Feb. 3	39.79	Sept. 29	42.58	Apr. 5	43.66	Mar. 1	20.73
Feb. 11	39.93	Oct. 13	42.46	Apr. 19	44.13	Mar. 15	24.41
Feb. 17	40.05	Oct. 19	42.44	Apr. 26	43.91	Mar. 30	27.05
Mar. 5	40.33	Oct. 28	42.54	May 3	44.01	Apr. 12	29.00
Mar. 9	40.36	Nov. 2	42.55	May 10	43.85	Apr. 26	30.87
Mar. 16	40.35	Nov. 9	42.54	May 18	43.55	May 10	32.33
Mar. 24	40.52	Nov. 23	42.52	May 24	43.35	May 26	33.62
Apr. 7	40.67	Nov. 30	42.43	June 3	42.88	June 8	34.62
Apr. 13	40.74	Dec. 7	42.41	June 14	42.64	June 28	36.75
Apr. 20	40.82	Dec. 14	42.47	June 21	45.09	July 11	37.10
May 5	40.94	Dec. 21	42.56	June 29	42.53	July 25	38.00
May 11	41.00	Dec. 28	42.68	July 7	42.58	Aug. 5	38.65
May 26	41.23	Jan. 4, 1965	42.74	July 21	43.12	Aug. 30	39.45
June 1	41.32	Jan. 11	42.80	Aug. 5	45.86	Sept. 26	41.16
June 8	41.45	Jan. 26	42.82	Sept. 30	42.85	Oct. 31	35.42
June 15	41.58	Feb. 8	43.04	Oct. 29	41.74	Nov. 29	35.90
July 6	41.99	Feb. 15	43.03	Nov. 12	36.16	Dec. 29	36.63
July 13	42.07	Feb. 23	43.19	Nov. 26	30.00	Jan. 31, 1967	37.46
July 20	42.05	Mar. 2	43.19	Dec. 14	24.28	Mar. 14	40.35

Well 36 (20-64.54-9-42)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS - 18 (Estate Thomas).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 31", long 64° 54' 49".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-56.
Depth.--144 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.9 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--83 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--61.92 ft below lsd, Dec. 14, 1965.
Lowest water level.--82.67 ft below lsd, June 1, 1967.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: November and
December 1964.
Water levels: 1965-68.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter													Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)		Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate				
Nov. 23, 1964	--	28	0.00	--	88	68	205	580	0	56	280	0.8	18	--	* 1,100	499	23	1,836	7.7	29	--
Dec. 15	--	--	--	--	82	72	--	748	0	--	280	.3	30	--	--	500	0	1,830	7.4	29	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Aug. 5, 1965	81.81	Jan. 3, 1966	63.78	June 8, 1967	75.06	Mar. 13, 1967	81.10
Aug. 7	81.63	Jan. 17	64.42	June 28	77.09	Apr. 18	81.75
Aug. 21	80.94	Jan. 27	65.18	July 11	78.08	June 1	82.67
Aug. 31	80.48	Feb. 14	67.45	July 25	78.92	July 6	79.69
Sept. 30	79.57	Mar. 1	69.10	Aug. 5	79.54	Aug. 2	78.88
Oct. 29	78.30	Mar. 15	70.06	Aug. 30	79.52	Sept. 1	79.99
Nov. 12	76.27	Mar. 30	70.82	Sept. 26	81.18	Oct. 3	82.36
Nov. 26	73.90	Apr. 12	71.80	Oct. 31	78.40	Nov. 1	80.78
Dec. 8	73.67	Apr. 26	73.24	Nov. 29	77.41	Dec. 7	78.88
Dec. 14	61.92	May 10	73.63	Dec. 29	77.59	Jan. 4, 1968	78.41
Dec. 23	66.65	May 26	74.59	Jan. 31	78.33		

Well 37 (20-64.54-10-42)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.Name.--USGS--19 (Estate Thomas).Location.--Lat 18° 20' 34", long 64° 54' 51".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-58.Depth.--130 ft.Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 2.9 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--88 ft above msl.Highest water level.--69.23 ft below lsd, Jan. 27 1966.Lowest water level.--87.19 ft below lsd, Oct. 3, 1967.Records available.--Chemical analyses: December 1964
and April 1967.Water levels: 1965-68.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non- carbonate
Dec. 5, 1964	--	--	--	--	38	38	--	820	0	--	165	0.9	11	--	--	252	0	1,400	7.6	28	--
Apr. 3, 1967	--	31	0.07	0.00	46	32	255	628	0	36	170	.6	10	--	* 904	246	0	1,520	8.0	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Aug. 5, 1965	86.75	Jan. 3, 1966	70.95	June 8, 1966	79.39	Apr. 18, 1967	86.28
Aug. 7	86.55	Jan. 17	69.62	June 28	81.47	June 1	86.70
Aug. 21	85.70	Jan. 27	69.23	July 11	82.15	July 6	83.61
Aug. 31	85.34	Feb. 14	70.54	July 25	82.92	Aug. 2	83.37
Sept. 30	84.51	Mar. 1	72.04	Aug. 5	83.74	Sept. 1	84.67
Oct. 29	83.67	Mar. 15	73.24	Aug. 30	83.85	Oct. 3	87.19
Nov. 12	82.34	Mar. 30	74.10	Sept. 26	85.60	Nov. 1	85.55
Nov. 26	80.55	Apr. 12	75.22	Oct. 31	82.98	Dec. 7	83.60
Dec. 8	80.45	Apr. 23	77.00	Nov. 29	81.68	Jan. 4, 1968	83.24
Dec. 14	76.65	May 10	79.46	Dec. 29	82.00		
Dec. 23	74.62	May 26	78.56	Jan. 31, 1967	82.92		

Well 38 (20-64.54-8-32)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.Name.--USGS - 17 (Estate Thomas).Location.--Lat 18° 20' 37", long 64° 54' 52".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-29.Depth.--110 ft.Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 0.5 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--90 ft above msl.Highest water level.--36.45 ft below lsd, Jan. 17, 1966.Lowest water level.--45.44 ft below lsd, Sept. 30, 1965.Records available.--Chemical analysis: November 1964.Water levels: 1965-68.Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Calcium, magnesium		Non-carbonate					
Nov. 14, 1964	--	32	0.00	--	42	43	281	688	0	34	200	0.9	9.8	--	*1,000	282	0	1,696	7.6	29	--	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Aug. 5, 1965	45.30	Jan. 3, 1966	37.00	June 8, 1966	40.93	Mar. 13, 1967	43.48
Aug. 7	45.30	Jan. 17	36.45	June 28	41.31	Apr. 18	43.70
Aug. 21	45.40	Jan. 27	36.56	July 11	41.59	June 1	43.87
Aug. 31	45.35	Feb. 14	37.24	July 25	41.79	July 6	44.05
Sept. 30	45.44	Mar. 1	37.80	Aug. 5	41.95	Aug. 2	44.18
Oct. 29	45.28	Mar. 15	38.35	Aug. 30	42.30	Sept. 1	44.33
Nov. 12	44.84	Mar. 30	38.85	Sept. 26	42.59	Oct. 3	44.52
Nov. 26	44.10	Apr. 12	39.32	Oct. 31	42.77	Nov. 1	44.68
Dec. 8	43.29	Apr. 26	39.82	Nov. 29	42.97	Dec. 7	44.87
Dec. 14	41.57	May 10	40.22	Dec. 29	43.16	Jan. 4, 1968	45.04
Dec. 23	39.27	May 26	40.62	Jan. 31, 1967	43.30		

Well 39 (20-64.55-39-29)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
 Name.--USGS -7 (High School).
 Location.--Lat 18° 20' 43", long 64° 55' 06".
 Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-53.
 Depth.--70 ft.
 Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.9 ft above lsd.
 Land elevation.--60 ft above msl.
 Highest water level.--12.42 ft below lsd, Jan. 3, 1966.
 Lowest water level.--25.64 ft below lsd, Aug. 21, 1965.
 Records available.--Chemical analysis: November 1963.
 Water levels: 1963-69.
 Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, July 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Nov. 24, 1963	--	35	0.00	--	36	49	294	674	0	30	240	0.7	8.4	--	* 990	292	0	1,710	8.4	29	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Nov. 23, 1963	21.00	Sept. 29, 1964	23.24	July 9, 1965	24.37	Aug. 5, 1966	21.74
Dec. 2	21.58	Oct. 13	23.22	July 10	24.38	Aug. 30	21.68
Dec. 10	21.99	Oct. 19	23.35	July 12	24.40	Sept. 26	22.26
Dec. 16	22.24	Oct. 28	23.34	July 13	24.40	Oct. 31	22.27
Dec. 30	23.34	Nov. 2	23.36	July 15	24.50	Nov. 29	22.68
Jan. 6, 1964	23.36	Nov. 9	23.41	July 17	24.52	Dec. 29	22.89
Jan. 15	22.37	Nov. 23	23.48	July 19	24.47	Jan. 31, 1967	23.18
Jan. 22	22.40	Nov. 30	23.55	July 20	24.53	Mar. 7	23.40
Feb. 3	22.45	Dec. 7	23.62	July 22	24.48	Apr. 18	23.63
Feb. 11	22.48	Dec. 14	23.69	July 23	24.57	June 1	23.65
Feb. 17	22.49	Dec. 21	23.92	July 24	24.57	July 6	23.93
Feb. 24	22.55	Dec. 28	23.67	July 26	24.50	Aug. 2	24.07
Mar. 5	22.60	Jan. 4, 1965	23.87	Aug. 5	24.56	Sept. 1	24.18
Mar. 9	22.60	Jan. 11	23.89	Aug. 7	25.48	Oct. 3	24.37
Mar. 16	22.63	Jan. 26	23.94	Aug. 21	25.64	Nov. 1	24.42
Mar. 24	22.67	Feb. 8	24.09	Aug. 31	24.62	Dec. 7	24.63
Mar. 30	22.64	Feb. 15	24.10	Sept. 30	24.27	Jan. 4, 1968	24.76
Apr. 7	22.66	Feb. 23	24.15	Oct. 29	24.30	Feb. 6	24.90
Apr. 13	22.66	Mar. 1	24.05	Nov. 12	22.29	Mar. 5	24.88
Apr. 20	22.65	Mar. 9	24.23	Nov. 26	20.38	Apr. 3	24.90
May 5	22.74	Mar. 15	24.26	Dec. 8	19.67	May 3	25.03
May 11	22.78	Mar. 23	24.32	Dec. 14	13.79	June 3	25.15
May 18	22.80	Mar. 30	24.38	Dec. 23	13.27	July 8	25.27
May 26	22.83	Apr. 5	24.38	Jan. 3, 1966	12.42	Aug. 1	25.12
June 1	22.85	Apr. 26	24.32	Jan. 17	13.71	Sept. 3	24.88
June 8	22.86	May 3	24.34	Jan. 27	14.83	Oct. 1	25.20
June 15	22.90	May 7	24.29	Feb. 14	16.94	Nov. 5	25.45
June 22	22.94	May 10	24.21	Mar. 1	17.27	Dec. 4	25.23
June 29	23.00	May 18	24.01	Mar. 15	18.00	Jan. 3, 1969	25.19
July 6	22.96	May 24	24.01	Mar. 30	18.52	Feb. 5	24.58
July 13	22.99	June 2	24.12	Apr. 12	19.08	Mar. 24	22.81
July 20	22.98	June 7	24.15	Apr. 23	19.59	Apr. 23	23.50
Aug. 10	23.13	June 14,	24.25	May 10	19.96	May 23	22.52
Aug. 24	23.15	June 21	24.32	May 26	20.40	June 23	15.28
Aug. 31	23.14	June 29	24.35	June 8	20.73	July 23	17.75
Sept. 9	23.25	July 6	24.36	June 28	21.14		
Sept. 14	23.31	July 7	24.37	July 11	21.44		
Sept. 23	23.27	July 8	24.37	July 25	21.57		

Well 40 (20-64.55-42-50)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS -21 (Grade School).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 34", long 64° 55' 02".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-70, 4-in slotted liner 68-88.
Depth.--88 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 2.2 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--49 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--34.54 ft below lsd, Jan. 17, 1966.
Lowest water level.--47.85 ft below lsd, July 24, 1965.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: December 1964
 and March 1967.
Water levels: 1965-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, June 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Dec. 12, 1964	--	34	0.00	--	110	99	442	544	0	12	835	0.7	6.7	--	* 1,940	682	236	3,460	7.7	29	--
Mar. 31, 1967	--	28	.04	0.00	250	224	705	438	0	168	1,800	.5	5.7	--	* 3,900	1,545	1,186	6,070	7.6	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
June 14, 1965	43.90	Aug. 5, 1965	45.53	June 8, 1966	41.31	Feb. 5, 1968	43.20
June 21	44.30	Aug. 31	44.30	June 28	43.04	Mar. 5	44.00
June 29	44.19	Sept. 30	43.48	July 11	43.62	Apr. 3	43.93
July 2	44.14	Oct. 29	42.65	July 25	44.11	May 3	43.08
July 6	46.15	Nov. 12	41.24	Aug. 5	44.77	June 3	43.63
July 7	46.36	Nov. 26	39.88	Aug. 30	44.96	July 8	43.98
July 8	46.38	Dec. 8	41.70	Sept. 26	45.95	Aug. 1	43.04
July 9	46.73	Dec. 14	37.63	Oct. 31	44.54	Sept. 3	41.85
July 12	47.06	Dec. 23	36.79	Nov. 29	42.21	Oct. 1	41.92
July 13	47.25	Jan. 3, 1966	35.13	Dec. 29	44.83	Nov. 5	43.63
July 15	47.31	Jan. 17	34.54	Jan. 31, 1967	43.40	Dec. 4	41.81
July 19	47.49	Jan. 27	34.70	Apr. 18	46.04	Jan. 3, 1969	41.14
July 20	47.05	Feb. 14	35.65	June 1	46.22	Feb. 5	40.49
July 22	47.76	Mar. 1	36.37	July 6	43.24	Mar. 24	39.12
July 23	47.62	Mar. 15	37.06	Aug. 1	43.03	Apr. 23	41.03
July 24	47.85	Mar. 30	38.43	Sept. 1	44.12	May 26	38.84
July 28	46.62	Apr. 12	38.20	Oct. 3	46.50	June 23	35.72
July 30	47.28	Apr. 23	39.73	Nov. 1	45.30		
Aug. 2	45.90	May 10	39.73	Dec. 7	43.21		
Aug. 4	46.62	May 26	40.45	Jan. 4, 1968	45.30		

Well 41 (20-64.54-11-41)

Owner.--U.S. Government—V.I. Government.

Name.--USGS—20 (Estate Thomas).

Location.--Lat 18° 20' 31", long 64° 54' 56".

Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-84, slotted 74-84.

Depth.--118 ft.

Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 2.2 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--55 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--44.40 ft below lsd, Jan. 24, 1966.

Lowest water level.--59.05 ft below lsd, July 24, 1965.

Records available.--Chemical analysis: December 1964.

Water levels: 1965-69.

Remarks.--Recorder.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Dec. 8, 1964	--	--	--	--	36	39	--	820	0	--	150	0.7	12	--	--	250	0	1,420	7.6	28	--

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1965												
5	--	55.93	56.20	56.50	56.75	55.50	56.85	56.70	--	54.60	--	50.05
10	--	55.87	56.56	56.75	56.25	55.25	57.95	56.70	55.35	54.55	52.30	50.05
15	--	56.00	56.56	56.75	55.90	55.15	58.40	56.05	54.80	54.65	51.90	45.80
20	--	56.10	56.50	56.95	55.85	55.40	57.90	56.05	--	54.50	--	46.58
25	--	56.11	56.40	57.25	55.60	55.30	58.75	55.75	54.80	--	--	46.02
eom	55.72	55.98	56.40	56.25	55.30	55.25	57.25	55.50	54.70	53.65	50.30	45.00
1966												
5	44.84	44.92	46.98	48.42	50.32	51.46	54.08	55.59	--	56.30	54.04	52.95
10	44.80	45.14	47.10	48.62	50.36	--	54.26	54.92	56.26	56.20	53.30	52.81
15	44.58	45.72	47.40	48.74	50.50	--	--	54.68	--	55.18	53.16	52.90
20	44.42	45.90	47.58	49.10	51.42	--	55.05	55.28	56.52	53.86	54.06	53.02
25	44.42	46.30	47.98	50.34	51.10	--	54.70	54.95	56.79	54.19	--	53.11
eom	44.66	46.70	48.32	50.58	51.04	53.94	55.25	56.11	56.53	53.91	52.98	53.14
1967												
5	53.15	54.40	--	57.08	--	55.74	54.23	53.82	55.47	57.00	54.60	--
10	53.15	54.60	56.08	56.30	--	55.34	54.16	54.22	55.82	57.24	54.22	--
15	53.58	55.10	56.42	57.10	55.69	--	54.54	53.78	56.24	55.74	--	--
20	53.45	55.60	56.10	56.88	56.42	--	--	54.80	56.60	55.70	--	--
25	53.85	55.56	56.82	57.02	56.74	--	--	56.06	57.02	56.26	--	--
eom	53.69	56.32	56.22	57.28	56.40	54.40	--	54.80	--	55.24	--	--
1968												
5	53.16	53.70	54.68	53.97	53.41	54.20	--	53.60	51.86	52.24	53.26	51.95
10	52.96	--	54.69	53.78	53.38	--	--	52.92	51.86	52.46	53.62	51.95
15	53.12	--	54.69	53.23	53.60	--	--	52.78	52.08	52.72	53.47	51.57
20	53.15	--	--	53.32	53.79	--	--	52.72	52.28	53.02	53.42	51.57
25	53.43	--	--	54.53	53.92	--	--	52.98	52.48	53.30	53.26	51.57
eom	53.59	--	--	53.28	54.26	--	54.18	52.20	52.28	53.24	52.95	51.57
1969												
5	--	--	--	49.69	51.30	45.75	45.78	47.54	47.96	48.65	--	--
10	--	--	49.09	50.25	51.34	45.70	--	47.62	48.16	48.59	--	--
15	--	--	49.08	50.41	51.48	45.52	--	47.36	48.18	49.03	--	--
20	--	--	49.36	50.72	51.34	45.64	--	47.37	48.21	49.04	--	--
25	--	--	49.64	51.09	47.30	45.52	47.00	47.50	48.22	--	--	--
eom	--	51.30	49.70	51.02	45.78	45.70	47.04	47.96	48.56	--	--	--

Well 42 (20-64.55-38-02)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.Name.--USGS - 6 (Lyton's Fancy).Location.--Lat 18° 20' 59", long 64° 55' 51".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-21.Depth.--122 ft.Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 0.3 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--320 ft above msl.Highest water level.--29.75 ft below lsd, Nov. 27, 1963.Lowest water level.--59.65 ft below lsd, Dec. 10, 1963.Records available.--Chemical analyses: November 1963.Water levels: 1963-64.Remarks.--Well destroyed, December 1964.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Hardness as CaCO ₃	Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated						Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Nov. 11, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	440	--	--	--	--	280	--	--	--	29	--		
Nov. 19	--	23	0.00	--	48	45	464	726	0	90	432	1.2	17	--	* 1,440	305	0	2,490	8.0	29	--	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Nov. 27, 1963	29.75	Mar. 5, 1964	55.70	June 1, 1964	57.50	Sept. 14, 1964	58.10
Dec. 2	58.76	Mar. 9	55.67	June 8	57.75	Sept. 29	58.40
Dec. 10	59.65	Mar. 16	55.17	June 15	57.85	Oct. 13	58.59
Dec. 16	51.02	Mar. 24	55.70	June 22	58.53	Oct. 19	58.52
Dec. 30	55.03	Mar. 30	55.73	June 29	58.54	Oct. 27	58.67
Jan. 6, 1964	55.07	Apr. 7	55.90	July 6	58.19	Nov. 2	58.72
Jan. 15	55.06	Apr. 13	56.01	July 13	58.09	Nov. 9	58.81
Jan. 22	55.13	Apr. 20	56.16	July 20	58.13	Nov. 23	58.95
Feb. 3	55.45	May 5	56.61	Aug. 10	58.03	Dec. 1	58.97
Feb. 11	55.55	May 11	56.76	Aug. 24	57.91	Dec. 7	59.00
Feb. 17	55.60	May 18	57.08	Aug. 31	58.94	Dec. 14	58.99
Feb. 24	55.68	May 26	57.26	Sept. 10	58.07		

Well 43 (20-64.58-5-20)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS--8 (Thatch Farm).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 49", long 64° 58' 05".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-25.
Depth.--80 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.3 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--80 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--12.34 ft below lsd, Jan. 3, 1966.
Lowest water level.--29.54 ft below lsd, Mar. 30 and
 May 3, 1965.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: December 1963.
Water levels: 1963-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, August 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Dec. 12, 1963	--	27	0.04	--	44	43	495	892	0	79	385	0.2	8.0	--	*1,460	287	0	2,520	7.9	28	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 16, 1963	24.96	Sept. 23, 1964	28.62	June 14, 1965	28.66	Jan. 3, 1967	25.89
Dec. 30	26.75	Sept. 29	28.62	July 7	29.15	Jan. 31	26.29
Jan. 6, 1964	26.80	Oct. 13	28.67	July 19	29.40	Mar. 13	26.86
Jan. 15	26.86	Oct. 19	28.69	Aug. 5	29.45	Apr. 17	27.16
Jan. 22	26.94	Oct. 27	28.71	Aug. 21	29.32	June 1	27.44
Feb. 3	27.08	Nov. 2	28.71	Aug. 31	29.20	July 6	27.75
Feb. 10	27.15	Nov. 9	28.78	Oct. 19	27.99	Aug. 1	27.73
Mar. 2	27.32	Nov. 23	28.85	Nov. 12	25.30	Sept. 1	27.92
Mar. 16	27.44	Nov. 30	28.88	Nov. 26	21.50	Oct. 3	28.07
Mar. 24	27.53	Dec. 7	28.92	Dec. 8	21.19	Nov. 1	27.95
Mar. 30	27.55	Dec. 14	28.96	Dec. 14	18.24	Dec. 7	28.18
Apr. 7	27.62	Dec. 21	29.00	Dec. 23	16.80	Jan. 4, 1968	28.25
Apr. 13	27.68	Dec. 28	29.00	Jan. 3, 1966	12.34	Feb. 2	29.13
Apr. 20	27.75	Jan. 4, 1965	29.07	Jan. 17	13.56	Mar. 5	28.32
May 5	27.80	Jan. 11	29.06	Jan. 27	15.15	Apr. 3	28.51
May 11	27.87	Jan. 26	29.19	Feb. 14	18.18	June 3	28.50
May 18	27.94	Feb. 8	29.29	Mar. 15	20.95	July 3	29.40
May 26	28.00	Feb. 15	29.32	Mar. 30	20.60	Aug. 1	27.12
June 1	28.00	Feb. 23	29.36	Apr. 12	21.37	Sept. 3	26.68
June 8	28.00	Mar. 1	29.40	Apr. 23	21.73	Oct. 1	28.13
June 15	28.06	Mar. 8	29.43	May 10	22.24	Nov. 4	24.68
June 22	28.13	Mar. 15	29.48	May 26	22.69	Dec. 4	21.37
June 29	28.20	Mar. 23	29.52	June 8	23.05	Jan. 3, 1969	24.95
July 6	28.24	Mar. 30	29.54	June 27	23.55	Feb. 5	23.32
July 13	28.28	Apr. 5	29.52	July 12	23.99	Mar. 24	23.12
July 24	28.24	May 3	29.54	July 25	24.28	Apr. 23	25.24
Aug. 10	28.37	May 10	29.44	Aug. 5	24.53	May 23	20.59
Aug. 24	28.43	May 18	28.75	Aug. 29	25.02	June 23	13.26
Aug. 31	28.47	May 24	28.60	Sept. 26	24.86	July 23	19.09
Sept. 9	28.62	June 2	28.54	Oct. 31	24.57	Aug. 22	16.22
Sept. 14	28.58	June 7	28.57	Nov. 29	25.20		

Well 44 (20-64.58-4-49)

Owner.--V.I. Government.
 Name.--Golf Course Dug Well.
 Location.--Lat 18° 20' 32", long 64° 58' 07".
 Description.--Dug unused water-table well,
 diam 7 ft.
 Depth.--15 ft.
 Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of curb, 0.0 ft above lsd.
 Land elevation.--15 ft above msl.
 Highest water level.--1.19 ft below lsd, Dec. 14, 1965.
 Lowest water level.--9.31 ft below lsd, Apr. 7, 1965.
 Records available.--Chemical analyses: December 1962,
 February 1963, and July 1966.
 Water levels: 1962-68.
 Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, January 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃						
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate	
Dec. 17, 1962	--	21	0.15	--	22	16	385	638	8	43	265	0.8	0.5	--	--	* 1,120	121	0	1,810	8.3	24	--
Feb. 21, 1963	--	28	.04	--	23	10	403	684	0	40	262	.9	.2	--	--	* 1,160	98	0	1,870	8.2	28	--
July 25, 1966	--	18	.01	0.00	28	46	664	744	6	10	760	.7	.3	--	--	* 1,980	259	0	3,490	8.3	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
Dec. 17, 1962	6.63	Mar. 26, 1964	7.71	June 18, 1965	8.21	Oct. 31, 1966	6.58
Dec. 31	6.88	Apr. 22	7.65	July 7	8.36	Nov. 29	6.98
Jan. 7, 1963	6.85	May 26	7.74	Aug. 5	9.01	Jan. 3, 1967	7.05
Jan. 14	6.92	June 22	8.04	Aug. 31	8.35	Jan. 31	7.12
Jan. 21	6.99	July 20	8.10	Nov. 1	6.29	Mar. 13	7.78
Jan. 28	7.08	Aug. 24	8.60	Dec. 2	3.13	Apr. 17	8.65
Feb. 4	7.02	Sept. 23	8.76	Dec. 14	1.19	June 1	8.67
Feb. 21	7.24	Oct. 27	8.65	Jan. 27, 1966	2.04	July 6	8.02
Apr. 22	6.53	Nov. 23	8.82	Mar. 30	2.89	Aug. 1	8.12
May 20	4.04	Dec. 14	8.90	Apr. 26	4.25	Sept. 1	8.30
June 18	7.01	Jan. 11, 1965	9.08	May 26	5.22	Oct. 3	8.50
July 24	7.16	Feb. 8	9.14	June 27	5.97	Nov. 1	8.35
Aug. 20	6.96	Mar. 8	9.23	July 25	8.85	Dec. 7	8.17
Jan. 22, 1964	8.18	Apr. 7	9.31	Aug. 29	6.68	Jan. 4, 1968	8.10
Mar. 3	7.91	May 8	9.07	Sept. 26	6.39		

Well 45 (21-65.00-1-71)

Owner.--P. Brown.
 Name.--Fortuna.
 Location.--Lat 18° 21' 13", long 65° 00' 58".
 Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-20.
 Depth.--220 ft.
 Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 2.0 ft above lsd.
 Land elevation.--370 ft above msl.
 Highest water level.--54.80 ft below lsd, June 15, 1969.
 Lowest water level.--92.85 ft below lsd, Aug. 26, 1965.
 Records available.--Water levels: 1963-69.
 Remarks.--Recorder.

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1963												
5	--	--	--	--	--	--	89.12	86.65	83.60	84.50	86.55	87.75
10	--	--	--	--	--	87.59	--	85.50	80.85	--	86.80	87.90
15	--	--	--	--	--	88.07	88.76	87.06	82.08	--	87.05	88.00
20	--	--	--	--	--	88.34	89.09	87.32	82.89	--	87.25	88.10
25	--	--	--	--	--	88.71	89.35	87.46	83.48	--	87.30	--
eom	--	--	--	--	--	87.79	89.56	87.02	84.08	86.30	87.55	88.45
1964												
5	88.55	89.10	89.60	90.07	90.30	--	90.90	91.10	91.15	91.50	91.60	91.75
10	88.65	89.20	89.65	90.15	90.40	--	90.95	91.15	91.30	91.50	91.65	91.80
15	88.70	89.25	89.80	90.16	90.50	90.75	90.95	91.15	91.35	91.55	91.75	91.80
20	88.90	89.30	89.75	90.20	90.60	90.75	--	91.20	91.35	91.50	91.75	91.95
25	88.95	89.50	89.95	90.25	--	90.80	91.00	91.20	--	91.60	91.80	92.00
eom	89.05	89.60	89.97	90.30	--	90.85	91.10	91.20	91.50	91.60	91.70	92.00
1965												
5	92.05	92.30	92.35	92.50	92.25	--	92.70	92.75	92.75	--	--	67.85
10	92.05	92.30	92.45	92.45	92.55	92.80	92.65	92.75	92.75	--	62.40	71.05
15	92.10	92.35	92.40	92.40	92.50	92.70	92.70	92.80	92.70	90.60	--	60.20
20	92.25	92.25	92.50	92.55	92.60	92.70	--	92.75	92.65	90.55	--	61.30
25	92.30	92.35	92.55	92.55	--	92.65	--	92.80	92.65	--	--	63.25
eom	92.20	92.30	92.50	92.60	--	92.60	92.75	92.80	92.60	--	--	70.55
1966												
5	71.80	--	76.65	--	--	--	--	82.10	--	--	83.25	83.75
10	72.55	74.70	77.00	--	--	--	--	82.15	--	--	--	83.85
15	73.05	75.20	77.35	--	--	--	--	82.20	82.75	--	--	83.90
20	72.75	75.60	77.50	--	--	--	81.75	82.45	82.80	--	--	83.95
25	--	76.00	^e 77.75	--	--	--	81.80	82.50	--	--	--	84.10
eom	--	76.20	^e 78.10	--	--	--	81.95	--	--	83.20	83.75	--
1967												
5	--	84.55	84.85	85.20	85.55	--	86.10	86.15	86.40	86.40	86.75	86.95
10	84.40	--	85.00	^e 85.25	85.55	--	86.15	86.30	86.30	86.65	86.75	87.05
15	84.50	--	84.95	--	85.60	--	86.20	86.30	86.40	86.65	86.85	87.10
20	84.55	--	85.05	85.30	^e 85.65	85.90	--	86.35	86.45	86.65	86.85	87.25
25	84.55	84.80	85.10	85.40	85.70	--	--	86.40	86.50	86.75	86.95	87.20
eom	--	84.85	85.10	85.45	--	86.05	--	86.40	86.50	86.65	87.00	87.25
1968												
5	87.35	89.50	87.70	88.00	88.15	88.30	88.50	88.65	88.25	88.50	88.65	88.75
10	87.40	87.55	87.75	87.95	88.10	--	88.55	--	88.30	88.50	88.70	88.80
15	87.35	87.65	87.80	87.95	88.10	--	^e 88.60	--	88.35	88.60	88.70	88.75
20	87.25	86.55	87.80	88.00	88.25	--	88.60	--	88.35	88.60	88.75	88.80
25	87.35	87.65	87.80	88.00	88.25	--	^e 88.60	--	88.40	88.70	88.70	88.80
eom	87.40	87.75	87.90	88.00	88.25	--	^e 88.65	88.20	88.55	88.75	88.75	88.85
1969												
5	88.85	89.00	85.05	86.85	87.35	57.95	--	--	--	--	--	--
10	88.80	89.00	85.55	^e 86.95	87.55	62.60	--	--	--	--	--	--
15	88.80	88.95	86.00	^e 87.05	87.60	54.80	--	--	--	--	--	--
20	88.90	89.00	86.20	^e 87.15	84.65	58.60	--	--	--	--	--	--
25	88.90	89.05	86.45	87.20	55.25	61.85	--	--	--	--	--	--
eom	88.85	80.75	86.65	87.25	55.45	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

^eEstimate.

Figure 3.--Locations of stations in St. John.

STREAMFLOW STATIONS

3910. Cinnamon Bay Spring near Cruz Bay, St. John, V.I.

Location.--Lat 18° 21' 11", long 64° 45' 12". At Cinnamon Bay. 3.1 miles northeast of Government House at Cruz Bay.Drainage area.--0.12 sq mi.Records available.--Discharge: Monthly measurements, September 1962 to January 1966.Chemical analyses: 1962-66.Remarks.--Sept. 15, 1962 - 1.3 gpm; Oct. 10, 1962 - 1.8 gpm; no flow Mar. 29 and July 18, 1963; 14 observations of no flow between Mar. 2, 1964 and Aug. 25, 1965; Nov. 12, 1965 - less than 0.1 gpm; no flow Jan. 18 and June 2, 1966.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Discharge (GPM)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) & Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃						
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate	
Oct. 25, 1962	2.5	--	--	--	95	62	--	--	618	--	31	348	--	0.0	--	--	492	0	1,950	7.8	24	--
Feb. 22, 1963	.9	33	0.00	--	82	48	299	658	--	25	345	0.5	0	--	1,180	402	0	2,020	8.1	23	--	
Apr. 30	.2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	236	--	--	--	--	284	--	--	--	--	24	--
Sept. 20	.7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	299	--	--	--	--	380	--	--	--	--	29	--
Oct. 25	2.5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	400	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--	--	27	--
Nov. 22	2.2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	390	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--	--	25	--
Dec. 23	1.0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	410	--	--	--	--	562	--	--	--	--	--	--
Jan. 23, 1964	<.1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	410	--	--	--	--	544	--	--	--	--	24	--
Jan. 4, 1966	<.1	22	.01	--	76	61	194	384	--	8	342	1.0	.2	1,050	440	112	1,680	8.3	--	--	--	

*Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

2950. Guinea Gut at Bethany, St. John, V.I.

Location.--Lat 18° 19' 55", long 64° 46' 50", 1.0 mile east of Government House at Cruz Bay, 600 ft southeast of Bethany Church.

Drainage area.--0.37 sq mi.

Records available.--Discharge: January 1963 to October 1967.

Chemical analyses: December 1962 to August 1967.

Gage.--Water stage recorder, V-notch weir in concrete control. Altitude of gage is 230 ft above msl (from topographic map).

Extremes.--Discharge: Maximum and minimum (discharge in gallons per minute, gage height in feet).

Annual maximum discharge for years 1963-66				Annual minimum discharge for years 1963-66			
Date	Time	Discharge	Gage height	Year	Date	Discharge	Gage height
Aug. 27, 1963	--	25,600	1.33	1963	Nov. 29, Dec. 8	0.7	0.05
July 1, 1964	1600	16	.18	1964	--	.0	.00
Nov. 4, 1965	--	49,800	1.60	1965	--	.0	.00
Mar. 18, 1966	2330	1,540	.81	1966	--	.2	.03

1963-66: Maximum discharge, 49,800 gpm Nov. 4, 1965 (gage height, 1.60 ft) computed flow over dam; minimum daily, no flow for extended periods.

Remarks.--Records poor.

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1963

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1	3.0	3.8	3.0	3.8	3.8	2.2	3.0	2.2	3.0	2.2	2.2	1.1
2	3.0	6.7	3.0	3.8	3.8	2.2	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.2	2.2	1.1
3	3.0	3.8	3.0	3.8	3.8	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	2.2	1.1
4	3.0	3.8	3.0	4.8	3.8	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	2.2	1.1
5	3.0	3.8	2.2	7.3	3.8	2.2	1.6	2.2	3.0	2.2	2.2	1.1
6	3.0	3.8	2.2	10	3.8	2.2	3.8	2.2	4.8	2.2	1.6	1.1
7	3.0	3.8	2.2	103	3.8	2.2	3.0	2.2	3.8	2.2	1.6	1.1
8	3.0	3.8	2.2	73	3.8	2.2	2.2	3.0	3.0	2.2	1.6	.7
9	3.0	3.8	2.2	19	3.8	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	2.2	1.1
10	3.0	3.8	2.2	8.8	3.8	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	2.2	1.1
11	3.8	3.8	2.2	6.0	4.8	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.6	1.1
12	3.8	3.0	2.2	3.8	3.8	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.6	1.1
13	3.8	3.0	3.0	3.8	3.8	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.1
14	3.8	3.0	3.0	3.8	3.8	1.6	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.1
15	3.8	3.0	3.0	3.8	3.0	1.6	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.1
16	3.8	3.0	3.8	3.8	3.0	1.6	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.1
17	3.8	3.0	4.8	3.8	3.8	1.6	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.1
18	3.8	3.0	3.0	3.8	3.8	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.1
19	3.0	3.0	2.2	3.8	3.0	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.1
20	3.0	3.0	2.2	3.0	3.0	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.1
21	3.0	3.0	1.6	3.0	3.0	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	1.1	1.1
22	3.0	3.0	2.2	3.0	3.0	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	1.1	1.1
23	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.1
24	3.0	3.0	2.2	3.0	2.2	2.2	4.0	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.1
25	3.0	3.0	4.8	3.0	2.2	3.0	2.2	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.6
26	2.2	3.0	3.0	3.8	2.2	3.0	2.2	2.2	3.8	2.2	1.1	1.1
27	2.2	3.0	2.2	3.8	2.2	3.0	2.2	1,320	3.0	1.6	1.1	1.1
28	2.2	3.0	3.0	3.8	2.2	3.0	2.2	119	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.1
29	2.2	--	3.0	3.8	2.2	3.0	2.2	60	2.2	1.6	.7	1.1
30	3.0	--	3.0	3.8	2.2	3.0	2.2	3.8	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.1
31	3.0	--	3.8	--	2.2	--	2.2	3.0	--	2.2	--	1.1
Total	96.2	95.7	86.4	310.7	99.6	68.4	73.4	1,564.6	87.0	64.0	42.8	34.2
Mean	3.10	3.42	2.79	10.4	3.21	2.28	2.37	50.5	2.57	2.06	1.43	1.10
Max	3.8	6.7	4.8	103	4.8	3.0	4.0	1,320	4.8	2.2	2.2	1.6
Min	2.2	3.0	1.6	3.0	2.2	1.6	1.6	2.2	2.2	1.6	0.7	0.7
Calendar year:	1963	Total: 2,623		Mean: 7.19		Max: 1,320		Min: 0.7				

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1964

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1	1.1	2.2	0.7	1.1	3.0	0.7	3.0	1.1	0.7	0.4	0	0.2
2	.7	1.6	1.1	1.1	2.2	1.1	2.2	1.6	.7	.4	0	.4
3	.4	1.6	1.6	1.1	2.2	1.1	2.2	3.0	.4	.4	0	.4
4	1.6	1.6	1.1	1.6	1.6	1.1	1.6	3.8	.4	.7	0	.2
5	1.1	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.1	1.1	1.6	3.8	.7	.4	0	.2
6	1.1	1.6	2.2	2.2	1.1	.7	1.6	3.0	.4	.4	0	.2
7	1.1	1.6	3.0	2.2	.7	.7	1.6	2.2	.4	.7	0	.07
8	1.1	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.6	.7	1.1	2.2	.4	.4	.07	.4
9	.7	1.1	2.2	1.1	1.1	.7	1.1	1.6	.4	.4	.01	.4
10	.7	1.1	1.6	1.6	1.6	.7	.7	1.1	.2	.4	.07	.2
11	.7	1.6	2.2	3.0	1.1	.7	.7	1.1	.2	.2	.2	.2
12	1.1	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.1	1.1	1.1	.2	.2	.07	.2
13	1.1	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	2.2	.2	.2	.01	.07
14	1.6	1.1	1.6	1.1	1.6	.7	1.1	1.1	.2	.2	.2	.01
15	1.6	1.1	1.6	1.1	1.6	.4	1.1	1.6	.2	.07	.07	0
16	1.6	1.1	2.2	1.1	1.1	.7	1.1	1.6	.2	.07	.01	0
17	1.1	1.1	2.2	2.2	2.2	.7	1.1	1.1	.2	.01	0	0
18	1.1	1.1	2.2	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.1	1.1	.4	0	0	0
19	1.1	1.1	1.6	1.6	1.1	1.1	1.1	.7	.4	0	0	0
20	1.1	1.1	1.6	3.0	.7	1.1	2.2	.7	.4	.4	.07	0
21	1.1	1.1	1.1	2.2	1.6	1.6	2.2	.7	.4	.4	.2	0
22	1.6	1.1	.7	3.0	1.1	3.0	2.2	.4	.2	.2	.07	0
23	2.2	.7	.7	3.0	1.1	2.2	1.6	.4	.2	.2	.01	0
24	2.2	1.1	.7	2.2	1.1	1.1	1.6	.4	.7	.2	.4	0
25	2.2	1.1	1.1	2.2	.7	1.1	1.6	.4	.4	.07	.2	0
26	1.6	2.2	.7	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.6	.4	.2	.07	.2	0
27	1.6	1.1	1.6	2.2	2.2	1.1	2.2	1.1	.4	.01	.07	0
28	1.6	1.6	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	2.2	1.6	.4	0	.07	0
29	1.1	1.1	1.6	2.2	1.6	.7	2.2	1.1	.4	0	.01	0
30	1.6	--	1.1	3.0	.7	1.1	1.6	1.1	.4	0	.07	0
31	1.1	--	1.1	--	1.1	--	1.1	1.1	--	0	--	0
Total	39.6	39.2	48.3	57.5	44.8	32.4	49.0	44.4	11.0	7.10	2.08	3.15
Mean	1.28	1.35	1.56	1.92	1.45	1.08	1.58	1.43	0.37	0.23	0.07	0.10
Max	2.2	2.2	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.8	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.4
Min	0.4	0.7	0.7	1.1	0.7	0.4	0.7	0.4	0.2	0	0	0
Calendar year: 1964			Total: 378.5		Mean: 1.0		Max: 3.8		Min: 0			

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1965

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1	0	0	0	0	0	3.0	2.2	3.8	2.2	1.1	1.1	2.2
2	0	0	0	0	0	3.0	2.2	3.0	1.6	1.1	1.1	2.2
3	0	0	0	0	0	3.0	2.2	3.0	1.6	1.1	121	2.2
4	0	0	0	0	.2	3.0	2.2	3.0	1.6	1.1	1,750	2.2
5	0	0	0	0	1.1	3.0	3.0	3.0	1.6	2.2	100	2.2
6	0	0	0	2.9	1.6	3.8	3.0	2.2	1.6	1.6	7.3	2.2
7	0	0	0	3.8	1.6	3.8	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	3.8	2.2
8	0	0	0	1.6	1.6	3.8	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	3.0	2.2
9	0	0	0	1.1	1,170	3.8	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.1	2.2	3.0
10	0	0	0	.7	68	3.0	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.6	269
11	0	0	0	.4	3.0	3.0	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.6	344
12	0	0	0	.2	.7	2.2	3.0	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.6	210
13	0	0	0	.07	.4	1.6	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.1	1.6	85
14	0	0	0	0	.07	3.8	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.1	1.6	45
15	0	0	0	0	.2	6.0	3.8	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.6	30
16	0	0	0	0	.2	6.0	3.0	1.6	1.6	.7	1.6	19
17	0	0	0	0	.4	4.8	2.2	1.1	1.6	1.1	1.6	12
18	0	0	0	0	.2	3.8	2.2	1.1	1.6	1.6	1.6	8.8
19	0	0	0	0	.07	3.0	2.2	1.1	1.6	.7	1.6	6.0
20	0	0	0	0	13	2.2	2.2	1.1	1.6	3.8	1.6	4.8
21	0	0	0	0	1.6	1.6	3.0	1.6	1.6	173	1.6	4.8
22	0	0	0	0	1.1	1.6	3.0	2.2	2.2	57	1.6	4.8
23	0	0	0	0	.7	1.6	3.0	2.2	1.6	3.0	1.6	4.8
24	0	0	0	0	1.1	1.6	3.0	1.6	1.6	2.2	1.6	6.0
25	0	0	0	0	826	1.6	3.8	1.6	1.6	1.6	9.2	4.8
26	0	0	0	0	419	2.2	3.8	1.1	1.1	1.1	13	4.8
27	0	0	0	0	68	3.0	3.8	1.1	1.6	1.1	30	4.8
28	0	0	0	0	21	3.0	4.8	1.6	1.6	1.1	12	4.8
29	0	--	0	0	7.3	2.2	3.8	2.2	1.6	.7	6.0	4.8
30	0	--	0	0	3.8	3.0	3.8	2.2	1.1	.7	3.8	4.8
31	0	--	0	--	3.8	--	3.8	2.2	--	.7	--	4.8
Total	0	0	0	10.77	2,615.74	91.0	90.0	65.0	48.4	268.2	2,087.5	1,108.2
Mean	0	0	0	.36	84.4	3.03	2.90	2.10	1.61	8.65	69.6	35.7
Max	0	0	0	3.8	1,170	6.0	4.8	3.8	2.2	173	1,750	344
Min	0	0	0	0	0	1.6	2.2	1.1	1.1	.7	1.1	2.2
Calendar year: 1965			Total: 6,384.8		Mean: 17.5		Max: 1,750		Min: 0			

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1966

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1	4.8	3.0	3.8	2.2	1.6	2.2	1.6	2.2	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.2
2	6.0	3.0	3.8	1.6	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.6	.7	.4	.2	.4
3	4.8	3.0	3.8	1.6	1.6	2.2	2.2	1.6	.7	.4	.2	.4
4	4.8	3.0	4.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	.2	.7
5	4.8	3.0	4.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	.2	.7
6	4.8	3.0	4.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.1	.7	.7	.2	.7
7	4.8	3.0	4.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	.7	.2	.7
8	4.8	3.0	4.8	1.6	3.0	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	1.1	.2	.4
9	3.8	3.8	4.8	1.6	3.0	1.6	1.1	.7	1.1	1.1	.2	.4
10	3.8	3.8	3.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	2.2	.7	.2	.4
11	3.8	3.8	3.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	1.6	.7	.2	.4
12	4.8	3.8	3.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	1.1	1.1	.2	.2
13	37	3.8	3.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	.7	.2	.2
14	21	3.8	3.8	3.0	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	1.6	.2	.2
15	8.8	3.8	3.8	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	1.1	.2	.7
16	6.0	3.8	3.8	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	1.6	.2	.4
17	3.8	3.8	3.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.1	.7	1.1	.2	.2
18	3.8	3.8	28	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.1	.7	.7	.2	.2
19	3.8	3.8	30	1.6	3.0	1.6	1.1	.7	1.1	.7	.2	.2
20	3.8	3.8	7.3	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	1.1	.7	.2	.2
21	3.8	3.8	4.8	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.6	.7	1.6	.7	.2	.2
22	3.8	3.0	14	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.6	.7	1.1	.7	.2	.2
23	3.8	3.0	7.3	2.2	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	.7	2	.7
24	3.8	3.0	6.0	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	1.1	.2	.7
25	3.8	3.0	4.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	1.1	.7	.2	.4
26	3.0	3.0	3.8	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.1	1.1	.7	.2	.2
27	3.0	3.0	3.0	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.1	.7	.4	.2	.2
28	3.0	3.0	3.0	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.6	3.0	.4	.2	.4
29	3.8	--	3.0	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	1.1	1.1	.4	.2	.2
30	3.8	--	2.2	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.1	.7	.7	.4	.2	.2
31	3.0	--	2.2	--	2.2	--	1.6	.7	--	.4	--	.2
Total	182.4	94.4	190.0	53.6	68.8	49.8	38.7	29.1	29.8	23.8	6.2	11.5
Mean	5.88	3.37	6.13	1.79	2.22	1.66	1.25	0.94	0.99	0.77	0.21	0.37
Max	37	3.8	30	3.0	3.0	2.2	2.2	2.2	3.0	1.6	0.4	0.7
Min	3.0	3.0	2.2	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.1	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.2	0.2
Calendar year: 1966			Total: 778.1		Mean: 2.1		Max: 37		Min: 0.2			

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1967

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1	0.2	0.07	0.07	0.07	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
2	.2	.07	.07	.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
3	.2	.07	.07	.4	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
4	.2	.01	.07	.4	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
5	.2	.01	.07	.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
6	.2	.01	.07	.07	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
7	.4	.01	.07	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
8	.2	.01	.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
9	.2	.01	.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
10	.2	.01	.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
11	.2	.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
12	.07	.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
13	.07	.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
14	.07	.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
15	.07	.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
16	.2	1.4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
17	1.1	.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
18	.7	.4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
19	.4	.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
20	.2	.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
21	.2	.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
22	.2	.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
23	.4	.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
24	.2	.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
25	.2	.07	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
26	.07	.07	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--
27	.07	.07	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--	--
28	.07	.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--	--
29	.07	--	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--	--
30	.2	--	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--	--
31	.07	--	.01	--	0	--	0	0	--	--	--	--
Total	7.03	4.63	0.53	1.34	0	0	0	0	0	--	--	--
Mean	.23	.17	.02	.04	0	0	0	0	0	--	--	--
Max	1.1	1.4	.07	.4	0	0	0	0	0	--	--	--
Min	.07	.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	--	--	--
Calendar year:	1967											

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Discharge (GPM)	Milligrams per liter														Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate				
Dec. 13, 1962	--	30	0.00	--	50	51	332	610	0	38	358	0.3	14	--	374	0	2,030	8.0	24	3	
Feb. 22, 1963	3.0	30	.02	--	78	48	325	736	0	39	335	.6	8.2	--	392	0	2,080	8.1	24	--	
May 1	6.7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	406	--	--	--	25	--	
May 24	1.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	335	--	--	--	476	--	--	--	27	--	
June 17	1.1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	380	--	--	--	28	--	
July 18	3.2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	400	--	--	--	28	--	
Aug. 22	2.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--	460	--	--	--	28	--	
Sept. 20	10.0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	294	--	--	--	476	--	--	--	27	--	
Oct. 25	1.8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	152	--	--	--	26	--	
Nov. 22	1.0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	408	--	--	--	26	--	
Dec. 23	.8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	478	--	--	--	--	--	
Jan. 22, 1964	1.5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	422	--	--	--	422	--	--	--	25	--	
Mar. 2	.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	476	--	--	--	476	--	--	--	26	--	
Mar. 25	.7	31	.00	--	76	76	268	718	0	6.0	345	.5	2.9	--	*1,250	502	0	2,140	7.9	24	--
Apr. 24	1.2	30	.00	--	82	74	292	684	0	6.7	362	.5	1.1	--	*1,260	509	0	2,200	7.8	27	--
May 25	.5	35	.00	--	80	73	285	704	0	34	355	.7	3.9	--	*1,220	500	0	2,150	7.9	27	--
July 1	1.2	35	.04	--	80	73	306	670	0	64	388	.7	.5	--	*1,300	500	0	2,240	7.9	28	--
July 20	2.2	27	.00	--	84	85	314	652	0	80	440	.4	1.8	--	*1,390	559	24	2,380	7.9	29	--
Aug. 26	.3	20	.10	--	76	68	289	668	0	38	360	.4	2.6	--	*1,250	469	0	2,050	8.1	28	--
Sept. 21	.2	25	.00	--	58	66	278	612	0	33	340	.6	3.0	--	*1,170	416	0	1,990	8.1	28	40
Oct. 26	.1	34	.00	--	70	68	286	664	0	36	348	.6	3.8	--	*1,180	454	0	2,060	7.8	29	30
May 17, 1965	--	34	.00	--	100	69	287	636	0	92	380	.6	1.9	--	*1,280	533	11	2,180	7.8	24	25
June 18	--	32	.00	--	104	78	313	760	0	42	420	.6	.4	--	*1,380	580	0	2,390	8.1	28	--
July 20	.7	31	.00	--	90	72	295	728	0	26	380	.6	.7	--	*1,260	520	0	2,220	8.2	29	3
Aug. 25	.9	27	.00	--	76	72	277	680	0	10	368	.6	.1	--	*1,230	468	0	2,100	8.1	26	10
Oct. 5	.5	26	.00	--	70	69	286	662	0	20	365	.5	.4	--	*1,180	458	0	2,090	8.2	27	7
Oct. 26	1.4	31	.00	--	76	68	268	612	0	10	380	.5	1.7	--	*1,160	469	0	2,110	7.9	27	5
Nov. 24	1.2	32	.00	--	86	71	266	626	0	54	362	.6	4.6	--	*1,160	506	0	2,040	8.0	--	--
Dec. 9	2.4	32	.00	--	94	72	303	704	0	60	385	.6	6.2	--	*1,290	530	0	2,240	8.0	25	--
Jan. 4, 1966	9.2	31	.02	0.00	42	77	306	532	0	20	406	.5	3.9	--	*1,200	422	0	2,140	8.2	--	5
Jan. 19	4.3	30	.00	--	74	77	287	636	0	66	376	.5	5.0	--	*1,240	501	0	2,160	8.0	23	0
Feb. 1	--	29	.00	--	62	79	334	644	0	70	424	.5	6.5	--	*1,310	480	0	2,300	7.8	--	0
Mar. 2	2.2	30	.00	.00	32	83	294	540	0	56	392	.5	7.0	--	*1,160	421	0	2,070	8.2	27	5
Apr. 1	2.2	30	.01	.00	58	77	294	606	0	48	388	.8	7.0	--	*1,220	461	0	2,120	8.1	28	5
May 3	1.4	30	.02	.00	70	71	291	644	0	44	369	2.3	.1	--	*1,200	466	0	2,100	8.1	27	0
June 3	.5	30	.00	--	78	71	281	656	10	43	350	.5	3.6	--	*1,252	486	0	2,130	8.5	27	15
July 6	1.1	27	.00	.00	86	66	302	666	0	56	380	.5	1.4	--	*1,260	486	0	2,190	8.2	27	20
Aug. 4	.9	28	.00	.00	84	60	286	654	0	35	356	.6	3.0	--	*1,240	456	0	2,050	8.1	28	15
Sept. 6	.6	25	.00	.00	78	71	316	676	0	88	372	.6	2.3	--	*1,240	486	0	2,130	8.1	28	20
Oct. 3	1.2	27	.00	.00	84	74	314	650	0	66	420	.5	2.3	--	*1,320	514	0	2,310	7.8	27	30
Nov. 3	--	26	.00	.00	84	68	302	692	0	44	375	.5	2.0	--	*1,260	489	0	2,220	8.0	25	20
Dec. 1	.2	27	.02	.00	72	66	286	648	0	40	351	.5	4.3	--	*1,180	451	0	2,020	8.0	26	15

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

GROUND-WATER STATIONS

Well 1 (20-64.46-3-15)

Owner.--U.S. Government.Name.--NPS-7 (Hawksnest).Location.--Lat 18° 20' 53", long 64° 46' 36".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, diam 6-in, cased 0-28.Depth.--36 ft.Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing 5.90 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--40 ft above msl.Highest water level.--14.94 ft below lsd, Dec. 28, 1967.Lowest water level.--18.02 ft below lsd, June 28, 1967.Records available.--Chemical analysis: August 1964.Water levels: 1964-69.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter													Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)				
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)				Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Aug. 8, 1964	38	0.05	--	106	577	628	360	0	276	2,425	0.0	0.4	--	*	5,640	2,637	2,342	7,440	7.5	27

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Aug. 25, 1964	17.10	May 7, 1965	17.27	May 16, 1966	17.25	Feb. 27, 1968	16.46
Aug. 31	17.05	May 17	17.34	June 3	17.85	Mar. 29	15.65
Sept. 9	16.81	June 2	17.38	July 6	17.75	Apr. 25	16.39
Sept. 18	16.77	June 17	17.30	July 21	17.44	May 31	17.06
Sept. 21	16.70	June 30	17.06	Aug. 4	17.62	July 1	16.80
Sept. 26	16.90	July 22	17.17	Sept. 6	17.52	July 30	16.27
Oct. 5	16.84	Aug. 4	17.87	Oct. 7	17.78	Aug. 30	15.95
Oct. 12	16.99	Aug. 25	17.90	Nov. 4	17.45	Sept. 30	15.62
Oct. 19	16.89	Sept. 10	17.55	Dec. 1	17.60	Oct. 30	16.48
Oct. 23	16.96	Oct. 5	17.55	Dec. 27	17.84	Nov. 27	16.62
Nov. 6	17.08	Oct. 26	17.38	Jan. 26, 1967	17.86	Dec. 30	16.65
Nov. 19	16.83	Nov. 17	17.23	Feb. 27	17.74	Jan. 30, 1969	16.72
Nov. 30	17.03	Nov. 26	17.13	Mar. 28	17.63	Mar. 5	16.43
Dec. 17	16.96	Dec. 22	17.00	May 1	17.13	Apr. 2	16.74
Dec. 28	17.04	Jan. 4, 1966	16.89	May 26	17.90	May 2	16.77
Jan. 12, 1965	17.05	Jan. 18	16.88	June 28	18.02	Jun. 3	15.18
Jan. 25	17.43	Feb. 1	16.74	July 27	17.77	July 7	15.22
Feb. 14	17.30	Feb. 23	17.02	Aug. 30	17.51	Aug. 15	16.25
Feb. 24	17.34	Mar. 8	17.10	Oct. 3	16.60	Sept. 24	15.80
Mar. 10	17.40	Mar. 22	17.06	Oct. 26	17.61	Oct. 21	15.34
Mar. 22	17.58	Apr. 1	17.62	Nov. 29	15.28	Nov. 19	15.81
Apr. 6	17.23	Apr. 19	17.24	Dec. 28	14.94	Dec. 17	15.82
Apr. 21	17.41	May 3	17.45	Jan. 26, 1968	15.79		

Well 2 (21-64.46-1-79)

Owner.--U.S. Government.Name.--NPS-16, (Trunk Bay Dug Well).Location.--Lat 18° 21' 15", long 64° 46' 05".Description.--Dug water-table production well,
diam 6.5 ft.Depth.--7 ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of well, 2.60 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--6 ft above msl.Highest water level.--1.10 ft below lsd, Mar. 5, 1969.Lowest water level.--6.70 ft below lsd, July 30, 1968.Records available.--Chemical analyses: May 1965 to
December 1969.Water levels.--1963-69.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated				Hardness as CaCO ₃		
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate	
May 17, 1965	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5,760	--	--	--	--	304	--	--	--	--	
Mar. 12, 1968	21	0.00	--	560	1,180	9,160	320	338	0	2,505	16,950	0.9	--	0.0	30,860	6,249	5,972	39,480	7.9	--	
Mar. 29	22	.00	0.00	490	1,215	9,610	350	310	0	2,645	17,400	.9	--	.4	31,900	6,220	5,960	40,400	7.9	26	
Apr. 26	22	.00	.04	448	1,163	9,600	420	328	0	2,220	17,750	1.6	--	.2	31,800	5,900	5,631	42,500	7.7	26	
May 31	21	.00	.00	500	1,465	8,820	375	318	0	2,520	17,400	.9	--	.4	31,200	7,272	7,011	42,200	8.0	27	
July 1	24	--	.28	540	1,120	9,680	298	322	0	2,490	17,500	.8	--	.4	31,800	5,950	5,690	43,700	8.0	--	
July 30	22	--	.00	550	1,170	9,560	320	328	0	2,350	17,300	.9	--	.3	31,400	6,180	5,910	43,300	8.0	--	
Aug. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	12,400	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Sept. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	13,600	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Oct. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	20,200	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Dec. 1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	16,200	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Dec. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	12,400	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Jan. 30, 1969	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	15,600	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Mar. 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3,050	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Apr. 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	8,000	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
May 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	15,800	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
June 3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,660	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
July 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	10,000	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Aug. 8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	7,700	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Dec. 17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5,900	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 20, 1963	3.64	June 17, 1965	6.04	Jan. 26, 1967	5.60	July 1, 1968	5.87
Oct. 25	5.13	July 22	5.86	Feb. 27	5.49	July 30	6.70
Nov. 22	5.33	Aug. 25	6.06	Mar. 28	5.11	Aug. 30	5.52
Dec. 23	5.45	Oct. 5	4.83	May 1	4.83	Sept. 30	5.19
Jan. 22, 1964	4.89	Nov. 17	4.24	May 26	6.15	Oct. 30	5.39
Mar. 2	5.33	Dec. 8	4.87	June 28	6.30	Nov. 27	4.67
Mar. 25	4.82	Jan. 4, 1966	4.85	July 27	5.92	Dec. 30	4.31
Apr 24	5.43	Feb. 1	4.40	Aug. 30	6.18	Jan. 30, 1969	4.69
May 25	5.80	Mar. 2	5.45	Oct. 3	5.60	Mar. 5	1.10
July 20	5.35	Apr. 1	5.83	Oct. 26	5.43	Apr. 2	4.68
Aug. 25	5.60	May 2	6.16	Nov. 29	6.09	May 2	6.63
Oct. 26	5.27	June 3	6.26	Dec. 28	5.68	June 3	3.21
Nov. 19	4.84	July 6	5.78	Jan. 26, 1968	5.73	July 7	5.13
Dec. 17	4.82	Aug. 4	5.70	Feb. 27	5.35	Aug. 16	4.92
Jan. 25, 1965	5.41	Sept. 6	4.80	Mar. 12	4.70	Sept. 24	4.08
Feb. 24	5.06	Oct. 3	5.75	Mar. 29	5.72	Oct. 21	4.79
Mar. 22	5.66	Nov. 4	5.11	Apr. 26	4.87	Nov. 19	5.21
Apr. 21	4.98	Dec. 1	4.62	May 31	6.28	Dec. 17	4.44
May 17	5.35	Dec. 27	5.03				

Well 3 (21-64.46-5-90)

Owner.--U.S. Government.
Name.--NPS-14 (Trunk Bay).
Location.--Lat 18° 21' 08", long 64° 46' 04".
Description.--Drilled horizontal production well,
 cased 0-420.
Length of bore.--803 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Pressure gage at mouth of bore.
Land elevation.--50 ft above msl.
Highest pressure.--35 psi, Dec. 17, 1969.
Lowest pressure.--0 psi.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1966-69.
Water pressure: 1966-69.
Remarks.--Used to recharge NPS-5.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)		
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated				Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Apr. 29, 1966	30	0.00	--	125	148	169		496	0	181	490	0.4	0.5	--	*1,900	920	513	2,870	7.9	--
June 3	34	.00	0.04	106	76	265		574	0	66	435	.4	.0	--	*1,320	577	106	2,210	7.9	27
July 18	35	.02	.04	98	64	204		554	0	40	322	.3	.1	--	*1,080	508	54	1,860	7.6	27
Oct. 19	--	--	--	--	--	--		--	--	--	310	--	--	--	--	488	--	--	--	--
Oct. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--		--	--	--	310	--	--	--	--	484	--	--	--	--
Dec. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--		--	--	--	320	--	--	--	--	400	--	--	--	--
Jan. 26, 1967	--	--	--	--	--	--		--	--	--	300	--	--	--	--	480	--	--	--	--
Feb. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--		--	--	--	290	--	--	--	--	424	--	--	--	--
May 26	--	--	--	--	--	--		--	--	--	290	--	--	--	--	208	--	--	--	--
June 28	1.7	.02	.00	12	34	178		174	0	4.0	290	.5	.0	--	*610	170	27	1,200	7.7	--
July 27	1.1	.01	.00	12	58	181		288	8	5.6	288	.3	.2	--	*702	268	19	1,350	8.3	26
Aug. 30	1.0	.07	.00	6	46	169		212	6	3.2	272	.3	.1	--	*642	204	20	1,260	8.4	--
Oct. 3	.6	.00	.00	4	39	173		176	0	5.2	290	.4	.0	--	*603	170	26	1,210	7.9	--
Nov. 29	32	.00	.00	78	76	185		560	0	26	298	.6	.0	--	*956	505	46	1,710	8.1	26
Jan. 2, 1968	32	.00	.04	92	66	208		614	0	30	295	.6	.0	--	*989	500	0	1,770	7.7	26
Jan. 26	37	.00	.04	92	68	198	3.3	520	16	35	330	.7	.1	0.0	1,040	510	57	1,760	8.4	27
Feb. 27	28	.00	.00	88	64	203	3.4	534	8	32	320	.7	.2	.0	1,010	485	34	1,750	8.3	26
Mar. 29	21	.00	.01	12	56	198	3.2	272	18	11	305	.5	.0	.0	759	260	8	1,430	8.6	26
Apr. 26	30	.00	.01	88	61	202	3.2	542	0	35	302	.7	.1	.0	989	470	26	1,750	8.2	27
May 31	23	.00	.00	82	67	202	3.2	286	20	16	310	.4	.0	.0	791	296	32	1,470	8.6	28
July 1	18	--	.00	57	52	203	3.2	238	20	3.8	320	.4	.0	.0	743	228	0	1,400	8.7	--
July 30	11	--	.00	49	44	196	3.4	332	10	2.8	320	.5	.5	.0	800	303	14	1,520	8.4	--
Aug. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	290	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Sept. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	300	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Oct. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	270	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Dec. 10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	300	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Dec. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	280	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Jan. 30, 1969	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	290	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Mar. 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	290	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Apr. 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	290	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
May 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	300	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
June 3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	330	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
July 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	310	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Aug. 15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	310	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Dec. 17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	318	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water pressure, in pounds per square inch

Date	Water pressure	Date	Water pressure	Date	Water pressure	Date	Water pressure
July 21, 1966	24.5	May 1, 1967	30	Jan. 26, 1968	12	Dec. 30, 1968	19
Aug. 4	29	May 26	30	Feb. 27	14	Jan. 30, 1969	n
Sept. 6	29	June 28	30	Mar. 29	16	Mar. 3	20
Oct. 3	30	July 27	30.5	Apr. 26	14	Apr. 2	n
Dec. 1	28	Aug. 30	30.0	May 31	17	May 2	30
Dec. 14	n	Oct. 3	30.0	July 1	19	June 3	34
Dec. 27	29.5	Oct. 24	n	July 30	20	July 7	30
Jan. 26, 1967	n	Oct. 26	n	Aug. 30	24	Aug. 15	34
Feb. 3	n	Nov. 29	18	Sept. 30	18	Sept. 24	33.5
Feb. 27	26	Dec. 28	n	Oct. 30	1	Dec. 17	35
Mar. 28	29	Jan. 2, 1968	14	Nov. 27	20		

n - flowing, value pressure 0 psi

Well 4 (21-64.46-4-90)

Owner.--U.S. Government.

Name.--NPS-5 (Trunk Bay).

Location.--Lat 18° 21' 09", long 64° 46' 03".

Description.--Drilled water-table, production well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-12.

Depth.--60 ft.

Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.0 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--60 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--16.76 ft below lsd, June 3, 1969.

Lowest water level.--57.29 ft below lsd, Nov. 27, 1968.

Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1964-69.

Water levels: 1964-69.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)		Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate			
July 17, 1964	38	0.05	--	80	61	188	482	0	39	300	0.0	0.0	--	*988	450	55	1,670	7.9	26	
July 21, 1966	37	.02	--	204	122	240	542	0	91	705	.3	.1	--	*2,110	1,010	566	3,050	7.4	26	
Sept. 6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	760	--	--	--	--	864	--	--	--	--	
Oct. 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	570	--	--	--	--	780	--	--	--	--	
Nov. 8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	520	--	--	--	--	680	--	--	--	--	
Dec. 1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	550	--	--	--	--	772	--	--	--	--	
Dec. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	540	--	--	--	--	764	--	--	--	--	
Jan. 26, 1967	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	--	504	--	--	--	--	
Feb. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	540	--	--	--	--	752	--	--	--	--	
Mar. 28	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	540	--	--	--	--	640	--	--	--	--	
May 1	36	.04	.02	168	99	214	552	0	108	515	.3	.1	--	*1,650	826	373	2,550	7.4	--	
May 26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	510	--	--	--	--	484	--	--	--	--	
June 28	35	.01	.04	164	100	217	556	0	99	520	.4	.0	--	*1,640	820	364	2,320	7.4	--	
July 27	35	.02	.01	160	95	226	550	0	96	518	.3	.2	--	*1,540	790	339	2,490	7.9	27	
Aug. 30	34	.03	.04	158	99	208	552	0	98	495	.3	.1	--	*1,560	801	348	2,490	7.4	--	
Oct. 3	35	.00	.00	116	95	228	432	0	98	510	.4	.1	--	*1,550	680	326	2,370	8.0	--	
Oct. 26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	310	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Nov. 29	34	.00	.00	94	72	189	612	0	21	295	.5	.4	--	*981	530	28	1,800	8.0	26	
Dec. 28	35	.00	.00	112	80	188	612	0	48	330	.6	.0	--	*1,090	610	108	1,880	7.9	--	
Jan. 26, 1968	34	.00	.02	92	63	206	3.6	508	20	35	320	.7	.6	0.0	1,020	490	40	1,770	8.5	27
Feb. 27	32	.00	.02	134	79	230	4.2	548	12	70	440	.6	.0	.0	1,270	660	191	2,160	8.3	26
Mar. 29	36	.00	.01	28	74	223	4.0	190	--	74	440	.6	.0	.0	984	374	199	1,820	8.5	27
Apr. 26	35	.00	.02	96	67	205	3.8	552	--	37	340	1.0	.0	.0	1,060	515	62	1,850	8.0	27
May 31	28	.00	.04	33	79	200	3.7	444	4	35	305	.4	.0	.0	907	408	37	1,850	8.3	27
July 1	34	--	.02	27	71	224	3.5	272	8	61	385	.3	.0	.0	948	360	124	1,760	8.3	--
July 30	38	--	.01	17	80	239	3.8	172	10	87	460	.2	.0	.0	1,020	372	215	1,910	8.5	28
Aug. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	460	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Sept. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	430	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Oct. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	310	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Nov. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	380	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Dec. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Jan. 30, 1969	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	280	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Apr. 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	290	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
May 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
June 3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	290	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Aug. 25, 1964	32.58	June 2, 1965	30.50	July 6, 1966	49.09	Jan. 26, 1968	48.27
Aug. 31	32.57	June 17	30.68	July 21	42.29	Feb. 27	47.55
Sept. 9	32.61	June 30	31.14	Aug. 4	40.00	Mar. 12	43.25
Sept. 18	32.78	July 22,	33.50	Sept. 6	47.38	Mar. 29	55.81
Sept. 21	32.77	Aug. 4	34.35	Oct. 7	45.47	Apr. 26	48.09
Sept. 26	32.63	Aug. 25	39.71	Oct. 17	40.54	May 31	43.28
Oct. 5	32.59	Sept. 10	^a 49.03	Oct. 19	37.53	July 1	43.49
Oct. 12	32.64	Oct. 5	47.26	Nov. 4	36.69	July 30	43.45
Oct. 19	32.79	Oct. 26	41.80	Dec. 1	45.95	Aug. 30	47.09
Oct. 23	32.83	Nov. 17	35.19	Dec. 27	^a 49.10	Sept. 30	47.74
Nov. 6	33.05	Nov. 26	34.14	Jan. 26, 1967	42.47	Oct. 30	53.77
Nov. 19	33.19	Dec. 22	^a 35.45	Feb. 27	47.09	Nov. 27	57.29
Nov. 30	33.33	Jan. 4, 1966	^a 43.43	Mar. 28	^a 49.17	Dec. 30	33.08
Dec. 17	33.54	Jan. 18	44.30	May 1	^a 48.96	Jan. 30, 1969	28.55
Dec. 28	33.66	Feb. 1	45.35	May 26	46.37	Mar. 5	27.52
Jan. 12, 1965	33.82	Feb. 23	47.63	June 28	46.03	Apr. 2	24.49
Jan. 25	33.95	Mar. 8	46.95	July 27	46.13	May 2	31.46
Feb. 14	34.14	Mar. 22	47.84	Aug. 30	46.07	June 3	16.76
Feb. 24	34.25	Apr. 1	47.54	Oct. 3	46.25	July 7	16.78
Mar. 10	34.37	Apr. 19	47.24	Oct. 23	46.27	Aug. 15	20.77
Mar. 22	34.50	May 3	42.14	Oct. 26	43.44	Sept. 24	22.31
Apr. 6	34.60	May 16	44.50	Nov. 29	41.52	Oct. 21	23.40
Apr. 21	34.68	June 1	^a 48.60	Dec. 28	50.22	Nov. 19	25.46
May 7	34.42	June 3	^a 47.54	Jan. 2, 1968	47.46	Dec. 17	20.53
May 11	33.55	June 21	^a 49.10				

a - pumping.

Well 5 (21-64.45-11-77)

Owner.--U.S. Government.

Name.--NPS-12 (Cinnamon Bay Gallery Well).

Location.--Lat 18° 21' 17", long 64° 45' 23".

Description.--Dug unused water-table gallery,
14 ft by 20 ft.

Depth.--14 ft.

Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of concrete standpipe, 1.5 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--10 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--2.37 ft below lsd, Mar. 5, 1969.

Lowest water level.--7.83 ft below lsd, July 1, 1968.

Records available --Chemical analyses: July 1963 to
October 1964.

Water levels: 1964-69.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Hardness as CaCO ₃	Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)					Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
July 23, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	26		
Oct. 5, 1964	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4,900	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Oct. 6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3,650	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	28		
Oct. 8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,720	--	--	--	--	--	1,750	--	--	28		

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
Mar. 25, 1964	6.86	June 17, 1965	7.00	June 3, 1966	7.17	Feb. 27, 1968	6.84
Apr. 24	7.02	June 30	7.10	July 6	7.52	Mar. 29	6.74
Aug. 25	7.33	July 22	7.32	Aug. 4	6.97	Apr. 25	6.83
Sept. 18	6.82	Aug. 4	7.27	Sept. 6	4.50	May 31	7.29
Oct. 7	7.36	Aug. 25	7.31	Oct. 3	6.60	July 1	7.83
Oct. 23	6.94	Oct. 5	6.50	Nov. 1	6.55	July 30	7.22
Nov. 6	6.91	Oct. 26	4.46	Dec. 1	6.38	Aug. 30	7.09
Nov. 19	6.90	Nov. 17	4.63	Dec. 27	6.31	Sept. 30	6.86
Nov. 30	6.97	Nov. 26	5.50	Jan. 26, 1967	7.07	Oct. 30	7.03
Dec. 11	6.82	Dec. 9	6.22	Feb. 27	6.96	Nov. 27	7.46
Dec. 29	6.68	Dec. 22	3.95	Mar. 28	6.92	Dec. 30	6.10
Jan. 12, 1965	6.56	Jan. 4, 1966	5.48	May 1	6.96	Jan. 30, 1969	6.24
Jan. 25	6.98	Jan. 18	5.90	May 26	7.20	Mar. 5	2.37
Feb. 14	7.16	Feb. 1	5.85	June 28	7.27	Apr. 2	6.17
Feb. 24	6.92	Feb. 23	6.55	July 27	7.34	May 2	6.83
Mar. 10	6.94	Mar. 2	6.63	Aug. 30	7.27	June 3	3.39
Mar. 22	7.07	Mar. 22	6.41	Oct. 3	6.50	Sept. 24	3.10
Apr. 6	7.15	Apr. 1	6.82	Oct. 26	6.60	Oct. 21	5.20
Apr. 21	6.81	Apr. 19	6.62	Nov. 29	6.45	Nov. 19	5.94
May 7	6.93	May 3	6.77	Dec. 28	6.57	Dec. 17	5.56
May 17	6.49	May 16	6.90	Jan. 26, 1968	6.92		

Well 6 (21-64.45-1-67)

Owner.--U.S. Government.Name.--NPS-15 (Cinnamon Bay Dug Well).Location.--Lat 18° 21' 18", long 64° 45' 20".Description.--Dug unused water-table well, diam 6.5 ft.Depth.--9 ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium at Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 3.40 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--7 ft above msl.Highest water level.--2.23 ft below lsd, May 9-10, 1965.Lowest water level.--6.55 ft below lsd, June 26, 1968.Records available.--Water levels: 1963-69.Remarks.--Recorder.

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1963												
5	--	--	5.79	5.43	5.33	5.92	6.08	5.62	--	5.04	4.82	--
10	--	--	5.97	4.55	5.51	6.04	5.87	5.62	--	5.15	4.86	--
15	--	--	5.95	4.85	5.56	6.04	5.82	5.68	--	4.96	4.85	--
20	--	--	5.89	4.95	5.48	5.99	5.97	5.84	--	5.21	4.92	5.57
25	--	5.78	5.63	--	5.78	6.05	5.93	5.79	5.15	--	5.02	--
eom	--	5.86	5.53	--	5.86	6.02	6.04	4.09	5.05	4.92	5.12	--
1964												
5	5.53	--	--	5.72	6.13	6.40	--	5.93	5.61	--	--	--
10	5.63	--	--	5.92	5.84	6.38	--	6.07	5.53	--	--	--
15	5.43	--	5.52	5.97	6.13	6.35	--	6.16	5.67	--	--	--
20	5.23	--	5.57	5.94	6.27	6.23	5.67	6.25	5.48	--	5.87	--
25	--	--	5.71	5.95	6.32	6.10	5.84	--	--	--	--	--
eom	--	--	5.59	6.02	6.20	6.17	5.84	5.46	--	--	--	5.84
1965												
5	5.74	6.11	5.93	--	5.53	5.72	6.11	5.53	5.88	5.56	2.95	5.09
10	5.57	6.17	5.88	5.86	2.23	5.81	6.11	6.24	5.42	5.56	--	3.34
15	5.80	6.12	--	5.64	3.74	5.83	6.29	6.39	5.90	5.80	4.20	3.44
20	5.95	5.99	--	--	5.27	5.98	6.35	6.40	--	4.84	4.61	3.69
25	6.05	5.88	6.15	6.06	3.51	6.07	6.37	5.62	--	4.20	4.37	4.02
eom	6.14	5.99	--	6.11	5.35	6.06	6.25	4.30	--	4.85	4.89	4.42
1966												
5	4.71	4.87	5.54	5.71	5.60	6.13	6.26	5.56	5.67	5.66	5.49	--
10	5.07	4.88	5.55	5.89	5.53	6.21	6.33	5.65	4.63	5.69	5.28	--
15	4.57	5.17	5.50	3.85	5.65	6.16	5.96	5.98	5.35	4.97	5.28	--
20	4.98	5.38	5.36	5.43	5.36	6.09	5.67	6.05	5.38	4.92	5.30	--
25	5.06	5.43	5.33	5.56	5.69	6.12	5.52	6.10	5.65	5.49	5.36	--
eom	4.81	5.48	5.60	5.66	5.90	6.29	5.12	5.61	4.97	5.46	5.24	--
1967												
5	5.51	5.83	5.65	5.68	5.33	6.06	6.37	5.93	6.02	5.42	4.55	--
10	5.55	6.02	5.96	5.91	5.59	6.12	6.35	6.01	5.85	5.64	5.17	--
15	5.71	6.07	6.07	5.89	5.83	6.14	6.04	6.05	5.43	5.47	4.53	--
20	5.79	5.66	5.80	5.95	5.94	6.14	6.09	6.14	5.32	5.44	4.85	--
25	5.85	5.86	5.75	5.84	6.09	6.19	6.18	6.15	5.52	5.52	5.32	--
eom	5.92	5.60	5.62	--	6.06	6.33	5.83	6.13	5.54	4.81	5.40	--
1968												
5	5.68	5.61	5.22	5.97	5.93	6.33	6.35	6.07	5.84	5.97	6.01	4.09
10	5.68	5.63	--	--	6.06	6.42	6.46	5.61	--	5.70	5.99	4.91
15	5.57	5.62	--	--	5.96	6.39	6.30	5.96	--	5.69	5.82	4.82
20	5.58	5.57	5.46	--	6.05	6.45	6.24	6.10	--	5.81	5.77	5.10
25	5.74	5.59	--	--	6.13	6.53	6.14	6.13	--	5.84	5.76	5.25
eom	5.70	5.24	5.79	5.78	6.32	6.51	6.16	6.15	5.75	6.04	4.37	5.13
1969												
5	--	--	h 2.99	5.24	--	--	--	--	4.70	3.99	4.15	2.79
10	--	--	--	5.51	--	--	--	--	4.84	3.83	4.12	3.19
15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.81	4.01	4.18	3.75
20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.80	3.93	4.16	4.43	4.11
25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.75	3.47	4.37	2.37	4.08
eom	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.72	3.59	4.18	2.37	4.04

h - tape measurement

Well 7 (21-64.45-10-78)

Owner.--U.S. Government.

Name.--NPS-11 (Cinnamon Bay).

Location.--Lat 18° 21' 17", long 64° 45' 17".

Description.--Dug unused water-table well, diam 5 ft,
back-filled around 2-in diam well point.

Depth.--27 ft.

Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of 2-in well point, 1.9 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--27 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--23.80 ft below lsd, Dec. 22, 1965.

Lowest water level.--26.57 ft below lsd, June 28, 1967.

Records available.--Water levels: 1964-67.

Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, December 1967.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 18, 1964	25.56	May 7, 1965	26.23	Feb. 1, 1966	24.30	Dec. 1, 1966	25.55
Oct. 23	26.03	May 17	26.05	Feb. 23	25.65	Dec. 27	25.47
Nov. 6	26.06	June 17	26.27	Mar. 2	25.95	Jan. 26, 1967	26.24
Nov. 19	26.15	June 30	25.97	Mar. 22	25.85	Feb. 27	26.08
Nov. 30	26.16	July 22	26.53	Apr. 1	26.08	Mar. 29	26.48
Dec. 17	26.10	Aug. 4	26.47	Apr. 18	26.15	May 1	25.80
Dec. 29	25.39	Aug. 25	26.43	May 3	26.33	May 26	26.38
Jan. 12, 1965	25.89	Oct. 5	25.75	May 16	26.03	June 28	26.57
Jan. 25	26.00	Oct. 26	24.99	June 3	26.35	July 27	26.41
Feb. 14	26.30	Nov. 16	24.37	July 6	26.49	Aug. 30	26.35
Feb. 24	26.14	Nov. 26	25.10	Aug. 4	26.13	Oct. 3	25.66
Mar. 10	26.14	Dec. 8	25.34	Sept. 6	26.26	Oct. 26	26.04
Mar. 22	26.30	Dec. 22	23.80	Oct. 3	25.82	Nov. 29	25.66
Apr. 6	26.24	Jan. 4, 1966	24.90	Nov. 4	26.18	Dec. 28	25.75
Apr. 21	26.18	Jan. 18	25.26				

Well 8 (21-64.45-14-78)

Owner.--U.S. Government.

Name.--NPS-9 (Cinnamon Bay).

Location.--Lat 18° 21' 14", long 64° 45' 17".

Description.--Drilled water-table, production well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-39.

Depth.--60 ft.

Aquifer.--Volcanic rock of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.2 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--50 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--36.19 ft below lsd, Dec. 17, 1969.

Lowest water level.--56.49 ft below lsd, Aug. 15, 1969.

Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1964-69.

Water levels: 1964-69.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)		Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate			
Oct. 6, 1964	36	0.00	--	58	71	183	484	10	30	275	0.5	0.0	--	*964	436	23	1,610	8.4	27	
Nov. 17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	280	--	--	--	--	392	--	--	--	29	
Nov. 18	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	270	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	26	
Nov. 20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	280	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	26	
Nov. 23	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	270	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	26	
Nov. 24	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	280	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	27	
Nov. 25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	280	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	27	
Nov. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	270	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	29	
Feb. 17, 1965	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	300	--	--	--	--	420	--	--	--	--	
Mar. 22	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	300	--	--	--	--	328	--	--	--	29	
Mar. 29	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	300	--	--	--	--	320	--	--	--	28	
May 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	348	--	--	--	--	312	--	--	--	--	
June 17	35	.00	--	72	66	246	512	18	70	328	.6	.1	--	*1,050	451	1	1,800	8.4	26	
July 21, 1966	38	.00	0.00	82	50	260	562	0	38	335	.4	1.1	--	*1,100	410	0	1,900	7.7	--	
Oct. 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	480	--	--	--	--	
Nov. 8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	320	--	--	--	--	448	--	--	--	--	
Dec. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	--	448	--	--	--	--	
Jan. 26, 1967	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	--	456	--	--	--	--	
Feb. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	480	--	--	--	--	
May 1	35	.02	--	76	71	236	562	0	50	340	.4	1.0	--	*1,060	482	21	1,920	7.6	--	
May 26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	302	--	--	--	--	
June 28	34	.03	--	80	68	233	568	0	37	340	.6	.6	--	*1,080	479	13	1,840	7.7	--	
July 27	35	.00	.00	74	67	235	566	0	18	338	.5	.5	--	*1,080	460	0	1,900	8.0	26	
Aug. 30	36	.02	.01	76	72	216	566	0	36	320	.4	.9	--	*1,080	486	22	1,910	7.7	--	
Nov. 29	37	.00	.00	67	86	217	614	0	14	335	.6	.4	--	*1,060	520	17	1,890	8.2	26	
Dec. 28	38	.00	--	84	95	200	630	0	35	340	.6	.5	--	*1,090	600	83	1,940	7.8	--	
Jan. 26, 1968	38	.00	.01	80	71	250	532	20	45	360	.7	.0	--	1,130	490	20	1,920	8.4	27	
Feb. 27	44	.00	.01	76	71	234	554	10	38	350	1.3	.4	--	1,120	485	9	1,920	8.3	26	
Mar. 29	38	.00	.00	19	62	252	328	30	37	360	.5	.0	0.0	964	302	0	1,700	8.6	26	
Apr. 26	38	.00	--	80	62	260	576	0	32	360	.8	.5	--	1,120	455	0	1,960	7.6	26	
May 31	38	.00	.00	37	83	220	3.5	490	0	40	340	.5	.2	.0	1,000	434	32	1,850	8.2	27
July 1	39	--	.00	22	60	245	3.8	336	24	41	352	.5	.8	.1	954	302	0	1,710	8.7	--
July 30	37	--	.00	26	64	243	3.6	402	8	39	340	.4	.0	.0	959	328	0	1,750	8.4	--
Aug. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Sept. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	380	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Oct. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	320	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Nov. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	320	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Dec. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	330	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Jan. 30, 1969	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	310	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Mar. 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Apr. 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	330	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
May 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
June 3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
July 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	365	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Aug. 15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	360	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Nov. 19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	358	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,050	--	--	
Dec. 17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	348	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,000	--	--	

*Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Nov. 6, 1964	42.52	Sept. 10, 1965	46.95	Sept. 6, 1966	^a 50.75	Mar. 29, 1968	46.87
Nov. 19	43.49	Oct. 5	45.78	Oct. 7	47.50	Apr. 26	46.72
Nov. 30	43.32	Oct. 26	44.86	Nov. 4	47.45	May 31	47.09
Dec. 17	44.82	Nov. 12	43.14	Dec. 1	46.67	July 1	48.10
Dec. 28	44.84	Nov. 26	43.27	Dec. 27	^a 51.05	July 30	47.55
Jan. 12, 1965	44.81	Dec. 8	43.27	Jan. 26, 1967	45.45	Aug. 30	48.30
Jan. 25	44.46	Dec. 22	42.14	Feb. 27	47.67	Sept. 30	47.23
Feb. 14	44.25	Jan. 4, 1966	42.24	Mar. 29	46.54	Oct. 30	47.50
Feb. 24	44.15	Jan. 18	43.44	May 1	^a 52.30	Nov. 27	46.49
Mar. 10	44.09	Feb. 1	^a 48.29	May 26	47.10	Dec. 30	46.13
Mar. 22	44.68	Feb. 23	44.19	June 28	47.65	Jan. 30, 1969	45.77
Apr. 6	46.39	Mar. 2	44.61	July 27	47.78	Mar. 5	44.71
Apr. 20	46.88	Mar. 22	44.07	Aug. 30	47.58	Apr. 2	46.34
May 7	48.70	Apr. 1	^a 52.05	Oct. 3	46.93	May 2	46.40
May 17	45.78	Apr. 19	^a 52.52	Oct. 26	46.38	June 3	41.82
June 2	46.38	May 3	47.50	Nov. 29	46.24	Aug. 15	56.49
June 17	46.52	May 16	46.85	Dec. 28	46.30	Sept. 24	^a 41.41
June 30	46.10	June 3	^a 52.77	Jan. 2, 1968	46.07	Oct. 21	^a 40.82
July 22	46.13	June 21	46.35	Jan. 26	46.73	Nov. 19	^a 47.44
Aug. 4	46.53	July 7	46.42	Feb. 27	46.42	Dec. 17	36.19
Aug. 25	47.27	Aug. 4	^a 47.42				

a - pumping

Well 9 (21-64.45-12-72)

Owner.--U.S. Government.

Name.--NPS-6 (Cinnamon Bay).

Location.--Lat 18° 21' 16", long 64° 45' 10".

Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-51.

Depth.--70 ft.

Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.6 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--60 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--41.72 ft below lsd, Aug. 15, 1969.

Lowest water level.--63.15 ft below lsd, July 1, 1968.

Records available.--Chemical analyses: August 1964 to
June 1969.

Water levels: 1964-69.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)		
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated				Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Aug. 2, 1964	34	0.00	--	46	81	224	390	--	47	400	0.3	0.4	--	--	*1,060	448	128	1,900	8.2	27
Aug. 30, 1968	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,140	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Sept. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,600	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Oct. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,200	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Nov. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,950	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Dec. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,200	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Jan. 30, 1969	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,200	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Mar. 7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,860	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Apr. 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,800	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
May 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,200	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
June 3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,600	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Aug. 31, 1964	56.68	May 17, 1965	56.78	June 3, 1966	56.70	Feb. 27, 1968	57.68
Sept. 9	56.48	June 2	56.51	June 21	56.95	Mar. 29	57.83
Sept. 18	56.59	June 17	56.52	July 6	57.06	Apr. 26	62.03
Sept. 21	56.44	June 30	56.89	July 21	56.85	May 31	57.52
Sept. 26	56.29	July 20	57.19	Aug. 4	56.70	July 1	63.15
Oct. 5	56.51	Aug. 4	57.14	Oct. 3	56.63	July 30	57.60
Oct. 12	56.62	Aug. 25	57.20	Nov. 4	57.19	Aug. 30	57.31
Oct. 19	56.71	Sept. 10	56.82	Dec. 1	56.24	Sept. 30	57.45
Oct. 23	56.48	Oct. 5	56.48	Dec. 23	56.32	Oct. 30	57.55
Nov. 6	56.73	Nov. 12	54.76	Jan. 26, 1967	56.78	Nov. 27	56.70
Nov. 19	56.79	Nov. 26	55.37	Feb. 27	56.85	Dec. 30	56.67
Nov. 30	56.87	Dec. 9	55.72	Mar. 28	56.78	Jan. 1, 1969	59.54
Dec. 17	56.86	Dec. 22	53.96	May 1	56.88	Mar. 5	54.19
Dec. 28	56.81	Jan. 4, 1966	54.90	May 26	57.07	Apr. 2	56.02
Jan. 12, 1965	56.44	Jan. 18	55.06	June 28	57.32	May 2	56.75
Jan. 25	56.85	Feb. 1	55.29	July 27	57.23	June 3	52.82
Feb. 14	56.97	Feb. 23	55.92	Aug. 30	57.25	July 7	44.38
Feb. 24	56.77	Mar. 2	61.08	Oct. 3	56.66	Aug. 15	41.12
Mar. 10	56.78	Mar. 22	56.10	Oct. 26	56.58	Sept. 24	59.38
Mar. 22	56.96	Apr. 1	56.37	Nov. 29	56.44	Oct. 21	55.17
Apr. 6	56.92	Apr. 19	56.45	Dec. 28	57.78	Nov. 19	60.75
Apr. 21	56.62	May 3	56.60	Jan. 2, 1968	56.82	Dec. 17	53.72
May 7	56.91	May 16	56.62	Jan. 26	57.05		

Well 10 (21-64.44-7-8)

Owner.--U. S. Government.
Name.--Mary Point Dug Well.
Location.--Lat 18° 21' 57", long 64° 44' 16".
Description.--Dug unused water-table well,
 diam 10 ft.
Depth.--20 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of curb, 3.0 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--25 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--16.84 ft below lsd, Sept. 6, 1966.
Lowest water level.--17.87 ft below lsd, Apr. 27, 1967.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: October 1964.
Water levels: 1965-67.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, December 1967.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)				Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium magnesium	Non-carbonate
Oct. 14, 1964	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	550	--	--	--	--	496	--	--	27	

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
June 18, 1965	17.48	Jan. 18, 1966	17.33	July 21, 1966	17.07	Mar. 28, 1967	17.70
July 20	17.54	Feb. 1	17.33	Aug. 4	17.25	Apr. 27	17.87
Aug. 4	17.50	Feb. 23	17.47	Sept. 6	16.84	May 26	17.57
Aug. 25	17.54	Mar. 2	17.54	Oct. 3	17.30	June 28	17.73
Oct. 5	17.27	Mar. 22	17.38	Nov. 4	17.20	July 27	17.47
Oct. 26	17.01	Apr. 19	17.52	Dec. 1	17.35	Oct. 3	17.09
Nov. 16	17.00	May 3	17.52	Dec. 23	17.40	Oct. 26	17.02
Nov. 26	17.00	June 3	17.58	Jan. 26, 1967	17.64	Nov. 29	17.15
Dec. 8	17.14	July 6	17.57	Feb. 27	17.67	Dec. 28	17.22
Jan. 4, 1966	17.30						

Well 11 (20-64.43-6-07)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-14A (Coral Bay).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 59", long 64° 43' 23".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-42.
Depth.--80 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 2.5 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--55 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--15.90 ft below lsd, Jan. 4, 1966.
Lowest water level.--39.01 ft below lsd, May 6, 1965.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: September 1964.
Water levels: 1964-67.
Remarks.--Plugged. Measurement discontinued, March 1967.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)				Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Sept. 22, 1964	32	0.00	--	38	54	288	330	--	94	405	0.3	1.8	--	*1,040	317	46	1,940	7.9	27	

* Residue on evaporation at 180° C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 18, 1964	36.88	Mar. 10, 1965	38.50	Nov. 12, 1965	21.43	June 21, 1966	35.59
Sept. 26	36.47	Mar. 22	38.65	Nov. 26	24.25	July 6	36.07
Oct. 7	36.49	Apr. 6	38.79	Dec. 9	27.44	July 21	36.42
Oct. 12	36.56	Apr. 20	38.89	Dec. 22	17.30	Aug. 4	36.68
Oct. 19	36.65	May 6	39.01	Jan. 4, 1966	15.90	Sept. 6	37.38
Oct. 23	36.72	May 17	31.22	Jan. 18	20.47	Oct. 7	30.19
Nov. 6	36.84	June 2	25.30	Feb. 8	24.17	Nov. 3	35.65
Nov. 19	36.99	June 17	28.53	Feb. 23	26.94	Dec. 1	35.97
Nov. 30	37.19	June 30	31.22	Mar. 2	27.97	Dec. 22	26.73
Dec. 17	37.46	July 20	34.37	Mar. 22	30.28	Jan. 27, 1967	31.95
Dec. 28	37.59	Aug. 4	35.68	Apr. 1	31.23	Mar. 1	35.40
Jan. 12, 1965	37.80	Aug. 25	36.87	Apr. 19	32.62	Mar. 28	38.69
Jan. 25	37.95	Sept. 10	37.45	May 5	33.59		
Feb. 11	38.19	Oct. 5	38.13	May 16	34.14		
Feb. 24	38.32	Oct. 26	29.37	June 3	34.91		

Well 12 (20-64.42-1-01)

Owner.--V.I. Government.
Name.--Coral Bay Dug Well.
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 55", long 64° 42' 59".
Description.--Dug water-table production well,
 diam 12 ft.
Depth.--11 ft.
Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of wall, 2.0 ft above msl.
Land elevation.--7 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--3.75 ft below lsd, June 3, 1969.
Lowest water level.--7.48 ft below lsd, Mar. 22, 1965.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: July to September 1963.
Water levels: 1963-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, June 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)				Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
July 17, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	--	270	--	--	--	26
Sept. 20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	406	--	--	--	--	--	635	--	--	--	29

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 20, 1963	5.31	Feb. 24, 1965	7.11	Sept. 6, 1966	6.42	Dec. 28, 1967	6.27
Oct. 25	5.82	Mar. 22	7.48	Oct. 7	5.85	Jan. 26, 1968	6.43
Nov. 22	6.14	Apr. 20	6.74	Nov. 5	6.13	Feb. 27	6.55
Dec. 23	6.39	May 17	5.62	Dec. 1	5.99	Mar. 29	6.93
Jan. 22, 1964	6.24	July 20	6.52	Dec. 22	5.88	Apr. 25	7.10
Mar. 2	6.54	Aug. 25	6.41	Jan. 27, 1967	6.31	May 31	6.81
Mar. 25	6.49	Oct. 5	6.12	Mar. 1	7.10	July 17	6.78
Apr. 24	6.55	Nov. 12	5.39	Mar. 28	6.79	Aug. 6	6.56
May 25	6.73	Dec. 9	5.58	Apr. 27	6.89	Aug. 30	6.80
July 1	6.44	Jan. 4, 1966	5.74	May 26	6.75	Sept. 30	6.66
July 20	6.06	Feb. 8	6.21	June 30	7.17	Oct. 30	6.75
Aug. 25	6.41	Mar. 2	6.93	July 27	6.43	Nov. 27	5.65
Sept. 18	6.43	Apr. 1	6.76	Aug. 29	6.50	Dec. 30	5.63
Oct. 23	6.39	May 5	6.42	Oct. 3	6.04	Jan. 30, 1969	5.63
Nov. 19	6.48	June 3	6.55	Oct. 26	5.90	Apr. 2	5.62
Dec. 17	6.95	July 7	6.88	Nov. 29	6.14	June 3	3.75
Jan. 25, 1965	7.38	Aug. 4	5.88				

Well 13 (19-64.42-6-17)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-15 (Estate Calabash Boom).
Location.--Lat 18° 19' 51", long 64° 42' 21".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, diam 6-in,
 cased 0-61, slotted 40-61 ft.
Depth.--62 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.4 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--50 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--40.50 ft below lsd, Jan. 18, 1966.
Lowest water level.--44.55 ft below lsd, Mar. 22, 1965.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: September 1964.
Water levels: 1964-67.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, December 1967.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)				Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Sept. 22, 1964	30	0.00	--	106	168	802	738	0	316	1,250	0.6	0.0	--	*3,040	956	351	5,080	7.8	29	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 26, 1964	43.79	Apr. 21, 1965	44.31	Jan. 4, 1966	42.98	Oct. 7, 1966	43.82
Oct. 7	43.77	May 6	44.26	Jan. 18	40.50	Nov. 3	43.78
Oct. 12	43.82	May 17	44.16	Feb. 8	43.30	Dec. 1	43.91
Oct. 19	43.88	June 2	44.06	Feb. 23	43.47	Dec. 22	43.70
Oct. 23	43.88	June 18	44.01	Mar. 2	43.50	Jan. 27, 1967	43.90
Nov. 6	43.97	June 30	44.03	Mar. 22	43.62	Mar. 1	44.09
Nov. 19	44.01	July 20	44.11	Apr. 1	43.73	Mar. 20	44.26
Nov. 30	44.02	Aug. 4	44.20	Apr. 19	43.87	Apr. 27	44.44
Dec. 17	44.18	Aug. 25	44.29	May 5	43.87	May 26	44.34
Dec. 18	44.21	Sept. 10	44.24	May 16	43.88	June 30	44.40
Jan. 12, 1965	44.35	Oct. 5	44.24	June 3	43.87	July 27	44.26
Jan. 25	44.38	Oct. 26	44.06	June 20	44.00	Aug. 29	44.26
Feb. 11	44.46	Nov. 12	43.73	July 6	44.05	Oct. 3	44.13
Feb. 24	44.46	Nov. 26	43.50	July 21	43.80	Oct. 26	43.96
Mar. 10	44.50	Dec. 9	43.50	Aug. 4	43.82	Nov. 29	43.87
Mar. 22	44.55	Dec. 22	43.12	Sept. 6	43.90	Dec. 28	44.14
Apr. 6	44.46						

Well 14 (19-64.43-3-47)

Owner.--U.S. Government.Name.--NPS-10 (Lameshur Bay).Location.--Lat 18° 19' 31", long 64° 43' 23".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-53.Depth.--67 ft.Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.8 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--40 ft. above msl.Highest water level.--12.97 ft below lsd, Sept. 10, 1966.Lowest water level.--41.25 ft below lsd, Oct. 30, 1968.Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1964-69.Water levels: 1964-69.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)				
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)				Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate	
Oct. 30, 1964	23	0.04	--	70	111	626	544	--	--	1,003	0.3	0.9	--	*	2,380	631	185	4,090	7.8	29	
Dec. 1, 1968	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,300	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Jan. 30, 1969	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,180	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Apr. 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,260	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Nov. 30, 1964	28.81	Oct. 5, 1965	29.29	Nov. 4, 1966	26.90	Mar. 29, 1968	30.78
Dec. 17	28.97	Oct. 26	14.38	Dec. 1	27.12	Apr. 25	31.54
Dec. 28	29.02	Nov. 15	13.24	Dec. 22	26.25	May 31	32.08
Jan. 12, 1965	29.14	Nov. 26	25.52	Jan. 27, 1967	25.84	July 17	32.64
Jan. 25	29.21	Dec. 9	25.47	Mar. 1	26.79	Aug. 6	32.75
Feb. 14	29.35	Jan. 4, 1966	14.20	Mar. 28	27.52	Aug. 30	32.78
Feb. 24	29.42	Jan. 18	20.39	Apr. 27	28.20	Sept. 30	32.93
Mar. 10	29.52	Feb. 8	22.14	May 26	28.58	Oct. 30	41.25
Mar. 22	29.59	Feb. 23	23.04	June 30	29.05	Nov. 27	33.17
Apr. 6	29.70	Apr. 1	24.78	July 27	29.35	Dec. 30	32.25
Apr. 20	29.78	May 23	26.20	Aug. 29	29.63	Jan. 30, 1969	^a 36.80
May 6	29.89	June 17	27.71	Oct. 26	29.83	Apr. 2	^a 29.95
June 18	28.05	July 17	26.55	Nov. 29	30.04	June 3	17.29
June 30	28.26	Aug. 15	27.46	Dec. 28	30.20	Sept. 24	14.09
July 20	28.20	Sept. 10	12.97	Jan. 26, 1968	30.38	Oct. 21	23.98
Aug. 25,	28.68	Oct. 7	26.97	Feb. 27	30.57	Dec. 17	19.13

Well 15 (20-64.45-4-23)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
 Name.--USGS-16 (Estate Herman Farm).
 Location.--Lat 18° 20' 43", long 64° 45' 47".
 Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-158, perforated 50-158 ft.
 Depth.--158 ft.
 Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.10 ft above lsd.
 Land elevation.--650 ft above msl.
 Highest water level.--33.27 ft below lsd, Aug. 15, 1969.
 Lowest water level.--70.04 ft below lsd, Oct. 30, 1968.
 Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1964-69.
 Water levels: 1964-69.
 Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, August 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated				Hardness as CaCO ₃		
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate	
Oct. 23, 1964	36	0.00	--	52	51	161		646	0	22	90	0.6	11	--	* 817	339	0	1,310	8.2	26	
June 28, 1967	36	.01	0.01	56	49	173		660	0	26	98	.9	9.9	--	* 791	341	0	1,290	7.8	--	
July 27	36	.02	.0	52	51	186		668	0	28	112	.7	9.7	--	* 824	339	0	1,340	8.2	27	
Aug. 29	36	.14	.0	56	51	180		682	0	25	105	.7	7.0	--	* 788	349	0	1,380	8.0	--	
Nov. 29	40	.01	.0	54	60	218		770	0	24	132	1.4	10.0	--	* 876	380	0	1,460	8.1	--	
Dec. 28	38	.00	.01	58	60	210		770	0	21	130	.9	10.0	--	* 833	390	0	1,440	8.2	--	
Jan. 26, 1968	39	.00	.0	56	54	210	3.8	634	31	29	136	1.1	9.6	--	882	360	0	1,430	8.6	--	
Feb. 27	38	.00	.0	56	50	212	3.8	642	24	21	140	1.1	10.0	--	872	344	0	1,440	8.5	27	
Mar. 29	34	.00	.0	10	45	209	3.6	496	35	27	130	.7	4.0	0.0	796	210	0	1,270	8.7	23	
Apr. 25	40	.00	.0	52	50	213	4.0	700	0	24	135	1.3	9.5	.0	900	335	0	1,460	8.1	27	
May 31	39	.00	.00	42	62	200	3.4	628	31	41	120	.8	2.4	.0	851	360	0	1,490	8.6	--	
July 1	41	--	.0	8.9	52	203	3.2	504	24	29	138	.6	7.5	.0	755	236	0	1,260	8.6	--	
July 30	39	--	.0	5.5	49	206	3.4	476	33	27	130	.7	8.5	.0	736	215	0	1,360	8.7	--	
Sept. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Oct. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Nov. 27	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Dec. 30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Jan. 30, 1969	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Apr. 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
May 2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
June 3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
Nov. 6, 1964	43.69	Aug. 25, 1965	46.71	July 6, 1966	41.39	Nov. 29, 1967	-----
Nov. 19	43.89	Sept. 10	46.89	July 21	41.99	Dec. 28	53.78
Nov. 30	44.09	Oct. 5	47.32	Aug. 4	41.50	Jan. 26, 1968	54.58
Dec. 17	44.42	Nov. 12	46.58	Sept. 6	43.35	Feb. 27	55.05
Dec. 28	44.62	Nov. 26	45.46	Oct. 3	43.40	Mar. 29	54.60
Jan. 12, 1965	45.20	Dec. 9	44.44	Nov. 3	43.05	Apr. 25	57.93
Jan. 25	45.43	Dec. 22	40.82	Dec. 1	43.51	May 31	58.98
Feb. 11	45.76	Jan. 4, 1966	39.00	Dec. 22	44.02	July 1	56.85
Feb. 24	45.95	Jan. 18	36.40	Jan. 26, 1967	45.75	July 30	56.39
Mar. 10	46.19	Feb. 1	34.82	Mar. 1	45.62	Aug. 30	65.48
Mar. 22	46.43	Feb. 23	35.12	Mar. 23	-----	Sept. 30	56.93
Apr. 6	46.67	Mar. 8	35.72	Apr. 27	48.98	Oct. 30	^a 70.04
Apr. 20	46.84	Mar. 22	36.35	May 26	51.50	Nov. 27	57.33
May 6	47.01	Apr. 1	36.68	June 28	52.08	Dec. 30	56.27
May 17	47.11	Apr. 19	37.67	July 27	62.88	Jan. 30, 1969	56.03
June 2	46.90	May 3	38.19	Aug. 29	58.30	Mar. 5	55.28
June 18	46.53	May 16	38.43	Aug. 30	-----	Apr. 2	54.54
June 30	46.22	June 3	39.57	Oct. 3	-----	June 3	46.89
July 20	46.05	June 21	40.57	Oct. 28	-----	Aug. 15	33.27
Aug. 4	46.30						

a - pumping

Well 16 (20-64.45-2-21)

Owner.--U.S. Government.

Name.--Estate Adrian Dug Well.

Location.--Lat 18° 20' 43", long 64° 45' 55".

Description.--Dug unused water-table well,
diam 10 ft.

Depth.--23 ft.

Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of cover, 2.2 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--620 ft.

Highest water level.--14.90 ft below lsd, Nov. 22, 1963.

Lowest water level.--Dry.

Records available.--Chemical analysis: April 1963.

Water levels: 1963-67.

Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, October 1967.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)				Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Apr. 3, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--	--	400	--	--	24		

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 20, 1963	15.12	Sept. 18, 1964	21.82	Dec. 9, 1965	f	Dec. 1, 1966	22.44
Oct. 25	14.92	Oct. 23	22.46	Jan. 4, 1966	20.39	Dec. 22	f
Nov. 22	14.90	Nov. 19	f	Feb. 1	18.23	Jan. 26, 1967	f
Dec. 23	16.22	Dec. 17	f	Mar. 2	17.55	Mar. 1	f
Jan. 22, 1964	16.83	Jan. 25, 1965	f	Apr. 1	17.61	Mar. 28	f
Mar. 2	17.92	Feb. 24	f	May 3	18.36	Apr. 27	f
Mar. 25	18.60	Mar. 22	f	June 3	19.31	May 26	f
Apr. 24	19.39	Apr. 20	f	July 7	20.77	July 27	f
May 25	20.72	July 20	f	Aug. 4	21.34	Aug. 29	f
July 1	16.85	Aug. 25	f	Sept. 6	22.16	Oct. 3	f
July 20	20.94	Oct. 5	f	Oct. 3	22.27	Oct. 26	f
Aug. 25	21.49	Nov. 12	f	Nov. 3	22.77		

f - dry

Well 17 (20-64.46-4-49)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-13 (Estate Adrian)
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 33", long 64° 46' 11".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
diam 6-in, cased 0-54.
Depth.--60 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.8 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--580 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--13.87 ft below lsd, June 3, 1969.
Lowest water level.--32.23 ft below lsd, Sept. 30, 1968.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: August 1964.
Water levels: 1964-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, August 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)				Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium magnesium	Non-carbonate
Aug. 25, 1964	23	0.00	--	42	67	180	530	0	22	222	0.3	0.0	--	* 751	380	0	1,490	8.0	28	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 9, 1964	27.35	May 6, 1965	28.18	Apr. 19, 1966	25.70	Oct. 3, 1967	28.35
Sept. 18	25.87	May 11	26.75	May 3	25.70	Oct. 26	29.21
Sept. 21	26.99	June 2	25.70	May 16	26.54	Nov. 29	28.50
Sept. 28	25.46	June 18	27.48	June 3	27.27	Dec. 28	29.81
Oct. 7	27.43	June 30	27.16	June 20	27.14	Jan. 26, 1968	29.87
Oct. 12	27.95	July 20	28.27	July 6	27.25	Feb. 27	30.55
Oct. 19	28.34	Aug. 4	27.30	July 21	24.79	Mar. 29	30.21
Oct. 23	28.34	Aug. 25	28.33	Aug. 4	26.07	Apr. 25	31.02
Nov. 6	28.47	Sept. 10	28.56	Sept. 6	27.78	May 31	31.02
Nov. 19	27.75	Oct. 5	28.28	Oct. 3	25.50	July 1	30.68
Nov. 30	27.86	Nov. 12	24.38	Nov. 3	27.41	July 30	30.42
Dec. 17	28.20	Nov. 26	25.62	Dec. 1	27.90	Aug. 30	30.99
Dec. 22	28.48	Dec. 9	27.27	Dec. 22	27.36	Sept. 30	32.23
Jan. 12, 1965	28.98	Dec. 22	21.09	Jan. 26, 1967	26.94	Oct. 30	35.02
Jan. 25	28.74	Jan. 4, 1966	22.12	Mar. 1	27.48	Nov. 27	27.63
Feb. 11	29.21	Jan. 18	23.00	Mar. 28	28.74	Dec. 30	25.34
Feb. 24	29.23	Feb. 1	25.11	Apr. 27	28.69	Jan. 30, 1969	24.86
Mar. 10	29.47	Feb. 23	25.84	May 26	27.86	Apr. 2	26.62
Mar. 22	29.59	Mar. 8	25.95	June 28	27.55	May 2	27.80
Apr. 6	25.79	Mar. 22	23.27	July 27	29.09	June 3	13.87
Apr. 30	29.07	Apr. 1	26.55	Aug. 29	29.30	Aug. 15	19.61

Well 18 (19-64.47-2-49)

Owner.--A. Massac.
Name.--Great Cruz Bay Dug Well.
Location.--Lat 18° 19' 34", long 64° 47' 10".
Description.--Dug unused water-table well.

Depth.--13 ft.
Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of wall 0.6 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--12 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--5.80 ft below lsd, Jan. 18, 1966.
Lowest water level.--11.55 ft below lsd, July 1, 1964.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: July 1963.
Water levels: 1963-67.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, December 1967.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)				Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
July 22, 1963	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	370	--	--	--	--	420	--	--	--	26

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Sept. 20, 1963	7.83	Nov. 19, 1964	8.97	Jan. 4, 1966	5.92	Dec. 22, 1966	8.99
Sept. 25	8.20	Dec. 17	8.62	Jan. 18	5.80	Jan. 26, 1967	9.20
Oct. 22	8.84	Jan. 25, 1965	9.81	Feb. 1	6.36	Mar. 1	9.63
Dec. 23	9.54	Feb. 24	10.40	Mar. 2	7.40	Mar. 23	10.06
Jan. 22, 1964	10.00	Mar. 22	10.68	Apr. 1	7.09	Apr. 27	10.55
Mar. 2	10.70	Apr. 21	9.77	May 2	7.85	May 27	10.42
Mar. 25	10.98	May 17	8.22	June 3	8.51	June 28	10.26
Apr. 24	11.07	July 20	8.28	July 6	9.56	July 27	10.53
May 25	11.44	Aug. 25	9.15	Aug. 4	9.37	Aug. 29	9.73
July 1	11.55	Oct. 5	8.93	Sept. 6	9.36	Oct. 3	9.72
July 20	10.51	Oct. 26	7.96	Oct. 7	8.73	Oct. 26	9.42
Aug. 25	11.15	Nov. 15	6.64	Nov. 3	8.40	Nov. 29	8.38
Oct. 23	9.26	Dec. 9	6.24	Dec. 1	9.22	Dec. 28	8.82

Well 19 (20-64.47-5-99)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-12 (Cruz Bay Gut).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 04", long 64° 47' 07".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-151, slotted 110-150 ft.
Depth.--192 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 4.3 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--260 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--18.21 ft below lsd, Aug. 15, 1969.
Lowest water level.--29.44 ft below lsd, Nov. 29, 1968.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: March 1964.
Water levels: 1964-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, August 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)		
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium* (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated				Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium magnesium	Non-carbonate
Mar. 2, 1964	47	0.00	--	80	46	53	452	0	11	85	0.2	0.7	--	*612	388	17	942	7.9	28	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
May 14, 1964	21.08	Dec. 12, 1964	24.18	Jan. 4, 1966	21.48	July 27, 1967	25.20
May 19	21.09	Dec. 29	24.29	Jan. 18	20.15	Aug. 21	25.66
May 22	21.00	Jan. 12, 1965	24.45	Feb. 1	20.22	Oct. 3	25.98
June 1	21.28	Jan. 25	24.66	Feb. 23	20.42	Oct. 26	26.39
June 8	21.38	Feb. 11	24.96	Mar. 8	20.66	Nov. 29	26.02
June 15	21.60	Feb. 24	25.06	Mar. 22	19.22	Dec. 28	26.38
June 22	20.65	Mar. 10	25.30	Apr. 1	20.38	Jan. 26, 1968	26.65
June 29	21.96	Mar. 22	25.36	Apr. 19	20.56	Feb. 27	27.06
July 6	21.84	Apr. 6	25.66	May 3	20.65	Mar. 29	27.40
July 13	21.88	Apr. 20	25.88	June 3	20.97	Apr. 25	27.56
July 20	21.79	May 6	26.04	June 21	21.12	May 31	27.87
Aug. 3	22.16	May 11	25.96	July 6	21.26	July 1	28.16
Aug. 25	22.47	June 2	24.85	July 21	21.40	July 30	28.47
Aug. 31	22.64	June 18	24.93	Aug. 4	21.55	Aug. 30	28.61
Sept. 7	22.78	June 30	25.02	Sept. 6	21.70	Sept. 30	28.90
Sept. 18	22.90	July 20	25.17	Oct. 3	21.80	Oct. 30	29.30
Sept. 21	23.06	Aug. 4	25.36	Nov. 3	21.27	Nov. 29	29.44
Sept. 28	23.06	Aug. 25	25.73	Dec. 1	21.87	Dec. 30	28.36
Oct. 7	23.17	Sept. 10	25.89	Dec. 23	22.19	Jan. 30, 1969	27.79
Oct. 12	23.14	Oct. 7	26.02	Jan. 26, 1967	22.46	Mar. 5	26.03
Oct. 19	23.37	Oct. 26	25.46	Mar. 1	22.66	Apr. 2	26.81
Oct. 23	23.28	Nov. 12	24.77	Mar. 28	23.33	May 2	27.47
Nov. 6	23.56	Nov. 26	24.40	Apr. 27	23.75	June 3	24.64
Nov. 19	23.74	Dec. 9	24.03	May 26	24.35	July 7	19.99
Nov. 30	23.89	Dec. 22	22.48	June 28	24.78	Aug. 15	18.21

Well 20 (20-64.47-6-86)

Owner.--U.S. Government.
Name.--NPS-2 (Cruz Bay).
Location.--Lat 18° 20' 10", long 64° 47' 26".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-20.
Depth.--99 ft.
Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 4-in casing, 1.4 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--60 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--37.06 ft below lsd, Jan. 18, 1966.
Lowest water level.--42.56 ft below lsd, Aug. 30, 1967.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: May 1964.
Water levels: 1964-67.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, December 1967.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)		
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated				Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
May 18, 1964	31	0.00	--	66	67	377	664	--	46	470	0.6	4.9	--	*1,400	440	0	2,490	7.9	28	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
May 19, 1964	42.19	Oct. 23, 1964	39.74	Aug. 4, 1965	40.18	July 6, 1966	40.08
May 22	39.70	Nov. 6	39.85	Aug. 25	40.30	July 21	40.07
May 25	39.63	Nov. 19	39.94	Sept. 10	40.38	Aug. 4	40.28
June 1	39.93	Nov. 30	40.05	Oct. 25	41.03	Sept. 6	39.98
June 8	40.01	Dec. 17	40.10	Nov. 17	39.78	Oct. 7	39.80
June 15	39.98	Dec. 28	39.70	Nov. 26	39.73	Nov. 4	39.29
June 22	39.99	Jan. 12, 1965	40.27	Dec. 22	37.29	Dec. 1	39.55
June 29	39.85	Jan. 25	40.38	Jan. 4, 1966	37.27	Dec. 27	39.73
July 6	39.68	Feb. 14	40.56	Jan. 18	37.06	Jan. 26, 1967	39.92
July 13	40.40	Feb. 24	40.64	Feb. 1	37.46	Feb. 27	40.32
July 20	39.33	Mar. 10	40.71	Feb. 23	38.37	Mar. 29	40.49
Aug. 3	39.22	Mar. 22	40.78	Mar. 2	38.83	May 1	41.92
Aug. 25	39.53	Apr. 6	40.82	Mar. 22	38.13	May 26	41.58
Aug. 31	39.56	Apr. 21	40.81	Apr. 1	39.04	June 28	42.11
Sept. 9	39.69	May 7	40.85	Apr. 19	39.28	July 27	41.38
Sept. 18	39.77	May 11	39.93	May 3	39.49	Aug. 30	42.56
Sept. 21	39.80	June 2	39.80	May 16	39.68	Oct. 2	40.91
Sept. 26	39.75	June 17	39.57	June 3	39.76	Nov. 27	40.30
Oct. 7	39.65	June 30	39.64	June 21	40.08	Dec. 28	40.24
Oct. 12	39.64						

Well 21 (20-64.47-7-86)

Owner.--U.S. Government.
 Name.--NPS-3 (Cruz Bay).
 Location.--Lat 18° 20' 09", long 64° 47' 28".
 Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
 diam 6-in, cased 0-25.
 Depth.--54 ft.
 Aquifer.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

Measuring point.--Top of 6-in casing, 1.2 ft above lsd.
 Land elevation.--40 ft above msl.
 Highest water level.--22.92 ft below lsd, June 3, 1969.
 Lowest water level.--49.12 ft below lsd, Oct. 5, 1965.
 Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1964-67.
 Water levels: 1964-69.
 Remarks.--Not pumped since June 1967.

CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)			
	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)				Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																			Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
June 3, 1964	34	0.00	--	94	77	320	632	0	45	480	0.5	4.4	--	*1,420	551	33	2,270	7.8	--	
May 7, 1965	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	440	--	--	--	--	--	464	--	--	--	--
June 17	32	.00	--	98	69	345	614	8	82	472	.6	12	--	*1,430	528	11	2,390	8.3	--	
July 21, 1966	36	.00	0.00	106	79	345	624	0	51	542	.4	12	--	*1,560	590	78	2,640	7.8	--	
May 26, 1967	37	.01	.00	112	88	332	610	10	64	545	.5	12	--	*1,580	642	125	2,690	8.3	--	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
June 8, 1964	26.48	Feb. 14, 1965	27.04	Mar. 22, 1966	25.80	Oct. 26, 1967	26.77
June 15	26.49	Feb. 24	27.09	Apr. 1	25.93	Nov. 27	26.18
June 22	26.36	Mar. 10	27.12	Apr. 19	26.25	Dec. 28	26.63
June 29	26.07	Mar. 22	27.16	May 3	30.67	Jan. 26, 1968	26.77
July 6	25.68	Apr. 6	27.18	May 16	26.52	Feb. 27	27.17
July 13	25.97	Apr. 21	27.46	June 3	27.16	Mar. 29	27.10
July 20	25.31	May 7	27.22	June 21	26.77	Apr. 25	27.25
Aug. 3	25.73	May 11	26.41	July 6	26.62	May 31	27.37
Aug. 25	26.16	June 2	25.31	July 21	26.56	July 1	27.26
Aug. 31	26.09	June 17	25.89	Aug. 4	26.67	July 30	27.00
Sept. 9	26.19	June 30	26.19	Sept. 6	26.35	Aug. 30	26.44
Sept. 18	26.34	July 22	26.78	Oct. 7	25.86	Sept. 30	26.78
Sept. 21	26.33	Aug. 4	26.62	Nov. 4	26.11	Oct. 30	27.07
Sept. 26	26.04	Aug. 25	27.36	Dec. 1	26.27	Nov. 27	26.59
Oct. 5	25.87	Sept. 10	26.93	Dec. 27	26.11	Dec. 30	26.02
Oct. 12	25.98	Oct. 5	49.12	Jan. 26, 1967	26.46	Jan. 30, 1969	26.23
Oct. 19	26.14	Oct. 26	26.05	Feb. 27	26.76	Mar. 5	25.28
Oct. 23	26.20	Nov. 17	26.28	Mar. 28	29.62	Apr. 2	26.19
Nov. 6	26.31	Nov. 26	^a 30.40	May 1	28.18	May 2	26.80
Nov. 19	26.32	Dec. 22	25.68	May 26	48.55	June 3	22.92
Nov. 30	26.40	Jan. 4, 1966	24.38	June 28	27.79	Sept. 24	23.19
Dec. 17	26.44	Jan. 18	24.54	July 27	27.16	Oct. 20	24.78
Dec. 28	26.51	Feb. 1	25.54	Aug. 30	26.99	Nov. 19	26.84
Jan. 12, 1965	26.79	Feb. 23	25.78	Oct. 6	26.88	Dec. 17	23.86
Jan. 25	26.90	Mar. 2	26.70				

a - pumping

Figure 4.--Locations of stations in St. Croix.

STREAMFLOW STATIONS

3320. River Gut at River, St. Croix, V.I.

Location.--Lat 17° 44' 32", long 64° 48' 50", 0.3 mile west of Coble, 4.8 miles northeast of Ft. Frederick, Frederiksted.

Drainage area.--1.42 sq mi.

Records available.--Discharge: January 1963 to September 1967.

Chemical analyses: 1962-67.

Gage.--Water-stage recorder and concrete control. Altitude of gage is 155 ft (from topographic map).

Extremes.--Maximums and minimums (discharge in gallons per minute, gage height in feet).

Annual maximum discharges for years 1963-67				Annual minimum discharges for years 1963-67			
Date	Time	Discharge	Gage height	Date	Time	Discharge	Gage height
May 18, 1963	1000	76,000	3.39	1963	--	20	--
Sept. 22, 1964	1200	860	1.53	1964	--	3	--
May 24, 1965	1500	5,300	1.94	1965	--	3	--
Oct. 14, 1966	0400	2,850	1.77	1966	--	No flow	--
June 20, 1967	1200	+5,951	1.98	1967	--	No flow	--

+ Period January to September.

1963-1967: Maximum discharge, 76,000 gpm May 18, 1963 (gage height 3.39 ft); minimum discharge, many days of no flow 1966-67.

Remarks.--Records poor. 19 observations of no flow from Oct. 10, 1967 to May 7, 1969.

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1963

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	75	75	50	50	75	50	100	560	100	140	180	140
2	75	100	50	75	75	75	100	3,930	100	270	5,320	140
3	5,510	140	50	50	75	75	75	220	180	140	800	140
4	6,280	180	35	50	75	75	75	100	270	140	370	140
5	950	220	35	50	75	50	75	75	140	140	270	131
6	540	270	50	140	75	50	75	75	1,120	140	220	131
7	540	180	50	483	75	50	220	75	540	140	180	123
8	370	140	35	370	75	50	140	100	180	140	220	123
9	370	180	35	270	75	50	100	100	180	140	420	123
10	320	180	35	180	75	50	75	75	220	140	270	131
11	370	270	35	100	180	50	75	75	270	140	220	123
12	420	140	35	75	180	50	75	75	220	180	180	115
13	420	100	50	75	270	50	300	75	180	140	180	115
14	370	100	50	75	220	50	370	75	140	270	180	107
15	320	140	50	75	180	50	180	75	180	370	178	99
16	270	180	75	75	530	35	75	100	180	180	166	107
17	270	140	75	100	730	35	75	100	140	140	175	107
18	270	180	50	100	9,840	35	75	100	140	180	193	115
19	220	180	75	75	660	515	75	100	100	180	184	107
20	180	140	100	75	320	320	75	100	100	140	157	99
21	220	220	75	75	140	100	50	100	100	140	166	107
22	100	180	75	75	75	100	50	75	140	140	149	99
23	140	100	75	75	75	100	50	75	220	140	149	84
24	140	100	75	75	75	75	50	75	180	140	149	84
25	75	75	75	100	75	75	75	75	180	180	175	91
26	75	75	100	140	75	75	75	75	140	140	157	91
27	50	35	75	100	75	75	75	1,420	270	370	149	91
28	75	35	75	75	100	477	180	660	180	180	166	99
29	75	--	75	75	75	270	140	220	140	100	140	107
30	75	--	75	75	100	180	75	140	180	100	131	107
31	75	--	50	--	75	--	75	100	--	100	--	107
Total	19,340	4,055	1,845	3,405	14,800	3,292	3,230	9,200	6,410	5,180	11,594	3,483
Mean	624	145	60	113	477	110	104	297	214	167	386	112
Max	6,280	270	100	480	9,840	515	370	3,930	1,120	370	5,320	140
Min	50	35	35	50	75	35	50	75	100	100	131	84
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1963 : Total	85,834			Mean 235		Max 9,840	Min 35	Cfsm --			Ac-ft --	

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1964

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.		
1	123	84	54	47	54	46	10	28	40	28	22	22		
2	157	131	56	47	54	61	6	28	34	28	22	34		
3	140	115	69	47	54	54	6	28	34	22	22	28		
4	220	99	61	40	54	47	6	28	34	22	22	22		
5	149	84	61	54	55	47	6	22	28	22	22	28		
6	149	84	61	40	54	40	6	22	28	22	22	28		
7	149	91	61	40	54	34	6	22	28	22	22	22		
8	123	91	54	47	47	28	4	22	22	22	22	22		
9	149	91	54	40	54	28	4	22	22	22	22	22		
10	131	115	56	34	54	22	4	22	22	22	22	22		
11	107	123	58	34	47	22	6	22	22	22	22	22		
12	115	123	54	34	47	22	22	22	22	22	22	22		
13	140	115	54	77	54	22	62	22	22	22	22	22		
14	131	107	61	54	47	18	47	22	22	22	22	18		
15	107	109	73	40	47	18	24	22	22	22	28	22		
16	91	95	55	28	47	18	18	22	18	22	28	22		
17	107	85	54	22	47	18	18	22	18	22	28	22		
18	115	84	47	22	47	24	18	22	18	47	34	18		
19	115	77	47	28	40	18	22	18	18	34	28	18		
20	140	77	47	28	34	18	22	18	18	22	28	18		
21	149	77	47	40	34	10	22	18	18	22	22	18		
22	123	77	40	34	34	14	22	18	116	22	22	18		
23	107	80	40	34	34	22	22	28	47	22	22	18		
24	107	85	40	34	34	18	22	22	22	22	22	18		
25	107	61	40	34	28	14	28	22	40	22	22	18		
26	107	69	40	47	28	10	34	18	34	22	22	18		
27	99	61	47	54	28	10	28	18	34	22	22	18		
28	84	54	40	54	22	10	28	40	34	22	18	18		
29	77	54	47	61	10	6	28	28	28	22	18	18		
30	69	---	47	61	10	4	28	84	28	22	18	18		
31	77	---	47	---	10	---	28	40	---	22	---	18		
Total	3,764	2,598	1,612	1,256	1,263	723	607	792	893	731	690	652		
Mean	121	89.6	52.0	42	41.9	24.1	20	25.6	29.8	23.6	23.0	21.0		
Max	220	131	73	77	55	61	62	84	116	47	34	34		
Min	69	54	40	22	10	4	4	18	18	22	18	18		
Cfsm														
In.														
Ac-ft														
Year 1964 : Total	15,581		Mean	42.6	Max	220	Min	4	Cfsm	--	In.	--	Ac-ft	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1965

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	18	6	18	22	18	40	22	10	10	10	6	18
2	18	10	18	22	18	40	22	14	6	10	6	14
3	18	18	18	28	18	40	22	14	10	6	6	14
4	18	18	18	42	49	40	18	22	18	6	14	14
5	18	14	18	34	66	54	18	14	22	4	6	10
6	18	10	22	28	34	47	14	10	10	4	4	10
7	18	10	18	302	28	40	18	14	10	4	18	10
8	18	14	22	34	36	40	14	14	17	4	14	10
9	18	14	22	28	34	34	14	14	10	4	102	10
10	18	10	22	34	34	34	14	22	10	4	14	6
11	18	10	22	28	28	34	18	14	10	4	10	333
12	18	10	22	22	22	40	18	14	10	4	16	863
13	18	6	22	22	22	34	18	14	10	4	30	234
14	18	10	18	22	22	28	18	28	10	4	28	131
15	18	10	18	93	22	28	14	22	10	4	22	61
16	18	14	18	28	22	22	10	18	10	4	14	54
17	18	14	18	18	49	22	10	14	6	24	42	47
18	18	14	18	18	1,305	22	14	9	6	12	18	40
19	18	14	22	18	270	40	14	6	6	10	18	40
20	18	14	22	22	236	88	14	6	6	27	22	40
21	18	18	18	18	306	59	10	14	17	14	22	36
22	14	18	102	40	95	68	14	10	14	14	22	40
23	14	18	48	37	69	60	10	10	14	10	28	47
24	14	18	168	28	2,630	40	14	14	10	6	28	47
25	14	18	34	28	2,145	34	10	18	10	6	148	61
26	14	18	34	28	301	28	18	18	10	6	138	95
27	14	18	28	34	74	28	28	14	10	10	47	61
28	14	18	28	28	54	28	22	14	10	6	34	54
29	10	--	22	22	185	28	22	10	10	6	28	47
30	10	--	119	22	267	22	29	10	10	6	22	47
31	10	--	28	--	73	--	14	10	--	6	--	54
Total	506	384	1,025	1,150	8,532	1,162	515	435	322	243	927	2,548
Mean	16.3	13.7	33.1	38.3	275	38.7	16.6	14.0	10.7	7.8	30.9	82.2
Max	18	18	168	302	2,630	88	29	28	22	27	148	863
Min	10	6	18	18	18	22	10	6	6	4	4	6
Cfsm												
In.												
Ac-ft												
Year 1965 : Total	17,749											
	Mean 48.6											
	Max 2,630											
	Min 4											
	Cfsm --											
	In. --											
	Ac-ft --											

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1966

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	54	40	34	18	6	4	0	0	0	0	6	10
2	54	40	34	18	4	6	0	0	0	0	4	10
3	54	40	34	18	4	4	0	0	0	0	6	52
4	54	34	40	14	6	4	0	0	0	0	10	14
5	54	34	40	14	4	1	0	0	0	0	6	25
6	54	34	40	10	4	0	0	0	0	0	4	102
7	54	28	40	10	4	0	0	0	0	0	6	10
8	47	28	40	10	4	0	0	0	0	0	6	18
9	47	28	34	10	4	0	0	0	0	0	6	52
10	54	28	28	10	4	0	0	0	0	0	10	39
11	47	28	22	10	6	0	0	0	22	52	6	22
12	90	34	28	10	6	0	0	0	0	27	6	18
13	83	34	22	6	6	1	0	0	0	44	6	18
14	47	28	28	8	6	1	0	0	0	90	6	22
15	40	28	34	6	6	0	0	0	0	18	4	28
16	47	28	28	6	6	0	0	0	0	14	6	22
17	40	28	22	6	10	0	0	0	0	14	22	18
18	43	31	22	10	6	0	0	0	0	14	10	22
19	47	34	22	11	10	0	0	0	0	18	6	18
20	47	34	22	10	6	0	0	0	0	18	6	22
21	47	34	22	10	10	0	0	0	0	18	6	22
22	40	34	22	6	6	0	0	0	0	14	10	22
23	40	34	18	6	10	0	0	0	0	14	10	22
24	47	40	22	6	10	0	0	0	0	18	33	22
25	47	28	18	6	6	0	0	0	0	10	14	22
26	47	40	22	4	4	0	0	0	0	14	10	18
27	47	40	22	4	4	0	0	0	0	14	10	18
28	54	40	22	4	6	0	0	0	0	14	25	18
29	47	--	18	6	4	0	0	0	0	14	67	18
30	40	--	18	6	1	0	0	0	0	14	14	18
31	40	--	18	--	1	--	0	0	--	10	--	18
Total	1,553	931	836	273	174	21	0	0	22	463	341	760
Mean	50.1	33.2	27.0	9.1	5.6	0.1	0	0	0.7	14.9	11.4	24.5
Max	90	40	40	18	10	6	0	0	22	52	67	102
Min	40	28	18	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	10
Cfsm												
In.												
Ac-ft												
Year 1966 : Total	5,374			Mean 14.7		Max 102	Min 0	Cfsm --	In.--		Ac-ft --	

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Dec. 20, 1962	70	37	0.04	--	43	32	86	384	0	7.2	73	0.4	0.2	--	469	239	0	804	7.5	26	--
Jan. 15, 1963	150	31	.00	--	39	18	65	278	0	12	51	.3	.2	--	* 354	172	0	598	7.6	26	--
Feb. 18	90	38	.00	--	36	22	--	318	0	--	62	.1	.2	--	--	180	0	669	7.3	26	--
May 28	85	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	65	--	--	--	--	204	--	--	--	26	--
June 21	111	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--	--	192	--	--	--	27	--
July 26	61	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--	--	222	--	--	--	27	--
Aug. 27	2,890	26	.00	--	32	28	53	260	0	11	59	.2	1.8	--	339	195	0	596	7.4	28	--
Aug. 28	318	30	.02	--	35	31	63	302	0	14	64	.2	.5	--	387	215	0	667	7.8	28	--
Sept. 23	125	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	76	--	--	--	--	218	--	--	--	28	--
Oct. 17	97	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--	--	228	--	--	--	27	--
Nov. 26	106	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--	--	186	--	--	--	27	--
Dec. 17	80	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--	--	246	--	--	--	25	--
Jan. 20, 1964	97	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	60	--	--	--	--	244	--	--	--	30	--
Feb. 25	40	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	60	--	--	--	--	286	--	--	--	26	--
Mar. 23	26	47	.00	--	60	44	77	482	--	3.2	70	.3	.5	--	539	330	0	910	7.7	26	--
Apr. 20	18	47	.00	--	56	46	80	476	--	8.8	72	.4	.1	--	* 554	328	0	915	7.9	27	--
May 25	9.4	52	.00	--	64	39	80	476	--	3.6	70	.4	.1	--	* 548	320	0	821	7.9	26	--
June 22	13.5	52	.00	--	62	45	72	452	12	2.4	72	.4	.3	--	* 540	340	0	922	8.3	26	--
July 28	16	58	.10	--	62	43	88	480	--	2.8	90	.0	.0	--	* 609	332	0	907	8.0	28	--
Sept. 24	9.4	50	.12	--	66	40	111	496	--	2.4	98	.4	.0	--	612	329	0	988	8.2	27	3
Sept. 26	--	63	.00	--	70	44	75	484	--	2.4	85	.1	.0	--	* 597	355	0	932	8.0	28	--
Oct. 20	18	60	.00	--	68	38	92	492	--	.8	85	.3	.5	--	* 584	326	0	965	7.9	26	70
Nov. 18	6	53	.00	--	60	41	--	--	--	2.0	83	.5	.6	--	* 550	318	0	934	7.9	26	5
Dec. 18	15.7	47	.00	--	68	45	84	504	--	3.2	85	.4	.2	--	* 585	354	0	979	8.2	24	5
Jan. 15, 1965	18	48	.00	--	66	49	77	502	--	.8	85	.3	.0	--	* 563	366	0	981	8.0	24	7
Mar. 18	13.5	47	.00	--	20	39	92	314	16	2.0	88	.6	.0	--	459	210	0	782	8.6	24	5
Apr. 14	18	48	.02	--	66	44	86	464	10	1.6	95	.5	.0	--	579	345	0	967	8.3	25	0
May 12	9.4	49	.02	--	68	44	95	496	--	8.0	100	.4	.0	--	* 625	350	0	1,010	8.1	26	5
June 17	15.7	49	.00	--	68	39	97	484	--	8.4	95	.4	.1	--	595	330	0	991	8.2	25	5
July 16	4.6	47	.00	--	64	40	87	476	--	2.0	85	.4	.4	--	560	324	0	940	8.1	27	10
Aug. 17	4.5	50	.00	--	58	39	88	458	8	1.6	74	.5	.0	--	544	305	0	904	8.3	26	5
Sept. 27	9.4	43	.00	--	60	38	84	472	--	2.4	70	.5	.3	--	* 544	306	0	905	8.0	26	5
Oct. 29	5.8	46	.00	--	62	41	81	480	--	2.4	72	.5	.0	--	* 556	323	0	918	8.0	24	5
Nov. 30	4.5	51	.00	--	68	43	92	500	--	14	85	.5	2.0	--	* 586	346	0	979	8.2	24	--
Dec. 20	25	51	.00	--	64	44	95	496	--	17	85	.5	.9	--	* 618	340	0	1,000	7.9	26	--
Jan. 18, 1966	23	49	.00	0.00	58	49	83	482	--	18	80	.3	.0	--	574	346	0	942	8.2	25	10
Feb. 18	16	49	.00	.00	58	43	87	482	--	16	70	.3	.1	--	560	322	0	918	7.9	25	5
Mar. 17	5.8	50	.01	.00	54	40	80	436	4	15	66	.4	.1	--	* 536	299	0	867	8.3	--	5
May 11	4.5	50	.01	.00	56	46	74	458	--	12	72	.4	.2	--	* 555	328	0	898	8.0	26	10
Oct. 11	13.5	20	.26	.00	32	21	47	140	--	35	76	.3	13	--	* 362	166	51	572	7.2	--	70
Nov. 9	4.5	44	.00	.00	73	46	103	524	--	14	106	.3	.4	--	645	371	0	1,090	7.8	26	15
Dec. 7	9.4	45	.03	.00	72	41	107	514	--	11	104	.4	.3	--	634	348	0	1,070	7.4	--	10
Jan. 4, 1967	11.2	46	.00	.01	70	60	76	508	--	14	110	.4	.4	--	* 625	421	5	1,070	8.0	24	--
Feb. 7	9.4	45	.00	.00	66	45	105	508	--	13	104	.4	.6	--	* 629	350	0	1,060	8.0	--	--
Mar. 10	4.5	20	.00	.00	74	28	122	502	--	10	100	.4	.3	--	602	300	0	1,040	8.0	24	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

3330. River Gut at Golden Grove, St. Croix, V. I.

Location.--Lat 17° 42' 59", long 64° 48' 16", 1,600 ft south of Centerline Road. 4,700 ft north of runway at Alexander Hamilton Airport, 5.0 miles east of Ft. Frederick, Frederiksted.

Drainage area.--5.14 sq mi.

Records available.--Discharge: January 1963 to December 1969.

Chemical analyses: 1962-64.

Gage.--Water-stage recorder and flume in concrete control. Altitude of gage is 50 ft (from topographic map).

Extremes.--Maximums and minimums (discharge in gallons per minute, gage-height in feet).

Annual maximum discharge for years 1963-69				Annual minimum discharge for years 1963-69			
Date	Time	Discharge	Gage height	Year	Date	Discharge	Gage height
May 18, 1963	1100	211,000	9.03	1963	Oct. 25, 26	10	1.60
Jan. 23, 1964	2200	131	1.82	1964	--	0	--
May 24, 1965	2200	6,860	2.62	1965	--	0	--
1966	--	0	--	1966	--	0	--
Oct. 31, 1967	1600	7,700	2.67	1967	--	0	--
Dec. 14, 1968	1400	88	2.62	1968	--	0	--
May 23, 1969	--	330,000	11 (from floodmark)	1969	--	0	--

1963-1969: Maximum discharge, 330,000 gpm May 23, 1969 (gage height 11 ft from floodmark); No flow many days in 1964-69.

Remarks.--Records poor. Flume installed and concrete control changed June 1968. No flow 1966.

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1963

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	60	410	170	140	60	410	410	17,700	500	350	60	130
2	40	380	170	170	60	410	350	9,660	470	470	9,330	120
3	49,500	380	140	170	40	410	260	1,160	440	320	3,640	100
4	62,200	380	140	200	60	380	260	600	470	230	770	80
5	16,900	350	140	260	60	320	200	470	350	170	500	60
6	6,370	350	110	170	60	320	260	350	1,650	140	380	50
7	720	350	110	1,320	60	290	560	350	640	110	320	50
8	720	350	110	1,680	60	260	530	470	410	110	260	50
9	680	320	80	720	60	230	350	380	260	80	1,070	60
10	680	320	80	560	80	200	290	350	260	80	470	60
11	640	320	80	380	80	170	260	350	260	60	260	60
12	640	320	60	290	80	170	230	380	290	80	170	70
13	600	290	60	230	200	170	2,040	410	320	110	110	70
14	600	290	60	170	110	170	2,230	470	350	140	110	60
15	560	290	40	140	80	170	680	470	380	320	80	50
16	560	380	40	110	140	170	470	470	380	290	80	50
17	560	350	40	140	2,570	140	410	470	440	200	25	50
18	530	290	40	170	78,500	170	350	470	410	200	110	50
19	530	260	40	110	16,000	1,240	320	440	380	230	80	50
20	500	260	40	110	6,000	870	290	350	350	170	80	60
21	500	260	40	110	1,000	440	260	290	320	110	970	60
22	500	230	40	110	700	440	260	230	260	60	140	50
23	470	230	40	80	600	320	260	170	290	60	170	50
24	470	230	40	60	600	290	260	110	320	40	140	50
25	470	200	60	80	600	260	230	110	290	25	200	50
26	440	200	80	40	500	410	200	60	350	25	170	45
27	440	200	80	40	500	410	170	5,620	470	170	190	40
28	410	170	80	40	470	2,170	260	3,970	380	170	190	40
29	410	--	80	40	440	1,160	200	970	290	110	150	30
30	410	--	80	80	410	560	170	600	260	80	140	30
31	380	--	110	--	410	--	170	470	--	80	--	30
Total	148,490	8,360	2,480	7,920	110,590	13,140	13,190	48,370	12,240	4,790	20,365	1,805
Mean	4,790	298	80	264	3,570	438	425	1,560	408	154	679	58
Max	62,200	410	170	1,680	78,500	2,170	2,230	17,700	1,650	470	9,330	130
Min	380	170	40	40	40	140	170	60	260	25	25	30
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1963 . Total	391,740	Mean	1,060	Max	78,500	Min	25	Cfsm	--	In.	--	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1964

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.		
1	40	50	30	25	25	15	0	0	0	0	0	0		
2	35	50	30	25	25	10	0	0	0	0	0	0		
3	35	45	30	25	25	10	0	0	0	0	0	0		
4	40	45	25	25	25	10	0	0	0	0	0	0		
5	50	45	25	25	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
6	90	45	25	25	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
7	90	40	25	25	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
8	80	40	25	25	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
9	80	35	25	25	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
10	100	35	30	25	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
11	80	35	30	25	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
12	70	45	30	30	25	5	2	0	0	0	0	0		
13	100	45	30	30	25	5	1	0	0	0	0	0		
14	100	40	30	30	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
15	100	40	30	30	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
16	90	35	30	30	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
17	80	40	30	30	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
18	70	40	30	30	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
19	60	40	30	30	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
20	50	40	30	35	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
21	50	35	30	30	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
22	50	35	30	30	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
23	110	35	30	30	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
24	130	35	30	30	25	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
25	90	35	30	30	25	3	0	0	0	0	0	0		
26	60	30	30	30	25	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
27	50	30	30	30	25	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
28	50	30	25	30	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
29	50	30	25	30	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
30	50	---	25	30	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
31	50	---	25	---	15	---	0	0	---	0	---	0		
Total	2,180	1,125	880	850	755	150	3	0	0	0	0	0		
Mean	70	39	28	28	24	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Max	130	50	30	35	25	15	3	0	0	0	0	0		
Min	35	30	25	25	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Year 1964 : Total	5,943		Mean	16	Max	130	Min	0	Cfsm	--	In.	--	Ac-ft	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1965

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2,640
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	401
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	0	0	0	0	1,030	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	0	0	0	0	155	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21	0	0	0	0	904	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24	0	0	0	0	1,630	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25	0	0	0	0	6,770	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
26	0	0	0	0	675	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30	0	---	---	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31	0	---	---	0	---	---	0	0	---	---	---	0
Total	0	0	0	0	11,171	0	0	0	0	0	0	3,041
Mean	0	0	0	0	360	0	0	0	0	0	0	98
Max	0	0	0	0	6,766	0	0	0	0	0	0	2,644
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cfsm	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
In.	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Ac-ft	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Year 1965 : Total	14,212		Mean	39	Max	6,766	Min	0	Cfsm	---	In.	---

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1967

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30	0	---	---	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31	0	---	---	0	---	---	0	0	---	911	---	0
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	911	0	0
Mean	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29	0	0
Max	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	911	0	0
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1967 : Total	911		Mean	3	Max	911	Min	0	Cfsm	--	In.	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1968

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.		
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17		
15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15		
16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
23	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4		
28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32		
29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
30	0	---	---	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
31	0	---	---	0	---	---	0	0	---	---	---	0		
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	68		
Mean	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2		
Max	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32		
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Year 1968 : Total	68		Mean	.2	Max	32	Min	0	Cfsm	--	In.	--	Ac-ft	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1969

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,110	850
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	750	880
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	650	9,200
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	600	1,880
5	0	0	0	0	9,940	0	0	0	0	0	600	1,110
6	0	0	0	0	35,900	0	0	0	0	0	550	900
7	0	0	0	0	174	0	0	0	0	20	550	800
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6,000	550	750
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3,500	550	750
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,500	650	700
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,000	3,310	750
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,500	1,270	700
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,200	800	650
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,000	700	650
15	0	0	0	0	0	260	0	0	0	900	650	650
16	0	0	0	0	0	140	0	0	0	800	650	600
17	0	0	0	0	0	104	0	0	0	700	600	600
18	0	0	0	0	0	21	0	0	0	650	650	550
19	0	0	0	0	10,700	0	0	0	22	5,630	600	550
20	0	0	0	0	23,700	0	0	0	0	2,720	600	600
21	0	0	0	0	45,800	0	0	0	27	1,190	650	600
22	0	0	0	0	2,990	0	0	0	1	950	71,000	3,000
23	0	0	0	0	29,300	0	0	0	10	800	27,000	1,000
24	0	0	0	0	69,600	0	0	0	0	13,600	3,230	700
25	0	0	0	0	1,380	0	0	0	0	1,620	1,750	600
26	0	0	0	0	127	0	0	0	0	850	1,510	600
27	0	0	0	0	80	36	0	0	0	750	1,270	600
28	0	0	0	0	50	13	0	0	0	650	1,430	550
29	0	0	0	0	30	0	0	0	0	650	1,190	550
30	0	---	---	0	20	0	0	0	0	5,470	950	550
31	0	---	---	0	10	---	0	0	---	3,840	---	550
Total	0	0	0	0	229,801	574	0	0	60	57,495	126,370	33,420
Mean	0	0	0	0	7,410	19	0	0	2	1,850	4,210	1,080
Max	0	0	0	0	69,600	260	0	0	27	13,600	71,000	9,200
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	550	550
Cfsm	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
In.	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Ac-ft	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Year 1969 : Total	447,720			Mean 1,230	Max 71,000	Min 0		Cfsm --	In. --		Ac-ft --	

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Dec. 20, 1962	75	40	0.00	--	61	36	331	632	0	60	210	0.7	1.0	--	1,050	300	0	1,650	7.9	24	--
Jan. 15, 1963	406	35	.00	--	65	30	212	496	0	56	198	.4	.8	--	* 869	289	0	1,440	7.9	23	--
Feb. 18	251	38	.02	--	62	28	225	550	0	49	182	.4	.2	--	856	270	0	1,400	7.9	24	--
May 28	326	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	185	--	--	--	--	194	--	--	--	25	--
June 21	210	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--	--	269	--	--	--	25	--
July 26	125	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	200	--	--	--	--	274	--	--	--	26	--
Aug. 27	8,050	22	.04	--	46	16	54	184	0	43	64	.3	15	--	* 365	181	30	603	7.3	25	--
Aug. 28	2,500	27	.04	--	59	28	104	296	0	69	119	.2	4.8	--	557	262	19	952	8.0	26	--
Sept. 23	258	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	318	--	--	--	27	--
Oct. 16	177	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--	--	272	--	--	--	26	--
Nov. 26	130	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--	--	200	--	--	--	24	--
Dec. 17	37	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--	--	342	--	--	--	26	--
Jan. 20, 1964	39	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--	--	326	--	--	--	23	--
Feb. 25	20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	296	--	--	--	27	--
Mar. 24	20	38	.00	--	46	52	300	744	0	63	215	.7	1.1	--	1,140	329	0	1,830	8.1	24	--
Apr. 20	16	8.6	.02	--	42	46	285	648	0	73	215	.8	.5	--	1,020	294	0	1,680	8.1	25	--
May 25	11	43	.00	--	54	48	290	750	0	50	208	.8	.1	--	1,100	332	0	1,810	8.2	24	--
June 22	2.6	43	.00	--	36	51	310	748	0	54	215	1.0	.3	--	1,100	300	0	1,770	8.0	26	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

3339. Bethlehem Gut at Colquhoun, St. Croix, V.I.

Location.--Lat 17° 44' 28", long 64° 48' 55", at Colquhoun bridge, Estate Colquhoun, 1 mile west of community of Friedensfeld.

Drainage area.--0.98 sq mi.

Records available.--Discharge: Monthly measurements, 1963-69.

Chemical analyses: 1962-66.

Remarks.--No flow Dec. 20, 1962; Jan. 15, 1963--73 gpm; Feb. 18, 1963--11 gpm; no flow Mar. 26, 1963; Apr. 23, 1963--11 gpm; 21 observations of no flow between Dec. 18, 1963 and Feb. 16, 1965; 5 observations of no flow between June 15, 1965 and Oct. 29, 1965; 35 observations of no flow between Feb. 18, 1966 and Mar. 21, 1969; unmeasured flow May 7, 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
May 28, 1963	40	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	125	--	--	--	--	--	186	--	--	--	25	--
July 26	7.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	26	--
Aug. 28	219	30	0.04	--	85	41	266	496	--	103	315	0.4	0.5	--	--	380	0	1,860	7.9	26	--
Sept. 23	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	185	--	--	--	--	336	--	--	--	27	--
Oct. 16	5.8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--	--	396	--	--	--	25	--
Nov. 27	14	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--	24	--
May 12, 1965	13.5	43	.02	--	90	56	145	448	0	130	188	.4	2.0	--	* 934	455	88	1,450	7.7	26	15
Nov. 30	11	39	.00	--	98	58	99	452	0	101	155	.3	2.9	--	781	483	112	1,270	7.9	23	--
Dec. 21	34	52	.00	--	60	40	102	396	0	52	108	.4	4.1	--	608	314	0	981	8.1	24	--
Jan. 18, 1966	9.4	49	.00	--	52	52	117	484	0	61	132	.2	.9	--	754	394	0	1,200	8.2	23	17

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

3345. Bethlehem Gut at Upper Bethlehem, St. Croix, V.I.

Location.--Lat 17° 42' 34", long 64° 47' 16", about 50 feet downstream of bridge over stream, 1 mile east of terminal building at Alexander Hamilton Airport.

Drainage area.--4.11 sq mi.

Records available.--Discharge: Monthly measurements 1963-69.

Chemical analyses: 1963-65.

Remarks.--No flow Dec. 18 and Jan. 20, 1964; also 10 observations of no flow between May 25, 1964 and Feb. 16, 1965; 11 observations of no flow between June 15, 1965 and Apr. 14, 1966; unmeasured flow May 11, 1966; 31 observations of no flow between June 9, 1966 and June 6, 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Jan. 15, 1963	200	32	0.02	--	96	5.0	397	572	0	84	400	0.6	0.7	--	1,350	260	0	2,250	8.0	24	--
Feb. 18	47	48	.74	--	98	28	414	804	0	13	415	.6	1.2	--	1,560	360	0	2,470	7.6	24	--
Mar. 26	74	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	26	--
Apr. 23	57	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	25	--
May 28	85	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	435	--	--	--	--	780	--	--	--	27	--
July 25	34	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	380	--	--	--	--	372	--	--	--	27	--
Aug. 27	12,450	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	25	--
Aug. 28	4,900	17	.02	--	59	26	--	230	0	--	185	.0	.9	--	--	254	65	1,100	7.5	27	--
Sept. 23	110	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	390	--	--	--	--	410	--	--	--	28	--
Oct. 16	8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	440	--	--	--	--	278	--	--	--	28	--
Nov. 27	18	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	390	--	--	--	--	434	--	--	--	25	--
Feb. 25, 1964	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	400	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	24	--
Mar. 24	14	75	24	--	350	83	17	672	0	18	475	1.0	11	--	* 3,840	1,220	664	3,900	4.8	24	--
Apr. 21	142	56	32	--	274	79	15	356	0	118	438	1.0	9.1	--	* 3,490	1,010	716	3,270	4.7	24	--
May 12, 1965	9.4	48	.54	--	244	60	356	1,270	0	50	375	.7	1.8	--	1,840	856	0	2,830	7.7	27	70

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

3350. River Gut at Alexander Hamilton Airport, St. Croix, V.I.

Location.--Lat 17° 42' 31", long 64° 47' 15", 300 ft upstream of bridge on former airport road, 0.2 mile upstream of eastern end of airport runway.

Drainage area.--6.90 sq mi.

Records available.--Discharge: Monthly measurements 1962-69.

Chemical analyses: 1962-66.

Remarks.--No flow Jan. 20, 1964; also 10 observations of no flow between May 25, 1964 and Jan. 14, 1965; 10 observations of no flow between July 15, 1965 and Apr. 14, 1966; 32 observations of no flow between June 9, 1966 and Mar. 21, 1969; unmeasured flow observed May 7, 1969; no flow on June 6 and July 22, 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color			
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃		
																				Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate	
Nov. 27, 1962	20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	91	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	25	--		
Dec. 20	26	29	0.00	--	70	34	444	772	0	77	390	0.7	0.5	--	--	1,440	314	0	2,460	8.0	24	--
Jan. 15, 1963	525	33	.02	--	75	30	291	572	0	77	278	.6	.6	--	--	*1,120	310	0	1,850	8.0	23	--
Feb. 18	76	40	.42	--	87	26	407	780	0	41	372	.6	.7	--	--	1,360	324	0	2,290	7.8	26	--
Mar. 26	56	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	29	--
Apr. 23	76	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	25	--
May 28	319	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	480	--	--	--	--	--	284	--	--	--	27	--
July 25	61	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	330	--	--	--	--	--	320	--	--	--	27	--
Aug. 28	8,120	20	.06	--	57	31	--	260	0	--	168	.0	2.8	--	--	--	270	57	1,080	8.0	27	--
Sept. 23	342	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	297	--	--	--	--	--	788	--	--	--	28	--
Oct. 16	117	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	--	--	244	--	--	--	28	--
Nov. 26	80	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	280	--	--	--	--	--	218	--	--	--	26	--
Dec. 18	18	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	370	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	26	--
Jan. 20, 1964	0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Feb. 26	47	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	440	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	23	--
Mar. 24	16	82	23	--	334	89	110	760	0	28	550	1.4	10	--	4,020	1,200	577	4,090	4.9	24	--	
Apr. 20	111	61	39	--	324	83	55	624	0	108	450	1.0	12	--	3,920	1,150	638	3,620	4.8	25	--	
May 12, 1965	5.8	45	.02	--	208	54	417	1,150	0	132	400	.6	.1	--	1,790	741	0	2,900	8.0	27	5	
May 11, 1966	54	61	.50	0.01	212	88	629	1,600	0	36	645	.8	2.5	--	2,540	891	0	4,010	7.7	26	70+	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

3360. Envy Spring at Alexander Hamilton Airport, St. Croix, V.I.

Location.--Lat 17° 41' 47", long 64° 48' 04", 2,300 ft south of runway, 5.6 miles southeast of Fort Frederick, Frederiksted.

Drainage area.--Unknown.

Records available.--Discharge: Monthly measurements, 1963-66.

Chemical analyses: 1962-65.

Remarks.--4 observations of no flow between Apr. 20 and June 22, 1964. No flow Mar. 18 and Apr. 14, 1965.

7 observations of no flow between June 16, 1965 and Jan. 19, 1966.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter													Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃		Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)		Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Feb. 19, 1963	41	42	0.00	--	40	24	461	690	0	108	362	0.9	12	--	1,390	198	0	2,310	8.0	26	--	
May 28	16	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	188	--	--	--	--	29	--
July 25	20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--	--	27	--
Aug. 27	40	36	.08	--	36	41	--	658	16	--	360	.6	8.0	--	--	258	0	2,260	8.4	27	--	
Sept. 23	16	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	356	--	--	--	--	238	--	--	--	--	28	--
Oct. 16	20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	142	--	--	--	--	28	--
Nov. 26	7.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	380	--	--	--	--	228	--	--	--	--	24	--
Dec. 18	11	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	360	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	27	--
Jan. 20, 1964	16	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	350	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	--	28	--
Feb. 24	3.2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	340	--	--	--	--	238	--	--	--	--	28	--
Mar. 23	2	39	.04	--	38	38	434	696	0	112	352	1.0	11	--	*1,420	251	0	2,290	7.9	28	--	
July 28	4.5	42	.05	--	42	40	413	688	--	96	350	.7	8.4	--	1,340	270	0	2,250	8.1	31	--	
Aug. 26	15.7	44	.05	--	46	55	546	680	--	132	585	.6	9.2	--	1,830	341	0	3,000	7.9	28	--	
Sept. 24	34.1	40	.00	--	26	32	433	592	22	98	360	1.0	4.5	--	1,370	196	0	2,220	8.4	28	3	
Oct. 20	18	40	.00	--	24	40	414	584	26	94	350	.8	9.9	--	1,320	224	0	2,190	8.4	28	25	
Nov. 18	7.6	46	.00	--	38	40	--	908	--	--	365	1.1	10	--	1,430	260	0	2,350	8.1	28	15	
Dec. 18	7.6	36	.02	--	42	44	431	686	12	106	368	1.1	9.4	--	1,450	286	0	2,350	8.3	24	20	
Jan. 14, 1965	5.8	38	.00	--	42	43	420	704	--	89	368	1.0	5.1	--	1,390	282	0	2,330	8.2	23	10	
Feb. 16	1	37	.00	--	46	60	611	638	16	150	692	1.1	6.3	--	1,960	362	0	3,350	8.3	26	7	
May 13	7.6	39	.02	--	40	38	--	688	--	--	372	1.0	3.2	--	1,420	256	0	2,340	8.1	26	5	

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

3450. Jolly Hill Cut at Jolly Hill, St. Croix, V.I.

Location.--Lat 17° 44' 00", long 64° 51' 47", 0.5 mile north of Fort Frederick, Frederiksted.Drainage area.--2.10 sq mi.Records available.--Discharge: 1963-68, Station discontinued. Monthly measurements, 1962, 69.Chemical analyses: 1962-67.Gage.--Water-stage recorder and U-notch concrete control.Extremes.--Maximums and minimums (discharge in gallons per minute, gage height in feet).

Annual maximum discharges for years 1963-68				Annual minimum discharges 1963-68			
Date	Time	Discharge	Gage height	Date	Time	Discharge	Gage height
Jan. 4, 1963	1000	90,000	3.04	1963	--	(No	--
Jan. 20, 1964	--	8	.44	1964	--	flow	--
Dec. 12, 1965	1600	100,000	3.15	1965	--	many	--
Oct. 14, 1966	0500	13,000	2.40	1966	--	days	--
Nov. 20, 1967	1200	1,000	1.13	1967	--	each	--
1968	--	0	--	1968	--	year.)	--
				1969	--	--	--

1963-1968: Maximum discharge, 100,000 gpm Dec. 12, 1965 (gage height 3.15 ft); minimum, no flow many days each year.

Remarks.--Discharge records poor. No flow during 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Hardness as CaCO ₃						
															Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate	
Dec. 21, 1962	2.5	28	0.00	--	107	27	93	508	0	8.4	108	0.5	0.4	--	* 624	378	0	1,070	7.5	23	4
Feb. 18, 1963	26	28	.00	--	109	15	101	474	0	8.4	110	.3	.1	--	605	334	0	1,000	7.4	25	--
May 29	31	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	115	--	--	--	--	166	--	--	--	24	--
June 20	20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--	--	370	--	--	--	26	--
July 25	18	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	--	354	--	--	--	25	--
Aug. 27	13.5	22	.02	--	89	26	--	372	12	--	100	.1	.1	--	--	329	4	852	8.4	26	--
Sept. 24	11	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	226	--	--	--	--	388	--	--	--	26	--
Oct. 16	9.4	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--	25	--
Nov. 26	14.5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	--	276	--	--	--	23	--
Dec. 18	5.8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	--	404	--	--	--	23	--
Jan. 20, 1964	9.4	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--	--	400	--	--	--	24	--
Feb. 25	3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--	--	394	--	--	--	23	--
Dec. 21, 1965	11.2	22	.00	--	124	39	66	422	--	53	148	.5	3.6	--	679	470	124	1,150	8.1	24	--
Jan. 19, 1966	20.2	26	.00	.00	100	37	61	370	--	28	142	.3	1.7	--	636	402	99	1,040	7.6	23	10
Feb. 23	14.6	26	.00	.00	90	34	64	356	--	20	135	.3	.0	--	582	364	72	979	7.7	24	5
Mar. 17	5.8	28	.00	.00	56	46	47	270	--	22	132	.3	.1	--	505	328	107	848	8.0	--	5
May 11	2	28	.01	.00	115	42	59	470	--	19	129	.4	.1	--	660	460	75	1,090	7.8	26	5
Dec. 7	13.5	24	.02	.00	128	34	74	496	--	31	126	.3	3.5	--	715	460	53	1,170	7.7	--	10
Jan. 4, 1967	4.5	27	.00	.00	116	46	64	472	--	25	145	.3	.2	--	683	478	91	1,160	7.9	23	--
Feb. 8	1.6	26	.00	.00	144	37	76	570	--	18	134	.4	.3	--	777	511	44	1,250	8.0	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

° Estimated.

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1963

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	1	26	26	1	1	50	32	2	16	57	21	8
2	0	21	26	1	1	38	32	21	21	44	16	8
3	580	21	26	2	1	38	26	12	21	32	21	8
4	5,640	26	38	4	0	44	16	4	21	32	21	8
5	102	32	32	2	0	50	16	4	16	26	16	8
6	44	32	26	4	0	50	32	4	26	21	16	8
7	38	32	21	12	0	38	57	8	21	21	16	8
8	38	32	16	1	1	38	50	16	26	26	21	8
9	32	32	16	1	1	38	32	2	16	26	21	8
10	38	32	16	1	1	44	32	2	16	26	12	8
11	38	32	21	1	1	44	32	2	16	21	8	16
12	44	32	26	1	1	38	32	2	16	21	21	21
13	38	32	26	1	1	32	38	8	16	21	12	21
14	26	32	26	1	1	32	21	8	12	32	12	12
15	38	32	12	1	1	21	21	8	16	21	12	8
16	32	32	12	1	1	21	26	8	26	21	12	12
17	32	32	12	2	200	21	26	12	21	12	12	12
18	32	32	12	1	4,000	26	21	12	16	21	8	12
19	26	26	16	1	100	65	21	16	16	12	4	4
20	21	21	12	1	44	16	16	16	16	8	12	4
21	26	21	12	1	38	16	16	12	16	8	16	4
22	16	21	16	1	38	21	8	16	21	8	21	8
23	16	16	16	1	32	32	8	16	16	8	26	12
24	16	16	16	1	38	38	8	12	21	8	26	8
25	21	21	16	1	44	38	2	8	38	4	26	8
26	16	21	16	1	38	32	2	8	38	8	16	8
27	21	26	12	1	38	21	2	44	32	12	16	8
28	16	21	8	1	38	38	4	16	32	12	12	12
29	21	--	4	1	44	32	2	12	44	21	8	12
30	26	--	1	1	50	26	4	16	44	21	8	8
31	32	--	1	--	44	--	2	16	--	21	--	1
Total	7,067	752	536	50	4,798	1,038	637	343	673	632	469	291
Mean	229	26.9	17.9	1.7	155	34.6	20.5	11.1	22.4	20.4	15.6	9.4
Max	5,640	32	38	12	4,000	65	57	44	44	57	26	21
Min	0	16	1	1	0	16	2	2	12	4	4	1
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1963:	Total 17,286	Mean 47.4	Max 5,640	Min 0	Cfsm --	In. --	Ac-ft --					

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1964

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	4											
2	8											
3	8											
4	8											
5	8											
6	4											
7	1											
8	2											
9	4											
10	4											
11	2											
12	2											
13	2											
14	1											
15	1											
16	1											
17	1											
18	1											
19	2											
20	12											
21	12											
22	8											
23	2											
24	1											
25	1											
26	0											
27	0											
28	0											
29	0											
30	0	--										
31	0	--		--		--			--		--	
Total	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	3.2											
Max	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Year 1964:	Total 100	Mean .3	Max 12	Min 0	Cfsm --	In. --	Ac-ft --					

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1965

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	
1					0							0	
2					0							0	
3					0							0	
4					0							0	
5					0							0	
6					0							0	
7					0							0	
8					0							0	
9					0							0	
10					0							0	
11					0							1,520	
12					0							2,560	
13					0							74	
14					0							32	
15					0							16	
16					0							12	
17					0							12	
18					76							12	
19					0							12	
20					1							12	
21					0							16	
22					0							16	
23					0							16	
24					0							21	
25					0							26	
26					0							38	
27					0							26	
28					0							26	
29					0							21	
30		--			0							26	
31		--		--	0	--			--		--	38	
Total	0	0	0	0	77	0	0	0	0	0	0	4,532	
Mean					2.5							146	
Max	0	0	0	0	76	0	0	0	0	0	0	2,560	
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Year 1965:	Total 4,609		Mean 12.6		Max 2,560		Min 0		Cfsm --		In. --		Ac-ft --

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1966

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.		
1	44	44	16	16	26					0	0	0		
2	44	44	16	12	26					0	0	3		
3	44	44	16	12	21					0	0	5		
4	44	44	21	12	16					0	0	2		
5	44	44	21	12	16					0	0	0		
6	44	38	21	8	16					0	0	34		
7	44	38	21	8	19					0	0	19		
8	44	38	16	8	28					0	0	16		
9	44	38	26	8	21					0	0	12		
10	50	32	26	8	16					0	0	25		
11	57	32	26	4	16					0	0	8		
12	65	32	21	8	16					0	0	8		
13	74	44	21	4	16					8	0	4		
14	57	44	21	14	16					2,340	0	2		
15	50	44	26	12	12					0	0	4		
16	44	44	21	8	8					0	0	4		
17	44	44	16	8	4					0	0	2		
18	44	44	16	8	4					0	0	4		
19	44	44	28	23	12					0	0	8		
20	44	44	26	26	4					0	0	4		
21	44	44	21	21	2					0	0	4		
22	44	32	21	16	2					0	218	4		
23	44	26	16	16	1					0	0	4		
24	44	26	16	12	1					0	0	4		
25	44	21	16	12	1					0	0	4		
26	44	21	16	16	1					0	0	4		
27	44	21	16	16	1					0	0	4		
28	44	21	16	21	1					0	0	4		
29	44	--	16	26	0					0	0	4		
30	44	--	16	26	0					0	0	4		
31	44	--	16	--	0	--			--	0	--	4		
Total	1,673	1,032	608	401	323	0	0	0	0	2,348	218	208		
Mean	54.0	36.9	19.6	13.4	10.4					75.7	7.3	6.7		
Max	74	44	28	26	28	0	0	0	0	2,340	218	34		
Min	44	21	16	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Year 1966:	Total	6,811	Mean	18.7	Max	2,340	Min	0	Cfsm	--	In.	--	Ac-ft	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1967

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.		
1	2	1								0	0			
2	2	1								0	0			
3	2	1								0	0			
4	2	1								0	0			
5	2	1								0	0			
6	4	1								0	0			
7	2	1								0	0			
8	2	1								0	0			
9	1	1								0	0			
10	1	1								0	0			
11	1	1								10	0			
12	1	1								0	0			
13	1	1								0	0			
14	1	1								0	0			
15	1	1								0	0			
16	1	9								0	0			
17	2	1								0	0			
18	4	1								0	0			
19	2	1								0	0			
20	1	1								0	54			
21	1	1								0	0			
22	1	1								0	0			
23	1	0								0	0			
24	1	0								0	0			
25	1	0								0	0			
26	1	0								0	0			
27	1	1								0	0			
28	1	1								0	0			
29	1	--								0	0			
30	1	--								0	0			
31	1	--		--		--			--	0	--			
Total	46	32	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	54	0		
Mean	1.5	1.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	.3	1.8			
Max	4	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	54	0		
Min	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Year 1967:	Total 142		Mean .4		Max 54		Min 0		Cfsm --		In. --		Ac-ft --	

3470. Creque Gut above Mt. Washington Reservoir, St. Croix, V.I.

Location.--Lat 17° 44' 58", long 64° 52' 07", 0.1 mile upstream of headwaters of reservoir, 0.2 mile upstream from dam, 2.6 miles north of Ft. Frederick, Frederiksted.

Drainage area.--0.50 sq mi.

Records available.--Discharge: September 1964-October 1968 (discontinued).

Chemical analyses: 1963-68.

Gage.--Water-stage recorder and V-notch weir in concrete control. Altitude of gage is 420 ft (from topographic map).

Extremes.--Maximums and minimums (discharge in gallons per minute, gage height in feet).

Annual maximum discharges for years 1965-67				Annual minimum discharge for years 1965-68			
Date	Time	Discharge	Gage height	Date	Time	Discharge	Gage height
Dec. 11, 1965	1430	69,000	3.77	1965	April & March	No flow (many days)	--
Oct. 14, 1966	0400	41,000	3.30	1966	July 15	0.4	1.00
Oct. 10, 1967	2300	12,000	2.59	1967	June 12-19	No flow	--
				1968	Feb. 14-16	No flow	--

1965-1967: Maximum discharge, 69,000 gpm Dec. 11, 1965 (gage height 3.77 ft); minimum, no flow several days in 1965, 1967-68.

Remarks.--Discharge records poor.

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1964

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1										7	3	3
2										7	3	7
3										6	3	5
4										6	3	4
5										6	3	5
6										4	3	4
7										4	3	2
8										7	3	6
9										6	5	4
10										5	5	4
11										4	5	4
12										4	4	4
13										4	4	4
14										4	5	2
15										4	7	4
16									2	4	3	4
17									3	4	3	4
18									3	11	4	3
19									3	6	4	3
20									1	4	3	3
21									6	4	3	3
22									15	13	2	3
23									13	4	3	3
24									13	4	3	3
25									11	4	7	3
26									9	7	4	3
27									5	6	3	3
28									13	7	5	3
29									13	7	4	3
30		--							11	5	4	3
31		--		--		--			--	4	--	3
Total										172	114	112
Mean										5.5	3.8	3.6
Max										13	7	7
Min										4	2	2
Cfsm									--	--	--	--
In.									--	--	--	--
Ac-ft									--	--	--	--
Year 1964:	Total		Mean		Max	Min	Cfsm	--	In.	--	Ac-ft	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1965

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.		
1	2	2	1	1	3	29	20	11	4	15	11	104		
2	2	2	1	7	4	26	17	9	4	13	11	89		
3	2	2	1	4	4	26	17	11	4	13	11	70		
4	2	2	1	3	1,660	26	17	9	7	11	11	75		
5	2	2	1	2	943	35	17	9	31	11	20	70		
6	2	2	1	2	96	55	17	9	36	13	15	70		
7	2	2	1	1	50	40	17	9	32	15	15	70		
8	2	1	1	1	32	40	17	7	32	13	15	112		
9	2	1	1	1	23	36	17	6	37	11	1,280	89		
10	2	1	1	1	20	36	15	6	20	9	64	116		
11	2	1	1	1	15	36	13	6	26	7	50	2,960		
12	2	3	1	0	13	36	11	6	20	6	1,770	2,060		
13	2	1	1	0	13	36	15	6	15	6	336	600		
14	2	1	1	0	13	36	13	6	13	6	190	440		
15	2	1	1	0	15	32	21	6	13	6	140	400		
16	2	1	1	1	23	29	15	6	13	6	140	385		
17	3	1	1	1	15	32	15	6	13	106	160	370		
18	3	1	0	1	2,510	32	13	6	11	15	160	370		
19	4	1	0	2	204	29	13	6	13	13	160	355		
20	4	1	1	4	284	29	11	6	23	26	160	385		
21	4	1	0	4	170	26	11	10	15	15	160	340		
22	6	1	4	9	84	26	9	9	13	17	160	325		
23	4	1	1	6	50	23	7	9	13	15	180	280		
24	4	1	1	5	57	23	7	7	13	13	170	280		
25	4	1	1	4	50	23	6	6	15	13	400	280		
26	5	1	1	5	40	23	9	6	13	13	333	350		
27	4	1	1	6	36	23	9	5	15	17	112	250		
28	4	1	2	3	36	23	13	7	15	13	96	250		
29	4	--	1	3	32	20	11	6	15	11	96	220		
30	4	--	1	3	29	20	13	5	15	11	93	184		
31	3	--	1	--	29	--	9	5	--	11	--	205		
Total	92	37	32	81	6,553	906	415	233	509	470	6,519	12,154		
Mean	3.0	1.3	1.0	2.7	211	30.2	13.4	7.5	17.0	15.2	217	76.7		
Max	6	3	4	9	2,510	55	21	11	37	106	1,770	2,960		
Min	2	1	0	0	3	20	6	5	4	6	11	70		
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Year 1965:	Total 28,001		Mean 76.7		Max 2,960		Min 0		Cfsm --		In. --		Ac-ft --	

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1966

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.		
1	180	150	60	36	23	15	6	5	3	6	7	13		
2	190	140	60	36	23	15	6	5	3	6	7	13		
3	180	140	60	36	23	13	7	5	3	6	7	13		
4	170	120	70	36	17	15	6	5	5	9	7	11		
5	170	112	60	32	17	15	5	5	6	9	6	9		
6	180	150	70	32	17	13	10	5	5	9	9	44		
7	170	160	60	32	17	13	9	5	10	9	7	17		
8	160	150	60	32	20	13	6	5	6	6	6	17		
9	160	120	55	29	20	15	5	5	5	5	8	15		
10	170	89	55	29	17	20	5	5	6	6	6	15		
11	150	89	55	26	17	15	5	5	17	5	6	15		
12	321	96	50	26	20	15	5	4	6	5	6	13		
13	907	89	55	26	17	20	6	4	6	115	6	11		
14	295	89	55	31	17	20	2	6	6	1,030	6	11		
15	235	89	60	29	15	15	1	5	6	15	5	11		
16	235	96	55	29	17	13	2	5	7	13	5	9		
17	220	96	55	29	17	13	2	4	6	15	6	11		
18	220	104	55	26	15	13	3	5	6	13	6	11		
19	220	82	85	66	17	13	4	7	6	11	7	11		
20	220	75	65	104	15	11	4	6	7	13	6	9		
21	220	75	55	29	20	9	6	6	6	11	6	9		
22	205	70	50	23	17	7	6	7	6	11	135	9		
23	180	70	45	26	17	7	6	5	6	11	11	9		
24	180	75	45	26	17	7	6	5	6	11	11	9		
25	180	65	45	23	20	7	6	6	6	9	11	9		
26	170	75	45	23	17	6	6	11	6	7	9	7		
27	170	70	40	23	20	7	5	13	6	7	9	7		
28	180	60	40	26	17	6	5	17	6	7	9	7		
29	223	--	36	23	15	13	6	6	6	9	214	7		
30	160	--	36	20	15	9	6	5	6	7	17	6		
31	160	--	36	--	15	--	6	5	--	7	--	7		
Total	6,781	2,796	1,673	964	551	373	163	187	185	1,403	531	365		
Mean	219	99.9	54.0	32.1	17.8	12.4	5.3	6.0	6.2	45.3	17.7	11.8		
Max	907	160	85	104	23	20	10	17	17	1,030	214	44		
Min	150	60	36	20	15	6	1	4	3	5	5	6		
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Year 1966:	Total	15,972	Mean	43.8	Max	1,030	Min	1	Cfsm	--	In.	--	Ac-ft	--

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1967

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	
1	7	5	5	5	2	1	3	1	1	2	1	2	
2	7	5	5	9	2	1	3	1	1	2	2	2	
3	7	5	5	6	2	1	2	2	1	3	2	2	
4	6	5	7	2	1	1	3	2	1	2	2	1	
5	6	5	5	2	1	1	2	8	1	2	2	2	
6	6	5	5	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	
7	5	5	5	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	5	1	
8	6	4	5	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	
9	5	4	5	2	1	1	5	2	2	1	2	2	
10	5	4	5	2	1	1	3	2	2	277	3	1	
11	6	4	5	2	1	1	2	1	4	89	2	1	
12	5	4	5	2	1	0	1	1	2	2	4	2	
13	5	4	7	2	1	0	1	1	2	2	2	2	
14	5	4	7	2	1	0	1	2	1	2	2	3	
15	4	5	6	2	1	0	1	2	1	2	2	5	
16	5	7	5	2	1	0	1	2	1	3	2	4	
17	5	5	5	2	1	0	1	1	1	2	2	3	
18	4	5	5	2	1	0	1	5	1	2	2	2	
19	4	5	5	2	1	0	1	1	2	2	1	2	
20	4	4	7	2	1	4	1	1	2	2	1	2	
21	4	4	7	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	
22	5	4	5	2	1	3	1	3	2	2	1	2	
23	5	4	4	2	1	3	1	2	2	2	1	2	
24	5	4	4	2	1	3	1	1	2	2	1	2	
25	4	4	4	2	1	5	1	1	2	2	1	2	
26	5	10	6	2	1	5	2	1	2	2	1	2	
27	5	6	5	1	1	4	2	1	2	1	1	2	
28	5	5	4	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	2	
29	5	--	4	4	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	
30	5	--	5	2	1	3	1	1	3	1	1	2	
31	6	--	5	--	1	--	1	1	--	1	--	2	
Total	161	135	162	74	34	49	50	51	50	420	53	64	
Mean	5.2	4.8	5.2	2.5	1.1	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.7	13.5	1.8	2.1	
Max	7	10	7	9	2	5	5	8	4	277	5	5	
Min	4	4	4	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
Year 1967 :	Total 1,303		Mean 3.6		Max 277		Min 0		Cfsm --		In. --		Ac-ft --

Discharge in thousand gallons per day, calendar year 1968

Day	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1	2	3	0	2	2	1	2	2	1	8		
2	2	2	0	6	1	1	2	5	1	8		
3	2	2	1	3	1	1	2	4	1	5		
4	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	5	1	5		
5	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	5	1	5		
6	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	5	1	5		
7	2	1	0	1	1	1	2	15	1	8		
8	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	15	1	5		
9	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	8	5	5		
10	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	8	3	5		
11	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	5	1	5		
12	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	5	1	5		
13	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	5	1	3		
14	2	0	1	3	1	2	1	3	1	3		
15	2	0	1	2	1	2	1	3	1	3		
16	1	0	2	1	1	2	1	3	1	3		
17	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	3	1	3		
18	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	24	1	3		
19	2	1	2	3	1	1	1	3	1	3		
20	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	3	1	23		
21	2	1	2	2	1	2	3	3	88	5		
22	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	3	8	5		
23	13	1	1	2	1	2	2	3	3	5		
24	3	1	1	2	2	2	2	3	3	5		
25	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	3	3	3		
26	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	3	3		
27	3	4	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	3		
28	3	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	3		
29	3	1	2	6	1	2	1	1	22	3		
30	3	--	5	2	1	2	1	1	8	3		
31	2	--	2	--	1	--	1	1	--	3		
Total	78	36	41	59	35	44	48	150	166	154		
Mean	2.5	1.2	1.3	2.0	1.1	1.5	1.5	4.8	5.5	5.0		
Max	13	4	5	6	2	2	3	24	88	23		
Min	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	3		
Cfsm	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
In.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Ac-ft	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
Year 1968 :	Total		Mean	Max	Min	Cfsm	In.	Ac-ft				

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Color	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Jan. 15, 1963	--	21	.00	--	61	8.0	62	284	--	8.0	55	0.4	0.2	--	* 354	185	0	623	7.8	24	--
Feb. 18	--	26	.00	--	82	11	82	398	--	1.2	71	.4	.4	--	470	250	0	797	8.0	24	--
Feb. 19	--	26	.00	--	96	54	18	452	--	1.2	91	.5	.1	--	* 510	462	91	936	8.0	24	--
May 29	400	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	95	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--	24	--
June 20	28	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--	--	285	--	--	--	25	--
July 25	7.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--	25	--
Aug. 27	40	17	.02	--	69	31	--	318	--	--	82	.1	.1	--	300	47	733	8.1	24	--	
Sept. 24	25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	362	--	--	--	310	--	--	--	--	25	--
Oct. 16	26	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--	122	--	--	--	--	24	--
Nov. 26	28	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--	152	--	--	--	--	23	--
Dec. 18	9.4	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	232	--	--	--	--	23	--
Jan. 20, 1964	4.5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	354	--	--	--	--	23	--
Feb. 25	3.2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	376	--	--	--	--	23	--
Mar. 23	.8	26	.00	--	100	31	91	514	--	8.4	102	.4	.1	--	* 652	377	0	1,070	8.1	24	--
Apr. 20	.8	25	.00	--	102	28	99	500	--	20	108	.6	.1	--	* 647	370	0	1,060	7.9	25	--
May 25	.8	28	.00	--	100	27	84	474	--	11	100	.7	.1	--	* 595	360	0	1,020	8.0	23	--
Sept. 24	--	24	.00	--	94	22	112	356	35	25	135	.6	.0	--	* 648	325	0	1,070	8.6	25	20
Oct. 20	7.5	25	.00	--	98	26	94	472	--	14	108	.6	.0	--	* 612	352	0	1,040	8.1	24	50
Nov. 16	2.1	29	.00	--	100	27	133	604	--	12	100	.7	.1	--	* 615	360	0	1,010	7.9	23	15
Dec. 18	4.9	24	.00	--	104	28	91	488	--	15	110	.7	.5	--	* 639	375	0	1,060	8.2	23	10
Jan. 15, 1965	.84	26	.02	--	100	28	95	492	--	13	108	.6	.4	--	613	364	0	1,060	8.0	22	10
Feb. 16	--	24	.00	--	104	23	108	508	--	11	112	.7	.5	--	* 633	354	0	1,080	8.2	23	7
Mar. 18	.29	22	.00	--	96	24	103	486	--	2.4	112	.7	.7	--	* 584	338	0	1,080	8.2	23	5
Apr. 14	2	24	.02	--	96	24	135	466	--	15	165	.8	.1	--	690	338	0	1,150	8.1	22	0
May 12	10	26	.00	--	140	37	133	508	--	97	192	.6	1.3	--	* 921	502	85	1,470	7.9	24	5
June 16	--	24	.00	--	116	32	95	484	--	34	138	.6	.1	--	678	421	24	1,150	8.0	26	5
July 15	8	27	.00	--	126	31	103	544	--	23	138	.6	.0	--	* 714	442	0	1,220	8.0	--	3
Aug. 17	--	28	.00	--	40	30	101	288	4	17	128	.5	.3	--	* 505	224	0	885	8.3	25	7
Sept. 27	1.1	25	.02	--	116	31	95	522	--	18	125	.6	.1	--	* 678	417	0	1,180	7.4	25	30
Oct. 29	8.6	25	.00	--	108	31	98	516	--	17	120	.6	.0	--	* 652	397	0	1,130	8.0	24	5
Nov. 30	54	25	.00	--	88	27	65	396	--	16	92	.6	.0	--	509	330	5	885	7.9	23	--
Dec. 21	e 333	25	.01	.001	76	35	41	344	--	11	90	.5	.1	--	* 471	334	52	816	7.9	24	5
Jan. 19, 1966	111	23	.00	.00	70	24	66	348	--	9.6	86	.5	.1	--	* 482	273	0	787	7.7	22	10
Mar. 16	34	26	.00	.00	54	35	69	316	--	12	110	.6	.0	--	* 463	278	19	816	7.9	--	5
Apr. 13	20	27	.00	.00	60	38	66	336	--	10	115	.5	.1	--	* 478	306	30	864	7.9	32	5
May 11	13	27	.01	.00	64	38	68	358	--	9.2	112	.6	.1	--	* 505	316	22	888	7.9	24	5
June 9	--	29	.00	.00	95	39	81	480	4	10	115	.5	.7	--	* 642	398	0	1,070	8.3	24	10
July 13	3.0	28	.00	.00	118	27	94	522	--	12	119	.5	.1	--	* 684	406	0	1,140	7.9	25	10
Aug. 12	2.0	28	.00	.00	102	33	117	510	--	50	122	.5	.1	--	* 643	390	0	1,110	7.9	--	15
Sept. 13	3.0	27	.00	.00	132	39	125	502	--	98	175	.5	.0	--	* 802	490	78	1,360	7.9	--	5
Nov. 9	4.8	26	.00	.00	116	30	99	528	--	18	125	.5	.2	--	* 670	413	0	1,180	7.8	24	10
Dec. 7	12.5	25	.01	.00	104	32	93	512	--	16	111	.4	.4	--	* 640	391	0	1,110	7.8	--	10
Jan. 4, 1967	3.4	28	.02	.00	118	34	94	542	--	18	125	.4	.1	--	* 685	434	0	1,170	8.1	23	--
Feb. 8	1.6	27	.00	.00	114	29	98	528	--	16	118	.5	.4	--	* 679	404	0	1,160	7.9	--	--
Mar. 10	2.3	26	.00	.00	118	12	124	526	--	15	118	.5	.3	--	* 663	344	0	1,148	8.0	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

e Estimated.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃						
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate	
Apr. 4, 1967	1.6	28	0.03	0.00	114	43	71	512	--	18	125	0.5	0.3	--	* 653	462	0	1,140	7.9	23	--	
May 9	1.2	28	.00	.00	108	26	104	516	--	14	115	.5	.4	--	* 658	376	0	1,120	7.9	24	--	
June 7	.38	28	.00	.00	112	33	88	512	--	17	118	.5	1.9	--	* 647	415	0	1,110	7.9	26	--	
July 11	0	27	.04	--	108	29	99	508	--	16	120	.6	.6	--	* 635	388	0	1,120	7.9	25	--	
Aug. 8	--	28	.00	.00	130	38	140	486	--	46	240	.4	.3	--	* 874	480	82	1,500	7.7	24	--	
Sept. 12	--	26	.00	.00	96	29	113	458	--	23	145	.2	.2	--	* 639	358	0	1,140	7.9	--	--	
Oct. 10	.51	28	.00	.00	106	38	77	490	4	16	115	.6	.1	--	* 647	415	0	1,110	8.3	26	--	
Nov. 9	1.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Jan. 12, 1968	--	28	.00	.00	84	23	111	2.3	450	--	15	122	.7	.0	0.2	* 608	305	0	1,050	8.1	--	--
Jan. 18	.6	28	.00	.00	84	29	115	2.4	470	--	15	120	.8	.0	.2	626	330	0	1,080	8.1	--	--
Feb. 13	2.6	27	.02	.00	104	24	108	2.3	500	--	16	122	.8	.0	.2	650	360	0	1,110	8.2	--	--
Mar. 14	--	34	--	.00	41	24	107	2.7	330	--	6.0	118	.4	.2	.0	495	200	0	862	8.0	--	--
Apr. 11	--	26	.00	--	106	27	120	5.0	532	--	9.6	135	.9	.4	.7	693	375	0	1,180	8.2	--	--
May 9	--	30	.00	.00	104	24	115	3.7	522	--	14	122	.9	.1	.6	* 684	360	0	1,140	8.2	--	--
June 5	--	3.7	--	.00	4.6	5.4	105	2.8	26	45	11	115	.4	.3	.0	365	34	0	607	9.9	--	--
Aug. 8	--	28	--	.00	114	28	158	5.1	438	6	56	235	.6	2.0	.4	849	400	31	1,450	8.3	--	--
Sept. 5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

* Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

GROUND-WATER STATIONS

Well 1 (45-64.46-2-50)

Owner.--V.I. Government.

Name.--Concordia-7.

Location.--Lat 17° 45' 32", long 64° 46' 03".

Description.--Drilled water-table production well, diam 6-in, cased 0-81.

Depth.--81 ft.

Aquifer.--Limestone of Tertiary age.

Measuring point.--Hole in pump base, 2.5 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--29 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--1.75 ft below lsd, May 11, 1966.

Lowest water level.--57.40 ft below lsd, Mar. 5, 1964.

Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1964-67.

Water levels: 1962-68.

Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, October 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃						
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate	
Oct. 5, 1964	--	34	0.00	--	104	74	328	420	--	122	570	0.5	0.5	--	*1,440	564	220	2,600	7.9	--	--	
May 13, 1965	--	30	.00	--	58	48	264	534	--	104	260	.7	3.1	--	*1,030	342	0	1,750	8.1	27	--	
July 16	--	29	.00	--	64	50	250	538	--	88	262	.6	7.5	--	*1,050	365	0	1,760	8.0	27	--	
Feb. 15, 1967	--	34	.00	--	68	60	256	536	--	108	288	.3	16	--	*1,120	416	0	1,900	7.8	27	--	
Oct. 13	--	30	.00	0.00	56	61	240	528	--	98	260	.7	12	--	*1,040	390	0	1,780	8.1	--	--	
Nov. 9	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

*Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
June 12, 1962	a 25.17	Feb. 4, 1963	a 18.72	Jan. 23, 1964	a 43.14	Nov. 29, 1965	a 46.71
July 2	a 25.16	Feb. 11	a 18.70	Feb. 4	a 43.92	Dec. 21	a 46.00
July 10	a 22.65	Feb. 18	a 18.60	Feb. 13	a 36.50	Jan. 18, 1966	a 41.60
July 19	a 24.70	Feb. 25	a 18.47	Feb. 18	a 45.12	Feb. 23	a 41.92
July 26	a 22.65	Feb. 28	a 18.40	Mar. 5	a 57.40	Mar. 16	a 42.54
Aug. 1	a 17.74	Mar. 4	a 15.68	Mar. 20	a 47.40	Apr. 14	8.43
Aug. 7	a 27.62	Mar. 11	a 17.00	Apr. 1	a 45.20	May 11	1.75
Aug. 16	a 27.64	Mar. 20	a 42.10	Apr. 9	a 47.50	July 13	a 28.00
Aug. 24	a 27.89	Mar. 27	a 42.21	Apr. 23	a 45.70	Aug. 12	a 49.20
Aug. 29	a 28.00	Apr. 3	a 42.46	Apr. 27	a 44.40	Sept. 13	a 50.15
Sept. 6	a 30.10	Apr. 22	a 39.25	May 6	a 46.40	Oct. 11	a 50.42
Sept. 14	a 28.97	Apr. 29	a 44.11	May 13	8.50	Nov. 9	a 48.40
Sept. 21	a 28.50	May 15	a 43.60	May 19	a 45.90	Dec. 7	a 44.50
Sept. 25	a 29.32	May 21	a 43.40	May 25	a 47.80	Jan. 4, 1967	a 43.75
Oct. 10	a 28.80	June 10	a 40.50	June 1	a 49.00	Feb. 7	a 43.47
Oct. 24	a 28.10	June 19	a 42.70	June 15	8.50	Feb. 15	a 44.58
Oct. 30	a 29.50	June 25	a 42.47	July 13	a 52.50	Mar. 9	a 43.40
Nov. 8	a 27.25	July 3	a 41.00	July 24	a 49.90	Apr. 4	a 43.24
Nov. 13	a 25.77	July 15	a 42.01	Aug. 12	a 47.50	May 9	a 42.04
Nov. 20	a 26.50	July 23	a 43.50	Aug. 21	a 52.90	June 7	a 40.70
Nov. 27	a 26.18	July 31	a 41.10	Sept. 9	a 50.50	July 11	a 39.64
Dec. 6	a 26.18	Aug. 7	a 39.80	Oct. 5	a 12.40	Aug. 8	a 40.40
Dec. 13	a 26.50	Aug. 21	a 40.90	Feb. 3, 1965	a 55.40	Sept. 12	a 43.68
Dec. 21	a 26.80	Sept. 5	a 37.10	May 13	a 47.84	Oct. 13	a 40.89
Dec. 28	a 27.33	Sept. 12	a 37.40	July 16	a 46.56	Nov. 9	a 41.48
Jan. 11, 1963	a 21.58	Sept. 18	a 37.50	Aug. 18	a 47.23	Dec. 13	a 43.30
Jan. 22	a 18.35	Oct. 3	a 37.90	Sept. 28	a 45.99	Oct. 3, 1968	a 38.30
Jan. 31	a 17.65	Jan. 7, 1964	a 43.45	Oct. 29	a 47.84		

a - Pumping.

Well 2 (44-64.44-6-27)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.Name.--Estate Thomas, USGS-39.Location.--Lat 17° 44' 48", long 64° 44' 20".Description.--Drilled water-table production well,
diam 4--in, cased 0--250, perforated 210-250 ft.Depth.--390 ft; plugged back to 250 ft.Aquifer.--Marl and limestone of Tertiary age.Measuring point.--Top of casing, 1.40 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--300 ft above msl.Highest water level.--121.23 ft below lsd, Nov. 7, 1968.Lowest water level.--202.60 ft below lsd, July 10, 1968.Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1966-67.Water levels: 1966-69.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃				
																Calcium, magnesium				Non-carbonate
Aug. 23, 1966	--	32	0.00	0.00	360	146	1,240	408	0	732	2,200	0.6	1.0	--	4,910	1,500	1,140	7,830	7.4	--
July 12, 1967	--	29	.06	.04	326	143	1,050	476	0	632	1,880	.5	.0	--	4,290	1,400	1,010	6,300	7.6	--
Nov. 17, 1969	--	35	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1,850	--	--	--	--	--	--	6,950	--	28

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 11, 1966	197.36	June 8, 1967	^a 198.33	Apr. 11, 1968	200.7	Jan. 7, 1969	201.28
Nov. 10	197.50	Aug. 15	200.35	Mar. 9	200.9	Feb. 6	201.50
Dec. 7	197.74	Sept. 12	^a 199.07	June 5	201.25	June 6	200.38
Jan. 4, 1967	197.90	Oct. 13	^a 199.10	July 10	202.60	July 22	201.65
Feb. 7	198.22	Dec. 11	199.23	Aug. 7	200.60	Sept. 23	187.40
Mar. 9	198.60	Jan. 11, 1968	199.40	Sept. 3	200.60	Nov. 17	201.68
Apr. 5	198.74	Feb. 13	199.60	Nov. 7	121.23	Dec. 15	186.28
May 8	199.00	Mar. 14	200.6	Dec. 5	201.29		

a - Pumping.

Well 3 (44-64.44-4-86)

Owner.--U.S. Government.Name.--NPS-1 (Sion Farm).Location.--Lat 17° 44' 07", long 64° 44' 26".Description.--Drilled water-table production well, diam 6-in, cased 0-248, perforated 208-248 ft.Depth.--248 ft.Aquifer.--Marl of Tertiary age.Measuring point.--Hole in casing cover, 0.9 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--240 ft above msl.Highest water level.--191.91 ft below lsd, Oct. 16, 1969.Lowest water level.--232.45 ft below lsd, June 5, 1968.Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1963-68.Water levels: 1965-69.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
June 23, 1963	--	24	0.00	--	20	11	512	590	0	102	435	0.5	5.3	--	--	*1,430	95	0	2,450	7.8	--	--
June 21, 1965	--	22	.00	--	20	7.3	512	594	8	118	398	.5	9.6	--	--	*1,390	80	0	2,290	8.3	--	--
Dec. 7, 1966	--	23	.03	--	20	12	480	609	0	76	396	.6	11	--	--	*1,380	100	0	2,320	7.7	--	--
Mar. 6, 1968	--	24	.00	0.00	22	6.1	496	596	10	85	400	.5	2.5	--	--	1,340	80	0	2,340	8.3	26	--
Oct. 16, 1969	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	410	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,380	--	27	--
Nov. 24	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	408	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,360	--	27	--
Dec. 15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	405	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2,360	--	29	--

*Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 21, 1965	216.1	Feb. 7, 1967	219.45	Jan. 11, 1968	216.9	Dec. 5, 1968	^a 219.10
May 11, 1966	218.51	Mar. 9	216.50	Feb. 13	224.0	Jan. 7, 1969	218.56
July 14	218.30	Apr. 5	225.98	Mar. 14	225.7	Feb. 6	216.33
Aug. 12	216.30	May 8	217.05	Apr. 11	218.5	June 6	214.12
Sept. 14	219.90	July 11	^e 210.00	May 9	220.0	July 22	220.21
Oct. 11	218.74	Aug. 15	218.33	June 5	232.45	Oct. 16	191.91
Nov. 10	217.00	Sept. 12	216.89	July 10	232.25	Nov. 24	201.03
Dec. 7	216.60	Oct. 13	^a 221.50	Aug. 7	221.90	Dec. 15	215.32
Jan. 4, 1967	217.40	Dec. 11	220.52	Nov. 7	217.93		

a - Pumping.
e - Estimated.

Well 4 (43-64.44-14-32)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.Name.--USGS--46 (Castle Coakley).Location.--Lat 17° 43' 39", long 64° 44' 51".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, diam 6-in, cased 0-154, slotted 94-154 ft.Depth.--154 ft.Aquifer.--Marl and limestone of Tertiary age.Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 3.07 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--97 ft above msl.Highest water level.--86.70 ft below lsd, Dec. 25, 1969.Lowest water level.--90.11 ft below lsd, May 10, 1969.Records available.--Water levels: 1969.Remarks.--Recorder.

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1969												
5	89.95	89.81	89.83	89.99	--	87.34	87.35	87.40	88.11	88.10	87.79	86.82
10	89.88	89.78	89.86	90.00	90.11	87.20	--	87.45	88.20	88.12	--	86.80
15	89.76	89.78	--	90.01	90.00	87.20	--	87.48	88.23	88.12	--	86.78
20	89.74	89.80	--	90.09	89.71	87.26	--	87.99	88.28	88.00	--	86.76
25	89.76	89.81	89.96	--	89.08	87.29	87.33	88.03	88.18	87.95	--	86.70
eom	89.77	89.79	89.98	--	88.59	87.34	87.36	88.09	88.16	87.90	86.83	--

Well 5 (43-64.45-16-15)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.Name.--USGS--43 (Estate Strawberry).Location.--Lat 17° 43' 52", long 64° 45' 31".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, diam 4-in, cased 0-200, perforated 110-200 ft.Depth.--200 ft.Aquifer.--Marl of Tertiary age.Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 3.00 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--117 ft above msl.Highest water level.--96.02 ft below lsd, Jan. 15, 1968.Lowest water level.--97.37 ft below lsd, Sept. 5, 1968.Records available.--Chemical analysis: June 8, 1967.Water levels: January to September 1968.Remarks.--Well destroyed.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium	Non-carbonate
June 8, 1967	--	30	0.01	--	290	126	973	486	--	572	1,680	0.4	1.2	--	3,910	1,240	844	5,940	7.5	--	--	--

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1968												
5	--	96.19	96.34	96.52	96.65	96.85	96.99	97.17	97.37	--	--	--
10	--	96.21	96.34	96.53	96.65	96.85	97.10	97.18	--	--	--	--
15	96.02	96.26	96.41	96.53	96.71	96.87	97.09	97.18	--	--	--	--
20	96.17	96.24	96.42	96.54	96.70	96.90	97.05	97.18	--	--	--	--
25	96.11	96.28	96.42	96.59	96.75	96.94	97.11	97.21	--	--	--	--
eom	96.20	96.33	96.48	96.58	96.78	96.96	97.14	97.30	--	--	--	--

Well 6 (43-64.45-15-15)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-41 (Estate Strawberry).
Location.--Lat 17° 43' 50", long 64° 45' 32".
Description.--Drilled water-table production well, diam
 4-in, cased 0-340, perforated 120-340 ft.
Depth.--340 ft.
Aquifer.--Limey sediments of Tertiary and Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of casing, 1.25 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--115 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--63.50 ft above lsd, Oct. 11, 1966.
Lowest water level.--68.75 ft above lsd, Dec. 5, 1968.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: Sept. 8, 1968.
Water levels: 1966-69.
Remarks.--Well destroyed.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Milligrams per liter														Hardness as CaCO ₃	Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote			
	Discharge (gpm)	Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)						Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Sept. 8, 1968	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	820	--	--	--	--	416	--	--	--	--	--	

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 11, 1966	63.50	May 8	64.71	Jan. 18, 1968	66.02	Aug. 7, 1968	67.45
Nov. 10	64.12	June 7	65.30	Feb. 13	66.09	Sept. 5	67.70
Dec. 7	63.83	July 11	65.23	Mar. 14	66.25	Oct. 3	65.15
Jan. 4, 1967	64.10	Aug. 8	65.17	Apr. 11	66.40	Nov. 7	64.30
Feb. 7	64.32	Sept. 12	65.85	May 9	66.57	Dec. 5	68.75
Mar. 9	64.42	Oct. 13	65.42	June 5	66.87	Jan. 7, 1969	67.08
Apr. 5	64.54	Dec. 13	65.90	July 10	66.94		

Well 7 (43-64.46-10-40)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-40 (Estate Barren Spot).
Location.--Lat 17° 43' 38", long 64° 46' 05".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, diam
 4-in, cased 0-220, perforated 80-220 ft.
Depth.--240 ft.
Aquifer.--Marl of Tertiary and Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of 4-in casing, 1.95 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--90 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--64.96 ft below lsd, Mar. 9, 1967.
Lowest water level.--76.07 ft below lsd, Aug. 7, 1968.
Records available.--Water levels: 1966-69.
Remarks.--Measurement temporarily discontinued.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 11, 1966	73.05	June 7, 1967	66.38	May 9, 1968	74.50	Dec. 5, 1968	74.16
Nov. 10	73.35	July 11	73.58	June 5	74.78	Jan. 7, 1969	74.05
Dec. 7	71.92	Aug. 8	73.52	July 10	74.11	Feb. 6	74.55
Jan. 4, 1967	72.46	Sept. 11	73.59	Aug. 7	76.07	June 6	74.25
Feb. 7	70.82	Feb. 13, 1968	74.60	Sept. 5	74.92		
Mar. 9	64.96	Mar. 14	74.32	Oct. 3	74.80		
May 8	73.95	Apr. 11	74.43	Nov. 7	74.17		

Well 8 (43-64.45-4-74)

Owner.--V.I. Government.
Name.--Barren Spot-7.
Location.--Lat 17° 43' 16", long 64° 45' 38".
Description.--Drilled water-table production well, diam
 6-in, cased 0-115, perforated 55-115 ft, open hole
 115-140 ft.
Depth.--140 ft.
Aquifer.--Limey sediments of Tertiary and Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--2.5 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--60 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--50.10 ft below lsd, Oct. 22, 1962.
Lowest water level.--63.65 ft below lsd, Nov. 14, 1967.
Records available.--Chemical analyses: 1965-67.
Water levels: 1962-68.
Remarks.--Continuous recorder used from November 1962 to
 October 1964.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote			
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)					Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
July 21, 1965	--	24	0.00	--	36	22	697	542	0	216	722	0.9	8.3	--	2,030	180	0	3,450	8.1	27	--	
Feb. 15, 1967	--	34	.00	--	68	60	256	536	0	108	288	.3	16	--	1,120	416	0	1,900	7.8	27	--	
July 12	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	660	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--	--	--	--
Aug. 8	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	660	--	--	--	--	164	--	--	--	--	--	--
Sept. 11	--	25	.00	0.00	42	21	672	586	0	172	700	.8	4.8	--	1,930	192	0	3,280	8.0	--	--	
Oct. 13	--	22	.00	.00	38	28	655	592	0	170	680	1.1	13	--	1,930	210	0	3,310	8.0	--	--	
Nov. 14	--	27	.00	.00	41	29	669	646	0	165	680	1.0	14	--	1,940	220	0	3,320	8.1	27	--	
Dec. 12	--	27	.01	.00	44	60	600	654	0	165	665	1.0	13	--	1,930	355	0	3,310	8.2	27	--	

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
June 4, 1962	52.12	July 30, 1962	51.94	Sept. 11, 1962	51.90	Oct. 29, 1962	52.25
June 12	51.93	Aug. 6	51.97	Sept. 17	51.84	Nov. 7	51.80
June 29	51.90	Aug. 13	51.95	Sept. 24	51.50	Nov. 14	51.80
July 9	51.08	Aug. 22	51.85	Oct. 3	51.80	Nov. 19	51.70
July 16	52.03	Aug. 27	51.90	Oct. 9	51.34		
July 23	52.03	Sept. 4	51.95	Oct. 22	50.10		

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1962												
5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52.82
10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52.78
15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52.76
20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52.77
25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52.84
eom	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52.83	52.85
1963												
5	52.77	52.83	52.96	52.89	52.90	52.87	--	52.75	52.57	52.55	52.57	52.75
10	52.77	52.86	52.94	52.86	52.90	52.89	52.80	52.71	--	52.54	52.59	52.76
15	52.77	52.88	52.92	52.88	52.88	52.87	52.71	52.68	--	52.53	52.59	52.79
20	52.82	52.91	52.92	52.91	52.81	52.83	--	52.67	--	52.55	52.63	52.80
25	52.88	52.93	--	52.95	52.85	52.84	--	52.64	52.62	52.57	52.66	52.77
eom	52.82	52.94	52.89	52.92	52.84	--	52.77	52.59	52.58	52.55	52.71	52.73
1964												
5	52.72	52.72	52.80	52.85	--	52.90	52.68	52.61	52.68	52.62	--	--
10	52.70	52.74	52.83	52.83	--	52.87	52.66	52.63	52.65	52.61	--	--
15	52.69	52.74	52.86	--	--	52.79	52.65	52.64	52.69	--	--	--
20	52.67	52.72	52.85	--	--	52.77	52.66	52.68	52.64	--	--	--
25	52.64	--	52.83	--	52.88	52.81	--	52.65	52.57	--	--	--
eom	52.71	52.79	52.84	--	52.90	52.77	--	52.70	--	--	--	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 13, 1964	52.35	Apr. 27, 1965	54.50	Apr. 14, 1966	^a 55.16	May 8, 1967	^a 54.33
Oct. 20	52.90	June 21	52.90	May 11	^a 55.08	June 7	^a 54.17
Oct. 27	^a 57.10	June 17	^a 55.10	July 13	^a 59.80	July 12	^a 52.10
Nov. 4	^a 56.50	July 21	^a 55.70	Aug. 12	^a 59.90	Aug. 8	^a 59.80
Nov. 13	52.70	Aug. 18	^a 55.13	Sept. 8	^a 54.80	Sept. 11	^a 60.03
Nov. 17	^a 54.90	Sept. 28	^a 54.95	Oct. 11	^a 54.70	Oct. 13	^a 60.50
Dec. 2	53.05	Oct. 28	^a 54.98	Nov. 10	59.16	Nov. 14	^a 63.65
Dec. 8	^a 55.50	Nov. 29	^a 54.72	Dec. 7	^a 54.68	Dec. 12	59.53
Jan. 4, 1965	^a 55.90	Dec. 20	^a 54.90	Jan. 4, 1967	^a 54.42	Oct. 3, 1968	53.08
Jan. 12	^a 56.15	Jan. 18, 1966	^a 54.84	Feb. 7	^a 54.55		
Mar. 29	50.70	Feb. 23	^a 55.23	Mar. 9	^a 54.53		
Apr. 15	54.83	Mar. 16	^a 54.92	Apr. 5	^a 54.17		

^a - Pumping.

Well 9 (43-64.45-7-94)

Owner.--V.I. Government.
Name.--Barren Spot-36.
Location.--Lat 17° 43' 00", long 64° 45' 36".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, cased
 0-110, perforated 44-110 ft, open hole 110-136 ft.
Depth.--136 ft.
Aquifer.--Limey sediments of Tertiary and Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 2.0 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--38 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--34.65 ft below lsd, Nov. 25, 1965.
Lowest water level.--35.01 ft below lsd, Sept. 10, 1965.
Records available.--Water level: May to November 1965.
Remarks.--Recorder. Discontinued, December 1965.

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1965												
5	--	--	--	--	--	34.86	--	34.91	34.99	34.96	34.81	--
10	--	--	--	--	--	34.90	--	34.94	35.01	34.86	34.83	--
15	--	--	--	--	--	34.90	--	34.96	34.94	34.86	34.80	--
20	--	--	--	--	34.92	34.95	34.95	34.94	--	34.91	34.76	--
25	--	--	--	--	34.91	34.90	34.92	34.96	--	34.89	34.65	--
eom	--	--	--	--	34.84	34.91	34.92	34.98	34.98	34.88	34.76	--

Well 10 (43-64.48-8-68)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-37 (Agricultural Station).
Location.--Lat 17° 43' 20", long 64° 48' 14".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well,
 diam 4-in.
Depth.--22 ft.
Aquifer.--Limey sediments of Tertiary and Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of casing, 2.7 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--75 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--7.30 ft above lsd, Mar. 17, 1966.
Lowest water level.--15.38 ft above lsd, Mar. 9, 1967.
Records available.--Water levels: 1966-67.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, March 1967.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Mar. 17, 1966	7.30	July 14, 1966	10.97	Oct. 11, 1966	12.90	Jan. 4, 1967	14.00
Apr. 15	8.17	Aug. 12	11.41	Nov. 9	13.40	Feb. 7	14.80
May 11	8.92	Sept. 14	12.27	Dec. 7	13.88	Mar. 9	15.38

Well 11 (43-64.48-1-83)

Owner.--V.I. Government.

Name.--Adventure-15.

Location.--Lat 17° 43' 06", long 64° 48' 45".

Description.--Drilled water-table production well, diam 6-in, cased 0-106, perforated 34-106 ft.

Depth.--106 ft.

Aquifer.--Marl of Tertiary age.

Measuring point.--3.3 ft above lsd.

Land elevation.--80 ft above msl.

Highest water level.--2.47 ft below lsd, Jan. 9, 1963.

Lowest water level.--75.62 ft below lsd, Mar. 9, 1967.

Records available.--Chemical analysis: Mar. 9, 1967.

Water levels: 1962-69.

Remarks.--Recorder used from November 1964 to June 1965.

Measurement discontinued, July 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter														Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote			
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)					Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium, magnesium	Non-carbonate
Mar. 9, 1967	--	45	0.06	26	44	26	404	778	--	84	260	1.0	2.6	--	*1,240	217	0	2,050	8.0	27	--	

*Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level						
June 13, 1962	8.06	Aug. 28, 1962	10.41	Oct. 26, 1962	7.90	Dec. 19, 1962	7.68
June 28	7.26	Sept. 5	10.52	Oct. 31	5.30	Dec. 28	7.76
July 9	7.80	Sept. 10	10.02	Nov. 7	5.90	Jan. 9, 1963	2.47
July 16	7.82	Sept. 14	10.00	Nov. 14	6.24	Jan. 16	3.35
July 24	8.68	Sept. 25	9.11	Nov. 21	6.20	Jan. 23	3.47
July 31	9.03	Oct. 4	8.20	Nov. 28	6.90	Feb. 1	4.00
Aug. 7	9.92	Oct. 9	8.54	Dec. 3	6.71	Feb. 6	4.12
Aug. 23	10.18	Oct. 16	3.43	Dec. 13	7.20	Feb. 13	4.54

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1964												
5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	20.91
10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	20.16	21.05
15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	20.32	21.19
20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	20.47	21.33
25	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	20.68	21.47
eom	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	20.87	21.62
1965												
5	21.80	22.69	23.49	24.31	24.95	25.23	--	--	--	--	--	--
10	21.95	22.83	23.63	24.42	25.05	25.30	--	--	--	--	--	--
15	22.08	22.97	--	24.50	25.16	25.38	--	--	--	--	--	--
20	22.23	23.12	--	24.68	24.80	25.48	--	--	--	--	--	--
25	22.38	23.26	--	24.71	24.78	25.53	--	--	--	--	--	--
eom	22.53	23.35	--	24.84	25.05	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Aug. 18, 1965	27.41	Sept. 8, 1966	29.83	Sept. 11, 1967	40.88	Sept. 5, 1968	46.51
Sept. 28	28.07	Oct. 11	30.58	Oct. 10	41.78	Oct. 3	47.29
Oct. 29	28.64	Nov. 9	31.28	Nov. 9	41.59	Nov. 7	48.26
Nov. 30	28.93	Dec. 7	32.03	Dec. 13	42.12	Dec. 5	47.43
Dec. 20	26.24	Jan. 4, 1967	32.77	Jan. 11, 1968	42.39	Jan. 7, 1969	40.10
Jan. 18, 1966	25.17	Feb. 7	40.42	Feb. 13	43.08	Feb. 6	39.43
Feb. 23	25.32	Mar. 9	^a 75.62	Mar. 14	43.93	May 7	38.36
Mar. 17	25.43	Apr. 5	^a 74.74	Apr. 11	44.15	June 6	22.52
Apr. 13	25.80	May 8	37.30	May 9	44.49	July 22	26.28
May 11	26.19	June 7	39.33	June 5	45.09		
July 14	28.27	July 11	36.00	July 10	46.05		
Aug. 12	29.15	Aug. 14	39.72	Aug. 5	46.36		

a - Pumping.

Well 12 (43-64.48-9-83)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.Name.--USGS--38 (Estate Adventure).Location.--Lat 17° 43' 08", long 64° 48' 40".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, diam 4-in, cased 0--50, perforated 30--50, open hole 50--97 ft (now plugged at 46.8 ft).Depth.--97 ft.Aquifer.--Limey sediments of Tertiary and Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 2.1 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--80 ft above msl.Highest water level.--20.37 ft above lsd, Nov. 15, 1969.Lowest water level.--Dry (well plugged at 46.8 ft).Records available.--Water levels: 1966-69.Remarks.--Affected by nearby pumpage. Recorder.

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1966												
5	--	--	--	29.93	30.03	30.42	31.21	--	--	33.08	34.75	34.59
10	--	--	--	30.28	30.09	30.66	31.58	--	32.85	33.48	33.20	--
15	--	--	--	30.02	30.24	31.00	--	--	32.84	34.35	34.26	--
20	--	--	29.98	--	30.25	30.90	--	--	32.86	34.21	34.25	--
25	--	--	29.95	29.96	30.29	31.29	--	--	33.37	34.45	34.31	--
eom	--	--	29.93	29.98	30.35	31.22	--	--	33.08	34.47	34.49	--
1967												
5	35.69	^e 38.70	40.77	41.62	41.97	42.15	40.07	41.63	41.55	43.37	43.25	43.44
10	35.54	39.31	40.92	41.73	41.94	42.12	--	41.84	41.81	43.49	43.17	43.33
15	36.14	39.75	41.09	41.89	41.95	42.05	41.15	42.89	42.36	43.43	43.21	42.68
20	^e 36.40	40.08	41.25	41.96	41.57	39.80	40.64	42.97	42.77	43.64	43.08	43.01
25	^e 37.10	40.41	41.31	41.97	41.71	39.80	41.28	42.35	42.99	43.39	41.11	42.27
eom	^e 37.97	40.58	41.52	42.00	42.00	39.87	41.45	41.82	43.13	43.14	42.30	43.72
1968												
5	43.97	44.70	45.91	46.33	46.39	46.74	f	f	f	f	f	44.20
10	44.23	44.89	45.95	46.22	46.53	46.74	f	f	f	f	f	44.62
15	44.33	45.35	45.98	45.65	46.63	f	f	f	f	46.67	f	43.96
20	44.56	45.31	46.16	45.97	46.71	f	f	f	f	46.18	f	44.16
25	44.59	45.61	46.48	45.77	46.72	f	f	f	f	f	f	44.20
eom	44.34	45.68	46.44	45.95	46.73	f	f	f	f	f	46.52	43.65
1969												
5	43.52	43.00	42.88	42.21	--	--	28.41	--	--	--	21.37	--
10	43.11	42.95	42.84	42.09	35.90	25.44	--	--	--	--	21.77	--
15	42.98	42.94	--	42.09	35.49	27.17	--	--	--	--	20.37	--
20	43.00	42.97	--	42.07	34.23	27.27	--	29.44	--	24.28	--	--
25	43.02	42.99	42.28	--	22.12	27.95	--	--	28.95	22.96	--	--
eom	43.01	42.98	42.24	--	--	27.78	--	--	26.13	22.03	--	--

^e - Estimated.

f - Dry.

Well 13 (41-64.48-2-07)

Owner.--V.I. Government.Name.--Airport-39.Location.--Lat 17° 41' 59", long 64° 48' 19".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, diam 8-in, cased 0-110, perforated 58-110.Depth.--110 ft.Aquifer.--Marl and limestone of Tertiary age.Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 1.7 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--35 ft above msl.Highest water level.--29.30 ft below lsd, Nov. 16, 1962.Lowest water level.--36.63 ft below lsd, June 27, 1962.Records available.--Water levels: 1962-69.Remarks.--Recorder used from May 1963.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
June 27, 1962	36.63	Sept. 13, 1962	30.68	Dec. 4, 1962	30.50	Mar. 6	30.68
July 2	30.92	Sept. 18	30.66	Dec. 12	30.50	Mar. 13	30.90
July 10	30.94	Sept. 27	30.30	Dec. 20	30.45	Mar. 21	30.65
July 17	30.96	Oct. 2	30.30	Jan. 4, 1963	30.39	Mar. 27	30.67
July 24	30.98	Oct. 10	30.35	Jan. 10	30.08	Apr. 5	30.67
July 31	30.94	Oct. 26	30.20	Jan. 17	30.16	Apr. 11	30.58
Aug. 7	30.94	Nov. 2	30.29	Jan. 24	30.29	Apr. 22	30.70
Aug. 14	31.01	Nov. 5	30.20	Jan. 29	30.28	May 2	30.70
Aug. 21	31.01	Nov. 16	29.30	Feb. 6	30.40	May 16	30.65
Aug. 27	31.00	Nov. 21	30.40	Feb. 14	30.50	May 27	30.60
Sept. 6	30.85	Nov. 29	30.48	Feb. 27	30.55		

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1963												
5	--	--	--	--	--	30.70	30.77	30.55	30.38	30.39	30.52	30.70
10	--	--	--	--	--	30.73	30.76	30.51	30.37	30.42	30.55	30.71
15	--	--	--	--	--	30.74	30.67	30.51	30.39	--	30.58	30.74
20	--	--	--	--	--	30.74	30.63	30.51	30.42	30.48	30.60	30.78
25	--	--	--	--	--	30.75	^e 30.63	30.51	30.47	30.49	30.61	30.76
eom	--	--	--	--	30.66	30.77	30.65	30.40	30.42	30.48	30.65	30.73
1964												
5	30.73	--	30.91	30.94	--	31.13	30.96	31.04	30.98	30.87	31.05	31.12
10	30.69	--	30.93	30.96	--	31.13	30.91	31.07	30.98	30.90	31.09	31.17
15	--	--	30.95	30.94	--	31.06	30.88	31.09	31.03	30.97	31.11	31.15
20	30.68	--	30.90	^e 30.98	--	31.03	30.91	31.12	31.00	31.02	31.10	31.13
25	--	30.86	30.89	30.98	31.10	31.08	30.97	31.08	30.89	31.04	31.07	31.15
eom	--	30.89	30.91	31.00	31.12	31.05	31.01	31.02	30.87	31.08	31.08	31.20
1965												
5	31.28	31.42	31.44	31.36	31.05	31.19	31.29	31.34	31.36	31.37	--	31.05
10	31.27	31.40	31.43	31.34	31.12	31.16	31.32	31.37	31.36	31.21	--	31.10
15	31.30	31.41	31.48	31.31	31.13	--	31.38	31.38	31.32	31.24	--	30.82
20	31.33	31.41	31.47	31.30	31.19	31.23	31.34	31.33	--	31.22	--	30.82
25	31.34	31.40	31.49	31.11	31.21	31.25	31.33	31.33	--	31.16	--	30.90
eom	31.41	31.44	31.45	31.01	31.19	31.27	31.32	31.34	31.31	31.15	31.00	30.76
1966												
5	30.80	31.04	31.23	31.27	31.36	31.44	31.29	31.40	31.41	--	31.25	31.29
10	30.89	31.11	31.17	31.33	--	31.46	31.24	31.38	31.40	--	31.22	--
15	30.87	31.21	31.22	31.39	31.39	31.47	31.20	31.42	31.41	31.23	31.24	--
20	30.93	31.24	31.24	31.38	31.35	31.44	31.23	31.38	31.33	31.25	31.24	--
25	30.98	31.22	31.23	31.39	31.36	31.35	31.24	31.41	31.32	31.28	31.28	--
eom	30.98	31.25	31.28	31.42	31.37	31.30	31.33	31.40	31.30	31.25	31.27	--

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
May 20, 1963	12.47	July 10, 1963	12.75	Sept. 6, 1963	12.20	Feb. 18, 1964	^a 13.50
May 27	12.38	July 16	12.60	Sept. 16	12.20	Mar. 10	^a 13.10
June 4	12.60	July 29	12.60	Sept. 25	12.50	Mar. 18	^a 13.20
June 12	12.85	Aug. 6	12.20	Oct. 1	12.20	Apr. 9	13.50
June 20	10.00	Aug. 14	12.35	Oct. 9	12.30	Apr. 27	^a 13.70
June 27	12.87	Aug. 23	12.40	Feb. 11, 1964	^a 13.20	May 25	^a 15.50

a - Pumping.

Well 15 (42-64.47-17-96)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.Name.--USGS--32A (Airport).Location.--Lat 17° 42' 05", long 64° 47' 25".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, diam 4-in, cased 0-120, perforated 20-120, open hole 120-157 ft.Depth.--157 ft.Aquifer.--Limey sediments of Tertiary and Quaternary age.Measuring point.--Top of 4-in casing, 0.05 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--16 ft above msl.Highest water level.--11.70 ft below lsd, Jan. 4, 1967.Lowest water level.--14.24 ft below lsd, Mar. 14, 1968.Records available.--Chemical analysis: Feb. 16, 1966.Water levels: 1966-68.Remarks.--Well plugged. Measurement discontinued, March 1968.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote		
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na)	Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated					Hardness as CaCO ₃	
																					Calcium	magnesium
Feb. 16, 1966	--	34	0.01	0.00	36	35	635	592	0	212	638	0.8	9.8	--	*1,880	234	0	3,180	8.0	27	--	

*Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Mar. 17, 1966	12.15	Oct. 12, 1966	12.33	May 8, 1967	12.99	Nov. 10, 1967	13.81
Apr. 11	12.70	Dec. 7	12.33	June 7	13.13	Dec. 12	13.60
June 9	12.68	Jan. 4, 1967	11.70	July 12	13.53	Jan. 11, 1968	13.65
July 14	12.28	Feb. 8	12.67	Aug. 8	13.69	Feb. 13	14.13
Aug. 12	12.43	Mar. 9	12.75	Sept. 11	13.84	Mar. 14	14.24
Sept. 8	12.45	Apr. 5	12.79	Oct. 10	13.78		

Well 16 (42-64.47-16-97)

Owner.--U.S. Government--V.I. Government.
Name.--USGS-31 (Airport).
Location.--Lat 17° 42' 06", long 64° 47' 20".
Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, diam 4-in, cased 0-115, perforated 15-115, open hole 115-137 ft.
Depth.--137 ft.
Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age.

Measuring point.--Top of 4-in casing, 0.1 ft above lsd.
Land elevation.--17 ft above msl.
Highest water level.--12.80 ft below lsd, Jan. 7, 1967.
Lowest water level.--16.19 ft below lsd, July 10, 1968.
Records available.--Chemical analysis: Feb. 3, 1966.
Water level: 1966-69.
Remarks.--Measurement discontinued, July 1969.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Date of collection	Discharge (gpm)	Milligrams per liter															Specific conductance (micromhos at 25°C)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Footnote	
		Silica (SiO ₂)	Iron (Fe)	Manganese (Mn)	Calcium (Ca)	Magnesium (Mg)	Sodium (Na) Potassium (K)	Bicarbonate (HCO ₃)	Carbonate (CO ₃)	Sulfate (SO ₄)	Chloride (Cl)	Fluoride (F)	Nitrate (NO ₃)	Orthophosphate (PO ₄)	Dissolved solids calculated	Hardness as CaCO ₃					
																Calcium, magnesium					Non-carbonate
Feb. 3, 1966	--	37	0.00	0.00	29	43	543	524	8	179	560	0.5	11	--	*1,990	250	0	3,430	8.3	28	--

*Residue on evaporation at 180°C.

Water levels, in feet below land surface

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Mar. 17, 1966	13.15	Mar. 9, 1967	13.50	Jan. 11, 1968	15.39	Nov. 7, 1968	15.53
May 11	13.66	Apr. 5	13.59	Feb. 13	15.67	Dec. 5	15.19
June 9	13.58	May 8	13.82	Mar. 14	15.81	Jan. 7, 1969	14.90
July 14	12.90	June 7	14.05	Apr. 11	15.97	Feb. 6	15.23
Aug. 12	13.40	July 11	14.75	May 9	16.06	May 7	15.26
Sept. 8	13.45	Aug. 8	15.01	June 5	16.10	June 6	13.93
Oct. 12	13.78	Sept. 11	15.31	July 10	16.19	July 22	13.32
Dec. 7	13.26	Oct. 10	15.25	Aug. 7	16.09		
Jan. 7, 1967	12.80	Nov. 10	15.25	Sept. 5	15.80		
Feb. 7	13.49	Dec. 12	15.33	Oct. 3	15.64		

Well 17 (43-64.52-3-45)

Owner.--V.I. Government.Name.--Mahogany Road-3.Location.--Lat 17° 43' 36", long 64° 52' 32".Description.--Drilled unused water-table well, diam 6-in, cased 0-104, perforated 64-104.Depth.--104 ft.Aquifer.--Alluvium of Quaternary age and volcanic rock of Cretaceous age.Measuring point.--Top of instrument platform, 2.57 ft above lsd.Land elevation.--70 ft above msl.Highest water level.--26.24 ft below lsd, Dec. 16, 1969.Lowest water level.--74.31 ft below lsd, Mar. 29, 1965.Records available.--Water levels: 1964-69.Remarks.--Affected by nearby pumpage. Recorder.

Highest water level below land surface on the 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, 25th, and end of each month from recorder graph (in feet)

Day	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
1964												
5	--	--	--	--	--	--	71.72	72.21	72.66	73.02	73.36	73.56
10	--	--	--	--	70.09	--	71.80	72.28	72.74	73.11	73.43	73.60
15	--	--	--	--	70.16	--	71.86	72.35	72.80	73.10	73.51	73.59
20	--	--	--	--	70.23	--	71.96	72.42	72.95	73.19	73.48	73.62
25	--	--	--	--	--	71.59	--	^e 72.51	72.86	73.25	73.54	73.66
eom	--	--	--	--	--	71.68	72.15	72.60	72.94	73.31	73.60	73.65
1965												
5	--	74.00	74.16	74.24	73.80	73.70	73.91	73.91	73.96	73.51	--	73.62
10	--	74.03	74.14	74.13	73.65	73.72	73.93	73.95	73.99	73.49	--	73.70
15	73.73	74.03	74.21	74.09	73.60	--	73.97	73.99	73.99	73.46	--	73.41
20	73.77	74.06	74.26	74.04	73.24	73.84	73.94	73.96	--	73.48	--	72.92
25	73.85	74.04	74.28	--	73.69	73.91	73.95	73.95	--	73.50	--	72.47
eom	73.93	74.06	74.30	73.86	73.70	73.91	73.91	73.93	73.57	73.53	73.59	71.95
1966												
5	71.67	--	--	58.16	60.08	62.61	65.63	67.86	69.33	70.22	70.34	70.47
10	71.52	--	--	58.53	60.42	63.16	66.09	68.18	69.51	70.31	70.38	70.15
15	71.30	--	--	58.86	60.76	63.66	66.50	68.46	69.69	69.85	70.37	70.35
20	70.82	--	57.54	59.19	61.13	64.19	66.86	68.68	69.83	70.40	70.44	70.31
25	70.17	--	57.61	59.47	61.56	64.70	67.22	68.90	69.97	70.38	70.47	70.23
eom	--	--	57.86	59.78	62.09	65.18	67.61	69.18	70.10	70.34	70.45	^e 70.14
1967												
5	70.08	69.41	69.21	69.59	69.85	70.61	70.82	71.44	71.83	71.96	72.06	72.01
10	70.00	69.35	69.26	69.65	69.99	70.64	70.93	71.51	--	71.98	71.92	72.00
15	69.93	69.32	69.36	69.72	70.12	70.66	71.04	71.59	71.85	71.93	--	72.05
20	69.80	69.27	69.44	69.81	70.23	70.71	71.14	71.70	71.89	71.96	--	72.14
25	69.72	69.27	69.48	69.82	70.33	70.81	71.26	71.77	71.90	72.02	--	72.25
eom	69.58	69.21	69.50	69.80	70.47	70.84	71.34	71.85	71.91	72.06	--	72.34
1968												
5	72.43	72.73	73.21	73.15	73.48	73.68	73.52	73.37	73.20	72.96	^e 72.93	72.73
10	--	72.78	73.31	73.22	73.53	73.74	^e 73.48	73.22	73.19	72.95	72.88	72.77
15	72.55	--	73.30	73.23	73.59	73.76	73.47	--	--	72.93	72.62	72.50
20	72.64	72.88	73.34	73.22	73.61	73.70	73.45	73.12	--	73.04	72.79	72.86
25	72.70	72.97	73.25	73.38	73.57	73.70	73.40	73.15	73.13	72.95	72.75	72.84
eom	72.67	73.06	73.28	73.40	73.66	73.61	73.42	73.16	--	72.93	72.76	72.76
1969												
5	72.71	72.92	72.88	72.69	--	--	--	39.89	44.22	^e 46.84	45.54	^e 27.19
10	72.75	72.89	72.79	--	--	^e 57.18	--	40.55	44.77	--	45.05	--
15	72.76	72.91	--	--	--	--	--	41.44	45.35	^e 46.89	--	--
20	72.94	72.87	^e 72.71	^h 70.38	--	--	--	42.26	45.92	46.73	43.32	26.85
25	72.83	72.88	72.67	--	--	--	39.88	42.95	46.25	46.45	35.20	27.76
eom	72.89	72.98	72.65	--	--	--	39.26	43.66	46.57	45.96	30.86	29.37

e- Estimate

h- Tape measurement.

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